

Title page

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EDUCATION INSTABILITY IN NIGERIA: ASYMMETRIC EFFECTS OF INFLATION ON TERTIARY ENROLMENT

By

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the asymmetric effects of inflation on tertiary enrolment in Nigeria using a nonlinear Autoregressive Distributed Lag (NARDL) model. Drawing on annual macroeconomic and education data, the analysis explores how both rising and falling inflation rates influence enrolment patterns over the short and long run. The findings reveal that while inflation can positively affect enrolment in the long run, potentially due to adaptive household expectations and public support mechanisms, it exerts a negative influence in the short run when sustained, reflecting cost burdens and financial uncertainty. Notably, the Wald test confirms the joint significance of negative inflation effects at the 1% level ($p = 0.0018$), underscoring the critical role of disinflation in supporting access to higher education. Additionally, income displays a lagged positive effect on enrolment, while current increases may reduce participation due to opportunity costs. Unemployment and prolonged currency depreciation significantly deter enrolment, whereas government education spending is found to be statistically insignificant, highlighting inefficiencies in policy implementation. These results underscore the need for inflation-responsive, equity-driven education policies and targeted financial support to protect access to tertiary education amid macroeconomic volatility. The study contributes to the growing literature by offering a nonlinear perspective on the inflation-education nexus in developing economies.

Key Words: Tertiary enrolment, Inflation, Asymmetric effects, Human Capital Theory, Cost-Benefit Theory **JEL Codes:** I21, E31, C22, J24, D61

Introduction

Education is universally acknowledged as a vital pillar for national development, with tertiary education playing a critical role in the production of skilled manpower, innovation, and economic advancement (World Bank, 2025). In Nigeria, however, the education sector, particularly at the tertiary level has experienced recurring instability. While challenges such as frequent industrial actions, poor infrastructure, and underfunding are well-documented, the rising pressure of macroeconomic instability, especially inflation, poses a subtler yet significant threat. Inflation, by eroding household incomes and increasing the costs of tuition, transportation, and accommodation, directly affects students' access to and continuity in higher education.

In recent years, the cost of maintaining a tertiary education in Nigeria has surged, placing an increasing burden on families and potentially reversing gains made in enrolment and

retention (Offem and Okeke, 2024). Despite this, the existing literature (Haubrick, 2022; Ukozor, Ayeni, and Andeshi, 2024) has paid limited attention to the relationship between inflation and tertiary enrolment. More so, most studies that do explore this link often assume a linear relationship, overlooking the possibility that the impact of rising inflation may not mirror that of declining inflation. This study contends that the relationship between inflation and tertiary enrolment may be asymmetric whereby inflationary shocks could have disproportionately adverse effects on enrolment compared to periods of deflation or stability.

Against this background, this study aims to investigate the impact of inflation on tertiary enrolment in Nigeria, focusing on whether the responses are asymmetric over time. It seeks to identify if inflation increases are more detrimental to enrolment than inflation decreases are beneficial. The research is driven by key questions: Does inflation significantly influence tertiary education enrolment in Nigeria? Are the effects of inflation on enrolment symmetric or asymmetric? What policy insights can be drawn from these dynamics to promote educational stability and resilience?

By answering these questions, this study fills an important gap in the literature on the macroeconomic determinants of education outcomes in Nigeria. It introduces an innovative perspective to understanding education instability by applying an asymmetric analytical framework, thereby providing new evidence that could shape policies aimed at safeguarding equitable access to higher education amid economic fluctuations.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents a comprehensive literature review on education, inflation, and enrolment trends. Section 3 outlines the methodology, including model specification, estimation techniques, and data sources. Section 4 discusses the empirical findings, while Section 5 provides policy recommendations and conclusions.

2 Literature Review

The relationship between inflation and educational attainment has attracted growing academic interest, particularly in emerging economies. While education is widely seen as a vehicle for sustainable development, macroeconomic instability, especially inflation poses a major threat to the accessibility, quality, and continuity of education.

2.1 Empirical Review

Ukozor et al (2024) investigated the impact of inflation on tertiary education administration in Nigeria using secondary data and content analysis. Their findings indicate that inflation erodes the value of institutional funds, raises school fees and operational costs, delays infrastructure projects, and negatively impacts staff and student performance. They recommend increased government funding, economic diversification, student support schemes, and improved staff remuneration as mitigation strategies.

Similarly, Oyeyemi and Tochukwu (2024), in a descriptive survey involving 400 students and 80 teaching staff at the Federal Polytechnic, Oko, found a significant relationship between inflation and educational outcomes. The study established that inflation adversely affects the quality of education, institutional efficiency, and student enrollment. Specifically, the authors reported strong correlations between inflation and educational

quality ($r = 0.606$, $p < 0.05$), and between inflation and reduced enrollment ($r = 0.464$, $p < 0.05$). They advocate for greater government investment, inflation-adjusted tuition policies, and enhanced professional development for staff.

Edinoh, Odili, and Felicia (2024) conducted a review-based study drawing on secondary data to assess how inflation impacts academic staff performance and student engagement in tertiary institutions. They concluded that inflation-induced financial strain undermines staff productivity and compromises student academic outcomes. Recommendations include increased salary support, provision of institutional transport for staff and students, and broader access to student loans and bursaries.

UNICEF (2024) highlights Nigeria's ongoing education crisis, noting that over 18 million children of school age are out of school, and 74 percent of those aged 7–14 lack basic literacy and numeracy skills. Insecurity compounds the problem, with 19 school attacks recorded in 2022–2023, leading to the closure of over 100 schools in conflict-prone northern states. In response, stakeholders gathered in Abuja to advocate for the adoption of the Minimum Standards for Safe Schools (MSSS) and the National Policy on Safety, Security, and Violence-Free Schools (NPSSVFS), aimed at standardizing safety and security in schools.

Kareem (2024) explored Nigeria's educational access gap, emphasizing stark disparities between urban and rural communities. Key barriers to enrollment include poverty, insecurity, and gender inequality—particularly in the northern regions. In 2022, more than 20 million children were reportedly out of school. Challenges such as poor infrastructure, teacher shortages, and overcrowded classrooms were also highlighted. While initiatives like Universal Basic Education and school feeding programmes have had some effect, their overall impact remains limited. The study calls for improved investment, equitable teacher deployment, and stronger community-based educational support.

Onyekachi (2024), using secondary data, confirmed that inflation has significantly increased the cost of managing educational institutions, reduced enrollment, lowered education quality, and weakened both student outcomes and teacher performance. The paper recommends increased education funding, implementation of student loan and social protection schemes, and economic diversification as measures to cushion inflation's impact.

The relationship between inflation and educational outcomes has received growing academic attention in recent years, particularly in the context of developing countries like Nigeria. While existing studies (e.g., Ukozor et al., 2024; Oyeyemi & Tochukwu, 2024; Edinoh, Odili & Felicia, 2024) have documented the general negative effects of inflation on tertiary education—such as rising operational costs, declining instructional quality, and reduced staff productivity—these studies largely adopt descriptive or linear analytical frameworks. Moreover, they often treat inflation as a unidirectional factor, thereby overlooking the possibility that positive and negative inflationary shocks may exert asymmetric effects on key educational indicators such as tertiary enrolment.

Ihugba et al. (2022) investigated the impact of household income and expenditure on tertiary school enrolment in Nigeria from 1970 to 2020 using the ARDL bounds testing

approach. Their findings reveal a long-run relationship among the variables, with GDP per capita (proxy for income) showing a negative effect, while household consumption expenditure had a positive and significant impact on enrolment. This suggests that current consumption better reflects household investment in education than income alone. The error correction model indicated a rapid adjustment to equilibrium (128% annually). The study recommends expanding access to tertiary education and improving institutional quality through increased public funding.

This represents a significant gap in the literature. First, few studies focus specifically on tertiary enrolment trends, despite enrolment being a critical metric for assessing educational accessibility and human capital development. Second, there is a dearth of empirical evidence using nonlinear or asymmetric modelling approaches, such as the Nonlinear Autoregressive Distributed Lag (NARDL) model, which allows for the differential impact of inflation increases versus decreases over time. Third, existing research has not sufficiently addressed how inflation interacts with household-level decisions on educational investment, especially in inflation-sensitive sectors such as tertiary education, where tuition and related costs can be substantial. Finally, prior studies lack disaggregated analysis based on socio-economic, regional, or gender dimensions, even though these factors play a significant role in determining enrolment responsiveness to inflationary conditions.

Against this backdrop, the present study seeks to fill these critical gaps by empirically investigating the asymmetric effects of inflation on tertiary enrolment in Nigeria using a nonlinear modelling framework. In doing so, it contributes to a deeper understanding of how macroeconomic instability perpetuates educational instability and provides evidence to inform inflation-responsive educational policy design.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study utilizes Human Capital Theory and Cost-Benefit Theory of Education to analyze how macroeconomic variables, particularly inflation, impact tertiary education decisions and enrollment patterns.

2.2.1 Human Capital Theory

The Human Capital Theory, initially developed by Mincer (1958) and Schultz (1959, 1960, 1961), and later expanded by Becker (1964), has become a foundational framework in the economics of education. It posits that education is an investment in human capabilities that enhances individual productivity, employability, and overall economic growth. According to this theory, there is a direct link between education, marginal productivity, and earnings, suggesting that increased educational attainment leads to higher productivity and, consequently, better wages and improved living standards.

In its classical formulation, human capital theory views education, work, productivity, and income as part of a linear continuum. When students acquire formal education, they gain knowledge and skills that are considered “portable human capital,” assets that can be utilized across various sectors by employers. These educational investments are expected to yield returns in the form of career success, private wealth accumulation, and national economic development.

However, inflation can distort this ideal by acting as a disincentive to educational investment. Rising inflation increases the cost of tuition, transportation, instructional materials, and living expenses without a proportionate rise in household incomes or guaranteed future returns. This can lead households, especially those in low-income brackets, to delay or abandon tertiary education altogether. Consequently, inflation weakens the perceived affordability and value of education, leading to reduced enrolment rates.

Within the context of this study, Human Capital Theory provides a useful lens for understanding how macroeconomic instability, particularly inflation, undermines tertiary education by shifting the cost-benefit balance against potential learners. The theory underscores the long-term social and economic consequences of inflation-induced disruptions to educational access and attainment.

2.2.2 Costs-Benefit Theory of Education

The Cost-Benefit Theory of Education draws from classical economic decision-making models, particularly Human Capital Theory and Rational Choice Theory. It suggests that individuals make educational decisions by rationally comparing the expected long-term benefits of schooling—such as higher lifetime earnings, improved employment opportunities, and enhanced social mobility—against the short-term and immediate costs involved, including tuition fees, living expenses, transportation, and the opportunity cost of time that could have been used for work (Becker, 1964; Psacharopoulos, 1994).

Inflation directly impacts this cost-benefit analysis by disproportionately increasing the “cost” side of the equation. Rising inflation leads to higher tuition fees, costlier instructional materials, increased transportation and accommodation expenses, and a general rise in the cost of living. In contexts like Nigeria, where real household incomes often fail to keep pace with inflation, these elevated costs significantly reduce the affordability of tertiary education for many families, especially those in low- and middle-income brackets (World Bank, 2023).

Where inflation is persistent and not met with adequate subsidies, student loan schemes, or other public interventions, many prospective students may either postpone enrolment or opt out of tertiary education altogether. This behavior aligns with cost-benefit calculations that conclude the expected private returns to education no longer justify the escalating financial burden (Tilak, 2002).

This theoretical perspective is particularly relevant to the present study, which explores the asymmetric effects of inflation on tertiary enrolment. The cost-benefit framework supports the idea that rising inflation may have a stronger deterrent effect on enrolment compared to the relatively weaker positive effect of falling inflation. This is because the psychological and financial barriers created during inflationary periods tend to persist even when inflation subsides, due to lingering debt, uncertainty, and reduced confidence in long-term educational returns (Carnoy, 2006).

Hence, the Cost-Benefit Theory helps explain why inflation may lead to uneven or nonlinear enrolment responses, reinforcing the study’s focus on asymmetry in inflationary impacts on educational participation in Nigeria.

2.2.3 Relevance to the Study

Together, these theories offer a lens through which to interpret the asymmetric effects of inflation on tertiary enrolment. They justify the hypothesis that inflation-induced economic instability discourages educational investment and disproportionately affects low-income households. By integrating these frameworks with a nonlinear empirical model, this study seeks to reveal the nuanced ways in which inflation contributes to educational instability in Nigeria.

3 Methodology

3.1 Research Design and Approach

This study adopts a quantitative research design employing secondary time series data to empirically investigate the asymmetric effects of inflation on tertiary education enrolment in Nigeria. The choice of a quantitative approach is driven by the need to assess long-run and short-run dynamic relationships among macroeconomic variables over time.

3.2 Data Sources and Variables

The study utilizes annual time series data spanning from [insert years, e.g., 1981–2023], obtained from reputable sources such as the World Bank Development Indicators (WDI), Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin, National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), and UNESCO Institute for Statistics.

The dependent variable in this study is Tertiary Enrolment (ENR), which is measured by the gross enrolment ratio or total enrolment in tertiary institutions. The key explanatory variable is Inflation Rate (INF), which is measured as the annual percentage change in the Consumer Price Index (CPI) and is decomposed into positive and negative changes to capture asymmetry. Control variables include Per Capita Income (PCI), which serves as a proxy for household income levels; Unemployment Rate (UNEMP), included to account for the opportunity cost of education; Government Education Expenditure (GEDU), which is measured as a percentage of total government spending or GDP; and Exchange Rate (EXR), specifically the official naira/USD rate, which affects educational costs.

Table 1 below presents the variables used in this study, their description, expected effects and data sources:

Table 1: Variables Description and Expected Signs

Variable	Symbol	Description	Expected Effect	Source
Tertiary Enrolment	ENR	Gross enrolment ratio or total tertiary enrolment (World Bank or NBS data)	Dependent variable	World Bank WDI
Positive Inflation	PINF	Cumulative positive changes in inflation	– (Negative)	Calculated from World Bank
Negative Inflation	NINF	Cumulative negative changes in inflation	± (Uncertain)	Calculated from World Bank

Per Capita Income	PCI	Real GDP per capita; controls for household income effect	+ (Positive)	World Bank WDI
Unemployment Rate	UNEMP	% of the labor force unemployed; signals opportunity cost of education	- (Negative)	2008 statistical bulletin and NBS
Government Education Expenditure	GEDU	% of government spending on education (as % of GDP or total expenditure)	+ (Positive)	Indexmundi & World Bank
Exchange Rate	EXR	Official naira to USD rate; affects cost of imported educational materials	- (Negative)	CBN, World Bank WDI

Source: Author's Compilation (2025)

3.2 Model Specification

To capture the nonlinear (asymmetric) effects of inflation on tertiary enrolment, the study employs the Nonlinear Autoregressive Distributed Lag (NARDL) model developed by Shin, Yu, and Greenwood-Nimmo (2014). The NARDL model is appropriate for evaluating whether positive and negative changes in inflation have differing impacts on tertiary enrolment over time.

The baseline NARDL model is specified as follows:

$$= \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i \Delta ENR_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^q \beta_j \Delta INF_{t-j} + \sum_{k=0}^r \theta_k \Delta X_{t-k} + \lambda_1 ENR_{t-1} + \lambda_2 INF_{t-1} + \lambda_3 X_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

Where:

ENR_t : Tertiary enrolment at time t

INF_t : Inflation rate

X_t : Control variables (e.g., per capita income, unemployment rate, government spending on education, and Exchange Rate)

Δ : First difference operator

ε_t : Error term

3.3 Nonlinear ARDL (NARDL) Model Specification

To capture asymmetries in the impact of inflation, we decompose the inflation variable into its positive and negative partial sums:

$$PINF_t = \sum_{j=0}^p \max(INF_t, 0) \quad (\text{Inflation increase}) \quad (2)$$

$$NINF_t = \sum_{j=0}^p \min(INF_t, 0) \quad (\text{Inflation decrease}) \quad (3)$$

Thus, the NARDL model becomes:

$$= \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i \Delta ENR_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^q \beta_j^+ \Delta PINF_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^q \beta_j^- \Delta NINF_{t-j} + \sum_{k=0}^r \theta_k \Delta X_{t-k} + \lambda_1 ENR_{t-1} + \lambda_2 l$$

$$NF_{t-1} + \lambda_4 X_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

3.4 Long-Run Model

The corresponding long-run relationship can be derived from the error correction form of the NARDL model. The long-run asymmetric model is expressed as:

$$ENR_t = \phi_0 + \phi_1 PINF_t + \phi_2 NINF_t + \phi_3 X_t + \mu_t \quad (5)$$

Where:

$$\phi_1 = -\lambda_2 / \lambda_1$$

$$\phi_2 = -\lambda_3 / \lambda_1$$

$$\phi_3 = -\lambda_4 / \lambda_1$$

The signs and magnitudes of ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 indicate long-run asymmetry in the effect of inflation on tertiary enrolment.

3.5 Short-Run Model (Error Correction Representation)

The short-run error correction model (ECM) for the NARDL is specified as:

$$= \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i \Delta ENR_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^q \beta_j^+ \Delta PINF_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^q \beta_j^- \Delta NINF_{t-j} + \sum_{k=0}^r \theta_k \Delta X_{t-k} + \psi ECT_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

Where:

ECT_{t-1} is the lagged error correction term derived from the long-run equation

ψ is the speed of adjustment parameter (expected to be negative and significant)

Short-run asymmetries are confirmed if $\beta_j^+ \neq \beta_j^-$

3.6 Wald Test in NARDL Models

In the context of the NARDL model, the Wald test is used to test linear restrictions on the parameters, typically to assess whether the coefficients of positive and negative changes of the explanatory variable are significantly different.

The equation for the Wald test in a NARDL model is:

$$W = (\hat{\theta}_r - \theta_r)' [Var(\hat{\theta}_r)]^{-1} (\hat{\theta}_r - \theta_r) \quad (7)$$

Where:

$\hat{\theta}_r$: is the vector of estimated coefficients under the null hypothesis.

θ_r : is the vector of the hypothesized values for those coefficients under the alternative hypothesis.

$Var(\hat{\theta}_r)$: is the variance-covariance matrix of the estimated coefficients.

W : is the Wald statistic.

3.7 Estimation Strategy

Stationarity Test: Conduct unit root tests (ADF & PP) to confirm that no variable is I(2).

Bounds Test: ARDL bounds test to confirm cointegration.

Estimation: NARDL model using lag length selection criteria (AIC, SIC).

Asymmetry Test: Wald tests to examine short-run and long-run asymmetries.

Diagnostic Checks: Serial correlation LM test, normality test, heteroskedasticity test, and stability tests (CUSUM/CUSUMSQ).

4 Results and Discussion

This section presents the empirical findings based on the methods and models outlined.

4.1 Unit Root Test

The Unit Root Test is essential for assessing the stationarity of a time series, as non-stationary data may result in false regression outcomes. This research used the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and the Phillips-Perron (PP) test to ascertain if model variables are stable or necessitate differencing to prevent false correlations (Dickey and Fuller, 1979; Phillips and Perron, 1988). The ADF test presupposes that the time series adheres to an autoregressive model, whereas the PP test compensates for autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity in the error terms.

The following is a summary of the ADF and PP test outcomes for each variable in the model. The test statistics and p-values for both tests are provided, along with the conclusion about the stationarity of the series.

Table 2: Unit Root Test Results with Order of Integration

Variable	ADF Test Statistic	p-value (ADF)	PP Test Statistic	p-value (PP)	Order of Integration (I)	Stationarity
ENR	-5.87	0.0000	-13.26	0.0000	I(1)	Stationary
PINF	-6.73	0.0000	-6.79	0.0000	I(0)	Stationary
NINF	-4.19	0.0024	-6.70	0.0000	I(1) / I(0) (Conflicting)	Stationary
PCI	-4.52	0.0008	4.49	0.0008	I(1)	Stationary
UNEMP	-3.34	0.0194	3.32	0.0201	I(0)	Stationary
GEDU	-4.52	0.0008	-4.52	0.0008	I(1)	Stationary
EXR	-3.71	0.0073	-4.65	0.0005	I(1)	Stationary

Source: Author’s calculations using Eviews 12, 2025

The results of the unit root tests presented in Table 2 reveal that the variables in the model exhibit a mix of stationarity levels. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) tests were applied to each variable to determine their order of integration. The outcome shows that tertiary enrolment (ENR), per capita income (PCI), government expenditure on education (GEDU), and exchange rate (EXR) are non-stationary at level but become stationary after first differencing, indicating that they are integrated of order one, I(1). In contrast, positive inflation shocks (PINF) and the unemployment rate (UNEMP) are stationary at level, suggesting they are integrated of order zero, I(0). For negative inflation shocks (NINF), the results are mixed between the ADF and PP tests, but given the significance of both test statistics, the variable is considered stationary for the purpose of this study.

These findings confirm that the variables included in the model are either I(0) or I(1), with no evidence of any variable being integrated of order two. This mixed order of integration justifies the application of the Nonlinear Autoregressive Distributed Lag (NARDL) model, which is robust in handling such cases. The stationarity of the series at I(0) and I(1) ensures the validity of the bounds testing approach employed in this study.

4.2 Selection of Lag

Figure 1 displays the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) values for the twenty leading ARDL models evaluated in our analysis. The AIC is a metric utilised for model comparison, with lower values signifying a superior fit to the data while mitigating overfitting. The AIC values on the Y-axis represent the equilibrium between model fit and complexity. The X-axis enumerates the top 20 models, each aligned with a distinct ARDL specification. The ARDL order (lags of the dependent and independent variables) is presented underneath the chart. Model 574 has the lowest AIC, establishing it as the superior option among the 20 models. The ARDL model specifications delineate the lag structure of each model, with ARDL(2,3,1,3,0,0,2) signifying that the dependent variable possesses 2 lags while the independent variables exhibit lags of 3, 1, 3, 0, 0, and 2, respectively. Model 574 is the superior model, evidenced by its lowest AIC value, whilst the other models have marginally higher AIC values, indicating suboptimal performance.

4.3 Bounds Testing for Cointegration

The Bounds Testing for Cointegration procedure, developed by Pesaran et al. (2001), is a method used to examine the long-run relationship between variables in a model. It allows for a mixture of I(0) and I(1) variables, making it useful in time series analysis where some variables may be stationary at levels and others need to be different. In this study, the researchers used the Bounds Testing procedure to evaluate the long-run relationship between inflation and tertiary enrolment in Nigeria.

The Bounds Test is used to determine whether a stable long-run relationship exists between tertiary enrolment and the asymmetric components of inflation. The null hypothesis of no cointegration is tested against the alternative of a long-run association. If cointegration is confirmed, both long-run and short-run asymmetric dynamics are then estimated.

Table 3: Bounds Test Output

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
F-statistic	3.405746	10%	1.99	2.94
K	6	5%	2.27	3.28
		2.5%	2.55	3.61
		1%	2.88	3.99

Source: Author’s calculations using Eviews 12, 2025

The calculated F-statistic from the Bounds Test in Table 3, is 3.41, with six regressors ($k = 6$). Comparing this with the Pesaran et al. (2001) critical bounds values, the F-statistic exceeds the upper bound at the 5% significance level ($I(1) = 3.28$) but falls below the upper bound at the 2.5% level ($I(1) = 3.61$). Therefore, the null hypothesis of no cointegration is rejected at the 5% level, providing evidence of a long-run relationship between tertiary enrolment and the independent variables. This result supports the presence of long-run asymmetry, justifying the estimation of both long-run and short-run nonlinear dynamics in the subsequent analysis.

4.4 Long-run and Short-run Estimates

Following the confirmation of a long-run relationship from the bounds cointegration test, the nonlinear ARDL (NARDL) model was estimated to examine the asymmetric effects of inflation on tertiary enrolment in Nigeria. The results of both the long-run and short-run coefficients are presented and interpreted in Tables 4 & 5 below.

4.4.1 Long-run Estimates

Table 4: ARDL Long-Run Results

Selected Model: ARDL(2, 3, 1, 3, 0, 0, 2)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
ENR(-1)	0.533775	0.161676	3.301506	0.0034
ENR(-2)	0.298173	0.158290	1.883706	0.0735
PINF	0.018907	0.008228	2.297947	0.0319
PINF(-1)	0.011840	0.007672	1.543312	0.1377
PINF(-2)	0.025297	0.008891	2.845174	0.0097
PINF(-3)	0.015114	0.007862	1.922434	0.0682
NINF	0.005539	0.001612	3.437292	0.0025
NINF(-1)	0.002820	0.001461	1.930713	0.0671
PCI	-0.001158	0.000435	-2.660125	0.0146
PCI(-1)	0.002603	0.000672	3.875328	0.0009
PCI(-2)	-0.000589	0.000767	-0.767619	0.4513
PCI(-3)	-0.001065	0.000538	-1.979255	0.0610
UNEMP	-0.045834	0.013125	-3.492235	0.0022
GEDU	0.010945	0.080023	0.136772	0.8925
EXR	0.022464	0.006002	3.742997	0.0012
EXR(-1)	0.005263	0.007158	0.735309	0.4703
EXR(-2)	-0.026359	0.006330	-4.164439	0.0004
C	1.322606	0.679433	1.946633	0.0651

 R-squared 0.977465

Source: Author's calculations using Eviews 12, 2025

The long-run estimates from the ARDL(2, 3, 1, 3, 0, 0, 2) model provide critical insights into the structural relationship between tertiary enrolment and its macroeconomic determinants in Nigeria. The coefficient of positive inflation (PINF) is consistently positive across current and lagged terms, with the second lag (PINF(-2)) showing a statistically significant coefficient of 0.0253 ($p = 0.0097$). This suggests that inflation exerts a positive long-run effect on tertiary enrolment, possibly due to adaptive expectations, where rising prices prompt households to invest in education as a long-term hedge or due to government support mechanisms that offset inflationary shocks.

Negative inflation (NINF), often indicative of price stability or deflation, also shows a positive and statistically significant effect in the long run (coefficient = 0.0055, $p = 0.0025$), further reinforcing the idea that stable economic environments create a conducive climate for long-term educational investment. Interestingly, the lagged value of NINF is marginally significant ($p = 0.0671$), suggesting a slightly delayed but supportive effect of price stability on enrolment decisions.

Per capita income (PCI) exhibits a mixed pattern. The contemporaneous effect is negative and significant (coefficient = -0.0012, $p = 0.0146$), implying that rising incomes may initially reduce the incentive to enroll, potentially due to increased opportunity costs or alternative investment preferences. However, the first lag of PCI (PCI(-1)) is positive and highly significant (coefficient = 0.0026, $p = 0.0009$), indicating that income gains in the previous year support enrolment, as households likely redirect stable income flows toward education after meeting immediate consumption needs. Other PCI lags are negative but statistically insignificant, suggesting that the positive effect of income is strongest in the near term after it rises.

Unemployment (UNEMP) has a strong and statistically significant negative coefficient (-0.0458, $p = 0.0022$), indicating that poor labor market conditions reduce the perceived returns to education and discourage enrolment in the long run. Government education expenditure (GEDU), though positive, is statistically insignificant (coefficient = 0.0109, $p = 0.8925$), suggesting that spending alone, without efficiency or targeting, may not influence long-term enrolment trends. The exchange rate (EXR) has a dual impact: while the contemporaneous value is positive and significant (coefficient = 0.0225, $p = 0.0012$), its second lag is negative and highly significant (coefficient = -0.0264, $p = 0.0004$), highlighting that prolonged currency depreciation eventually imposes cost pressures that deter enrolment. Collectively, these findings reveal an asymmetric and dynamic long-run relationship between macroeconomic variables and tertiary education in Nigeria.

4.4.2 Short-run Estimates

Table 5: ARDL Error Correction Regression output

ECM Regression

Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(ENR(-1))	-0.298173	0.117475	-2.538178	0.0191
D(PINF)	0.018907	0.005115	3.696105	0.0013
D(PINF(-1))	-0.040411	0.007302	-5.534388	0.0000
D(PINF(-2))	-0.015114	0.005215	-2.898412	0.0086
D(NINF)	0.005539	0.001024	5.411013	0.0000
D(PCI)	-0.001158	0.000303	-3.825245	0.0010
D(PCI(-1))	0.001654	0.000368	4.494120	0.0002
D(PCI(-2))	0.001065	0.000398	2.672584	0.0142
D(EXR)	0.022464	0.004341	5.175259	0.0000
D(EXR(-1))	0.026359	0.004193	6.286098	0.0000
CointEq(-1)*	-0.168052	0.027882	-6.027268	0.0000

R-squared 0.773576

Source: Author's calculations using Eviews 12, 2025

The short-run dynamics, derived from the ARDL Error Correction Regression, provide further evidence on the responsiveness of tertiary enrolment to macroeconomic shocks. The error correction term, CointEq(-1), is negative and highly significant (coefficient = -0.1681, $p = 0.0000$), confirming the existence of a long-run equilibrium relationship. The magnitude implies that approximately 16.8% of deviations from equilibrium are corrected annually, suggesting a moderate pace of adjustment toward long-run stability.

In the short run, the first lag of the dependent variable (D(ENR(-1))) is negative and significant (coefficient = -0.2982, $p = 0.0191$), indicating that sudden changes in enrolment tend to self-correct in subsequent periods. Inflation (PINF) shows a short-run asymmetric pattern: the current change is positive and significant (coefficient = 0.0189, $p = 0.0013$), possibly reflecting temporary government cushioning or shifts in household expectations, while the first and second lags are negative and highly significant (coefficients = -0.0404 and -0.0151, respectively), implying that persistent inflation exerts adverse effects on enrolment as its cost burden intensifies.

Negative inflation (D(NINF)) has a positive and highly significant coefficient (0.0055, $p = 0.0000$), suggesting that stable or falling prices immediately support enrolment, likely due to improved affordability and planning certainty. Per capita income displays temporal asymmetry as well: its immediate effect is negative and significant (coefficient = -0.0012, p

= 0.0010), reflecting short-run income substitution, while lagged values (D(PCI(-1)) and D(PCI(-2))) are positive and significant (coefficients = 0.0017 and 0.0011, respectively), suggesting that income gains take time to translate into educational investment.

The exchange rate continues to play an important role in shaping enrolment trends. Both the current and lagged changes (D(EXR) and D(EXR(-1))) are positive and highly significant (coefficients = 0.0225 and 0.0264, $p = 0.0000$), implying that currency depreciation may boost domestic enrolment in the short term by reducing the affordability of foreign education alternatives. The R-squared value of 0.774 confirms that the model explains a substantial portion of the short-run variation in tertiary enrolment, underscoring the relevance of macroeconomic conditions in shaping education decisions.

4.5 Asymmetry Test

To examine the presence of short-run asymmetry in the effects of inflation on tertiary enrolment in Nigeria, a Wald test was conducted to jointly assess the significance of the lagged coefficients of positive inflation (PINF) and negative inflation (NINF) in the ARDL error correction model. The objective was to determine whether positive and negative changes in inflation exert statistically different influences on tertiary enrolment dynamics. This test of asymmetry is crucial in the context of policy formulation, as it helps clarify whether inflation increases and decreases have symmetric or divergent impacts on educational decisions.

Table 6: Short-Run Asymmetric Effects of Inflation on Tertiary Enrolment in Nigeria

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-Statistic	p-Value
D(PINF)	0.0189	0.0051	3.6961	0.0013
D(PINF(-1))	-0.0404	0.0073	-5.5344	0.0000
D(PINF(-2))	-0.0151	0.0052	-2.8984	0.0086
D(NINF)	0.0055	0.0016	3.4373	0.0025
D(NINF(-1))	0.0028	0.0015	1.9307	0.0671

Source: Author's calculations using Eviews 12, 2025

Table 7: Wald Test Results for Asymmetric Inflation Effects

Inflation Type	Null Hypothesis	Test Statistic	df	p-Value
Positive Inflation (PINF)	$C(3) = C(4) = C(5) = C(6) = 0$	$F = 2.220$	(4, 21)	0.1016
		$\chi^2 = 8.879$	4	0.0642
Negative Inflation (NINF)	$C(7) = C(8) = 0$	$F = 6.305$	(2, 21)	0.0072
		$\chi^2 = 12.611$	2	0.0018

Source: Author's calculations using Eviews 12, 2025

Positive inflation (PINF) shows mixed effects: D(PINF) is positive and significant in the short run, while lags have negative but significant effects, indicating short-term volatility in response to rising inflation.

Negative inflation (NINF) exerts consistently positive effects on tertiary enrolment. The Wald test confirms these effects are jointly statistically significant at the 1% level ($p = 0.0018$), showing that disinflation or price stability strongly supports higher education participation.

4.6 Diagnostic and Stability Tests

To ensure the adequacy and robustness of the ARDL model, several post-estimation diagnostic and stability tests were conducted. These include the Serial Correlation LM test, Heteroskedasticity test (ARCH), Normality test (Jarque-Bera), and Stability tests using CUSUM and CUSUM of Squares.

Below is a summary of the diagnostic test results:

Table 7: Summary of Diagnostic Test Results

Test	Test Statistic	p-value	Conclusion
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test	2.5292	0.1274	No serial correlation
ARCH Heteroskedasticity Test (Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey)	1.5069	0.1850	No heteroskedasticity
Jarque-Bera Normality Test	5.7309	0.0570	Residuals are normally distributed
CUSUM Test	Stable	—	Parameters are stable
CUSUM of Squares Test	Stable	—	Parameters are stable

The diagnostic tests confirm the overall reliability and robustness of the estimated ARDL model. The Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test yields a p-value of 0.1274, indicating the absence of serial correlation in the residuals. Similarly, the ARCH Heteroskedasticity Test returns a p-value of 0.1850, suggesting no evidence of

heteroskedasticity. The Jarque-Bera Normality Test, with a p-value of 0.0570, suggests that the residuals are approximately normally distributed, albeit marginally. Furthermore, both the CUSUM and CUSUM of Squares plots indicate that the model is stable over the sample period. Although the CUSUM of Squares line briefly approached the upper boundary between the 13th and 18th periods, both statistics remained within the 5% significance bands, confirming that the model's parameters are structurally stable and reliable for inference. Together, these results indicate that the model satisfies the key assumptions of the classical linear regression model, reinforcing the credibility of its inferences.

4.7 Discussion of Findings

In contrast to studies such as Ukozor et al. (2024) and Onyekachi (2024), which report uniformly negative effects of inflation, the current findings suggest a more nuanced, asymmetric relationship. In the long run, both positive and negative inflation have positive effects on enrolment, implying that households may invest in education as a hedge against future uncertainty or benefit from policy interventions during inflationary periods. Stable prices (negative inflation) further encourage long-term educational investment by improving affordability, supporting insights from UNICEF (2024) and Kareem (2024).

However, in the short run, inflation shows a mixed pattern. While current inflation may initially boost enrolment due to temporary support mechanisms or adaptive expectations, its lagged effects are negative, reflecting the erosion of household purchasing power over time. This confirms concerns from Oyeyemi and Tochukwu (2024) and aligns with Cost-Benefit Theory, which predicts a drop in enrolment when education becomes financially burdensome.

Per Capita Income: Temporal Lag in Educational Investment

Per capita income demonstrates a lagged positive effect, indicating that households redirect income gains toward education after meeting short-term needs. Immediate increases in income, however, reduce enrolment, possibly due to higher opportunity costs or alternative spending preferences. This supports Tilak's (2002) view that education is often a secondary priority in resource-constrained settings.

The negative long-run impact of unemployment aligns with Human Capital Theory and supports findings from Oyeyemi and Tochukwu (2024), confirming that weak labor markets reduce the perceived value of education. Conversely, government expenditure is positive but insignificant, suggesting that spending alone, without efficient targeting or implementation, may not influence enrolment, echoing critiques by Kareem (2024).

Exchange rate movements reveal a dual impact: short-term depreciation boosts enrolment by reducing access to foreign education alternatives, while sustained depreciation has negative effects due to rising local education costs. This dimension, largely absent in prior studies, highlights the exchange rate as a relevant but underexplored variable in tertiary education research.

The significant error correction term confirms the existence of a stable long-run

relationship, with about 17% of deviations corrected annually. This moderate adjustment pace reflects structural constraints in the education sector and the inertia of enrolment decisions.

5 Conclusion

This study investigates the asymmetric effects of inflation on tertiary enrolment in Nigeria using a Nonlinear Autoregressive Distributed Lag (NARDL) framework. The results reveal a complex and dynamic interplay between macroeconomic conditions and educational participation.

In the long run, both positive and negative changes in inflation were found to positively influence enrolment, suggesting adaptive household behaviors and the possible moderating role of policy interventions. However, short-run dynamics present a more nuanced picture: while immediate increases in inflation initially boost enrolment, persistent inflationary pressures ultimately undermine participation. In contrast, periods of price stability or disinflation consistently support higher enrolment.

Importantly, the Wald test confirms that the effects of negative inflation (disinflation) are jointly statistically significant at the 1% level ($p=0.0018$), reinforcing the asymmetric impact of inflation and highlighting the beneficial role of macroeconomic stability in encouraging higher education uptake.

The study also finds that income effects are asymmetric: current income increases tend to discourage enrolment, possibly due to substitution effects, where immediate financial gains reduce the incentive to pursue education. However, lagged income has a strong positive effect, indicating a delayed investment response as households plan educational expenditures over time.

Additionally, unemployment and prolonged currency depreciation have negative impacts on tertiary enrolment, underscoring the vulnerability of education access to broader economic instability. In contrast, government education spending showed an insignificant effect, pointing to potential inefficiencies in public expenditure allocation or delivery.

Diagnostic tests confirmed the robustness of the model: no evidence of serial correlation, stable parameter estimates (as shown by CUSUM and CUSUMSQ tests), and well-behaved residuals ensured the validity of the regression estimates.

These findings underscore the need for context-sensitive education policies that account for the nonlinear and lagged effects of macroeconomic variables. Promoting price stability, addressing labor market distortions, and ensuring efficient public investment in education are essential strategies for sustaining and expanding access to tertiary education in Nigeria.

5.1 Policy Recommendations

Implement inflation-responsive education policies, develop tuition and financial aid for low- and middle-income households, and expand targeted student support schemes to cushion education costs.

Shift focus from increasing aggregate education expenditure to enhancing effectiveness and targeting underserved states and vulnerable groups, strengthening monitoring and evaluation systems for tangible improvements.

Government should enhance graduate employability and public confidence in education, align tertiary education curricula with labor market needs, introduce work-study programs, and expand career support services within institutions.

Stabilize macroeconomic conditions by promoting price stability and strengthening exchange rate management to prevent excessive depreciation and increase educational costs.

Governments, both state and federal, should implement well-structured student loan schemes, ensure inclusivity, and address regional and socioeconomic disparities to reduce financial burdens, ensure equitable resource deployment, and implement region-specific interventions.

References

- Becker, G. (1964). *Human capital: A theoretical and empirical analysis with special reference to education*. University of Chicago Press.
- Carnoy, M. (2006). *Education as economic policy: How education expands economic opportunity*. The Brookings Institution.
- Dickey, D. A., & Fuller, W. A. (1979). Distribution of the estimators for autoregressive time series with a unit root. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 74(366a), 427-431.
- Edinoh, K., Odili, C., & Felicia, O. (2024). Inflation, academic staff job performance, and students' academic work in tertiary education in Nigeria. *International Journal on Leadership*, 1(3), 9-16. Available online: <https://eminentpublishing.us/index.php/IJLIM>
- Haubrick, H. (2022). Inflation's role in tertiary enrollment: A global study. *Atlantic Economic Journal*, 50(3), 175–177. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11293-022-09754-5>
<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/FP.CPI.TOTL.ZG?locations=NG>
- Ihugba, O. A., Obiukwu, S., Akobundu, P. L., Osunkwo, T., Oyalede, O., & Okonkwo, K. (2022). Effect of household income and expenditure on tertiary school enrolment in Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies*, 14(2), 87-98.
- Kareem, T. (2024, November 5). The Nigeria education crisis 2: The access gap. *Edugist*. https://edugist.org/the-nigeria-education-crisis-2-the-access-gap/?utm_source=chatgpt.com

- Mincer, J. (1958). Investment in human capital and personal income distribution. *Journal of Political Economy*, 66(4), 281-302.
- Offem, O. O., & Okeke, K. C. (2024). Funding architecture and administrative autonomy for academic freedom: The challenges of rising cost of tertiary education in Nigeria. *Asaba Review*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11107582>.
- Onyekachi, M. C. (2024). Inflation and education in Nigeria: An analysis. *Electronic Research Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 6(3). ISSN: 2706-8242. Retrieved from www.eresearchjournal.com
- Oyeyemi, A. A., & Tochukwu, A. (2024). Perceived influence of inflation on Nigeria's educational system: A case study of Federal Polytechnic, Oke. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 8(3), 1602-1613. <https://doi.org/10.47772/IJRIS.2024.803117>.
- Pesaran, M. H., Shin, Y., & Smith, R. J. (2001). Bounds testing approaches to the analysis of level relationships. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 16(3), 289–326. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jae.616>
- Phillips, P. C. B., & Perron, P. (1988). Testing for a unit root in time series regression. *Biometrika*, 75(2), 335-346.
- Psacharopoulos, G. (1994). Returns to investment in education: A global update. *World Development*, 22(9), 1325–1343.
- Schultz, T. (1959). Investment in man: An economist's view. *Social Service Review*, 33(2), 109-117.
- Schultz, T. (1960). Capital formation by education. *Journal of Political Economy*, 68(6), 571-583.
- Schultz, T. (1961). Investment in human capital. *American Economic Review*, 51(1), 1-17.
- Shin, Y., Yu, B., & Greenwood-Nimmo, M. (2014).** Modelling asymmetric cointegration and dynamic multipliers in a nonlinear ARDL framework. In R. Sickles & W. Horrace (Eds.), *Festschrift in honor of Peter Schmidt* (pp. 281–314). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4899-8008-3_9
- Tilak, J. B. G. (2002). Determinants of household expenditure on education in rural India. National Council of Applied Economic Research.
- Ukozor, C. U., Ayeni, E. O., & Andeshi, C. A. (2024). Inflation and tertiary education administration in Nigeria. *American Journal of Open University Education*, 1(1).
- UNICEF. (2024, September 9). Immediate action needed to protect Nigeria's children and schools. *UNICEF*. https://www.unicef.org/nigeria/press-releases/immediate-action-needed-protect-nigerias-children-and-schools?utm_source=chatgpt.com

World Bank. (2023). Inflation and its impact on human capital investment in Sub-Saharan Africa. World Bank Publications.

World Bank. (2025). *Education overview*. The World Bank. Retrieved April 7, 2025, from <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/education/overview>.

THE LINK BETWEEN SOCIAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT AND INTERNATIONAL FINANCE CORPORATION PERFORMANCE STANDARDS

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the increasing importance of Social Impact Assessment (SIA) and International Finance Corporation (IFC) Performance Standards in sustainable development, especially for large-scale infrastructure and resource projects. Both frameworks are designed to lessen negative social and environmental impacts, making sure projects benefit communities, protect ecosystems, and foster economic growth. The study examines how SIA and IFC Performance Standards work together to create a more inclusive and sustainable development process. SIA is highlighted as vital for identifying social impacts early, addressing community needs, and minimizing negative effects, while also promoting stakeholder engagement and equitable benefit distribution. IFC Standards cover areas like environmental management, labour, health and safety, land acquisition, and cultural heritage protection. Following these standards helps projects align with international best practices in environmental and social governance. Despite these, challenges remain, such as limited resources, political pressures, local capacity gaps, and difficulty reconciling various stakeholder interests. This paper recommends building local expertise, strengthening stakeholder engagement, and improving monitoring and reporting systems for better implementation.

Keywords: Social Impact Assessment, International Finance Corporation, IFC Performance Standards, Sustainable Development, Social Risks, Risk Mitigation.
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1. Introduction

The process of development often comes with significant social, environmental, and economic impacts, which can affect local communities in both positive and negative

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ways. To manage these impacts, a structured approach is required to evaluate, predict, and mitigate any potential risks that might arise from large-scale development projects. This is where Social Impact Assessment (SIA) plays a crucial role. SIA is an organised process used to assess the social consequences of development projects and initiatives. It is a tool that helps to identify, evaluate, and predict the potential social impacts of a project on communities, ensuring that adverse effects are minimised and positive outcomes are enhanced. Through SIA, stakeholders, especially local communities, can engage in a meaningful dialogue with developers, allowing for a better understanding of the project's potential effects, both positive and negative (Esteban-Sanchez et al., 2017).

The significance of SIA cannot be overstated, particularly in the context of sustainable development. It ensures that communities, especially vulnerable groups, are not disproportionately affected by development, and that their rights and well-being are safeguarded. SIA also fosters transparency, accountability, and greater public participation in the decision-making process. By identifying potential risks early, SIA provides a foundation for developing mitigation strategies that ensure projects are socially responsible, equitable, and inclusive (Taliento et al., 2019) especially for larger companies or groups. Starting from this premise, we carried out an original study on the financial materiality of the E-S-G (environmental, social and governance).

On the other hand, the International Finance Corporation (IFC), part of the World Bank Group, has long recognized the importance of environmental and social governance in fostering sustainable development. The IFC plays a pivotal role in promoting private sector investment in emerging economies and ensuring that projects financed by the organization uphold strict standards of social responsibility and environmental sustainability (Chakroun et al., 2019). Through its Performance Standards first introduced in 2006 and updated in 2012, the IFC provides a comprehensive framework for addressing the social, environmental, and economic risks associated with development projects.

The IFC Performance Standards consist of a set of eight key principles aimed at guiding businesses and developers in assessing and managing environmental and social risks. These standards are designed to promote responsible business practices and ensure that projects contribute to the broader goal of sustainable development. They cover critical areas such as labor rights, community health and safety, land acquisition, and the protection of cultural heritage. The standards also emphasize the importance of engaging with stakeholders, respecting indigenous peoples' rights, and fostering community-driven development. By aligning projects with the IFC Performance Standards, companies and investors can reduce risks and avoid social and environmental harm, ultimately leading to better development outcomes (Saputra et al., 2024).

The link between SIA and the IFC Performance Standards is both significant and symbiotic. Social Impact Assessments, when conducted thoroughly, serve as a tool to operationalize and support the IFC's Performance Standards in practice. The alignment between these two frameworks ensures that development projects not only comply with international sustainability standards but also actively promote social inclusion, human rights, and community development. In essence, SIA provides the empirical and participatory foundation for meeting the requirements outlined in the IFC Performance Standards, enabling projects to achieve positive, sustainable, and socially responsible

outcomes (Mason & Martindale, 2023).

This paper seeks to explore the critical relationship between SIA and the IFC Performance Standards by providing a comprehensive examination of how these two frameworks work together to ensure sustainable development. The discussion will address the essential role of SIA in identifying, assessing, and mitigating the social risks associated with projects, and how these align with the IFC's commitment to promoting environmental and social responsibility. Furthermore, the paper will examine the challenges of integrating SIA with IFC standards and provide recommendations on improving their synergy to ensure that development projects contribute to both economic growth and social well-being.

2. The Importance of Social Impact Assessment in Development Projects

Social Impact Assessment (SIA) is a critical tool used in development planning and project implementation to evaluate, predict, and manage the social consequences of development activities. Its role in development projects cannot be overstated, as it ensures that the social aspects of a project are thoughtfully considered and that community well-being is prioritized alongside economic and environmental considerations. In this section, we will explore the multifaceted importance of SIA in development projects, detailing its purpose, key components, and the broader societal value it offers (Areesophonpichet et al., 2024) in Thailand. Employing mixed methods in an exploratory sequential design, the first phase involves qualitative data collection, including focus groups and field studies, to establish the SIA system. The second phase employs quantitative data collection and applies SIA and social return on investment (SROI).

2.1. Purpose of SIA in Project Development

The primary purpose of Social Impact Assessment is to identify and assess the social consequences of a project or development initiative before, during, and after its implementation. This forward-looking process allows stakeholders to anticipate social changes and mitigate negative outcomes. The proactive nature of SIA helps to address issues before they escalate into more significant social challenges, such as conflict, displacement, or community health issues. SIA provides decision-makers with the tools to make informed choices that can promote long-term sustainability and community prosperity (Tilt et al., 2009). Others include but not limited to:

Risk Management: One of the most significant roles of SIA is risk management. Through thorough social analysis, SIA identifies potential social risks, such as increased inequality, loss of livelihoods, or negative health outcomes. By recognizing these risks early, developers can implement strategies to avoid or mitigate them. This anticipatory approach ensures that development projects do not exacerbate existing social problems or create new ones. Additionally, identifying risks allows for the development of emergency response plans that can help address unforeseen challenges during the project lifecycle.

Enhanced Stakeholder Engagement: SIA emphasizes the importance of stakeholder engagement in the planning and execution phases of a project. It encourages open dialogue with affected communities, local governments, and civil society organizations, fostering an environment of collaboration and mutual respect. By engaging stakeholders early in the process, SIA creates opportunities for them to voice their concerns, share local knowledge, and suggest practical solutions. This collaborative approach can lead to more

culturally appropriate and contextually relevant project designs, ensuring that the project aligns with local needs and priorities.

Promoting Social Sustainability: Social sustainability is at the heart of SIA. The assessment process evaluates how a project will affect various aspects of social life, including community cohesion, cultural identity, and social equity. SIA helps ensure that projects contribute positively to the social fabric of communities by enhancing livelihoods, improving access to services, and promoting social well-being. When conducted effectively, SIA can highlight opportunities for fostering positive social outcomes such as job creation, skills development, and community empowerment, thereby contributing to long-term social stability and prosperity.

2.2. Key Aspects of SIA

Effective Social Impact Assessment involves several critical components that collectively ensure a comprehensive understanding of a project's potential social implications. These components guide the process of identifying social impacts, engaging with stakeholders, and designing strategies to manage those impacts (Imperiale & Vanclay, 2023).

Stakeholder Engagement and Participation: One of the cornerstones of SIA is stakeholder engagement. The assessment process is not complete without input from those who will be directly or indirectly affected by the project. Stakeholders may include local residents, indigenous groups, workers, governmental bodies, NGOs, and others. SIA seeks to understand their concerns, expectations, and aspirations regarding the project. Engaging stakeholders allows for the identification of social impacts that might not otherwise be apparent to project developers, such as changes to community social dynamics or traditional practices. It also builds trust among community members, increasing the likelihood of project acceptance and success.

Baseline Socio-Economic Analysis: A thorough baseline socio-economic analysis is essential to understanding the context in which a project will operate. This analysis collects data on the current social, economic, and cultural conditions of the community before the project begins. It includes demographic data, economic activities, health indicators, education levels, access to services, and cultural practices. By establishing this baseline, SIA provides a reference point to measure the project's effects over time, ensuring that the assessment is grounded in local realities.

Predictive Analysis of Social Impacts: Predictive analysis involves forecasting the potential positive and negative social impacts that a project may have on the community. These impacts could range from changes in employment rates, social mobility, and income distribution to more nuanced effects such as shifts in local power structures, changes in gender dynamics, or alterations to local customs and traditions. By predicting these impacts, developers can design targeted mitigation strategies, such as resettlement plans, skills training programs, or community health interventions, to minimize negative outcomes.

Mitigation and Enhancement Strategies: Once potential impacts are identified, SIA plays a crucial role in developing mitigation strategies to minimize or eliminate adverse effects. For instance, if a project leads to the displacement of communities, the SIA process

can guide the development of resettlement programs that prioritize community needs and ensure compensation and support for those affected. Moreover, SIA can identify opportunities for enhancement strategies that improve community well-being. This might include initiatives such as local employment schemes, infrastructure improvements, or community capacity-building projects, which can offset potential negative impacts by creating tangible social benefits.

2.3. The Legal and Ethical Necessity of SIA

SIA is not only a practical tool for managing social risks; it also plays a vital role in complying with both national regulations and international frameworks. Many countries have incorporated SIA requirements into their environmental and social governance frameworks, making it a legal necessity for large-scale projects, especially those funded by international organizations like the World Bank or the International Finance Corporation (IFC). These institutions require a robust SIA to ensure that projects meet environmental and social sustainability standards (Vanclay, 2020).

National Regulations: Many countries, especially those with developing economies, have adopted legal frameworks that mandate SIA for certain types of projects, particularly those that involve large-scale land acquisition, infrastructure development, or resource extraction. These regulations aim to safeguard local communities from the negative social consequences of development and ensure that their rights are respected throughout the project cycle.

International Standards: On an international level, organizations like the World Bank, IFC, and other multilateral development banks have incorporated SIA into their funding processes. These organizations require project developers to demonstrate that social impacts have been assessed and that risks have been properly managed. This ensures that projects funded by international organizations align with global standards for social responsibility and sustainable development.

Ethical Considerations: Beyond legal obligations, SIA is also guided by ethical principles of fairness, justice, and respect for human rights. The ethical imperative for conducting SIA lies in its capacity to protect vulnerable populations from the adverse impacts of development and to ensure that they benefit from the projects affecting their lives. Social equity and community participation are core ethical considerations, particularly when projects may disrupt traditional ways of life, lead to displacement, or threaten cultural heritage. SIA serves as an ethical safeguard to ensure that development projects proceed with due respect for the communities they affect.

2.4. The Broader Societal Value of SIA

Social Impact Assessment offers broader value beyond individual projects. It contributes to the global push for sustainable development, poverty reduction, and inclusive growth. By prioritizing social impacts in the development process, SIA helps to ensure that projects contribute positively to long-term societal goals (Pradhan, 2024) these initiatives often result in negative consequences alongside their positive outcomes. These negative effects can manifest in various forms, including social, cultural, economic, and environmental impacts. As such, it is imperative to anticipate and prevent these undesirable outcomes to achieve inclusive and sustainable development. The importance of Social Impact

Assessment (SIA).

Sustainability and Development: SIA is aligned with the principles of sustainable development, which seek to balance economic growth with environmental protection and social equity. Sustainable development requires that the benefits of development are equitably distributed, particularly among disadvantaged and marginalized groups. By identifying and addressing the social impacts of projects, SIA helps ensure that projects contribute to the achievement of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly those related to poverty reduction, inequality, and responsible consumption.

Community Empowerment: The process of conducting SIA itself can empower communities by giving them a platform to express their concerns, share their knowledge, and participate in decision-making processes. Through meaningful engagement and consultation, SIA helps communities gain a voice in development processes that directly impact their lives. This empowerment fosters a sense of ownership and control over development outcomes, increasing the likelihood of project success and long-term positive social outcomes.

3. Overview of IFC Performance Standards

The International Finance Corporation (IFC), a member of the World Bank Group, is a leading development institution that supports the private sector in developing countries. It provides investments, advisory services, and technical assistance to promote sustainable economic growth. The IFC Performance Standards, established in 2006, are a critical tool for ensuring projects adhere to international standards of social and environmental responsibility. These standards serve as a framework to assess, manage, and mitigate environmental, social, and governance (ESG) risks associated with development projects (Mason & Martindale, 2023).

The IFC Performance Standards aim to create sustainable development outcomes while minimizing negative impacts on local communities, ecosystems, and economies. They focus on promoting human rights, protecting labor standards, fostering environmental stewardship, and ensuring respect for cultural heritage. The standards were introduced to address growing concerns about the social and environmental impacts of private sector development projects, particularly those financed by international financial institutions (Bristol-Alagbariya, 2020).

The purpose of these standards is to ensure that projects financed by the IFC and its partners adhere to socially responsible and environmentally sound practices. By implementing the Performance Standards, the IFC aims to promote sustainable and inclusive development, ensure development projects respect human rights, prevent and minimize adverse social and environmental impacts, and encourage corporate responsibility and transparency in project execution. Over time, the Performance Standards have evolved to incorporate emerging global challenges, such as climate change, biodiversity conservation, and the rights of indigenous peoples, making them more comprehensive and responsive to contemporary development issues.

The International Finance Corporation (IFC) Performance Standards are a set of eight

principles that guide project developers, investors, and stakeholders in managing social and environmental risks throughout the project lifecycle. These standards aim to ensure that projects contribute positively to sustainable development by balancing economic, environmental, and social considerations (Bristol-Alagbariya, 2020).

Kvam, 2012

The first standard, Assessment and Management of Environmental and Social Risks and Impacts, establishes the foundation for identifying, assessing, and managing environmental and social risks associated with a project. It requires a comprehensive environmental and social risk assessment at the outset of the project, and a management plan is developed to address identified risks. This includes identifying potential risks to communities, workers, and the environment, and establishing measures to prevent or mitigate these risks.

The second standard, Labor and Working Conditions, focuses on the rights and welfare of workers involved in the project, aiming to ensure fair labor practices, safe working conditions, and respect for human rights. Key Requirements include adherence to international labor rights, fair wages, proper working hours, and the right to freedom of association (Amirkhanova & Vogelsberger, 2015)

The third standard, Resource Efficiency and Pollution Prevention, addresses the efficient use of resources and the prevention of pollution throughout the project's lifecycle. It requires projects to minimize the use of natural resources, reduce emissions, and prevent pollution. It also requires projects to adopt sustainable practices, such as energy-efficient technologies and waste management systems, to reduce their environmental footprint.

The fourth standard, Community Health, Safety, and Security, seeks to protect the health, safety, and security of local communities who may be affected by the project. Key Requirements include providing adequate health infrastructure, emergency response mechanisms, and securing the safety of communities against potential project-related security threats.

The fifth standard, Land Acquisition and Involuntary Resettlement, governs land acquisition processes, ensuring that affected individuals are compensated and resettled in a manner that respects their rights and livelihoods. Key Requirements include conducting biodiversity assessments, implementing conservation measures, and ensuring that natural resources are used sustainably. Performance Standard Six focuses on biodiversity conservation and sustainable management of living natural resources. It requires projects to minimize adverse impacts on biodiversity, ecosystems, and habitats. Key requirements include conducting biodiversity assessments, implementing conservation measures, and ensuring sustainable use of natural resources.

The seventh standard, Indigenous Peoples, ensures that the rights of indigenous peoples are respected, particularly when projects affect their land, resources, and cultures. Key Requirements include conducting culturally sensitive consultations with indigenous peoples and ensuring that their rights to land, territories, and resources are protected.

Lastly, the eighth standard, Cultural Heritage, seeks to protect cultural heritage from potential harm due to project activities. Key Requirements include taking steps to avoid damage to cultural heritage sites and developing a Cultural Heritage Management Plan to address potential impacts on cultural properties.

The IFC Performance Standards have had a profound impact on development projects worldwide, influencing both private and public sector approaches to social and environmental governance. Their implementation has led to more responsible investment, improved stakeholder relationships, and enhanced project outcomes in terms of social inclusion, environmental protection, and long-term economic sustainability (Amirkhanova & Vogelsberger, 2015)

4. The Link Between Social Impact Assessment and IFC Performance Standards

The relationship between Social Impact Assessment (SIA) and the International Finance Corporation (IFC) Performance Standards is both crucial and symbiotic. SIA and the IFC Performance Standards are complementary tools in the realm of sustainable development, both working toward the common goal of minimizing negative impacts and maximizing positive outcomes for communities, the environment, and the economy. While SIA focuses on identifying, assessing, and managing social risks and impacts, the IFC Performance Standards provide a structured framework for ensuring that these risks are adequately addressed in alignment with international best practices (Vanclay et al., 2015).

The link between SIA and the IFC Performance Standards lies in their shared objective: to promote sustainable development through the careful consideration of social, environmental, and economic impacts. SIA provides the empirical and participatory foundation for meeting the requirements set forth by the IFC Performance Standards.

This section explores how SIA and the IFC Performance Standards interact, with a focus on the practical integration of the two frameworks to ensure that development projects contribute to positive social outcomes while minimizing potential harm.

The International Finance Corporation (IFC) Performance Standards, specifically Performance Standard 1, mandate the rigorous assessment and management of environmental and social risks and impacts in development projects. SIA plays a crucial role in identifying and analyzing these risks from a social perspective, providing valuable insights into the social dynamics of affected communities. This information is crucial for developing mitigation strategies and ensuring socially responsible project design. SIA also supports the development of a comprehensive risk management framework, which aligns with IFC's guidance on risk management. This includes determining the severity of potential impacts, proposing mitigation strategies, and monitoring their effectiveness throughout the project lifecycle. Stakeholder engagement is also a critical aspect of Performance Standard 1, involving meaningful consultations with local communities, indigenous groups, and civil society organizations. This two-way communication strengthens the overall project design, fosters community support, and avoids conflicts, ensuring smoother project implementation (Kvam, 2018).

The Social Impact Assessment (SIA) plays a crucial role in ensuring that development projects are conducted responsibly, minimizing negative social and environmental impacts while promoting positive outcomes for communities. It helps developers identify potential risks to labor conditions, such as unsafe working environments, discrimination, and unfair wages, and ensures compliance with international labor laws. SIA also helps develop targeted mitigation strategies that align with Performance Standard 2, such as establishing grievance mechanisms for workers, implementing health and safety training, or ensuring fair wages and benefits (Vanclay, 2023). Social impact assessment is a valued part of project development and will continue to be so. Over time, there has been a shift in understanding, from social impact assessment being a regulatory tool to now being the process of managing social issues throughout the life of a project. The range of issues considered has become much wider, now also including human rights. More than a tool or approach, social impact assessment is a discourse, a body of scholars and practitioners, a paradigm, and a philosophy about development and the rights of affected communities. The proper consideration of social impacts is now expected by all project stakeholders and is a requirement of international standards and project financing. There is now recognition of the need for projects to gain and maintain social acceptance, or a social license to operate and grow. Key current issues include: human rights; doing good rather than just doing no harm; benefit-sharing arrangements; Indigenous-led social impact assessment and community-based social impact assessment; and gender, LGBTQI+, two-spirit people, and intersectionality. Social impact assessment is increasingly being used to assist communities in negotiating Impact and Benefit Agreements (or Community Development Agreements).

Performance Standard 4 focuses on protecting communities from risks arising from project activities, particularly in relation to health, safety, and security. SIA assesses potential health risks associated with the project, including the spread of disease, exposure to pollutants, or increased pressure on local health services. It provides the necessary foundation for developing community health and safety plans that align with

the requirements of Performance Standard 4. Security and Community Protection: SIA helps to assess potential risks to community security, particularly if the project requires security personnel or may lead to community unrest (Gulakov & Vanclay, 2024).

Performance Standard 5 addresses the complex issues of land acquisition, displacement, and resettlement. SIA plays a central role in identifying and mitigating the social impacts of land acquisition, ensuring that affected individuals and communities are treated fairly and their rights are protected. It evaluates the potential social impacts of land acquisition, including the loss of livelihood, disruption of social structures, and emotional and cultural effects of displacement. SIA directly informs the creation of Resettlement Action Plans (RAPs), which are essential for ensuring that the project complies with Performance Standard 5. By engaging with affected communities and conducting thorough assessments, SIA ensures that the resettlement process is transparent, equitable, and respectful of the rights of displaced people (Franks & Vanclay, 2013).

Performance Standards 7 and 8 are dedicated to the protection of Indigenous Peoples' rights and Cultural Heritage. SIA assesses the potential impacts of a project on indigenous peoples, including the risk of displacement, loss of traditional livelihoods, or destruction of sacred sites. By consulting with indigenous communities and experts in cultural heritage, SIA ensures that the project aligns with the specific requirements of Performance Standards 7 and 8.

The link between SIA and the International Framework for Convention on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (IFC Performance Standards) is essential in ensuring that development projects are conducted responsibly, minimizing negative social and environmental impacts while promoting positive outcomes for communities (Kamakia, 2015)the National Environment Management Authority of Kenya (NEMA).

5. Steps in the Social Impact Assessment (SIA) Process

Below are the outlines of a structured, 10-steps approach to conducting an SIA, as modelled after the Council on Environmental Quality (CEQ) guidelines:

ICGPSIA, 1974.

Public Involvement: This involves identifying and engaging all potentially affected groups (e.g., residents, displaced populations, stakeholders). This can be achieved using interviews, surveys, and participatory methods (not just public meetings) to capture diverse concerns.

Identification of Alternatives: Here, the proposed action is described (e.g., project, policy) and reasonable alternatives. This entails gathering details like location, workforce needs, and institutional resources to frame the SIA scope.

Baseline Conditions: At this stage, documentation of all existing social, economic, and cultural conditions in the affected area is made; taking cognizance of the historical context, demographic trends, political structures, and community resources of the area.

Scoping: This stage entails identifying probable social impacts through literature reviews, expert input, and public feedback; hence, prioritizing significant impacts using criteria like duration, reversibility, and equity.

Projection of Estimated Effects: This stage is concerned with comparing future conditions with and without the project to assess impacts by employing methods like comparative analysis, scenarios, expert testimony, or modelling.

Predicting Responses to Impacts: the crux of this stage is to estimate how affected groups will react (e.g., attitudes, actions) based on past cases and surveys and ensuring that potential conflicts or adaptive behaviours are highlighted.

Indirect and Cumulative Impacts: This involves assessing secondary effects such as community growth from new jobs and combined impacts from other projects.

Changes in Alternatives: This stage is characterized with recommendation of modifications to the project/policy in order to mitigate adverse impacts, and by so doing, evaluate consequences of new alternatives.

Mitigation: Critical in this stage is the development of strategies to avoid, minimize or compensate for negative impacts such as, rerouting infrastructure, community compensation, etc.

Monitoring: This is the final stage/step in the social impact assessment process. It requires establishing a program to track deviations from projected impacts and adapt mitigation measures, especially for projects with high uncertainty or data gaps.

Suffices to note that these processes ensure SIAs are comprehensive, transparent, and actionable for decision-makers under such frameworks like NEPA. Most importantly, the process must be evidence-based, flexible and follow a participatory approach (ICGPSIA, 1994).

6. Challenges in Implementing SIA and IFC Performance Standards

The implementation of Social Impact Assessment (SIA) and the framework for the International Finance Corporation (IFC) Performance Standards is crucial for ensuring

socially and environmentally sustainable development projects. However, these initiatives often face significant challenges due to limited resources, political and economic pressures, gaps in local capacity, and the complex nature of aligning social, environmental, and governance objectives within large-scale projects (Amirkhanova & Vogelsberger, 2015).

One of the main barriers to effective SIA implementation is the lack of technical expertise and trained personnel in developing countries. This can lead to superficial assessments that fail to capture the full scope of social impacts. To overcome this, it is recommended to build local capacity through training programs and workshops for SIA practitioners, as well as provide sufficient financial resources for in-depth assessments. International organizations and development agencies can support these efforts by providing technical assistance and funding for SIA-related activities (Gulakov et al., 2020).

Political and economic pressures can also hinder the effectiveness of SIA in identifying and mitigating social risks associated with development projects. In some cases, political considerations or the desire to attract foreign investment can pressure project developers or government officials to overlook or downplay the social risks identified through SIA. Ensuring that SIA processes are independent, transparent, and carried out with meaningful community participation can help mitigate political interference (Franks & Vanclay, 2013).

Time constraints and project deadlines can also pose challenges. Large-scale projects often operate under tight deadlines, which can lead to rushed or incomplete SIAs. To address this, SIA should be integrated into the early stages of project planning, and project timelines designed to accommodate thorough assessments. Developers should build flexibility into their project schedules to allow for adequate consultation and data analysis.

Aligning SIA with IFC Performance Standards can be challenging due to differences in regulatory frameworks, scope, and stakeholder expectations. The complexity of compliance with multiple standards can make it difficult to ensure that SIA addresses all aspects of the standards comprehensively. To address this complexity, SIA should be designed to encompass all eight IFC Performance Standards cohesively, ensuring that the social risks associated with each standard are identified and managed (Theißen et al., 2020) which means that their embodied impacts are usually underestimated. Open Building Information Modeling (BIM).

Conflicting interests among stakeholders, such as government officials, local communities, indigenous groups, and private investors, can also complicate the implementation process. Effective stakeholder engagement and conflict resolution strategies are essential for aligning the interests of different parties and navigating these conflicts (Vanclay, 2020).

The implementation of Social Impact Assessment (SIA) and International Finance Corporation (IFC) Performance Standards often faces challenges due to institutional capacity and regulatory frameworks. These issues stem from differences in local regulations, the ability of institutions to enforce standards, and coordination between governmental and non-governmental bodies.

Inadequate regulatory frameworks can lead to ineffective implementation of SIA and IFC Performance Standards due to weak or inadequate enforcement of policies. Strengthening national regulatory frameworks and building institutional capacity for monitoring and enforcement can ensure consistent implementation. Governments should work with international bodies to establish and enforce robust environmental and social governance standards (Imperiale & Vanclay, 2023).

Weak institutional capacity and coordination can result in fragmented oversight, leading to fragmented assessments and a lack of integrated decision-making. Establishing an integrated project governance structure that brings together various stakeholders, including government agencies, local communities, and external experts, can improve coordination and ensure all aspects of the IFC Performance Standards are properly addressed (Bristol-Alagbariya, 2020).

Monitoring and reporting on the implementation of mitigation strategies and compliance with the standards can be challenging even after an SIA has been conducted and the IFC Performance Standards have been aligned with project plans. Lack of long-term monitoring during the project's implementation or after its completion can make it difficult to ensure effective mitigation strategies and manage unintended social or environmental impacts (Amirkhanova & Vogelsberger, 2015)

Developing clear monitoring and evaluation frameworks as part of the SIA process and ensuring that monitoring continues throughout the project's lifecycle is critical. Involving local communities and other stakeholders in the monitoring process not only increases transparency but also provides valuable on-the-ground insights (Amirkhanova & Vogelsberger, 2015; Gulakov et al., 2020).

Resource and capacity constraints for small and medium-sized projects can limit their ability to fully implement these frameworks. High costs of conducting thorough SIAs and meeting the IFC Performance Standards can be prohibitively expensive for these projects. Governments and international organizations can play a role in providing support to SMEs by offering financial incentives, technical assistance, and capacity-building programs (Gulakov et al., 2020).

In conclusion, while SIA and IFC Performance Standards are crucial tools for promoting sustainable and socially responsible development, their effective implementation faces several challenges. To overcome these challenges, it is essential to strengthen local capacity, ensure coordination between stakeholders, provide adequate funding for SIA and monitoring, and improve regulatory frameworks.

7. Recommendations

The study recommends strengthening stakeholder engagement and participation by ensuring continuous engagement with local communities, indigenous groups, and vulnerable populations helps integrate local knowledge and address concerns early in the development process. It also recommends improving integration of SIA into the project lifecycle. As such, SIA should be incorporated from the early stages of the project and revisited throughout the project lifecycle to address emerging issues. And finally, leveraging technology for better impact assessment; thus, utilizing GIS and data analytics

tools can significantly improve the accuracy and effectiveness of SIA.

8. Conclusion

The integration of Social Impact Assessment (SIA) and the International Finance Corporation (IFC) Performance Standards is crucial for ensuring development projects contribute positively to communities, the environment, and the economy. SIA helps identify and manage social, environmental, and governance risks associated with development initiatives, providing a holistic approach to sustainable development. It involves stakeholders, assesses socio-economic, cultural, and environmental contexts, and enhances transparency, community participation, and accountability. The IFC Performance Standards provide guidelines for managing environmental impacts, labor conditions, community health and safety, land acquisition, indigenous peoples' rights, cultural heritage, and more. By aligning projects with these standards, developers and investors ensure they adhere to internationally recognized norms for responsible and inclusive development.

However, the successful implementation of SIA and IFC Performance Standards faces challenges such as capacity limitations, political and economic pressures, weak institutional frameworks, and the complexity of aligning diverse stakeholder interests. Addressing these challenges requires a multi-pronged approach that includes strengthening local expertise, ensuring effective regulatory frameworks, fostering collaboration among stakeholders, and providing adequate resources for monitoring and evaluation.

The future of development lies in balancing economic growth with social responsibility and environmental stewardship. Successful application of SIA and IFC Performance Standards allows for early risk identification, transparent decision-making, and equitable distribution of development benefits. By strengthening these frameworks, we can contribute to a more sustainable and equitable future where development serves the needs of both present and future generations.

REFERENCES

- Amirkhanova, E., & Vogelsberger, R. (2015). Challenges and Advantages of IFC Performance Standards: ERM Experience. 59–69. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-10311-2_3
- Areesophonpichet, S., Lawthong, N., & Panbamrungkij, T. (2024). Maximising the value of research projects for sustainable society development: The triple S system of social impact assessment – A case study of Chulalongkorn University research projects, Thailand. *Journal of Adult and Continuing Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14779714241306883>
- Bristol-Alagbariya, E. T. (2020). IFC Environmental & Social Performance Standards: Soft Law Project & Company Financing Partnerships towards Good Environmental Governance, Business Sustainability and Sustainable Development in Developing Countries. *International Affairs and Global Strategy*, 81, 51–68. <https://doi.org/10.7176/iags/81-07>
- Chakroun, S., Salhi, B., Amar, A. B., & Jarbouï, A. (2019). The impact of ISO 26000 social

- responsibility standard adoption on firm financial performance. *Management Research Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/mrr-02-2019-0054>
- Esteban-Sanchez, P., Cuesta-González, M., & Paredes-Gázquez, J. (2017). Corporate social performance and its relation with corporate financial performance: International evidence in the banking industry. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 162, 1102–1110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.06.127>
- Franks, D., & Vanclay, F. (2013). Social Impact Management Plans: Innovation in corporate and public policy. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 43, 40–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2013.05.004>
- Gulakov, I., & Vanclay, F. (2024). Continuing to Put People First: Embedding community investment in the sustainability standards of international financial institutions. *Sustainable Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.3003>
- Gulakov, I., Vanclay, F., Ignatev, A., & Arts, J. (2020). Challenges in meeting international standards in undertaking social impact assessment in Russia. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2020.106410>
- Imperiale, A., & Vanclay, F. (2023). From project-based to community-based social impact assessment: New social impact assessment pathways to build community resilience and enhance disaster risk reduction and climate action. *Current Sociology*, 72, 697–717. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00113921231203168>
- International Committee on Guidelines and Principles for Social Impact Assessment (1994). *Guidelines and principles for social impact assessment*. U.S. Department of Commerce, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, National Marine Fisheries Service. <https://www.iaia.org/pdf/IAIAMemberDocuments/Publications/SIA>
- Kamakia, A. M. (2015). Environmental and Social Impact Assessment (ESIA) Policy in Kenya and International Finance Corporation (IFC): A Comparative Perspective. <https://doi.org/10.2139/SSRN.2659517>
- Kvam, R. (2012). IFC's Sustainability Framework: Recent Updates & Changes. International Association for Impact Assessment (IAIA). International Finance Corporation (IFC) (World Bank Group). <https://www.iaia.org/pdf/wab/IFC>
- Kvam, R. (2018). Social Impact Assessment: Integrating Social Issues in Development Projects. <https://doi.org/10.18235/0001138>
- Mason, A. R., & Martindale, A. (2023). Rethinking Cultural Heritage in the International Finance Corporation Performance Standards. *Advances in Archaeological Practice*, 11, 388–401. <https://doi.org/10.1017/aap.2023.26>
- Pradhan, S. K. (2024). Social Impact Assessment of Urban Mass Transit: A Case Study of Metro Rail in India. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research*

- Technology (IJISRT). <https://doi.org/10.38124/ijisrt/ijisrt24mar1483>
- Saputra, C. C., Anthonie, R. M., & Hwihanus. (2024). Corporate Social Responsibility and International Business: A Study of the Impact on Firm Performance. *International Journal of Educational Research*. <https://doi.org/10.62951/ijer.v1i2.27>
- Taliento, M., Favino, C., & Netti, A. (2019). Impact of Environmental, Social, and Governance Information on Economic Performance: Evidence of a Corporate 'Sustainability Advantage' from Europe. *Sustainability*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU11061738>
- Theißen, S., Höper, J., Drzymalla, J., Wimmer, R., Markova, S., Meins-Becker, A., & Lambertz, M. (2020). Using Open BIM and IFC to Enable a Comprehensive Consideration of Building Services within a Whole-Building LCA. *Sustainability*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12145644>
- Tilt, B., Braun, Y., & He, D. (2009). Social impacts of large dam projects: A comparison of international case studies and implications for best practice. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 90 Suppl 3, 249–257. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2008.07.030>
- Vanclay, F. (2020). Reflections on Social Impact Assessment in the 21st century. *Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal*, 38, 126–131. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14615517.2019.1685807>
- Vanclay, F. (2023). After 50 years of social impact assessment, is it still fit for purpose? *Current Sociology*, 72, 774–788. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00113921231203189>
- Vanclay, F., Esteves, A., Aucamp, I., & Franks, D. (2015). Social Impact Assessment: Guidance for assessing and managing the social impacts of projects. <https://consensus.app/papers/social-impact-assessment-guidance-for-assessing-and-vanclay-esteves/8e5d91c94ace5fa29e62d90f11d2a227/>

CLIMATE CHANGE, AGRICULTURAL OUTPUT AND FOOD SECURITY IN NIGERIA: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Many Nigerian farmers are highly vulnerable to change in climate due to their dependence on rain-fed agriculture, which may impact food security negatively. This research study used the Auto Regressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL) to examine the long-term and short-term impact of change in climate and agricultural output on food security from 1981 to 2023. To achieve the research objective, we sourced data from the World Bank Development Indicator (WDI) and the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO). The results indicate that the agricultural output coefficient is positive and statistically significant at 5%. This implies that a higher level of agricultural output will guarantee food security (FS) in Nigeria. The findings also indicate a significant and positive relationship between annual average rainfall (AAR) and food security (FS). Meanwhile, our findings revealed that average annual temperature (AAT) has an adverse effect on food security (FS). This implies that climate change is a main factor in determining food security in Nigeria. The findings should be useful for policymakers and analysts in Nigeria, to design climate change adaptation strategies that mitigate the adverse effects of reduced agricultural productivity and threats to food security caused by climate change.

Keywords: Climate change, Agricultural output, ARDL, Food security.

JEL code: C32. L66. Q54

1.0 Introduction

In recent decades, change in climate has emerged as a fundamental global issue, having significant implications for the environment and public health, and poses significant threats to agricultural productivity and a nation's food security (Bouteska et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2023; Frona et al., 2021). This undermines one of the sustainable development goals that emphasizes the eradication of hunger, improvement of nutrition, and guarantee of food security, as food is majorly considered a global public good that should be easily accessible to all individuals at all point time.

Given the persistent insufficient food supply and the severe malnutrition and abject poverty in many low-income economies, especially African continent, the effect of climate change on agriculture and food security is a matter of significant concern (Waha et al., 2017; Ahmed et al., 2009). Furthermore, many developing nations, such as Nigeria, are highly susceptible to the impacts of climate change because of their dependence on rain-fed agriculture, inadequate irrigation infrastructure, and limited implementation of climate-smart agricultural techniques (Ogundari & Onyeaghala, 2021; Idumah et al., 2016). The occurrence of climate-related shocks, for instance, rising temperatures, droughts, floods, and more severe weather conditions, poses a significant threat to farming livelihoods. This

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is because traditional farming methods were based on predictable rainy seasons. Climate change decreases the productive capacity of crops, fisheries, and livestock, resulting in decreased agricultural production and increased food insecurity.

It is widely known that the amount of production or output does not solely determine food security. In addition to ensuring production stability at appropriate levels, it also includes guarantees of availability, access, distribution, and utilization. In Nigeria, food security is a serious concern, with millions of individuals facing difficulties in accessing an adequate, safe, and nutritional food supply. Climate-induced food insecurity worsens poverty, malnutrition, and hunger, especially among those most vulnerable, such as children, women, and the elderly. Climate change causes changes in water distribution and availability, early flowering dates, an increased risk of late frosts as a result of faster phenological development, longer growing seasons, more frequent crop failures, rise in pest infestations, and much more (Wood et al., 2019; Ojo & Adebayo, 2012; Ayinde et al., 2011). Moreover, the rapid increase in Nigeria's population, estimated to reach 440 million by 2050 (National Bureau of Statistics), will further increase the burden on the nation's food systems, complicating the task of guaranteeing food security given the threat of change. This backdrop has led to the investigation of the nexus between climate change, agricultural output, and food security in Nigeria from 1981 to 2023.

2.0 Literature Review

Climate change as a topical issue has adjudged as one of the major factors affecting agricultural activities in both developed and developing economies. It can take different forms, which vary from drought, carbon dioxide emission, rainfall, and temperature intensity (Adesete et al. 2023; Arias et al., 2023). The availability, utilization, stability and accessibility of food, are all impacted by climate change. When people have physical and financial access to enough safe, nourishing food that reasonably meets their dietary needs and choices for an active and healthy lifestyle, they are all guaranteed food security at all times (FAO, 2000; FAO, 1996). The primary way that climate change impacts food security is recognized through food availability. Geographical location will affect how climate change affects food supply. While moderate warming boosts agricultural and pasture yields and output in temperate regions, it could negatively impact cereal crops in tropical and seasonally arid regions. However, the (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [IPCC], (2007) anticipated that temperatures exceeding 30 degrees Celsius (30 °C) would adversely impact crop production and availability across all regions. Variations in agricultural production, given that feed crops constitute around 25 percent of global farmland, will affect the availability of meat and other livestock products.

Mayo (2008) defines food availability as the amount and quantity of food accessible in a particular country or region, encompassing domestic production, imports, exchanges, processed food, and stocks, after subtracting total exports. Access to food, conversely, denotes an individual's ability to secure their rights to food. Food access refers to an individual's ability to secure sufficient resources to obtain appropriate and nutritious food necessary for a healthy diet. Food utilization involves not only the dietary composition and methods of food preparation but also encompasses cultural and social dimensions—such as the suitability of specific foods for particular seasons or occasions. Furthermore, it includes considerations of food quality and safety, as inadequate standards can result in nutrient degradation and the spread of foodborne illnesses. Food stability is achieved

as a result of consistent, availability and accessibility of adequate food at the individual, household, or population level, without significant risk of disruption due to unexpected shocks or cyclical events (FAO, 2008).

Food stability encompasses the consistent availability, accessibility, and utilization of food over time. Agricultural output intricately links all aspects of food security, serving as a source of sustenance and income for households and the broader economy (Serba & Chimdessa, 2021). The vulnerability of food security to change in climate is contingent not only upon the severity of the shock but at the same time also on the susceptibility of the food system and its interrelated components to that specific shock, reflecting the system's inclination to suffer negative impacts (IPCC, 2007). Concentrating on the "food security vulnerability" as a result of climate change, which indicates food system's inability to provide food security outcomes in the context of climate change, encompasses environmental, social and economic dimensions (FAO, 2016).

Numerous empirical research works have explored the connection between climate change and food security in the past due to its significance (Ahmed et al., 2024; Lukman et al., 2024). countless number of these studies connect climate change to food security through the agricultural productivity channel (Ahmed et al. 2022; Dasgupta et al. 2023). To support their findings, Bouteska et al. (2024) used time series data from 2011 to 2023 to show that change in climate (abnormal rainfall and temperature) hurt foods like barley, maize, and sorghum in Ethiopia. Oyelami et al. (2023) also used cross-sectional autoregressive distributed lag (CS-ARDL) to show similar results in African countries. For a comprehensive review of the topic, see: El Bilali et al. (2020), Islam and Wong (2017), Sirba and Chimdessa (2021), and Thompson et al. (2010).

However, climate change and agricultural output can independently affect food security. Unfavorable weather patterns like drought and floods can alter the availability of food, leading to the direct destruction of crops and livestock, rather than relying solely on agricultural productivity. Few studies have investigated the relationship among change in climate, agricultural output, and food security in Nigeria. Hence, we intend to fill the research gap by investigating the nexus using novel data of average annual rainfall and average annual temperature as a proxy for change in climate

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Theoretical framework

This paper is grounded on the theoretical notion of Cobb Douglas production function, which includes climatic variables such as average rainfall and average temperature (see Belford et al. 2020; Ceesay & Ben Omar Ndiaye, 2022), which established the theoretical basis for the study. This theoretical framework provides guidance for the separation of climate change, agriculture output, and their effect on food security, as stated below:

$$FS_t = f(AAR_t, AAT_t, AGRIC_t, L_t, K_t) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where:

$Y_t = FS_t$: Food Security, at time t

AAR_t : Annual Average Rainfall (Proxy for climate change at time t)

AAT_t : Annual Average Temperature (Proxy for climate change at time t)

$AGRIC_t$: Agriculture Output, at time t

L_t :Total Labour force, at time t

K_t : Gross capital formation, at time t

Food security as a function of real capital stock (proxied by the Gross Capital Formation), change in climate (Average Annual Rainfall and Average Annual Temperature), labour (proxy Total Labour Force), and agriculture output. From equation 1, we follow the work of Dell et al. (2008), Also (Belford et al., 2020; Ceesay & Ben Omar Ndiaye, 2022; Dell et al., 2008)

$$Y_t = FS_t = Ab^{\alpha T} K_t^\rho L_t^{1-\rho-\infty-\gamma-\pi} AAR_t^\alpha AAT_t^\gamma AGRIC_t^\pi e^\epsilon \dots\dots\dots 2$$

Such that: $\rho + \infty + \alpha + \gamma + \pi = 1$

$$\frac{\Delta A_t}{A_t} = g = \beta T_t \dots\dots\dots 3$$

In this case, Y represents food security, L denotes labour, A represents level technology, K denotes gross capital formation, while T represents effect of change in climate (which is proxied as average annual temperature and average annual rainfall), g represents the growth rate of capital, t is the time, e stands for exponential, and ϵ represents the error term of the model. Meanwhile equation 2 illustrates the direct influence of climate change and agricultural output on food security. In contrast, Equation 3 highlights the indirect effects of climate change—specifically, how changes in climate can affect other variables that, in turn, affect food security. We derived equation 4 below by taking the logarithm of equation 2 and deviating it with respect to the time period.

$$g_t = g + (\alpha + \beta)T_t - \alpha T_{t-1} \dots\dots\dots 4$$

In this context, g represents output growth. The direct impact of change in climate on food security are captured by the coefficient α , reflecting factors such as changes in rainfall patterns. Meanwhile, the coefficient β accounts for the indirect effects of change in climate—such as the impact of flooding, drought, or other climate-related events on variables that, in turn, influence food security. This study aims to investigate both the direct and indirect effects of climate change and agricultural output on food security in Nigeria over the period under review. These variations of course, will offer valuable insights into the primary impact of climate and agriculture on food security indicators in Nigeria.

3.1.1 Model Specification: Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL)

The reason behind using ARDL bounds testing for co-integration in order to assess the

long-run relationship between change in climate and food security in Nigeria. The Auto-regressive Distributed Lag bound testing method, as used in the work of Pesaran et al. (2001), Pesaran (2007), Ceasey & Ben Omar Ndiaye (2022), Belford et al. (2020), Dell et al. (2008), and Menagaki (2019), are preferable compared to similar approaches and allow us to factor in the effect of lags on the variables for a reasonable period of time. We can formulate the Auto-regressive Distributed Lag bound testing approach for co-integration equations as follows:

ARDL model

$$\ln FS_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i \ln FS_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^p \beta_1 \ln AAR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^p \beta_2 \ln AAT_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^p \beta_3 \ln AGRIC_{t-i} + \epsilon_t \dots\dots\dots 5$$

Where t: t = 1, 2, 3, ..., T denotes time dimension (annual), are short run coefficients and are the long run parameters. The equations stated below are null and alternative hypothesis for testing cointegration

$$H_0: \alpha = \beta = 0$$

$$H_1: \alpha \neq \beta \neq 0$$

More specifically, the stated null hypothesis asserts that no long-run nexus exists among the variables. In contrast, alternative hypothesis suggests evidence of long run relationship.

Vector Error Correction (VECM) Model:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \ln FS_t = & \alpha_0 + \Phi T + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i \Delta \ln FS_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^p \beta_1 \Delta \ln AAR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^p \beta_2 \Delta \ln AAT_{t-i} \\ & + \sum_{i=0}^p \beta_3 \Delta \ln AGRIC_{t-i} + \epsilon_t + \lambda ECM_{t-1} + \epsilon_t \dots\dots\dots 6 \end{aligned}$$

where

ECM_{t-1} indicates lagged values after running long run model and generate residual

3.2 Data collection, Measurement and Presentation.

Data were obtained primarily from WDI and the Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis (FRED), Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO). Data descriptions, names and sources are presented in Table 1: Data on food security were obtained from FAO (2023). We used rainfall and temperature to proxy change in climate. Food security stands for the dependent variable, that is the total cereal availability in the country (see Pickson & Boateng, 2022).

Table 1

Name of Variable	Source	Proxy (Comment)	
Agriculture	WDI	Agriculture Output (\$)	
Food Security	FAO	Total Cereal Availability	
Rainfall	https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org	Average Annual Rainfall	
Temperature	https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org	Average	Annual Temperature

Own computation, 2025. Extracted from WDI and FAO

4.0 Results and Discussion

4.1 Preliminary Analysis

4.1.1 Unit Root Tests

Results of unit root test are presented in Table 2. Specifically, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF), Phillips-Perron (PP), and Kwiatkowski-Phillips-Schmidt-Shin (KPSS) tests were conducted on all variables using annual data from 1981 to 2023, both at levels and first differences. The results generated from the ADF, KPSS and PP tests indicate that the variables LFS and LAGRIC are non-stationary in their level forms but then become stationary after first differencing at the 1% significance level. In contrast, the variables LAAR and LAAT are stationary in both levels and first differences. These findings suggest that the variables are integrated of different orders—either I(0) or I(1)—but none is integrated of order two, I(2). As a result, the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model is deemed appropriate for the analysis (refer to Table 2).

Table 3 indicates descriptive statistics for the series estimated in this study. In all, four variables were presented by their proxies, which include: cereal production (proxy, food security), average annual temperature (°C) and average annual rainfall (millimeter), (proxy, climate change), and agricultural output (control variable). The mean of the variables ranges from 24.19 to 3.30. Agricultural output has the highest mean value, while temperature (°C) recorded the lowest value. Likewise, the standard deviation ranges from 0.83 to 0.0090. The number of observations is 42.

Table 2: Unit Root Test

Variable Names	ADF		PP		KPSS	
	Level	1st Diff	Level	1st Diff	Level	1st Diff
LFS	-2.3798	-2.7670**	-2.1329	-8.121***	0.7281	0.2734***
LAAR	-4.855***	-11.484***	-4.965***	-16.69***	0.4126**	0.4090***
LAAT	-6.080***	-2.754***	-1.4326	-2.541***	0.6104*	0.1602***
LAGRIC	-0.1885	-4.8886***	-0.6137	-4.844***	0.3365	0.4051***

Source: Authors' computation 2025

Note: The values in this table are the ADF, PPP and KPSS test statistics. (*), (**) and (***) represent the probability values of the t-statistics which show statistically significant at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively. While LFS, LAAR, LAAT and LGRIC represent Food Security, Average Annual Rainfall, Average Annual Temperature and Agricultural Output respectively.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	max
FS	42	16.86053	0.375360	15.90156	17.46758
AAR	42	7.054007	0.074868	6.789039	7.167640
AAT	42	3.304656	0.008953	3.287655	3.315276
AGRIC	42	24.19240	0.831327	22.95992	25.46629

Source: Authors' computation 2025

4.2 Result and Discussion

The dependent variable (LSF), the ADF, KPSS and PP, tests results satisfy the strict first-difference stationary condition. The Pesaran, Shin, and Smith (PSS) below denote the optimal lag for co-integration. Therefore, the unit root test results in Table 3 demonstrate a mixture order of integration, namely I(0) and I(1). The F-Bound test examines the co-integration of food security in Nigeria. The result of the F-Bound test in Table 4 indicates a significant cointegration test between food security (LSF), agriculture output (LAGRIC), average annual rainfall (LAAR), and average annual temperature (LAAT). In Table 4, the F-bound test statistics value of 6.90 is greater than the upper bounds critical values at 10%, 5%, 2.5%, and 1% levels of significance, which implied that there is a long-run relationship between food security, agriculture output, and climate change. As a result, cointegration (that is, a long-run relationship) exists among the variables in the model; the appropriate model is to evaluate both the short-run and long-run coefficients of the Auto-regressive Distributed Lag, which consist of the error correction model (ECM).

Table 4: ARDL (4,2,1,3)

Short-run Coefficients and (ECM) error correction coefficient. Dept. Variable is				
Variables	Coeff.	Std error	t-statistics	Prob.
C	17.92321	3.201927	5.597633	0.0000
@TREND	0.024039	0.004495	5.348078	0.0000
(-1)	0.074075	0.132865	0.557517	0.5826
	0.251713	0.211878	1.188007	0.2470
	0.529032	0.223379	2.368313	0.0267
	-21.60558	10.23564	-2.110818	0.0459
	-0.042877	0.039186	-1.094200	0.2852
(-1))	0.053848	0.042842	1.256902	0.2214
(-2))	0.099183	0.043922	2.258182	0.0337

-1)	-0.871336	0.155951	-5.587226	0.0000
Estimated Long run Coefficient with Dependent variable of				
	1.151705	0.611408	1.883694	0.0723
	-3.107110	4.551391	-0.682673	0.5016
	-0.088868	0.053118	-1.673017	0.1079
Bound and Diagnostic Test				
	Value		I(0)	I(1)
F-Statistics	6.9037***		5.17	6.36
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test				0.3618
Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey				0.4491

Source: Authors' computation 2025

ECM denotes cointegration equation coefficient and (*), (**) and (***) represents t-statistics which are significance at 10%, 5% and 1% respectively.

Table 4 contains the long-run and short-run coefficient evaluations of autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL: 4, 2, 1, 3), with trend and constant. Food security (FS) is the explanatory variable. It demonstrates that a change in food security growth on its own lag is insignificant and positive in the short run. In the short run, there is a positive but insignificant increase in the agricultural output coefficient at lag one. This suggests that the agricultural sector's contribution to addressing food security is insufficient. Meanwhile, lag (2) values of agricultural output have a positive impact on food security and are statistically significant at 5%. This shows that an increase in food production will guarantee food security in Nigeria. Numerically, a 1% increase in agricultural output leads to a 0.09% rise in food security; this result is in line with the results reported by Wood et al. (2019) and contradicts the findings of Ceesay & Ben Omar Ndiaye (2022), who reported that agricultural output has a negative effect on food security due to the poor performance of the agricultural sector. In the short run, the annual rainfall (average) has a positive insignificant effect on food security at 10%. Meanwhile, Lag 1 of average annual rainfall has a favorable effect on food security and is statistically significant at 5%. Numerically, a 1% rise in average annual rainfall will lead to a 0.53% increase in food security. Contrarily, average annual temperature has an adverse and significant effect on food security. This result corroborates the findings of (Bouteska et al. 2024; Oyelami et al., 2023; Ringler et al., 2010). The recent shifting pattern of rainfall in Nigeria, a result of climate change, has led to significant losses in agricultural output production. However, the effect of rainfall is not enough to offset the negative effect of annual temperature (average). This finding aligns with the findings of (Haque & Khan, 2022).

Meanwhile, the long result indicates that average annual rainfall has a positive and significant effect on food security in Nigeria. This implies that an increase 1% of average annual rainfall will increase food security by 1.15%. The increase in rainfall will have a positive impact on the agricultural sector, spurring food production and eventually increasing food security. On the contrary, both average annual temperature and agricultural output have an adverse and insignificant effect on food security.

ECM (-1) = -0.8713, P-value of 0.0000, standard error (0.15595), and the t-statistic value

of -5.587226. The result of ECM allows the long-run behavior of the dependent variable to align with the long-run equilibrium, while also aligning with a broader range of short-run dynamics coefficients estimated. The coefficient of the ECM dependent variable is rightly signed (-0.8713) and statistically significant at 1% level of significance. The speed of adjustment to the long-run equilibrium is 87% (see Table 4). The stability of the model is confirmed through a series of diagnostic tests, including the CUSUM and CUSUM of squares tests, the recursive estimation test, the Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test for serial correlation, and the normality test of the residuals. These results, presented in the Appendix, provide evidence that the model is both statistically sound and stable over the estimation period.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

This study examined the relationship between climate change, agricultural output, and food security in Nigeria using time series data from 1981 to 2023. The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) method of analysis was adopted to analyze the effect of change in climate and agricultural output on food security in Nigeria within the study period. The results indicate that agricultural output has a positive and statistically significant effect on food security at the 5% significance level, suggesting that increased agricultural production contributes to improved food security in Nigeria. Additionally, the analysis reveals a positive and significant relationship between annual average rainfall and food security. Conversely, annual average temperature exhibits a negative impact on food security, highlighting the role of climate change as a critical factor influencing food security outcomes in the country.

In light of these findings, the study recommends that policymakers in Nigeria prioritize the development of climate change adaptation strategies. These should include establishing alternative and reliable sources of water to reduce dependence on rainfed agriculture. Such measures are essential for mitigating the adverse effects of climate change on agricultural productivity and ensuring long-term food security in Nigeria.

Appendix

REFERENCES

- Adesete, A. A., Olanubi, O. E., & Dauda, R. O. (2023). Climate change and food security in selected Sub-Saharan African Countries. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 25(12), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-022-02681-0>
- Ahmed, S., Diffenbaugh, N., & Hertel, T. (2009) Climate volatility deepens poverty vulnerability in developing countries, *Environmental Research letters*, 4 (8), 19-

34.

- Arias, P. A., Rivera, J. A., Sörensson, A. A., Zachariah, M., Barnes, C., Philip, S., ... & Otto, F. E. (2024). Interplay between climate change and climate variability: the 2022 drought in Central South America. *Climatic Change*, 177(1), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-023-03664-4>
- Ayinde, O. E., Muchie, M., & Olatunji, G. B. (2011). Effect of Climate Change on Agricultural Productivity in Nigeria: A Co-integration Model Approach. *Journal of Human Ecology*, 35(3), 189-194.
- Belford, C., Delin, H., Ceesay, E., Ahmed, Y. N., & Jonga, R. H. (2020). Climate change effects on economic growth: mixed empirical evidence. *International Journal of Human Capital in Urban Management*, 5(2), 99–110. <https://doi.org/10.22034/IJHCUM.2020.02.02>
- Bouteska, A., Sharif, T., Bhuiyan, F., & Abedin, M. Z. (2024). Impacts of the changing climate on agricultural productivity and food security: Evidence from Ethiopia. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 449. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.141793>
- Canziani, J. P. Palutikof, P. J. vander Linden and C.E. Hanson, Eds., Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, 7-22
- Ceesay, E. K., & Ben Omar Ndiaye, M. (2022). Climate change, food security and economic growth nexus in the Gambia: Evidence from an econometrics analysis. *Research in Globalization*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resglo.2022.100089>
- Dasgupta, S., Emmerling, J., & Shayegh, S. (2023). Inequality and growth impacts of climate change—insights from South Africa. *Environmental Research Letters*, 18(12), 124005. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-022-02681-0>
- Dell, M., Jones, B. F., & Olken, B. A. (2008). *Climate Change and Economic Growth: Evidence from the Last Half Century*.
- El Bilali, H., Bassole, I. H. N., Dambo, L., Berjan, S. (2020). Climate change and food security. *Agriculture and Forestry*, 66 (3): 197-210. <https://doi: 10.17707/AgricultForest.66.3.16>
- FAO. (1996). *Rome Declaration on World Food Security and World Food Summit Plan of Action*. World Food Summit 13-17 November 1996. Rome.
- FAO. (2000). *Land resources and potential constraints at regional and country levels*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), Rome.
- FAO .(2008). *Climate change, bioenergy and food security: Options for decision makers identified by expert meeting*. Prepared for the high-level conference World Food Security: The Challenges of Climate Change and Bioenergy, June 3-5, Rome

- Frona, D., Szenderak, J., & Harangi-Rakos, M. (2021). Economic effects of climate change on global agricultural production. *Nat. Conserv.* 44(2), 117-139.
- Haque, M. I., & Khan, M. R. (2022). Impact of climate change on food security in Saudi Arabia: a roadmap to agriculture-water sustainability. *Journal of Agribusiness in Developing and Emerging Economies*, 12(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JADEE-06-2020-0127>
- Idumah, F., Mangodo, C., Igghodaro, U., & Owombo, P. (2016). Climate change and food production in Nigeria: Implication for food security in Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Science*, 8 (2), 74-83.
- Islam, M. S., & Wong, A. T. (2017). Climate change and food in/security: a critical nexus. *Environments*, 4(2), 38.
- IPCC. 2007. *Climate Change 2007. Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.*
- Mayo, R. (2008). Towards a simplified food balance sheet. Agenda item 10c, (APCAS/08/14) Asia and Pacific commission on agricultural statistics, twenty-second session, Kuching, Malaysia. Retrieved from <http://www.fao.org/3/a-bt544e.pdf>
- Menegaki, A. N. (2019). The ARDL method in the energy-growth nexus field; best implementation strategies. In *Economies* (Vol. 7, Issue 4). MDPI Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute. <https://doi.org/10.3390/economies7040105>
- National Bureau of Statistics (n.d.). Official website. <http://www.nigerianstat.gov.ng>
- Ogundari, K. & Onyeaghala, R. (2021). The effects of climate change on African agricultural productivity growth revisited. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. 28, 30035-30045
- Ojo, O., & Adebayo, A. (2012). Climate change and the Nigerian agricultural sector: Impacts and adaptation strategies. *Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 6(1), 21-35.
- Oyelami, L. O., Edewor, S. E., Folorunso, J. O., & Abasilim, U. D. (2023). Climate change, institutional quality and food security: Sub-Saharan African experiences. *Scientific African*, 20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2023.e01727>
- Pesaran, M. H. (2007). A simple panel unit root test in the presence of cross-section dependence. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 22(2), 265–312. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jae.951>
- Pesaran, M. H., Shin, Y., & Smith, R. J. (2001). Bounds testing approaches to the analysis of level relationships. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 16(3), 289–326. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jae.616>

- Pickson, R. B., & Boateng, E. (2022). Climate change: a friend or foe to food security in Africa? *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 24(3), 4387–4412. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-021-01621-8>
- Ringler, C., Zhu, T., & Cai, X. (2010). Climate change impacts on food security in Sub-Saharan Africa: Insights from comprehensive climate change scenarios. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/237137914>.
- Sirba, A. & Chimdessa, T. (2021). Review of Impact of Climate Change on Food Security in Africa, *International Journal of Research and Innovations in Earth Science* 8(3), 40-66 ISSN (Online): 2394-1375
- Thompson, H. E., Berrang-Ford, L., & Ford, J. D. (2010). Climate change and food security in sub-Saharan Africa: a systematic literature review. *Sustainability*, 2(8), 2719-2733. doi:10.3390/su2082719
- Waha, K., Krummenauer, L., Adams, S., Aich, V., Baarsch, F., Coumou, D. & Mengel, M. (2017). Climate changes impacts in the Middle East and Northern Africa (MENA) region and their implications for vulnerable population groups, *Regional Environmental Change*, 17(6), 1623-1638.
- Wang, X., Lu, C., Cao, Y., Chen, L., & Abedin, M (2023). Decomposition, decoupling and future trends of environmental effects in the Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei region: a regional heterogeneity-based analysis. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 331, 177-124.
- Wood, A., Ansah, P, Rivers, L. & Ligmann-Zielinska, A. (2019): Examining climate change and food security in Ghana through an intersectional framework, *The Journal of Peasant Studies*, DOI: 10.1080/03066150.2019.1655639

HEALTHCARE FINANCING AND UNDER-FIVE MORTALITY IN WEST AFRICA

By

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ABSTRACT:

Healthcare financing is crucial for reducing under-five mortality and achieving sustainable health outcomes, particularly in West Africa, where child mortality remains high despite global progress. Existing studies have yielded mixed findings and often fail to account for the combined effects of public, private, and external healthcare financing. This study examined the relative effect of these financing sources on under-five mortality rates in West Africa from 2000 to 2022. Using a dynamic common correlated effects (DCCE) estimator on panel data from 16 West African countries, the study accounts for cross-sectional dependencies and long-run relationships. Findings reveal that private healthcare expenditure significantly reduces under-five mortality, while public and external healthcare spending show no significant impact. Economic growth also plays a vital role in lowering child mortality, whereas institutional quality does not. The study concludes that optimizing healthcare financing through enhanced public sector efficiency, increased private sector participation, and better governance can improve child health outcomes. Policymakers should prioritize efficient resource allocation, strengthen regulatory frameworks, and promote sustainable health investments to achieve long-term reductions in under-five mortality.

Key Words: Healthcare Financing, Sustainable Development Goals, Under-Five Mortality Rates, Dynamic Common Correlated Effects, West Africa.

JEL Classification: I10, I15, I30, C33.

1. Introduction

Healthcare financing is essential for achieving the healthcare goals established in year 2000 under the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and revised in 2015 under the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), as it guarantees sufficient healthcare resources vital for mitigating health risks, as demonstrated by developed nations investing over 10% of their GDP in health. Global healthcare financing has risen from 4.4 trillion dollars in 2000 to approximately 9.8 trillion dollars in 2021, revealing significant disparities between developed and developing nations, with Europe and North America comprising over 75% and Africa a mere 1%. Additionally, per capita health expenditure exhibits stark differences, with an approximately 80-fold variation compared to developing nations. (Logarajan 2022; WHO 2023)

Child mortality rates remain critical issues for African countries, particularly in West Africa, where mortality rates are disproportionately high relative to other global regions. While the global under-five mortality rate has decreased from 12.8 million deaths in 1990 to 5 million in 2021, with a 59% reduction in the mortality rate from 93 per 1,000 live

births in 1990 to 38 in 2021, although this remains above the UN target of 25. Leading causes of death for children under five include infectious diseases such as acute respiratory infections, diarrhea, and malaria (WHO, 2023). In Africa, the under-five mortality rate fell from 159.2 per 1,000 live births in 2000 to 78.2 in 2021, with Cape Verde, Ghana, Gambia, Mauritania, and Senegal reporting rates below 50, while Niger, Nigeria, and Sierra Leone exceeded 100 (WHO, 2023; 2015; WDI, 2023).

Existing studies (Logarajan, 2022; Umar et al., 2022; Kilanko, 2020; Lagnel and Buracom, 2020; Osakade, 2020; Akinlo and Sulola, 2018; Arthur and Oaikhenan, 2017; Akinci et al., 2014) have provided mixed findings on the impact of healthcare financing on child mortality. However, most of these studies focused on public funding or combined public and private financing without examining the role of external healthcare financing. Furthermore, few studies have accounted for cross-sectional dependencies in their data, which is essential for robust panel data analysis. Notably, none of the existing studies have used the dynamic common correlated effects (DCCE) model to assess the relationship between healthcare financing and under-five mortality rates.

This study aims to fill these gaps by investigating the relative effect of public, private, and external healthcare financing on under-five mortality rates in West Africa from 2000 to 2022. The study will use a dynamic common correlated effects (DCCE) estimator to analyze panel data from 16 West African countries, taking into account cross-sectional dependencies and long-run relationships between the variables. The remainder of the study is organized as follows: a literature review, methodology, results discussion, conclusion, and policy recommendations.

2. Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

2.1 Conceptual Clarification

Concept of Healthcare Financing

Healthcare financing refers to the approaches used to generate, distribute, and utilize funds to sustain healthcare services within a health system, as outlined by the World Health Organization (2023). This framework involves public funding through government budgets, private contributions such as out-of-pocket payments, corporate investments, and insurance, as well as external assistance from global organizations targeting healthcare in low- to middle-income regions. Effective financing ensures the mobilization and equitable allocation of resources to meet the healthcare needs of populations, providing access to affordable, quality services. Key aspects include the role of public and private funding, the influence of external aid, and the adoption of innovative financial strategies. Success in healthcare financing depends on efficient resource utilization, transparency, and accountability to achieve favorable health outcomes. Additionally, the National Health Systems Resource Centre (NHSRC) (2018) emphasizes that healthcare financing involves methods and actions designed to fund healthcare services, ensuring accessibility, affordability, and quality for all.

This study describes healthcare financing as the combined financial inputs from public, private, and external sources dedicated to supporting healthcare services. This includes funding for infrastructure, disease management, and the effective use of resources to achieve health goals and enhance overall well-being.

Concept of Under-Five Mortality Rates

The under-five mortality rate (U5MR) measures the incidence of child fatalities prior to the attainment of the age of five, expressed per 1,000 live births. The calculation of the U5MR involves dividing the aggregate number of deaths occurring in children under five years of age by the population of that demographic at mid-period. This metric functions as a barometer for the calibre of healthcare available to infants and young children, encompassing variables such as nutritional status and living conditions, while also serving as a reflection of the success of healthcare programs, including vaccination efforts and improved accessibility to medical services (WHO 2022; MDGs 2015; Burstein et al 2019).

This study conceptualizes under-five mortality rate (U5MR) as the number of deaths of children under five per 1,000 live births. It reflects healthcare quality, nutrition, living conditions, and access to medical services. U5MR also indicates the effectiveness of child health programs and healthcare systems.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This research is anchored on the Health Expenditure Outcome theory which posits that increased healthcare expenditure leads to improved health metrics, particularly mortality rates, as first delineated by Joseph Newhouse in the 1970s. Subsequent research has affirmed its applicability in diverse contexts, particularly in developing nations, indicating that enhanced investment in healthcare systems promotes better health indicators through expanded access and quality of care. Furthermore, the theory elucidates the complex interplay of economic, social, and environmental factors within health production, while also recognizing potential diminishing returns on expenditure, which are critical for addressing health outcomes in West Africa. Going by this theory increased health expenditure from public, private and external sources will ensure access to quality healthcare services, thereby leading to reduction in Under-five mortality rates in West Africa. (Mosley&Chen,1984; Fayissa &Gutena 2005; Bokhari, et al 2007; Novignon &Lawanson 2017).

2.3 Empirical Literature

Logarajan et al. (2022) investigated the effects of public, private, and out-of-pocket health expenditures on under-five mortality in Malaysia. Using ARDL estimation on a 22-year time series dataset, the study assessed the influence of public health expenditure, private health expenditure, out-of-pocket spending, GDP per capita, unemployment rate, and urban population on under-five mortality. Data were obtained from Malaysia's Ministry of Health, the Economic Planning Unit, and the World Bank. Findings revealed that out-of-pocket health expenditure significantly reduced under-five mortality, while public and private health expenditures were not statistically significant. The study recommended the adoption of a robust health financing safety net to enhance child health outcomes. Unlike this country-specific time series analysis, the present research will employ panel data analysis to examine multiple West African nations.

Umar et al. (2022) analyzed the relationship between government health spending and health outcomes in Nigeria using time series data from 1981 to 2020. The study examined infant mortality rates, government health expenditure, school enrollment ratios, and GDP, with data sourced from the World Bank and the Central Bank of Nigeria. Utilizing the vector autoregressive (VAR) method, the findings revealed a negative relationship between

government health spending and infant mortality, suggesting that increased healthcare investment could reduce infant mortality rates. Additionally, school enrollment emerged as a key determinant of health outcomes. It recommends increased healthcare investment for better health and education outcomes. Unlike this Nigeria-focused time series study, the present research employs panel data analysis covering multiple West African nations, incorporates various healthcare funding sources.

Boachie et al. (2020) examined the relationship between government health spending and health outcomes in Ghana using annual data from 1980 to 2014. The study analyzed life expectancy, infant mortality, and under-five mortality as dependent variables, while independent variables included public and private health expenditures, real per capita income, immunization rates, education levels, access to clean water, and physician density. Applying OLS and two-stage least squares, the findings showed that higher public health spending improved health outcomes, with a 10% increase preventing 0.102–4.4 child deaths per 1,000 live births and extending life expectancy by up to 47 days annually. However, income had a greater impact than public spending on all health indicators. Immunization, clean water access, and physician availability enhanced health outcomes, while education showed no significant effect. The study recommended increased healthcare investment for better public health. Unlike this Ghana-focused time series analysis, the present study incorporates external healthcare funding and employs panel data analysis covering multiple West African nations.

Kilanko (2020) examined the impact of healthcare spending on health outcomes in selected West African countries, focusing on infant, under-five, and maternal mortality as dependent variables. Independent variables included healthcare spending as a share of GDP, per capita public and private health expenditure, malaria incidence, GDP per capita, urbanization, and foreign aid. Using World Bank data and a fixed effects model, the study found that a 1% increase in healthcare spending as a share of GDP reduced under-five mortality by 3.9%, infant mortality by 2.4%, and maternal mortality by 4.9%, highlighting its role in human capital development. Household consumption showed mixed but insignificant effects, while GDP per capita significantly reduce under-five mortality. Malaria incidence had a positive but insignificant relationship with mortality, urbanization significantly reduced all mortality rates. Foreign aid significantly affecting infant mortality. Government health spending showed no significant effects, whereas private healthcare spending significantly reduced infant and under-five mortality. Unlike this study, which used first generation panel technique, the present study used second generation technique of dynamic common correlated effects.

Langnel and Buracom (2020) investigated the influence of governance and health expenditure on infant mortality in 32 Sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries from 2000 to 2015. Using data from the World Bank Development Indicators and World Governance Indicators, the study analyzed variables including infant mortality, gross national income per capita, government health expenditure as a percentage of GDP, population growth, female literacy, foreign aid, access to sanitation, and governance indicators such as voice and accountability, political stability, government effectiveness, regulatory quality, rule of law, and control of corruption. Applying the generalized method of moments (GMM), the study found no direct relationship between health expenditure, governance, and infant mortality. However, the interaction between government effectiveness and health

expenditure showed a significant inverse effect on infant mortality, suggesting that the efficiency of healthcare spending depends on a country's administrative capacity. Sensitivity analysis confirmed that health expenditure, along with its interaction with government effectiveness and political stability, contributed to lower under-five mortality rates. Given the weak governance standards in SSA, the study recommended improving governance to enhance health outcomes. Unlike this research, which focused solely on government healthcare funding and ended in 2015, the present study includes additional funding sources and extends the analysis to 2022.

Osakede (2020) investigated the relationship between public healthcare expenditure and health outcomes in Nigeria using time series data from 1980 to 2017. The study assessed the role of governance, examining both its direct influence on health status and its indirect effect as a mediator of public health spending efficiency. Key health outcome indicators—life expectancy at birth, infant mortality rate, and maternal mortality rate—were analyzed as dependent variables. Independent variables included domestic government health expenditure as a percentage of GDP, GDP (constant 2010 US\$), labor force participation rate (ages 15-64), governance indicators, and their interaction with public health spending. Data sourced from the World Bank Development Indicators was analyzed using a two-stage least squares regression method. Results indicated that public health expenditure alone did not significantly impact health outcomes unless complemented by strong governance quality. The study is limited in geographical scope to only Nigeria, this current study covers all West African countries.

Yoorim and Jinhwan (2020) analyzed the impact of health spending on infant mortality using panel data from 100 countries (31 developed, 69 developing) between 2000 and 2017. Drawing from the World Bank Development Indicators, the study examined infant mortality, health expenditure per capita, its square term, unemployment rate, GDP per capita, female tertiary education, fertility rate, and female literacy. Using a panel fixed effects model, results showed that health spending significantly reduced infant mortality, but with diminishing returns, as indicated by the positive coefficient of its square term. Unemployment had a negative yet insignificant effect, while female education indicators showed no direct impact. Conversely, fertility rate had a significant positive association with infant mortality. The interaction between health expenditure and the Gini coefficient suggested that higher inequality weakens the benefits of increased health spending. Unlike this study, which overlooks other healthcare funding sources, the present research addresses this gap.

Akinlo and Sulola (2018) examined the relationship between public health expenditure and child mortality in ten selected Sub-Saharan African countries from 2000 to 2008. Using data from the World Bank Development Indicators, the study analyzed infant and under-five mortality rates as dependent variables, while independent variables included per capita health expenditure, total health expenditure, health aid, immunization rates, urban population, GDP per capita, and HIV prevalence among adults aged 15-49. To ensure robustness, the study employed pooled OLS, fixed effects, and the generalized method of moments (GMM) for analysis. The findings indicated that government health spending had a positive impact on under-five and infant mortality rates, while per capita GDP, health aid, HIV prevalence, and immunization rates were significantly associated with lower mortality rates. This suggests that despite increased healthcare spending, there

was no substantial improvement in child mortality rates across Sub-Saharan Africa. The study only considered public healthcare funding and had a limited time frame ending in 2008. In contrast, the present research incorporates additional healthcare funding sources and extends the analysis to 2022.

Arthur and Oaikhenan (2017) analyzed the impact of health expenditure on health outcomes across 40 Sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries using data from the 2014 World Bank Development Indicators. The study focused on infant mortality rate, under-five mortality rate, and life expectancy as dependent variables, while independent variables included total, public, and private health expenditure per capita, GDP per capita, immunization rates (measles and DPT), primary school enrollment, prevalence of malaria and HIV/AIDS, undernourishment rate, access to clean water and sanitation, age dependency ratio, urban population growth, and population distribution across different age groups. Using a panel fixed effects model, the findings revealed that public health expenditure significantly reduced infant and under-five mortality rates but had no substantial effect on life expectancy, despite a positive coefficient. Conversely, private health expenditure had a strong positive impact on life expectancy and a weak negative effect on infant and under-five mortality rates. The study also highlighted a complementary relationship between public and private health spending in SSA, with public expenditure playing a dominant role. Additionally, access to clean water, sanitation, and immunization contributed to improved health outcomes, while disease prevalence and urban population growth had adverse effects. The study recommended increasing public health spending to ease the financial burden on individuals and improve health outcomes. However, it overlooked the role of external healthcare funding, which this study aims to address.

Richards and Vining (2016) investigated national-level factors influencing under-five mortality reduction in 69 low-income countries from the early 2000s to the early 2010s. Using data from the World Bank and UN agencies, the study analyzed under-five mortality rates alongside public health spending, government effectiveness, healthcare resources, immunization rates, access to clean water, fertility rates, literacy, income, and poverty. Employing panel ordinary least squares regression, findings revealed that public health spending, government effectiveness, immunization rates, poverty levels, fertility rates, and literacy significantly impacted child mortality reduction. In difference form regressions, immunization rates, mosquito net usage, and poverty changes remained significant, while government effectiveness was not. The study emphasized the importance of strengthening public institutions managing healthcare and child welfare programs. It recommended sustained political commitment to education and health services as a means for policymakers to foster economic equity and gain public support for effective policies. Unlike this study, which is limited to data up to 2010, the present research extends the analysis to 2022.

Akinci et al. (2014) examined the impact of healthcare spending on health outcomes across 19 Middle Eastern and North African (MENA) countries from 1990 to 2010. Using data from the World Health Database and World Bank Development Indicators, the study analyzed infant, child, and maternal mortality as dependent variables. Independent variables included per capita government health expenditure, government health spending as a share of total health expenditure, per capita private health expenditure, out-of-pocket health spending as a share of private health expenditure, physician density,

hospital bed availability, access to safe drinking water, skilled birth attendance, and adult literacy. The analysis employed pooled OLS, random effects, and Hausman-Taylor instrumental variable techniques. Findings showed that both government and private health spending significantly reduced infant, under-five, and maternal mortality, with private expenditure having a stronger effect. Improved access to safe water, skilled birth attendance, and higher literacy rates also contributed to lower mortality rates. The study recommended policies to reduce financial barriers to healthcare, particularly for low-income populations in countries like Iraq, Libya, and Syria. Unlike this research, which is limited to the MENA region and data up to 2010, the present study extends the analysis to 2022 and covers all West African countries.

3. Methodology

3.1 Nature and Sources of Data

Secondary panel data spanning the years 2000 to 2022 was utilized for the analytical framework. The dataset pertaining to West African nations was sourced from the World Development Indicators, World Governance Indicators and the WHO Global Health Expenditure Database.

3.2 Model Specification

In this investigation, one model was constructed to evaluate the influence of healthcare financing on under-five mortality rates within West Africa. The model is predicated on the health expenditure outcome theory and the framework posited by Logarajan et al. (2022), which delineated its model with Under-five mortality as a function of public health expenditure, private health expenditure, out-of-pocket health expenditure, gross domestic product per capita, unemployment rate, and the percentage of the urban populace. The model was refined by maintaining U5MR (Under-Five Mortality Rate) as the dependent variable, segmenting health expenditure into Domestic General Government Health Expenditure Per Capita (DGGHE), Domestic Private Health Expenditure Per Capita (DPHE), and External Health Expenditure Per Capita (EXHE), while retaining GDPC as a control variable and incorporating INSQ (institutional quality) in alignment with this study's objectives. Furthermore, OOP was excluded as it is already encompassed within DPHE, and UEMP and UPOP were omitted based on the aims of this research. The functional form and econometric form are presented in the equation below

$$U5M_{it} = f(DGGHE_{it}, DPHE_{it}, EXHE_{it}, GDPPC_{it}, INSQ_{it}) \dots\dots\dots 1$$

$$U5M_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 DGGHE_{it} + \alpha_2 DPHE_{it} + \alpha_3 EXHE_{it} + \alpha_4 GDPPC_{it} + \alpha_5 INSQ_{it} + \mu_i + \lambda_t + e_{it} \dots\dots\dots 2$$

U5M denotes Under-Five Mortality Rate, DGGHE signifies Domestic General Government Health Expenditure per capita, DPHE represents Domestic Private Health Expenditure per capita, EXHE indicates External Health Expenditure per capita, GDPPC refers to Gross Domestic Product Per Capita, INSQ is the Principal Component index of the six institutional quality variables, i denotes the selected nations ($i=1-16$), t reflects the time specification, α_0 is the constant term, α_1 are the coefficients of the variables, μ_i denotes the country-specific effects, λ_t represents the time-specific effects, and e_{it} is the error term.

Apriori Expectation: $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4, \alpha_5 < 0$

3.3. Dynamic Common Correlated Effect Estimation Procedure

Before implementing the Dynamic Common Correlated Effect (DCCE) analysis proposed by Chudik and Pesaran (2015), it is essential to recognize its advantages as a second-generation dynamic panel estimation method. DCCE addresses the limitations of first-generation estimators and earlier second-generation techniques, including Mean Group (MG), Pooled Mean Group (PMG), Dynamic Fixed Effects (DFE), and Common Correlated Effects (CCE). A key drawback of these earlier methods is their inability to account for unobserved cross-sectional dependencies and autocorrelation in the error terms, which may result in biased regression estimates (Chudik & Pesaran, 2015).

The pre-estimation tests conducted before estimating DCCE are as follows: the initial phase encompassed the Descriptive Statistics Test, which evaluates the mean, minimum, and maximum values of the variables, subsequently, the Cross Section Dependence Test (CDS) was administered to ascertain whether the variables exhibit cross-sectional dependence. Following this, the Panel Unit Root Test utilizing the CIPS and CADF methodology was executed on the model to determine the order of stationarity. Additionally, the Panel Cointegration Analysis was performed to investigate long-term relationships among non-stationary variables through the application of the Westerlund cointegration test, which is deemed an appropriate method in the presence of cross-sectional dependence. Upon completion of the pre-estimation tests, the analysis was conducted utilizing the Dynamic Common Correlated Effects (DCCE).

The DCCE model is specified as:
$$Y_{it} = \alpha Y_{it-1} + \sigma_i x_{it} + \sum_{p=0}^{PT} Y_{xit} X_{t-p} + \sum_{p=0}^{PT} Y_{xit} Y_{t-p} + \mu_{it} \dots \dots \dots 3$$

where Y_{it} and Y_{it-1} refers to the dependent variable and lag of the dependent variable, $\sigma_i x_{it}$ represents set of independent variables, PT is a set of lags of cross-sectional averages, Y_{xit} and Y_{t-p} are unobserved common factors, while μ_{it} is the residual term.

4. Results and Findings

4.1 Presentation of Result

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	OBS	U5M	DGGHE	DPHE	EXHE	GDPPC	INSQQ
MEAN	368	102.6454	15.406	24.65985	8.347751	1070.858	-0.814822
MAX	368	228.4	209.043	78.75567	75.80813	4378.4	0.3409591
MIN	368	12.3	0.954772	3.386758	0.2638649	194.137	-1.807464
S T D . DEV	368	43.73537	25.564	15.57933	8.281578	804.4477	0.438006

Author's computation using STATA version 15

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for the model variables, based on 368 observations, making it suitable for a heterogeneous panel analysis. The mean under-five mortality (U5M) rate is 102.65 per 1,000 live births, with a standard deviation of 43.73, indicating significant variation across countries. Cape Verde recorded the lowest U5M at

12.3 in 2022, while Niger had the highest at 228.40 in 2000.

Regarding health financing, domestic general government health expenditure (DGGHE) per capita averages \$15.41 billion, with a standard deviation of \$25.56 billion, reflecting large disparities. The lowest spending was in Liberia (\$0.95 in 2003), while Cape Verde had the highest (\$209.04 in 2021). Private health expenditure (DPHE) per capita averages \$24.66, with a standard deviation of \$15.58. Burkina Faso recorded the lowest (\$3.39 in 2000), while Cape Verde had the highest (\$78.76 in 2022), highlighting varying private sector involvement in healthcare. External health expenditure (EXHE) per capita averages \$8.35, with a standard deviation of \$8.28. Ghana received the least external aid (\$0.26 in 2000), while Sierra Leone received the most (\$75.81 in 2014), illustrating disparities in donor support.

Economic disparities, captured by GDP per capita, show an average income of \$1,070.86, with a standard deviation of \$804.45. Niger recorded the lowest (\$194.14 in 2000), while Cape Verde had the highest (\$4,378.40 in 2019), reflecting significant income gaps. Institutional quality averages -0.8125, with a standard deviation of 0.4383, indicating governance variations. Guinea-Bissau recorded the lowest (-1.807 in 2017), while Cape Verde had the highest (0.341 in 2018), affecting policy effectiveness and corruption levels.

The high standard deviations in U5M, DGGHE, DPHE, EXHE, and GDPPC suggest notable deviations from their means, indicating the presence of outliers and potential non-stationarity, both of which were accounted for during estimation.

Table 2: CDS Test (Cross Sectional Dependence Test)

Variable	CD-Test	P-Value
U5M	51.46	0.000
DGGHE	32.85	0.000
DPHE	33.23	0.000
EXHE	26.32	0.000
GDPPC	45.59	0.000
INSQQ	-0.83	0.408

Author's computation using STATA version 15

The cross-sectional dependency test on Table 2 revealed that U5M, DGGHE, DPHE, EXHE, GDPPC were cross sectionally dependent, while INSQQ was cross sectionally independent leading to the adoption of second-generation panel techniques.

Table 3: Pesaran CADF and Pesaran CIPS Unit Root Test in the Presence of CDS

Pesaran CADF				Pesaran CIPS		
Variable	Levels	1 st Diff	Order of Int.	Levels	1st Diff	Order of Int.

U5M	-2.978	-1.349	I (0)	-2.934	-1.992	I (0)
DGGHE	-2.168	-3.390	I (0)	-2.550	-5.053	I (0)
DPHE	-2.015	-3.108	I (I)	-2.156	-4.227	I (0)
EXHE	-2.189	-3.775	I (0)	-3.108	-5.134	I (0)
GDPPC	-2.519	-3.131	I (0)	-2.643	-3.920	I (0)
INSQQ	-2.343	-3.682	I (0)	-2.085	-4.707	I (I)

Author's computation using STATA version 15

Presented on Table 3 is the unit root test results which showed that all the variables were stationary at levels and first difference, no variable exceeded first difference.

Table 4: Westerlund Cointegration Result

Model	Variance Ratio Stat.	P-Value	Decision
U5M	2.3546	0.0093	Co-integration

Presented in Table 4 is the result of Westerlund 2006 co-integration, the results shows that model U5M is co-integrated at the 5% level, Thus, short run and long run relationship will be estimated for model U5M.

Table 5: DCCE Long Run and Short Run Results

Dependent Variable: lnU5	Coefficients	Std. Error	Z-Stat	P>(Z)
Short run results				
LnDGGHE	0.001	0.006	0.23	0.816
LnDPHE	0.029	0.014	2.11	0.035
LnEXHE	-0.0002	0.004	-0.08	0.933
LnGDPPC	-0.031	0.013	-2.33	0.020
INSQQ	0.005	0.007	0.69	0.489
EC	-0.262	0.106	-2.48	0.013
lr lnDGGHE	-0.036	0.044	-0.82	0.413
lr lnDPHE	-0.138	0.061	-2.24	0.025
lr lnEXHE	0.001	0.019	0.07	0.946

lr lnGDPPC	-0.093	0.045	-2.06	0.039
lr INSQQ	0.006	0.049	0.12	0.904

Author's computation using STATA version 15

The short-run coefficients, which reflect the immediate impact of changes in the independent variables on under-five mortality in West Africa, indicate that domestic general government health expenditure per capita and institutional quality (measured by government effectiveness) lead to a rise in under-five mortality, though insignificantly. In contrast, domestic private health expenditure per capita significantly increases under-five mortality, while external health expenditure per capita and gross domestic product (GDP) per capita contribute to its reduction, with only GDP per capita showing a significant effect.

The error correction (EC) term confirms the existence of a long-run relationship, with an adjustment speed of 26%. The long-run estimates, which capture the sustained impact of the independent variables, reveal that domestic general government health expenditure per capita, domestic private health expenditure per capita, and GDP per capita contribute to lowering under-five mortality. However, only domestic private health expenditure and GDP per capita exhibit significant effects, whereas government health expenditure remains insignificant. Additionally, external health expenditure per capita and institutional quality unexpectedly show a positive association with under-five mortality, though their effects are not statistically significant.

Discussion of Findings

The analysis indicates that domestic private health expenditure per capita significantly reduces under-five mortality in West Africa, whereas domestic government health expenditure per capita and external health expenditure per capita show no significant impact. Similarly, gross domestic product (GDP) per capita plays a crucial role in lowering under-five mortality, while institutional quality does not have a significant effect. The strong impact of domestic private health expenditure suggests that private sector participation is vital in improving child health outcomes, likely due to greater efficiency, accountability, and targeted resource allocation compared to the public sector, leading to increase in healthcare infrastructure, healthcare workforce, healthcare access, medical products and technological adoption which invariably leads to reduction in under-five mortality rate. However, since private sector is profit driven it raises concerns about affordability of healthcare services for the vulnerable. Conversely, the lack of impact from government and external health spending points to inefficiencies such as resource misallocation, corruption, and weak implementation frameworks that undermine the effectiveness of public and donor-driven healthcare investments, leading to reduction in healthcare infrastructure, healthcare workforce, healthcare access, medical products and technological adoption which invariably leads to increase in under-five mortality rate. Additionally, the significance of GDP per capita highlights the broader role of economic growth in reducing child mortality, emphasizing the need for policies that promote economic development as an indirect strategy for improving health outcomes.

These findings align with studies such as Logarajan et al. (2022) which found out that public health expenditure not significant in reducing under-five mortality rate, Kilanko

(2020) which revealed the insignificant effect of public health expenditure on health outcomes, Langnel and Buracom (2020) which revealed no significant effect connection between health expenditure, governance and infant mortality rate, Osakede (2020) which revealed insignificant effect of public health expenditure on health outcomes and Akinlo and Sulola (2018) which study revealed that public health expenditure positively increase infant and under-five mortality rate, but contradict the conclusions of Logarajan et al. (2022) which revealed insignificant effect of private health expenditure on under-five mortality rate, Yoorim and Jinhwan (2020) which study revealed significant negative relationship between health expenditure and infant mortality rate Boachie (2020) which revealed that public health spending led to reduction of infant and under-five mortality rate, Arthur and Oaikhenan (2017) which revealed significant effect of public health spending in reducing infant and under-five mortality rate, while private health spending was weak, Richard and Vining (2016) which revealed significant effect of public health spending in affecting infant mortality and Akinci et al. (2014) which revealed that both public and private health spending reduced infant and under-five mortality rate, further highlighting the mixed evidence in the literature.

These findings reveal deep inefficiencies within healthcare systems, governance challenges, and socio-economic barriers that hinder the effectiveness of public and external health spending in reducing under-five mortality. As a result, under-five mortality rates in West Africa remain alarmingly high, exceeding the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) targets for reduction.

5. Conclusion

The study concludes that private healthcare financing significantly reduces under-five mortality in West Africa, while public and external health expenditures show no measurable impact. Additionally, economic growth is associated with lower under-five mortality rates, whereas institutional quality does not appear to influence child survival outcomes in the region.

5.1 Recommendations

- I. **Optimizing Public Healthcare Spending:** Governments should enhance efficiency in healthcare funding, prioritizing impactful child health programs to reduce under-five mortality.
- II. **Boosting Private Sector Involvement:** Policies should incentivize private investment in healthcare through partnerships, tax benefits, and regulatory support to improve accessibility and affordability.
- III. **Enhancing External Health Aid Efficiency:** Development partners must ensure accountability and transparency in aid allocation for sustainable health improvements.
- IV. **Aligning Economic Growth with Health Investment:** Policymakers should integrate economic and healthcare strategies to ensure development leads to better health outcomes.
- V. **Strengthening Healthcare Governance:** Reforms should improve policy execution, transparency, and accountability to enhance institutional quality in the health sector.

VI. Facilitating Cross-Regional Learning: Regions should exchange best practices in reducing under-five mortality, adapting successful strategies to local contexts.

REFERENCES

- Akinci, F., Hamidi, S., Suvankulov, F., & Akhmedjonov, A. (2014). Examining the impact of health care expenditures on health outcomes in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region *Journal of Health Care Finance*, 4(7), 1-23.
- Akinlo, A., E., & Sulola, A., O. 2018. Health care expenditure and infant mortality in Sub-Saharan Africa *Journal of Policy Modeling* 41 (1):168–78. doi: 10.1016/j.jpolmod.2018.09.001.
- Arthur, E., & Oaikhenan, H., E. (2017). The effects of health expenditure on health outcomes in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) *African Development Review* 29(3):524–36. . doi: 10.1111/1467-8268.12287.
- Boachie, M., Põlajeva, K., T. & Frimpong, A., O. (2020). Infant mortality in low-and middle-income countries: does government health spending matter? *Journal of Development Policy and Practice* 5(1):54–73. doi: 10.1177/2455133320909916
- Bokhari, F. A. S., Gai, Y., & Gottret, P. (2007). Government health expenditures and health outcomes. *Health Economics*, 16(3), 257-273.
- Burstein R, Henry NJ, Collison ML, Marczak LB, Sligar A, Watson S, et al. (2019). Mapping 123 million neonatal, infant and child deaths between 2000 and 2017. Nature. 574 (7778): 353–358. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-019-1493-6>*
- Chudik, A., & Pesaran, M., H. (2015) Common correlated effects estimation of heterogeneous dynamic panel data models with weakly exogenous regressors. *Journal of Econometrics*, Elsevier, 188(2):393-420. doi: 10.1016/j.jeconom.2015.03.007.
- Fayissa, B., & Gutema, P. (2005). Estimating a health production function for Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). *Applied Economics*, 37(2), 155-164.
- Kilanko, O. (2020). The effects of health care expenditures on health outcomes in West Africa: Analysis of selected 14 countries from 2000 to 2018. Master thesis, Eastern Illinois University.
- Langnel, Z., & Buracom. P. (2020). Governance, health expenditure and infant mortality in Sub-Saharan Africa. *African Development Review* 32(4):673–85. doi: 10.1111/1467- 8268.12470.
- Logarajan, R., D., Nor, N., M., Sirag, A., Said, R., & Ibrahim., S. (2022). The impact of public, private, and out-of-pocket health expenditures on under-five mortality in Malaysia. *Healthcare* 10(3):589-604. doi: 10.3390/healthcare10030589.

MDGs (2015) Global Report. United Nations Development Programme.

Mosley, W. H., & Chen, L. C. (1984). An analytical framework for the study of child survival in developing countries. *Population and Development Review*, 10(1), 25-45.

National Health Systems Resource Centre (NHSRC). (2018). Health Care Financing <https://nhsrcindia.org/>

Newhouse, J. P. (1977). Medical-care expenditure: A cross-national survey. *The Journal of Human Resources*, 12(1), 115-125.

Novignon, J., & Lawanson, A. O. (2017). Health expenditure and child health outcomes in Sub-Saharan Africa. *African Review of Economics and Finance*, 9(1), 96-121.

Osakede, U., A. (2020). Public health spending and health outcome in Nigeria: The role of governance. *International Journal of Development Issues* 20(1):95–112. doi: 10.1108/IJDI-10-2019-0169.

Richards, J., & Vining, A., R. (2016). Under-five mortality: Comparing national levels and changes over the last decade across low-income countries. *Journal of Comparative Policy Analysis: Research and Practice* 18(4):419–38. doi: 10.1080/13876988.2016.1151135.

Umar, A., P., Rotimi, M., E., & John, N., W. (2022). The link between government health expenditure and health outcome in Nigeria, 1981-2019. *ABUAD Journal of Social and Management Sciences* 3(1):12–29. doi: 10.53982/ajsms.2022.0301.02-j.

World Bank. (2023). World Development Indicators

World Health Organization. (2023). World Health Statistics 2023 – Monitoring Health for the SDGs. World Health Organization.

World Health Organization (2022). Child mortality and causes of death.

World Health Organization. (2015). Health in 2015: From MDGs, Millennium Development Goals to SDGs, Sustainable Development Goals. Geneva: World Health Organization.

Yoorim, B., & Jinhwan, O. (2020). Impacts of health expenditure financing on infant mortality and diminishing returns: Implications for Sub-Saharan Africa. *Global Business and Finance Review* 25(4):25–32. doi: 10.17549/gbfr.2020.25.4.25.

DETERMINANTS OF CASH HOLDINGS OF LISTED NON-FINANCIAL GROUP OF INDUSTRIES IN NIGERIA

BY

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ABSTRACT

Managing cash presents significant challenges for businesses across various industries. The challenge arises because excess cash should be invested to generate more profit, while businesses must also ensure sufficient liquidity is available to meet future demands. Additionally, agency issues arise due to conflicts between shareholders and managers over decisions regarding cash holdings. In view of this, the study examines the impact of firm characteristics on cash holding of listed nonfinancial firms in Nigeria from 2015 to 2023. The study analyzed a sample of 45 firms, using secondary data obtained from the firms' annual reports and the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) website. Robust panel corrected standard error regression analysis indicates that growth opportunities, cash flow and net working capital have negative and significant impact on cash holdings while, leverage have positive and significant impact on cash holdings. The study concludes that the growth opportunities, cash flow and net working capital reduces cash holdings of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria and leverage causes increase in the level of cash holdings of the listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. The study therefore recommends among others that management should adopt strategies that will improve cash sales. This could include discounts on earlier payment and management should properly evaluate their capital investment properly to avoid investment in unprofitable projects that will dilute cash holding.

Keywords: Growth Opportunities; Capital Expenditure; Cash Flow; Working Capital; Firm Size; Leverage and Cash Holding

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Cash and cash equivalents are essential components of the assets that are not more than one year of a firm and are considered as component element of corporate financial management. As results of the significant position of corporate cash holdings in the non-financial firms, a lot of studies have been carried out in the area. Cash holding indicates the amount of physical cash that are readily available for investment and in hand that can be distributed to the investors. Basically, companies in different industries demand different level of cash holdings to make operation run smoothly. What is essentially important for each company in an industry is to identify the significant of holding certain amount of cash, with a view to deciding the optimum amount of cash it should hold (Angelovska and Valentincic, 2020). Furthermore, cash is important, without it companies cannot carry out their operating, financing, and investing activities. In a world of perfect capital markets, it is expected that company's capital should be reinvested on project that have net present value, therefore, keeping huge amount of cash are considered to be irrelevant. Thus, non-financial companies can raise finance for investment from the capital markets and at lower costs (Ki & Adhikari, 2022). However, sometime this is not the case because the capital market is imperfect. Therefore, raising external capital is more costly for

companies considering the internal resources as a result of the market imperfections. In addition, the decision to hold cash by companies is derived from various motives such as transaction, precautionary and speculative motives (Kariuki et al., 2015).

Kumar et al., (2021) posit that companies with growth opportunities often prefer to have huge amount of cash. But when a company has opportunity of investing her capital to gain more profit and lack the sufficient cash, they may lose these opportunities. Therefore, as a results of that companies preferred hold large amounts of cash so as not to lose that investment opportunities (Vuong, Dao, Le and Nguyen, 2022). Moreover, the value of high growth companies largely depends on the value of their investment opportunities. These types of companies face higher information asymmetries between internal and external investors that allowed external financing to be more expensive (Shamsuddeen & Ibrahim, 2022). This makes the companies to save more cash in order to avoid financial distress. Senan et al. (2021) argue that only companies that have poor growth opportunities hold more cash because of the agency problem. Rehman and Wang (2015) opined that capital expenditure is the fund used by companies to purchase and maintained tangible assets such as property, plants and equipment. Conversely, companies can keep huge amount of cash once there is higher demand of capital expenditure, because having higher cash level will place the companies in a better positioned over the competitors. In addition, companies with higher capital expenditure will used as an assets when they want raise capital in the stock market (Okeke, Ezejiofor and Okoye, 2021). This will give an opportunity to managers to raise more debt for the companies which lead to decrease in demand for holding cash.

However, study has shown that any increase in the short-term investment would reduce the ability of firms in holding more cash (Vuong, Dao, Le and Nguyen, 2022). Companies tend to use cash when there they have high capital expenditure, while sometime they report low cash levels (Shamsuddeen and Ibrahim, 2022). On the other hand, cash flow involves providing cash by providers of capital for reinvestment, settling liabilities and paying dividend after fulfilling all the requirements of the business (Ferreira and Vilela, 2004). Saddour (2006) suggests that the presence of signaling problems associated with external funding, companies prefer internal over external finance. Furthermore, when companies hold more cash it always reduced their risk of moving into financial distress since there is higher cash flow. Accordingly, this happen as a result of companies can used their excess cash holdings in finance projects that have positive net present value. Companies that have higher cash flow may not necessarily have to raise cash in order to pay for the future expenses (Kumar et al., 2021).

Zahn and Rusmin, (2013) see a situation where manager own a share may trigger them to holder more cash as the Chief Executive Officer (CEO) and directors. This presumably implies that when agency problems occur between the managers and the shareholders its increase cash that become deemphasize (Pinkowitz, Stulz and Williamson, 2006). By extension, Masood, and Shah (2014) state that managers have incentive that are attached to cash holding which are beneficial them and enjoy perquisites at the expense of shareholders' wealth. In respect to that they increase the assets of the firms so that they can gain additional voting power over the companies' investment decision without being subject to effective internal monitoring by the board (Senan et al., 2021). This resulted to an entrenchment effect of managers. Moreover, as posits by Abdioglu (2016), Net

working capital can replace companies' cash as long as they can be readily converted to cash (Li, Jiang, Xia and Chu, 2020). This is because the amount companies can spend in the conversion of liquid assets to cash are considered to be lower than other assets. Thus, when companies have more liquid assets they used to convert the assets to cash which makes them to hold cash (Bigelli and Sánchez-Vidal, 2012). Most of the giant often have high level of net operational cash flow and typically perform better than small companies (Mohd-Ashhari and Faizal, 2018). This forces them to hold more cash in order to invest and make their operation run smoothly.

On the other hand, the cost of external financing is smaller for larger companies because of scale of economies resulting from a substantial fixed cost component of security issuance costs (Onyeka, Nnado and Ugwuanyi, 2020). Consequently, larger companies tend to have easier access to the financial markets, which provide them with funds when required and keep lower cash holdings. Manufacturing sector in Nigeria play significant roles in the socio-economic development of the country because of their nature of operations, the sector creates employment opportunity, wealth creation to the Government and corporate social responsibility. To this effect therefore, this study intends to assess the impact of cash holdings of listed Nigerian Manufacturing companies with a view to investigating the extent to which the independent variables influence cash holdings.

Study on cash holding has been very significant especially for the non-financial group of firms. As the company's daily operation usually stick on cash holding. This has aids in carrying out so many activities using the liquid cash, this has makes it easier in term of making payment for different kinds of activities. One of the most important components of corporate financial policies are cash holding (Khatib et al., 2022). Therefore, when there is insufficient liquid assets it will hamper the company from meeting the obligations and limit the firm from enjoying leverage, sale growth, increase capital expenditures, expanding the size of the firms and increased the cash flow which consequences could result in forcing the firm to file for bankruptcy. Thus, sometime companies' managers seem to have less concern on the relevance of cash holdings in the non-financial group of firms as they pursue their interest.

Also, empirical studies on capital expenditure and cash holding Ibrahim et al., (2020), Shamsuddeen & Ibrahim, (2022) argued that in line with pecking order theory managers of the companies usually hold more cash once there is need for higher of capital expenditure. While Israel, Omobolade and Jeremiah (2023) on the contrary argued that as firm capital expenditures increase, their cash holdings is negatively affected as capital expenditure consume cash reserves of firms according to trade off theory. Literatures on the link between cash flow and cash holdings such as Agustin, Halim and Agselia (2021), Okeke et al. (2021) etc argued that companies with greater capacity generate cash flows and hold higher cash holdings. While, Vuong et al. (2022) argued that growing companies who can generate more cash flows hold less cash. Therefore, based on the aforementioned problem and to structure the study the following questions were raise: What is the impact of growth opportunities on cash holdings of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria?, What is the influence of capital expenditure on cash holdings of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria?, What is the contribution of cash flow on cash holdings of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria?, What is the influence of working capital on cash holdings of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria?, What is the impact of firm

size on cash holdings of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria? and What is the impact of leverage on cash holdings of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria?. in line with the research questions, the main objective of this study is to examine the determinant of firm characteristics on cash holding of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. While, the specific objectives of this study are: Determine the impact of growth opportunities on cash holdings of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Assess the influence of capital expenditure on cash holdings of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Investigate the contribution of cash flow on cash holdings of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Ascertain the influence of working capital on cash holdings of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Determine the impact of firm size on cash holdings of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Examine the impact of Leverage on cash holdings of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Based on the specific objectives of this study, they were hypothesized as: H_1 Growth opportunities have no significant impact on cash holdings of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. H_2 Capital expenditure has no significant influence on cash holdings of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. H_3 Contribution of cash flow has no significant impact on cash holdings of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. H_4 working capital has no significant impact on cash holdings of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. H_5 Firm size has no significant impact on cash holdings of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria and H_6 Leverage has no significant influence on cash holdings of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

The study comprises four sections which deal with the introduction that constitutes the statement of the problem, research question, objectives of the study and hypothesis of the study. Section two reviewed related literature and theories. The methodology of the study and the section describes the research design, population, sample size, and data gathering instrument. Section four is the presentation of results and discussions of the findings. Then finally the paper contains conclusions and recommendations.

Literature Review

This section involves a synthesis of the relevant literature on determinants of cash holding (CSHD). The section begins with the review of concept of cash holdings and motives for CSHD. It reviews empirical studies on the various determinants of CSHD, which serve as independent variables such as: growth opportunities (GROP), capital expenditure (CAPE), cash flow (CSHL), net working capital (NWCP), firm size (FSIZ) and leverage (LEVG), in relation to their impact on cash holdings. In addition, other aspects in which literature is reviewed include theoretical framework.

2.1 The Concept of Cash Holdings

Cash holdings constitute a vital aspect in any company because they provide company with liquidity (Shamshudeen & Idris, 2022). In non-financial firms cash are kept as an emergency fund which help companies to pay off their obligations when due. CSHD are considered as one of the tools that decrease the risk, cost of converting assets into liquid cash (Peavler, 2019). Bouwman and Lowry (2012) and Agustin, Halim and Agselia (2021) define CSHD as sum of cash and cash equivalents that are associated to net assets. Lau and Block (2012), define cash holdings as sources that are available to managers in financing CAPE in order to enhance shareholders' wealth. Similarly, Fressard and Salva (2010) define CSHD as the most liquid assets that are used to measure the firm's ability

when settling bills on time.

2.2.1 Concept of Growth Opportunities

Raimi and Samaila (2022) defined GROF as the ability to measure CSHD by the number of sales over a particular period of time. This implies that GROF by practice is associated with CSHD of any company. Thus, this shows that a good GROF can be used to benefit the employees and company in respect to the expansion of company product. Agustin et al. (2021) view GROF as an increase or return both from the product sales and capital growth as the case may be. Khan et al. (2018) opined that GROF can be viewed as the operational change in sales and cash flow that caused by growth or decrease in business volume.

2.2.2 Concept of Capital Expenditure

Ki and Adhikari (2022) stated that capital expenditures can be viewed as funds that are used by a company in acquiring, upgrading, and maintaining of physical assets such as property, plants, buildings, technology, or equipment. Angelovska and Valentincic (2020) opined that capital expenditure are fund often used to carry out a new projects and investment in a company Similarly, Ahmed et al., (2021) said capital expenditure can be seen as the financial outlay that are set aside by the companies in an effort to increase the scope of their operations or to add some future economic benefit of the companies operation. Vuong & Nguyen (2022) defined capital expenditure as the sum total of all money spent to obtain, upgrade, manage, fix, or maintain physical assets of the company.

2.2.3 Concept of Cash Flow

A cash flow statement indicates the inflow and outflow of cash, its also providing insights into a company's financial health and how operational efficient. Agbata et al. (2021) viewed cash flow as the measures of the company are firing or how well managers of the company are managing its cash position. Barasa et al., (2018) opine that cash flow can be seen as the total cash that a company earns and spends in making payment(s) to creditors. Khuong (2018) defined cash flow as the net amount of cash and cash equivalent that moved in and out of a company over a specific period of time. Agustin et al. (2021) stated that Cash Inflow is the amount of money coming into a business through the source of income that is generated by the company.

2.2.4 Concept of Networking Capital

Vuong et al., (2022) opined that net working capital can be seen as the aggregate amount that are associated with all current assets and liabilities. Okeke (2021) viewed net working capital as the figure that can be used to express a general impression of the company ability of managing and utilization of [assets](#) in an efficient manner. Khatib et al., (2022) defined networking capital in term of short-term funds that are readily available from the current assets that can adequately pay for the current liabilities as they are due for payment. Ibrahim (2020) viewed net working capital as the figure that are more informative in showing a gradual improvement or on the other decline in the net amount of capital over an extended period.

2.2.5 Concept Firm Size

Firm size is one of the most significant features in organizational studies (Pandey et al., 2000). Firm size matters for several reasons. Larger firms are associated with lower fixed

costs per unit, cheaper access to outside financing, diversification of their financing sources and less likely to fail or liquidate (Gaddard et al., 2005). Pandey et al. (2000) opined as firm size increases; the fixed costs become relatively less significant. Firm size can be defined as the assets that are owned by the companies as a result of the opportunities that abound to the firms that are acquired as a result of production efficiency. Dang and Li (2015) Firm size can be measured using total asset-market value of equity and total sales this study defines and measures firm size as the total asset owned by the firm measured as log of total asset because it a control variable.

2.2.6 Concept of Leverage

Israel, Omobolade and Jeremiah (2023) said leverage can also be refers to as the amount of debt to equity ratio that can be seen in capital structure of a firm. This means the decision on uses of leverage to a firm is very crucial to the management of the firm, as it is used to influences the risk and returns of the shareholders as well as the cash holding of the firm. Abosede and Ibrahim (2022) Leverage can be viewed as the ratio debts that are present in the company's capital structure. Kenn, et al. (2019) leverage is the ratio debt to equity in the firm's capital structure it is used as a means of increasing return to the shareholders; and this in turn is referred to as financial leverage. Ndubuisi, Ifechi and Nweke (2019) stated that leverage can be describes as the uses of fixed financial charges in terms of increase in changes on firms' earnings.

2.3 Empirical Studies on the Determinants of Cash Holdings

This section provides empirical literature relevant to this study based on the results of previous studies conducted on the determinant of cash holdings. The section discusses the empirical studies on the following: growth opportunities, capital expenditure, cash flow, net working capital, firm size, leverage, and their impact on cash holdings.

2.3.1 Growth Opportunities and Cash Holdings

Agustin, Halim and Agselia (2021) investigated the determinant of GROPC, CAPE, LEVG, NWCP, CSHL and FSIZ on CSHD using 34 non-financial group of firms on IDX from 2016 to 2018. The study used secondary data and was analyzed using EViews version 10.0. The results of the study indicated that GROPC, NWCP, CSHL and FSIZ have no significant influence on CSHD, while CAPE, LEVG, has negative and significant influences on CSHD. It, therefore, suggested that the study should be extended to other independent variables of the determinant and the different proxy should be used in future research. Raimi and Samaila (2022) investigate the determinant of CSHD using five Conglomerate Companies listed on the Nigerian NGX over the period (2015-2021). The result of the study indicates that GROPC, FSIZ and LEVG have positive effect on CSHL with the exemption of CAPE that has no significant influence. Tayem (2017) carried out a study on cash holding using 47 Jordanian non-financial firms for the period 2005-2013 The result of the study revealed that GROPC have significant positive impact on CSHL. The results also indicate that there is a significant positive effect on determining CSHD targets. However, this study was conducted in South Africa which has a different market environment from Nigeria. However, based on the empirical findings above GROPC have both positive and negative relationship with CSHD.

2.3.2 Capital Expenditure and Cash Holdings

Israel et al. (2023) investigated the determinant of CSHD of 40 non-financial quoted on

the NGX over the years 2012 to 2021. The data were from secondary source and a panel regression was used. The findings of the work revealed that CAPE, CSHL, FSIZ and LEVG have significant positive effect on CSHD while, GROU, indicates negative significant effects on CSHD. Duru et al. (2019) investigate the effect of CAPE, CSHL, FSIZ and LEVG on CSHD of listed on NGX for the period of (2007 to 2017). The result of the study indicated that CAPE, CSHL, FSIZ and LEVG has effect on CSHD of listed consumer goods firms on the NGX while LEVG has no significant effect on CSHD. Amalia et al. (2018) examined the effect of CAPE on CSHD of listed manufacturing companies on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. The study spanned over the period 2011 to 2015. Using a sample of 105 firms, the results of the study indicate that CAPE has insignificant effect on CSHD.

2.3.3 Cash Flow and Cash Holdings

Agbata et al. (2021) investigate the determinant of CSHD of listed non-financial group of companies in NGX. 21 consumer goods firms were used for the study where the data was sources secondarily. Thus, it was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0. The findings of the study revealed a significant positive relationship between cash CSHL, FSIZ and LEVG and CSHD, while, CAPE and FSIZ indicate in significant negative relationship with CSHD. Barasa et al. (2018) examined the determinants of CSHD using 44 non-financial firms quoted on Nairobi securities exchange (NSE) over the period 2002 to 2013. The study used correlational and non-experimental research design as a bed rock for the study. The results evidence that a significant positive relationship exist between CSHL and CSHD. The study concluded that CSHL possible influence CSHD. Wijaya and Bandi (2018) examined the effect of CSHL on CSHD of listed manufacturing companies on the Indonesian Stock Exchange for the years 2006-2007. The result of the study indicates that CSHL show a significant positively affect CSHD. Jebran et al. (2019) investigated the determinants of corporate CSHD of 280 firms from 2005 to 2014 that were listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange. The results of the study revealed that CSHL is a determinant of CSHD.

2.3.4 Net Working Capital and Cash Holdings

Ibrahim et al. (2020) investigate the determinant of Cash holding decision of listed cash holding firm listed on NGX. The study considered the impact of Firm dynamism and firm characteristics on corporate CSHD. The study used 51 listed non-financial firms that were link with pecking order and resource dependence theory for the year 2012 to 2019. This period was considered relevant for the work because it falls behind post financial crisis and the beginning of financial crunch that happen in 2016. This affects non-financial group of firm in Nigeria and the result of the study indicate a significant positive relationship between NWCP, GROU, CAPE, LEVG, CSHL and FSIZ on CSHD. Shamsudeen, & Idris (2022) investigate the determinant of CSHD. The study used 51 firms listed on the NGX from the period of 2012 to 2019. The result of the revealed that NWCP, GROU, CAPE, LEVG, CSHL and FSIZ have significant positive effect on CSHD Listed on the NGX Jebran et al. (2019) investigated the determinants of corporate CSHD using 280 firms listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange over the period 2005 to 2014. The results of the study revealed a significant positive relationship between NWCP, GROU, CAPE, LEVG, CSHL and FSIZ on CSHD

2.3.5 Firm Size and Cash Holdings

Ogbebor et al. (2022) examine the effect of FSIZ on CSHD from quoted consumer goods

firms in Sub-Sahara Africa for the periods 2011-2020. The study used 16 consumer goods in Nigeria, 7 in Kenya, and 30 in South Africa. The result of the study indicates that FSIZ has significant positive relationship with CSHD. Onyeka et al. (2020) investigate the causal relationship between FSIZ, LEVG, DROP, CAPE and CSHL of listed manufacturing firms in NGX. The study used 37 non-financial groups of companies over the period 2005-2018. The study suggests that non-financial firms in Nigerian. The firm size, leverage, sale growth, capital expenditure is proportionately and significantly influenced by cash holdings. Li & Zeng (2020) investigate the effect of firm size and LEVG on cash holding. The study would add to literature as it has created a link with cash holding. Therefore, giving a concise role of firm size and leverage in financing the firms in relation to CSHD, the result of the study indicates that FSIZ and LEVG has significant positive relationship on CSHD.

2.3.6 Leverage and Cash holdings

Hassan et al. (2022) investigate the relationship between LEVG and CSHD. Considering the nature of the financial system in the country which were beveled with a lot of crises has affected the cash holding of listed consumer-goods firms in Nigeria. Financial firms the level of leverage is often explained by overall cash holding of the firms in Nigeria. The study used 21 firms over the period 2010 to 2020. At the end of the analysis, the result of the study shows that leverage of the non-financial firm in its debt capital mix that mean cash holding of the firm is negatively impacted. Thus, the study concluded that debt to finance of the selected firms has yielded a positive impact on the cash holding for the firms. It further suggested that external funding may raise cash-flows for the firms, but it increases the financial risks of the firms and its shareholders and may result in the dilution of ownership control of the shareholders, as well as lower cash holding of the firms. Hassan and Adegbe (2021) investigated the effect of LEVG on CSHD of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. The study used 99 non-financial firms NGX over the period 2011 to 2019. The result of the study shows that LEVG, CSHL, GROP was significantly affected by CSHD, while FSIZ, CAPE showed a negative significant effect on CSHD. Ghozali et al. (2020) investigates the determinants of LEVG in listed 300 Indonesia manufacturing firms for the period 2010- 2018. The result of the study indicates that FSIZ, GROP have significant positive influence on CSHD.

2.4 Theoretical Framework

Agency Theory

Agency theory was propounded from economic theory by Alchian and Demsetz (1972) and expanded by Jensen and Meckling (1976). It is the relationship between shareholders and managers (Samaila, 2014). According to the theory, shareholders who own the company can hire the agents to carry out some duties in their best interest (Ferreira & Vilela, 2004). Indeed, Daily et al. (2003) said two factors influence the prominence of agency theory. The first one is a simple theory that reduces the corporation to two participants that is the managers and shareholders, while, the second one is employees and managers in organizations (Kusnadi, 2011). Agency theory basic problem in the modern companies are primarily due to the separation of ownership between shareholders and managers. This is because; separation of ownership makes negligence of duties and misappropriation of cash (Al-Mamun et al., 2013). Similarly, Jensen and Meckling (1976) suggest that there is likelihood that the managers will not act in the best interest of the shareholders as both parties want to maximize their utilities. Therefore, as managers attempt to satisfy their

personal interests, at the same time shareholders are exploited. One of the ways managers enjoy private gains at the expense of the shareholders is cash management. The managers here prefer to hold excess cash to undertake investments that reduce the company value (Ginglinger & Saddour, 2010). However, the theory deals with the conflict of interest. In conclusion, the study adopts agency theory as the theory that underpins the relationship among GROG, CSHL, LEVG, CAPE, NWCP and CSHD.

3.1 Methodology

The study used correlation research design. The data was sourced secondarily from the annual reports and accounts of the sample companies. The population of this consisted of 74 non-financial firms listed on NGX as at 31st December, 2023. The study used 45 non-financial firms as sample that spread across all the subsectors as follows: Agricultural goods (2), consumer goods (18), conglomerates (4), industrial goods (11), natural gas (4) and healthcare (6). The study will employ panel regression analysis to test the determinants of CSHD.

3.2 Variables Measurement

The measurements of the dependent and independent variables are provided in the table below.

Table 1: Variables Measurement and Definition

Variable Name	Variables Types	Abreviation	Variable Measurement	AUTHOR
Cash Holdings	Dependent variable	CSHD	Measured as the ratio of cash and cash equivalents scaled by net assets	Bates et al. (2009);
Growth opportunity	Independent variable	GROG	This is measured as sales of current year minus sales of previous year scaled by sales of current year	Anjum (2013).
Capital expenditure	Independent variable	CAPE	This is measured as fixed assets of current year minus fixed assets of previous year plus depreciation of current year scaled by net assets	Kafayat et al.(2014)
Cash Flow	Independent variable	CSHL	Measured as the ratio of earnings before interest, tax, depreciation and amortization scaled by net assets	Jamil et al (2016)

Working Capital	Independent variable	NWCP	Measured as the ratio of current asset minus current liabilities scaled by net assets	Jamil et al (2016)
Firm Size	Control variable	FSIZ	This is measured as natural log of total assets	Kafayat et al.(2014)
LEVERAGE		LEVG	Total debt/total asset minus cash and cash equivalents	Jamil et al (2016)

Source: Computed by Authors, 2023

3.3 Model Specification

Since the study seeks to examine the determinants of cash holding of listed non-financial firms in NGX over eight years, the model for this study is a panel regression. The panel data model is succinctly captured below:

$$CSHD_{it} = \sigma_0 + \beta_1 GROP_{it} + \beta_2 CAPE_{it} + \beta_3 CSHL_{it} + \beta_4 NWCP_{it} + \beta_5 FSIZ_{it} + \beta_6 LEVG_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where:

$CSHD_{it}$: Cash Holdings

$GROP_{it}$: Growth Opportunities

$CAPE_{it}$: Capital Expenditure

$CSHL_{it}$: Cash Flow

$NWCP_{it}$: Working Capital

$LEVG_{it}$: Leverage

$FSIZ_{it}$: Firm Size

And σ_0 is the intercept, while β_1, \dots, β_6 : are the regression model coefficients of the independent variables.

ε_{it} : Error term

The model is adopted from the work of Al-Amarnah (2015), Kariuki et al (2015) and Magerakis et al (2015) because they used similar dependent variable and independent variables only the that the period of the study and the environment (Jordan, Kenya and UK) that differ from Nigeria. Therefore, the study is trying to replicate in the Nigerian environment in order to determine the effectiveness of the model.

4.1 Data Presentation and Analysis

This section discussed, examined, and described the findings obtained on the data acquired from various experiments carried out. It starts with the discussion on descriptive statistics, correlation, test of hypotheses, discussions of findings and policy implications of the findings.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics below shows the nature of the data used. It contains information about the mean, maximum, minimum and standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis.

Table 4.1: Summary of Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Obs	MEAN	STD. DV	MIN	MAX	skewnwss	Kurtosis
CSHD	360	1.009	.6600	.0031	2.933	0.000	0.422
GROP	360	.8029	.0888	.0987	1.006	0.000	0.025
CAPE	360	.8453	.0844	.5471	1.898	0.000	0.000
CSHL	360	.4003	.7101	.0002	4.216	0.000	0.000
NWCP	360	.8352	.0646	.5386	1.006	0.000	0.000
LEVG	360	.8586	.0600	.5399	1.018	0.000	0.000
FSIZ	360	.8476	.0504	.7538	1.004	0.012	0.125

Source: STATA Output, 2024

Table 4.1 reveals that cash holdings CSHL, growth opportunities (GROP), capital expenditure (CAPE), cash flow (CSHL), networking capital (NWCP), leverage (LEVG) and firm size FSIZ has a mean value of (1.01,.803,.845,.400,.835,.859 and .848), while, the standard deviation are (.660, .089,.084,.710,.065,.060,.050). Their maximum are (2.93,.1.01,1.89,4.22,1.01,1.02 and 1.00). Therefore, there mean value signifies that on average, the cash and cash equivalents of the firms' normal of the total asset. The growth opportunities show a wide dispersion across the industries. Also, capital expenditure (CAPE) indicating a widespread out of the individual firms which value suggests that in capital expenses in form of property, plant and equipment form the .total asset less cash and cash equivalent. In addition cash flow (CSFL) indicate a wide spread out of the individual firms CSFL from the mean during the period of the study. The standard deviation and maximum implies that even though these firms are listed in Nigeria group of stock exchange, there some non-financial firms in Nigeria that are still facing difficulties in generating internal cash flows. The networking capital (NWCP) has a mean value and standard implies that that most of the non-financial firms have enough short-term assets to cover their short-term liabilities. The natural logarithm of total assets is used as a proxy for our firm size. The average FSIZ signifying that the total assets of the listed non-financial firms in Nigeria are widely dispersed. The mean value of LEVG and standard deviation indicates that firm's asset (exclusive of cash and its equivalents) is covered by debt. This implies that the firms use more of debt to finance their operation or project in line with trade off theory.

4.3 Correlation Matrix of Dependent and Independent Variables

The correlation matrix represents the relationship between two sets of variables. According to Gujarati (2004), all explanatory variables with a coefficient of the correlation less than 0.80 are considered to be deemed harmless.

Table 4:2: Correlation Matrix

	CSHD	GROP	CAPE	CSHL	NWCP	FSIZ	LEVG
CSHD	1.00						
GROP	-0.1750*	1.000					
CAPE	0.0568	0.3908*	1.000				
CSHL	-0.2152*	-0.0074	-0.0407	1.000			
NWCP	-0.1504*	0.5344*	0.6487*	-0.0088*	1.000		
FSIZ	0.0366	0.5951*	0.6407*	-0.0625	0.7054*	1.00	
LEVG	0.0643	0.5250*	0.7032*	-0.0063*	0.7719*	0.7469*	1.000

Source: STATA Output, 2024

The correlation matrix the relationship between CSHD, GROP, CSHL and NWCP are (-0.18-0.22 and -0.15). This implies that GROP they reduced CSHD of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. It also implies that as they increase, they will lower the CSHD. The relationship between GROP and CSHL (-0.01) also, GROP and CSHL (-0.01), CAPE and CSH (-0.04) then CSHL and NWCP, FSIZ and LEVG (-0.01-0.06 and -0.01) all show reduction. This implies that as the companies NWCP, FSIZ and LEVG increase it affect the CSHL. All the other variables indicated that there is an increased in their relationship with CSHD. On the aspect of explanatory variables themselves, its shows that there is no multicollinearity among the independent variables as the highest value of the coefficient is approximately .77 which is between LEVG and FSIZ and it is below the threshold of 0.80 (Gujarati and Porter, 2009).

4.4 Result of Robustness Tests

To ensure validity and reliability of the statistical inference a robustness tests was carried out on normality of the data, multicollinearity, heteroskedasticity, auto correlation, and Hausman specification test.

4.4.1 Test for Multicollinearity

Table 4.3: Tolerance and VIF values

VARIABLES	VIF	1/VIF
GROP	1.63	0.61
CAPE	2.19	0.46
CSHL	1.01	0.99
NWCP	2.89	0.35
LEVG	3.47	0.29
FSIZ	2.90	0.34
Mean VIF	2.35	

Source: STATA Output, 2024

Classical Least square regression assumes no multicollinearity. Multicollinearity happens when there is harmful relationship among the explanatory variables. The result of the multicollinearity test is showed that the VIF values for all the variables are less than 4 and tolerance values are greater than 0.20 which indicated that there is no multicollinearity (Hair et al., 2010)

4.5 Presentation and Interpretation of Fixed Effect Regression Result

Table 4.4 the result from the fixed effect result is presented in table below.

Variables	Coefficient	Robust Std error	T- value	P>(Z)
GROP	-1.752	-2.59	0.76	0.000
CAPE	.744	-.313	1.38	0.168
CSHL	-.193	-.289	-3.94	0.000
NWCP	-4.89	-7.06	-4.41	0.000
FSIZ	1.12	-.844	1.12	0.264
LEVG	5.41	2.56	3.72	0.000
Constant	.3999	-.642	0.76	0.453
R2	.191			
Wald chi2	65.56			0.000

Source: STATA Output, 2024

In table 4.8, it can be observed that the Wald chi² is 65.56 with a p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05%. Also, there is clear indication that the model is fit and adequate. It shows that variables picked for this study jointly affect CSHD of the firms. The joint effect of all the independent variables R² .191 means the study account for 19% of the changes in the dependent variable. While, remaining are explained by other factors.

4.6 Hypotheses Testing

This section show the test of hypotheses using the linear regression and the result was analyzed below.

Ho₁ Growth opportunities have no significant impact on cash holdings of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

Table 4.4 above indicates that GROP has coefficient of -1.75 and p-value of (0.000) 1% level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis one (Ho₁) is rejected.

Ho₂ Capital expenditure has no significant impact on cash holdings of listed non-financial companies in Nigeria.

Table 4.4 above indicates that CAPE has coefficient of 1.38 and p-value of (0.168) 10% level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis two (Ho₂) is fail to be rejected.

Ho₃ Cash flow has no significant impact on cash holdings of listed non-financial companies in Nigeria.

Table 4.4 above indicates that CSHL has coefficient of $-.193$ and p-value of (0.000) 1% level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis three (H_{0_3}) is rejected.

H_{0_4} Net working capital has no significant impact on cash holdings of listed non-financial companies in Nigeria.

Table 4.4 above indicates that NWCP has coefficient of -4.89 and p-value of (0.000) 1% level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis three (H_{0_4}) is rejected.

H_{0_5} : Leverage has no significant impact on cash holdings of listed non-financial companies in Nigeria.

Table 4.4 above indicates that LEVG has coefficient of 5.41 and p-value of (0.000) 1% level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis three (H_{0_5}) is rejected.

H_{0_6} Firm size has no significant impact on cash holdings of listed non-financial companies in Nigeria.

Table 4.4 above indicates that FSIZ has coefficient of 1.12 and p-value of (0.264) 19% level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis six (H_{0_6}) is fail to be rejected.

4.7 Discussion of Finding

The result shows that growth opportunities have a negative coefficient of -1.75 with a p-value of 0.000 which is significant at 1% level of significance. This means when there is an increase in the sales growth it will lead to -1.75 decreases in CSHD. The finding is in consistence with the work of (Agustin et al., 2021; Raimi and Samaila, 2022; Nasar, 2018; Sheikh, et al., 2018).

Also, CAPE a coefficient of $.74$ and a p-value of 0.17 which is insignificant at 10%. This suggests that capital expenditure has a positive and insignificant impact on cash holdings of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. This shows that an increase in CAPE will lead to $.17$ increases in cash holdings. This by implication suggests that firm's engagement in capital expenses consumes a lot of cash leading to fall in cash reserves. (Omobolade and Jeremiah, 2023; Duru et al., 2019) and contrary to that of (Thu and Khuong, 2018). The CSHL has a coefficient of $-.193$ and a p-value of 0.000 . This shows that a decrease in cash flow will lead to decrease in cash holdings by $.19$. This implies that less cash flow non-financial firms retain lesser cash balance to save up for further investment opportunities or to avoid bankruptcy risk. This finding is in line with the studies by in line with the work of (Agbata, Nzewi et al., 2021; Barasa et al., 2018; Barasa, et al., 2018; Wijaya and Bandi, 2018) who discovered that firm with more cash flow accumulated more cash and it equivalent for precautionary motive.

The table reveals that networking capital has a coefficient that is negative -4.89 and a p-value of (0.000) 1% which is significant at 1%. It suggests that a decrease in networking capital will lead to lesser cash and equivalent balances. This finding is in line with the work of (Ibrahim et al., 2020 and Shamsudeen, & Idris, 2022). The result of the coefficient of leverage has a value of 5.41 and a p-value of (0.000) 1% which is significant at 1%. The

finding is consistent with the work of (Hassan et al., 2022: Hassan and Adegbe, 2021): Aloa and Sanyaolu, 2020: Ogundipe, et al., 2012: Wasiuzzaman, 2014: Amalia et al., 2018) and contrary to work of Tayem, 2017: Westerman and Gancherka, 2018). The above regression result shows that firm size has a coefficient value of 1.12 and a p-value of 0.264. This reveals that firm size has positive and insignificant effect on cash holdings of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. The finding is in line with the study of Onyeka, Nnado and Ugwuanyi (2020), Li & Zeng (2020), Boriçi and Kruja (2016), Chireka and Fakoya (2017), Abdioglu (2016) and contrary to Nasar (2018)

4.8 Policy Implication of the Findings

Our research has practical implications for most stakeholders of non-financial firms in Nigeria. Large corporate cash holdings correlate with possible friction between entities. A thorough knowledge of the connection between various firm characteristic considerations and the cash holdings of the managers may make rational decisions on the level of cash holdings of their choice. The findings provide evidence that the non-financial firms in Nigeria although listed holds cash for precautionary and transaction motives.

5.1 Conclusions and Recommendations

Cash is seen as one of the oil that greases the economy of a nation as firms need and hold cash for several motives. Thus, the study concludes as follows:

First and foremost, the inferential statistic revealed that growth opportunities, capital expenditure, firm size and leverage have statistical negative impact on cash holdings. The study provide basis for conclusion that the growth opportunities reduce cash holdings of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. Thirdly, the study findings revealed higher cash flow and net working capital negatively impact on cash holdings of the listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. Based on this the study concludes that lower cash flow leads to lack of improves in cash holdings. The study recommends that management should adopt strategies that will improve cash sales. This could include discounts on earlier payment. Management should properly evaluate their capital investment properly to avoid investment in unprofitable projects that will dilute cash holding. The study also recommends that management of non-financial firms should increase their cash flow by reevaluating their expenditures and improving efficiency. Management should come up with an effective Networking capital management policy especially on inventory management in order to enhance or increase the cash holdings so as to meet up with the day to day activities. The study found that leverage improves cash holdings. Hence, the study recommends that management of non-financial firms should seek for optimal capital structure by ensuring that the debt covenant on leverage are favorable in order to improve cash holdings.

REFERENCES

- Abdioglu, N. (2016). Managerial Ownership and Corporate cash holdings: Insights from and Emerging Market. *Business and economics research journal*. 7(2), 29-41.
- Abosedo, S. A. & Ibrahim, M. Y. (2022). Influence of firm's size and age on leverage of listed financial firms in Nigeria. *advanced International Journal of Banking, Accounting and Finance (AIJBAF)*. 4(11), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.35631/AIJBAF.411001>
- Agbata, A. E., Nzewi, Nkem V. & Uchegbu C. U. (2021). Effect of Cash Holdings on Financial Performance of Quoted Non financial Companies in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research*. 7(8) 12-26. www.ijaar.org
- Agustin E. Halim P. S. & Agselia A. (2021). Factors Determining Cash Holding in Non financial Companies. Tenth International Conference on Entrepreneurship and Business Management 2021 (ICEBM 2021). *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*. 6(5) 34-4.9
- Al-Amarneh, A. (2015). Corporate cash holdings and financial crisis: *evidence from Jordan International Business Research*, 8(5), 213- 222.
- Alchian. A. A. & Demsetz, H. (1972). Production, information costs, and economic organization. *The American Economic Review*, 62(5), 777-795.
- Barasa, C., Achoki, G. & Njuguna, A. (2018). Determinants of Corporate Cash Holding of Non-Financial Firms Listed on the Nairobi Securities Exchange. *International Journal of Business and Management*. 13(9), 222-235
- Bates, T., Kahle, K. M. & Stulz, R. M. (2009). Why do U.S. firms hold so much more cash than they used to?. *The Journal of Finance*, LXIV(5), 1985-2021.
- Bouwman, C. H. S. & Lowry, M. (2012). *Cash Holdings and the Effects of Pre-IPO Financing in Newly Public Firms*. Retrieved on 30/07/2023 from http://www.personal.psu.edu/mbl3/Bouwman_Lowry.pdf
- Daily, C. M., Dalton, D. R. & Cannella, A. A. (2003). Corporate governance: Decades of dialogue and data. *Academy of Management Review*. 28(3), 371-382.
- Dang, C. & Li F. (2015). Measuring firm size in empirical corporate finance; *JEL Classifications*: G3, G30, G31, G32, G34, G35, C23, C58, J31, J33.
- Ferreira, M. A. & Vilela, A. S. (2004). Why do firms hold cash? Evidence from EMU countries. *European Financial Management*, 10(4) 295-319.
- Fresard, L. & Salva, C. (2010). The value of excess cash and corporate governance: Evidence from U.S. cross-listings. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 98(2), 359-384.

- Gaddard, J., Tavapoli, M., & Wilson, (2005) Determinants of profitability in European manufacturing and services industry: Evidence from dynamic panel data. *Applied financial management*. 15 (18), 1261-1282
- Ginglinger, E. & Saddour K. (2010). *Cash holdings, corporate governance and financial constraints*. Retrieved on 10/07/2023 from https://halshs.archives-ouvertes.fr/halshs_0016_2404.
- Ibrahim L., Umar F. A. & Sanni O. N. (2020) Effect of Firm Dynamism and determinants on Cash Holding of Listed Non financial Firms in Nigeria. *Gusau Journal of Accounting and Finance*, I(2), October, 21-35
- Izadinia , N. & Rasaian, A. (2010), Company strategic supervisory tools, level of cash holding and performance of companies accepted in Tehran stock exchange market. *Economic Research and Policies Periodical*, 4(6) 141 - 154.
- Jebran, K., Iqbal, A., Bhat, K. U., Khan, M. A., & Hayat, M. (2019). Determinants of corporate cash holdings in tranquil and turbulent period: evidence from an emerging economy. *Financial Innovation*, 5(3) 78-89 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40854-018-0116-y>
- Jensen, M. & Meckling, W. (1976). Theory of the firm: managerial behaviour, Agency costs and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(4), 305-360
- Ji, Y., Chen, M., Lee, C. & Lin, Y. (2012). Ownership structure, excess cash holdings and corporate performance. *Journals of Global Economy and Finance*, 5(2), 1-25.
- Kafayat, A., Rehman, K. & Farooq, M. (2014). *Factor affecting corporate cash holdings of non financial firms in pakistan*. Retrieved on 20/02/2023 from <http://journals.univ-danubius.ro/index.php/oeconomica/article/view/2262>.
- Kariuki, S. N., Amusonge, G. S. & Orwa, G. O. (2015). Determinants of corporate cash holdings: Evidence from private manufacturing firms in Kenya. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences*, 4(6), 2278-6236.
- Khan, A., & Tanveer, S. (2016). The impact of corporate governance on cash holdings: A comparative study of the manufacturing and service industry. Retrieved from [fs.icfm.ro/l20\(3\)40-79.pdf](http://fs.icfm.ro/l20(3)40-79.pdf)
- Kumar, S., Kumar, B., Singh, D. & Khan, K. (2021). Innovation in corporate cash holding & management: an empirical investigation. *Empirical Economics Letters*, 20(3), 21-31.
- Li, Z., Jiang, J., Xia, L. & Chu, C. (2020). Empirical research on the relationship between industry working capital shortfall and company cash holding in the same industry. *Discrete Dynamics in Nature and Society*, 2022, 1-14.

- Magerakis, E., Siriopoulos, C. & Tsagkanos, A. (2015). Cash holdings and firm characteristics: evidence from UK market. *Journal of Risk & Control*, 2(1), 19-43.
- Mai, M.U.(2006). Analisis Variabel-Variabel yang Mempengaruhi Struktur Modal Pada Perusahaan-Perusahaan LQ-45 di Bursa Efek Jakarta. *Ekonomika*, 228-245. Politeknik Negeri, Bandung.
- Mohd-Ashhari, Z. & Faizal, D. R. (2018). Determinants and performance of cash holding Evidence from small business in Malaysia. *International Journal of Economics, Management and Accounting* 26 (2), 457-473
- Okeke, L. N., Ezejiofor, R. A. & Okoye, N. J. (2021). Leverage and cash ratio: an empirical study of conglomerates firm in Nigeria. *American Journal of Contemporary Management Sciences Research (AJCMSR)*, 2(3)76-84.
- Onyeka V. N., Nnado I. C. and Ugwuanyi U. B. (2020) firm size, profitability and cash holding: A causal analysis of selected quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business, Economics and Accountancy* 8,(3) 34-48. www.idpublications.org
- Pandey, I. M, Chotigeat, T., & Ranjit, M. K. (2000). Capital Structure Choices in an Emerging Capital Market: Case of Thailand, *Management and Change, Journal of Management* 4, (1) 1-14.
- Pinkowitz, L. E., Stulz, R. E. & Williamson, R. (2006). Does the contribution of corporate cash holdings and dividends to firm value depend on governance? A cross-country analysis, *Journal of Finance*, 61(6), 2725-2751.
- Rehman, A. & Wang, M. (2015). Corporate cash holdings and adjustment behaviour in Chinese firms: An empirical analysis using generalized method of moment. *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*,9(4), 20-37.
- Saddour, K. (2006). *The determinants and the value of cash holdings: Evidence from French firms*. Retrieved on 15/03/2015 from http://www.dauphine.fr/cereg/cahier_recherche/cereg_200606.pdf
- Saddour, K. (2006). *The Determinants and the Value of Cash Holdings: Evidence from French Firms* (Cahier de recherche n°2006-6). Universite Paris Dauphine: Recherches en Management.
- Samaila, A. I. (2014). Corporate governance and financial reporting quality in the Nigerian oil marketing industry. (Unpublished thesis). Bayero University, Kano.
- Shamsuddeen, S., S. and Idris I. (2022) Effect of firms-specific Characteristics on corporate cash holding of listed Manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *Journal Of Innovation Research & Advanced Studies International Journal Of African Sustainable Development* June 30, 2022 Vol. 18 No. 2 ISSN: 0199 – 4818

- Sheikh, N.A., Mehmood, K.K., & Kamal, M., (2018). Determinants of Corporate Cash Holdings: Evidence from MNCs in Pakistan. *Review of Economics and Development Studies*, 4 (1) 71-78 <https://DOI.org/10.26710/reads.v4i1.282>
- Shubita, M.F. (2019). The impact of working capital management on cash holdings of large and small firms: evidence from Jordan. *Investment Management and Financial Innovations*, 16(3), 76-86. <https://doi.org/10.21511/imfi>.
- Tayem, G. (2015). The Determinants of Corporate Cash Holdings: The Case of a Small Emerging Market. *International Journal of Financial Research*, 8(1), 143-154
- Westerman, W., & Gancherka, S. (2018). Financial and Institutional Determinants of Cash Holdings in the Oil and Gas Industry. *Journal of Corporate Finance Research*, 12(3), 60-72. <https://doi.org/10.17323/j.jcfr.2073-0438.12.3.2018.60-72>
- Wijaya, A.L. & Bandi H. (2018). The Effect of Leverage on Corporate Cash Holdings: Evidence from Indonesian Manufacturing Firms. 4(2), 61-72, <https://DOI.org/10.5817/FAI2018->

EDUCATION, SKILLS, AND EMPLOYMENT OUTCOMES IN NIGERIA: A PATH TO INCLUSIVE AND SUSTAINABLE GROWTH

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the disconnect between education and employment outcomes in Nigeria, where youth unemployment remains critically high. Drawing on 16 Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) with stakeholders in education and labor sectors, the research identifies six core challenges: obsolete curricula, institutional constraints, limited public-private collaboration, regional disparities, and weak monitoring systems. Findings reveal that education reforms, though well-intentioned, are undermined by bureaucratic inefficiencies, insufficient infrastructure, and poor alignment with labor market demands. Thematic and sentiment analyses highlight widespread frustration with existing systems but also optimism for locally driven, collaborative reform. Engaging Human Capital and Systems theories, the paper calls for context-specific, employer-informed strategies to enhance employability and inclusive growth. The study contributes to discourse on education reform by emphasizing the importance of institutional readiness, feedback mechanisms, and regional equity in shaping sustainable education-to-employment pathways in Nigeria.

Keywords: Education, Skills, Employment Outcomes, Human Capital, Growth, Nigeria

JEL Code: I25, J24, O15, I28

1.0 Introduction

Nigeria continues to grapple with an escalating youth unemployment crisis, with estimates reaching 42% in 2024 (NBS). This crisis is underpinned by structural inadequacies within the country's educational and labor market systems. Scholars have linked the persistence of socio-economic instability-including insurgency, banditry, and militancy-to widespread youth unemployment and underemployment. At the center of this issue lies a disjointed relationship between educational outcomes, skills acquisition, and labor market absorption capacity.

Despite the formal adoption of the 6-3-3-4 educational model, systemic challenges endure. These include inadequate infrastructure, limited funding, regional disparities, and severe teacher shortages (Ezewuzie, Udeogu, and Okoli, 2025). Consequently, learning outcomes remain poor, with over 18.5 million out-of-school children, the highest globally (UNICEF, 2023). Moreover, tertiary graduates frequently lack the technical, digital, and practical competencies demanded by today's labor markets, deepening the employability crisis (Osidiye, 2017).

Although national policy frameworks-such as the National Skills Policy and Youth Employment Action Plan-seek to address these challenges, weak implementation persists.

Bureaucratic inefficiencies, underfunding, and poor coordination between education and industry actors hinder progress (Adewolu Ogwo, 2024). Compared to countries like Germany and China, where over 40% of secondary students are enrolled in Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET), Nigeria records less than 10% (Osidipe, 2017). This underinvestment contributes to the dominance of informal, low-productivity employment, which currently accounts for over 83% of the workforce (Citaristi, 2022).

This situation raises a critical question: To what extent can Nigeria's education system equip its youth with the skills required by a dynamic, evolving labor market? While quantitative data has established the magnitude of the problem, there is limited understanding of the institutional dynamics shaping educational policy and its execution.

This study explores the intersection of education, skills development, and employment outcomes in Nigeria, with an emphasis on the institutional and political factors influencing reform efforts. It draws on Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) with policymakers and institutional actors to unpack the bureaucratic, strategic, and implementation challenges constraining systemic transformation. Through this approach, the study highlights the internal and external mechanisms that shape education policy effectiveness and labor market responsiveness.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Structural Challenges in Nigerian Education

Nigeria's education system remains hindered by structural deficits, including poor infrastructure, overcrowded classrooms, and a shortage of trained teachers. Although theoretically sound, the system is critically under-resourced, contributing to persistently low learning outcomes (Ezewuzie, Udeogu, and Okoli, 2025). Regional disparities further widen inequality, with rural areas-particularly in the North-facing chronic educational deprivation (Chibuokwu and Nwosu, 2016). Nwoke, Oyiga, and Cochrane, (2024) highlights that Nigeria leads globally in the number of out-of-school children, underlining systemic exclusion.

2.2 Skills Mismatches and Labor Market Irrelevance

A misalignment persists between formal education and labor market needs. Graduates often lack technical, digital, and problem-solving competencies critical in today's economy (Osidipe, 2017). Employers report dissatisfaction with graduate preparedness, especially in communication and practical application (Akanmu, 2011). This mismatch contributes to the paradox of rising educational attainment without improved employability (Ofor-Douglas, 2025).

2.3 Policy Implementation Deficits

Despite numerous national initiatives-such as the National Skills Policy and Youth Employment Action Plan-implementation remains inconsistent. Challenges include overlapping institutional mandates, inadequate coordination, and weak funding systems (Adewolu Ogwo, 2024). Political interference and limited accountability have further stalled reform efforts (Okolie, Elom, Igwe, Binuomote, Nwajiuba, and Igu, 2021; Onyekwelu, Okpalibekwe, and Dike, 2015).

2.4 Marginalization of TVET

Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) is underutilized, with less than 10% of secondary students enrolled in such programs, compared to over 40% in countries like Germany and China (Osidiye, 2017). Societal biases favor university education, while TVET institutions suffer from outdated facilities, limited investment, and underqualified personnel (Terna, 2021).

2.5 Informal Labor Market Dominance

The poor alignment between education and employment has led to the growth of informal labor, now encompassing over 83% of Nigeria's workforce (Citaristi, 2022). These jobs are often unstable, poorly paid, and lack career progression pathways. Scholars argue this reflects deeper failures in human capital development and labor policy (Akanmu, 2011).

2.6 Political Economy and Institutional Resistance

Institutional reform is frequently impeded by vested interests and politicized decision-making. Curriculum updates and resource allocations are often driven by political rather than empirical considerations (Eneh, and Owo, 2017; Maduagwu, and Otusinkama, 2024). The resistance from unions and bureaucracies poses significant barriers to policy enforcement and innovation.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study adopts a qualitative design to explore the institutional and policy-related dynamics affecting education-to-employment transitions in Nigeria. The approach is suitable for examining complex, context-dependent issues—such as curriculum relevance, skills development, and policy execution—that quantitative methods may overlook.

3.2 Data Collection Method

Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) served as the primary data source. These interviews provided insights from individuals directly involved in education planning, policy formulation, implementation, and labor market coordination. A semi-structured guide allowed for thematic coherence while enabling flexibility in responses.

3.3 Interview Framework

The KII guide was structured around seven thematic areas:

Informants' institutional roles and experience

Perceptions of education–employment linkages

Curriculum development and relevance

Institutional constraints and capacity issues

Public–private collaboration

Policy implementation and monitoring mechanisms

Recommendations for systemic reform

Each section comprised open-ended questions designed to elicit reflective, experience-based insights.

3.4 Sampling Strategy

Purposive sampling was used to select 16 key informants with relevant expertise. Participants included senior academics, policy planners, regulatory officials, and private sector representatives involved in education and skills training. The sample was stratified to reflect public–private and regional diversity.

3.5 Data Collection Procedure

Interviews were conducted either in person or via virtual platforms, depending on location and availability. Sessions lasted 45–60 minutes and were audio-recorded with informed consent. Recordings were transcribed verbatim to ensure accuracy and depth in analysis.

4.0 Data Analysis

Thematic analysis followed Braun and Clarke’s (2006) six-phase model:

Familiarization with data

Generation of initial codes

Theme identification

Review of themes

Theme definition and naming

Report production

Coding was both deductive, based on the interview guide, and inductive, allowing themes to emerge organically. NVivo 15 software facilitated systematic data management and analysis.

4.1 Findings and Thematic Analysis

This section presents the thematic analysis of 16 Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) with stakeholders across Nigeria’s education and labor sectors. Six major themes emerged, each reflecting core systemic challenges. Sub-themes are supported by illustrative quotes, frequency of mention, and a summary of sentiment.

Theme 1: Education-Labor Market Mismatch

Summary:

All respondents expressed concern about the misalignment between academic instruction and labor market requirements. The system remains heavily theory-based, producing graduates with limited technical and soft skills.

Sub-Themes:

Theory vs. Practical Orientation: Rote learning dominates pedagogy, leaving students ill-equipped for real-world tasks.

Digital Illiteracy: Most institutions lack the tools to deliver hands-on digital skills training.

Soft Skills Deficit: Skills like communication, adaptability, and teamwork are not

systematically taught.

Sentiment:

Frustrated/Concerned -12 | Neutral - 4 | Positive - 0

Quote:

“Our system teaches theory, not survival. Students can’t think critically or adapt in modern workplaces.” - Dean, Faculty of Education

Theme 2: Curriculum Reform - Progress and Limitations

Summary:

Although curriculum reform is ongoing, respondents noted slow, bureaucratic cycles and weak employer engagement. Reforms often remain in pilot phases without scaling.

Sub-Themes:

Entrepreneurship Mandates: Common but poorly implemented due to lack of resources.

Bureaucratic Review Cycles: Updates occur every 5-7 years with minimal industry input.

Pilot Saturation: Reforms rarely move beyond trials.

Sentiment:

Negative - 9 | Neutral - 6 | Positive - 1

Quote:

“Entrepreneurship is now in the curriculum, but the labs are empty and instructors not trained.” - Assistant Director, MOE

Theme 3: Institutional and Regional Constraints

Summary:

Funding shortfalls, faculty capacity issues, and regional inequities-especially between North and South-undermine reform.

Sub-Themes:

Infrastructure Gaps: Rural institutions lack electricity, internet, and labs.

Faculty Resistance: Some educators resist pedagogical change due to poor training.

Regional Disparities: Northern institutions face greater structural disadvantages.

Sentiment:

Negative - 13 | Neutral - 3 | Positive - 0

Quote:

“Without internet or power, how do we teach ICT?” - Curriculum Advisor, NCCE

Theme 4: Weak Public–Private Collaboration

Summary:

Collaboration with employers is largely informal, often driven by NGOs rather than institutional partnerships. Respondents called for structured engagement with industry.

Sub-Themes:

Informal Internships: Largely uncoordinated and unmonitored.

Donor Reliance: NGOs often lead skills initiatives.

Absent Advisory Structures: No formal mechanisms for industry input into curricula.

Sentiment:

Negative - 10 | Neutral - 4 | Positive - 2

Quote:

“We rely on donor funding. No real structure for public-private partnerships in our state.”
— Deputy Director, FMOE

Theme 5: Monitoring and Evaluation Deficiencies

Summary:

A lack of data systems hinders feedback loops. Graduate tracking is ad hoc, and reform outcomes are rarely measured systematically.

Sub-Themes:

No Graduate Tracing: Institutions lack systems for tracking employment outcomes.

Weak Feedback Cycles: Data rarely informs curriculum reform.

Sentiment:

Negative - 8 | Neutral - 7 | Positive - 1

Quote:

How do we measure success if we don't even track our graduates?" - Program Manager, NGO

Theme 6: Recommendations for Reform

Summary:

Respondents emphasized labor-aligned, localized reforms driven by stakeholder collaboration and infrastructural investment.

Sub-Themes:

Employer Involvement: Co-design of curricula with industry is essential.

Localized Design: Policies must reflect regional needs.

Capacity & Infrastructure: Reform must be supported with tools, training, and resources.

Sentiment:

Positive - 13 | Neutral - 3 | Negative - 0

Quote:

"Reform without funding is just rhetoric. Let's start from classrooms, not policy documents." - Principal Lecturer, COE

Cross-Cutting Patterns and Theme Interdependencies

Key Theme Pairs & Interpretations:

- Curriculum Reform ↔ Labor Mismatch: Outdated content contributes directly to unemployability.
- Institutional Constraints ↔ Regional Inequality: Rural disadvantage magnifies reform challenges.
- Monitoring Gaps ↔ Policy Ineffectiveness: Weak data limits responsive policymaking.
- Employer Linkage ↔ Curriculum Gaps: Lack of industry voice hampers curricular relevance.

These intersections highlight the need for a systems-level response. Reform in isolation-

without addressing infrastructure, feedback, and collaboration-has limited effect.

4.2 Discussion

This study explored how Nigeria’s education system aligns with labor market needs, focusing on graduate readiness, institutional capacity, and the effectiveness of current reforms. The analysis revealed widespread consensus that the system is misaligned with labor demands and hindered by institutional bottlenecks and weak implementation structures.

4.2.1 Theoretical Engagement

4.2.1.1 Human Capital Theory

The findings challenge the assumption that education alone leads to productivity gains. Despite increased access to higher education, graduate employability remains low due to skill mismatches and curriculum irrelevance-highlighting the limitations of traditional human capital frameworks in low-resource contexts.

4.2.1.2 Systems Theory

The results support a systems-based interpretation: education reform requires coordination across multiple domains—curriculum, infrastructure, industry input, and monitoring. A breakdown in any part disrupts overall impact. This interdependence was evident in co-occurrence patterns among the themes.

4.2.1.3 Postcolonial Curriculum Critique

Respondents voiced concerns that curricula remain externally modeled and detached from local economic and cultural realities, particularly in under-resourced Northern institutions. This reinforces critiques that postcolonial systems often perpetuate imported frameworks without contextual adaptation.

4.2.2 Interpretive Insights

Fragmented Reform Momentum

Although entrepreneurship and digital literacy have been introduced, implementation is slow and uneven. Educators express “reform fatigue,” where policies are seen as rhetorical rather than transformative.

Institutional Marginalization

Rural and Northern institutions suffer from compounded challenges—poor infrastructure, limited faculty capacity, and regional underinvestment—widening existing educational and economic divides.

Readiness for Change

Despite frustration, participants expressed a clear desire for reforms that are regionally grounded, co-created with industry, and supported by meaningful investment. This suggests an opportunity for targeted interventions that build on stakeholder insight and energy.

Policy and Practice Implications

Core Challenge	Policy Recommendation
Curriculum – Labor Mismatch	Institutionalize employer advisory boards to guide curriculum design
Infrastructure Gaps	Establish targeted federal investment in digital and physical infrastructure for rural institutions
Faculty Resistance	Link pedagogical retraining to career advancement and reform implementation metrics
Monitoring Deficits	Mandate graduate tracer systems tied to institutional accreditation
Regional Inequities	Introduce weighted funding formulas favoring underserved regions

5.0 Conclusion

5.1 Summary of Key Insights

This study examined the systemic challenges linking education, skills development, and employment outcomes in Nigeria. Through qualitative interviews with stakeholders, six interrelated barriers were identified: curriculum-labor market disconnect, institutional bottlenecks, weak public-private collaboration, inadequate monitoring systems, regional disparities, and limited infrastructure. These issues collectively hinder reform and perpetuate youth underemployment.

5.2 Implications for Reform

The findings highlight that reforms must extend beyond curriculum adjustments to address broader structural and institutional weaknesses. A systems approach-linking policy, pedagogy, infrastructure, and accountability-is essential for durable impact. Institutional readiness, regional equity, and employer engagement should form the foundation of national strategies for education reform.

5.3 Contribution to Knowledge

This research contributes to existing literature by offering grounded, insider perspectives on education policy implementation in Nigeria. It demonstrates the value of qualitative insight, co-occurrence analysis, and sentiment mapping in diagnosing systemic challenges and designing targeted reforms.

5.4 Recommendation

Nigeria's education system does not lack ideas-it lacks coherent execution, regional sensitivity, and sustained collaboration. The findings point to a sector rich in diagnostic clarity and stakeholder will. What remains is coordinated action driven by political will, institutional capacity, and strategic investment.

Reform must now shift from policy declarations to tangible interventions-designed with, and for, those within the system.

5.5 Limitations and Areas for Further Research

Limitations

While the study offers valuable insights, it is not without limitations. The sample size,

though diverse, is relatively small and may not fully represent the broader spectrum of education and labor stakeholders across Nigeria. Additionally, the study's reliance on stakeholder perceptions may introduce subjective bias, as responses reflect individual experiences rather than institutional performance data.

Future Research

Further research could benefit from a longitudinal, mixed-methods approach to track the evolution of specific reforms over time. Quantitative data on graduate employment outcomes, regional education investments, and institutional performance metrics would complement the qualitative findings. Future studies might also explore gendered and intersectional dimensions of access to education and employment in underserved regions.

REFERENCES

- Adewolu Ogwo, A. (2024). Higher education, skills development and students' preparedness for employability: A case study of the University of Lagos, Nigeria (towards a sustained practice approach with the triple helix model of innovation (Doctoral Dissertation, University College London). UCL.
- Akanmu, O. (2011). Graduate employment and employability challenges in Nigeria. In *Going global: The landscape for policy makers and practitioners in tertiary education* (p. 93). British Council.
- Chibuokwu, R. A., & Nwosu, F. I. (2016). Education and human capital development in Nigeria: The way forward. *Journal of Resourcefulness and Distinction*, 12(1), 56–68.
- Citaristi, I. (2022). International Labour Organization–ILO. In *The Europa directory of international organizations 2022* (pp. 343–349). Routledge.
- Eneh, O. C., & Owo, N. J. (2017). Education reforms in the Nigerian university system: A critique and suggested strategies. *Preface and Acknowledgements*, 101.
- Ezewuzie, S. O., Udeogu, P. A., & Okoli, H. N. (2025). Assessment of educational policies and reforms in Nigeria: Challenges and prospects. *Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University Journal of Arts and Social Science Education*, 4(1).
- Maduagwu, U. M., & Otusinkama, L. (2024). Influence of politics in curriculum innovation and change in Nigeria educational system. *African Journal of Educational Management, Teaching and Entrepreneurship Studies*, 11(2), 90–103.
- Nwoke, C., Oyiga, S., & Cochrane, L. (2024). Assessing the phenomenon of out-of-school children in Nigeria: Issues, gaps and recommendations. *Review of Education*, 12(3), e70011. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rev3.70011>
- Ofor-Douglas, S. (2025). Bridging the employment gap: Strategies for Nigeria's university system to reduce graduate unemployment. *BW Academic Journal*.
- Okolie, U. C., Elom, E. N., Igwe, P. A., Binuomote, M. O., Nwajiuba, C. A., & Igu, N.

- C. (2021). Improving graduate outcomes: Implementation of problem-based learning in TVET systems of Nigerian higher education. *Higher Education, Skills and Work-Based Learning*, 11(1), 92–110.
- Okolie, U. C., Nwosu, H. E., & Mlanga, S. (2019). Graduate employability: How the higher education institutions can meet the demand of the labour market. *Higher Education, Skills and Work-Based Learning*, 9(4), 620–636.
- Onyekwelu, R. U., Okpalibekwe, U. N., & Dike, E. E. (2015). The bureaucracy and the challenges of policy-formulation and implementation: The Nigerian experience. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review (Oman Chapter)*, 4(10), 12–20.
- OpenAI. (2023). ChatGPT (Mar 14 version) [Large language model]. <https://chat.openai.com/chat>. This paper made use of OpenAI's ChatGPT (April 2025 version) for editorial suggestions and language refinement. Final content and interpretation remain the author's responsibility
- Osidipe, A. (2017). Prospects for TVET in developing skills for work in Nigeria. *Prospects*, 8(21), 101–108.
- Terna, A. G. (2021). Revitalizing technical and vocational education for sustainable youth employment and national economic development in Nigeria. *ISSN*, 28(1), 8.

EFFECT OF NON-OIL EXPORTS ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN SUB-SAHARAN AFRICAN COUNTRIES

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ABSTRACT

The effect of non-oil exports on economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) countries has gained significant attention in recent years as the region seeks to diversify its exports and reduce dependence on oil. This study evaluated the effect of non-oil exports on economic growth in SSA. Using a panel secondary data which span the period 2004 to 2023. "The dependent variable was Gross Domestic Product proxied for economic growth; independent variables included Non-oil export output, inflation, exchange rate, gross capital formation and institutional quality." The techniques of analysis use to estimate the panel data is the Common Correlated Effect (CCE). Findings indicates that non-oil export output in both short run and long run exhibited a positive coefficient of (0.8020 & 0.8838) respectively and are found to be statistically significant to economic growth with p-value less than 5% critical value. On the other hand, all the other independent variables such as inflation, exchange rate, gross capital formation and institutional quality index were all found to be insignificant to economic growth, and exhibited a mixed sign of having an inverse and positive relationships in the short term and long term. The study recommends the development and implementation of diversification strategies to promote non-oil exports, such as identifying new markets and product, while ensuring that investment is being made on industries with strong development prospects.

Keyword: *Non-oil exports, Economic growth, Panel CCE and SSA*

JEL Classification: F19, O19, O4, C23

1.0 Introduction

Non-oil exports have been crucial in driving economic growth, generating employment, and boosting living standards on a worldwide scale (World Bank, 2019; Aljebri, 2020). Several nations have exploited non-oil exports to strengthen their economies and minimize their dependency on oil exports, especially those in Asia, Latin America, and Africa (OECD, 2018). For instance, the main non-oil exports from the United States between 1960 and 1970 were agricultural, equipment, and electronics goods. However, Asian countries continued to diversify their economies with an increasing percentage of advanced manufacturing and services from the 1980s to the 2000s, when high-tech products supplanted oil as the principal export (IMF, 2020).

During the 1960s and 1970s, Africa's main exports, in comparison to Asian nations, were basic commodities including metals, minerals, and agricultural products (UNECA, 2020). Nonetheless, African countries continued to diversify their exports during the 2000s,

placing a greater focus on high-value commodities like electronics, cars, and medicines (AFDB, 2020). Countries in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) have historically relied heavily on oil exports as their main source of economic expansion. However, the necessity for these nations to diversify their economies and look into alternate sources of development has been brought to light by the volatility of global oil prices and the limited amount of oil reserves (Arezki & Sy, 2013; World Bank, 2020). Exports of things other than oil, such as manufactured goods, minerals, and agricultural products, provide a viable path for economic expansion and diversification (Hausmann et al., 2017).

In the 1990s, the SSA countries began to diversify their trade policies, which led to a rise in their exports of commodities other than oil (World Bank, 2020). Nonetheless, non-oil exports from SSA rose from \$6.4 billion in 1990 to \$14.6 billion in 2000, making up about 70% of total exports in the 2000s (IMF, 2020; World Bank, 2001). The export of agricultural products, metals, and minerals from SSA nations including Zambia, Tanzania, Mozambique, Namibia, Cote d'Ivoire, and Uganda was the main driver of this growth (IMF, 2020). In many countries, exports of commodities other than oil—such as manufactured products, agricultural commodities, solid minerals, and services—are increasingly playing a major role in economic growth (World Bank, 2020). As a result, economic growth has not been distributed fairly between countries and areas.

It is clear from studies by Asmare and Haiyun (2020) that non-oil export growth has a positive impact on the economy as a whole. SSA countries like Ethiopia and Kenya have benefited greatly from export diversification, particularly in the non-oil sector, which has helped to stabilize their economies and promote economic growth even during times of low oil prices. Furthermore, to support this, UNCTAD (2019) has argued that overtime export-led growth is a major contributor to economic progress in many SSA nations. The export-led growth hypothesis states that there is a positive correlation between exports and economic growth, which is accurate since a country's economic growth tends to increase over time if it increases its exports. Other countries, such as those in America, Europe, and East Asia, have had remarkable growth and modernization, whereas certain countries in Sub-Saharan Africa have faced significant development challenges (World Bank, 2020). With the exception of complementary initiatives addressing infrastructure, non-oil exports have expanded, albeit more slowly than oil exports (Gabriel & David, 2021).

To increase non-oil exports and foster economic growth, SSA nations have put in place a number of initiatives. The Africa Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) is one such effort that seeks to expand non-oil exports, raise their revenue, and open up new markets. Additionally, nations like Nigeria have adopted the Export Expansion Facility Programme (EEFP), the Non-oil Exports Stimulation Facility, and the Exports for Survival Campaign approach, which was started by Nigeria Export Promotion Council (NEPC), in the western part of SSA. Kenya has put in place measures to encourage non-traditional exports, such as the National Exports Strategy (NES), which aims to boost exports of commodities and services other than oil in the southern area. South Africa established programs like the Export Marketing and Investment Assistance Scheme (EMIAS) to encourage non-traditional exports, which offers financial assistance to exporters, especially those who do not export oil. In the central area, nations like Rwanda have put policies in place to encourage non-oil exports, such as the National Export Strategy, which aims to increase

the export of commodities and services other than oil (AFDB, 2020).

The performance of non-oil exports is poor, and many SSA nations are unable to take advantage of new prospects in international commerce due to their over-reliance on oil exports, slow economic development, and little economic diversification. Additional barriers to the expansion of non-oil exports include a lack of infrastructure, fluctuations in the exchange rate have caused high inflation, ongoing conflict, feeble institutions, and a lack of manufacturing capacity because non-oil exports in SSA are concentrated in a few industries, such as agriculture.

In order to inform policy decisions that might help unlock the region's economic potential, this study aims to evaluate the effect of non-oil exports on economic growth in SSA in light of the region's economic difficulties and growth potential. The remainder of the study is arranged as follows: a literature review, methodology, findings and discussion, conclusion, and policy recommendations.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Clarification

Economic Growth

According to Okoli et al. (2023), economic growth is the consistent improvement in a country's GDP due to higher input productivity, trade volume (including import, export, and domestic trade), trade terms size, and general economic stability. One definition of "economic growth" is the steady rise in a country's output and consumption of goods and services. Typically, it is measured using the GDP growth rate. The entire value of all goods and services produced in a country over a specific time period is its GDP (Mankiw, 2018). The World Bank (2018) defines economic growth as an increase in a country's potential gross domestic product (GDP), though this may differ reliant on the methodology used to estimate a country's output. Several earlier studies and growth theories attribute economic growth to increased investment, which is funded by a number of sources, including foreign sources, particularly foreign capital inflows, and domestic savings (Chanie, 2017).

Non-oil Exports

Non-oil exports are commodities that are exchanged on the global market to make money, aside from crude oil (petroleum products) (Kenechukwu & Akunjinma, 2022). Furthermore, economic activities that are not directly related to or outside of the petroleum and gas industry are included in the non-oil sector. Increasing exports of items other than oil can diversify a nation's economy and decrease its reliance on oil revenue. They encourage the growth of the economy, the development of jobs, and foreign exchange earnings. The majority of non-oil exports are goods sold on international markets for the sole goal of making money, such as petroleum products, which are commodities other than crude oil. The IMF (2020) states that non-oil exports from Sub-Saharan Africa may be categorized into many significant groups that reflect the region's diverse natural resources, agricultural production, and emerging industries. These are some common categories, such as Agricultural Products: Among the numerous agricultural exports from Sub-Saharan Africa are products such as cocoa, coffee, tea, cotton, fruits, vegetables, and spices. These products are commonly exported in both their raw and processed forms, including cocoa beans and processed cocoa products like chocolate.

Theoretical Review

Export-led Growth Hypothesis

The ELGH originated in neoclassical economic theory and became well-known in the 1980s. Krueger (1985) and Findlay (1984) According to the notion of export-led growth, a nation's economic growth tends to be higher over time when it boosts its exports. The export-led growth hypothesis, one of the most hotly contested ideas, emphasizes a strong positive long-term association between exports and real GDP growth. This point toward a modification in approach from import substitution to improved trade liberalization and export growth.

Giving to this hypothesis, economic expansion depends on rising exports as well as increases in capital stock and labor force participation (Onose & Aras, 2021). In a similar vein, export growth is one of the main forces behind growth, according to the Export-Led Growth Hypothesis (EGH). It argues that in addition to bringing additional capital and manpower to the economy, increasing exports may also help a country thrive overall. The idea's proponents argue that exports may serve as a growth engine or catalyst.

A common explanation for the relationship between growth and exports is the potential advantages that participating in foreign markets may bring to the domestic economy, including the reallocation of existing resources, economies of scale, and various effects on labor training. As a result, throughout this time, international commerce became a significant force behind economic expansion. The idea that exports increase GDP growth is central to the ELGH. According to the main argument, the export industry boosts total labor and capital levels, which in turn propels growth (Krueger, 1980; Tyler, 1981; Feder, 1982; Shan & Sun, 1998; Alhowaish, 2014; Ee, 2016; Priyankara, 2018).

Unbalance Growth Theory

Scholars like Streeten, Fleming, and Singer (1968) and Hirschman (1958) have advanced the imbalanced growth idea. The approach emphasizes the value of investing in key strategic economic sectors rather than all of them at once, such exporting agricultural goods. According to this theory, every other sector would really flourish on its own because to the "Linkage's effect." According to the theory, deliberately unbalancing the economy in line with planned plans created by academics and researchers is the best approach to accomplish a nation's economic growth. In an ideal environment, if disequilibrium necessitates a development activity, this should lead to further disequilibrium and ultimately an unending circle. Development has proceeded in this way, according to Hirschman (1968), with growth extending from the main leading sectors of the economy, including industry and agriculture, to numerous subsectors.

For example, Hirschman (1958) stated that the theory suggested that in order to promote growth, emerging nations should focus their investments on important areas. However, this "creates imbalances" since certain sectors expand more quickly than others. Exports other than oil have the potential to link and spill over with other economic sectors, fostering economic development and diversification. Investment in non-oil industries like manufacturing and agriculture can also have a multiplier impact on the SSA economy, resulting in further economic development and prosperity.

More steady growth will result from diversification beyond oil exports, which means that SSA economies that are heavily dependent on oil exports and hence vulnerable to price swings can benefit from this approach of expanding into non-oil sectors. Therefore, encouraging exports other than oil can diversify the economy and result in more steady development (Johnson, 2023). Additionally, an increase in non-oil exports may boost non-oil output, produce revenues, and create new employment, all of which can raise GDP (Calderon et al., 2013).

Empirical Review

Shiro et al. (2023) studied the impact of non-oil exports on Nigeria's economy by means of data spanning 1981 to 2020. A model was developed utilizing the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Cointegration Technique as the analytical approach in order to determine if non-oil exports had an impact on Nigeria's real GDP. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF), a bound test, and a stability test were among the tests used to evaluate the study's variables, which included real economic growth, inflation, exchange rates, and non-oil exports. Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) was used as an analytical approach in the study. Nigerian economic development is strongly correlated with non-oil, oil, inflation, and exchange rate exports, according to the ARDL results and the t-test of the hypothesis inquiry. According to the coefficient of determination, 79% of the independent components are accounted for by the dependent variable. According to the report, in order to influence Nigeria's economic growth, policies that monitor inflation and maintain a stable exchange rate for both oil exports and non-exports must be in place.

Okoli et al. (2023) looked at how Nigeria's economic development was affected by non-oil exports between 1981 and 2021. This study found that there is a short-term and long-term relationship between the explained and explanatory components of both models using the Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bound test and the CUSUM stability test methodologies. While the outcomes of the ARDL bound tests indicate that nonoil export and trade circumstances have a negative impact on economic development, the Engel Granger (ECM) analysis indicates that non-oil exports contribute to Nigeria's economic growth. In contrast, the CUSUM stability test shows that nonoil exports have a consistent, positive impact on the economy, whereas the terms of trade associated with these exports have a variable, negative impact. Because Nigeria's non-oil commodities have a substantial influence on other nations, especially those that import more than they export, this study advises establishing important bilateral trade agreements with them.

Between 1980 and 2019, Onose and Aras (2021) investigated the export-led growth hypothesis and its applicability to services exports in five emerging countries: Brazil, India, Nigeria, China, and South Africa (BINCS). The panel mean group autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) was used in the study. This approach aided in determining if exporting services and GDP per capita are causally related. The results demonstrate that, if only temporarily, increasing service exports does contribute to economic growth. On the other hand, factors like labor, gross capital formation (GCF), and foreign direct investment (FDI) all have a major long-term impact on economic growth. Consequently, these nations would benefit from making internal investments to increase economic growth in both short term and long term.

The study by Fosong et al. (2020) looks at how Cameroon's economic development is influenced by both oil and non-oil revenue, with a particular emphasis on how they modulate it. The study used time series data from 1980 to 2018 using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model to assess the long- and short-term impact of the factors on economic growth. The results indicate that GDP, gross capital creation, oil revenue, non-oil revenue, and overall government spending are all correlated over the long run. The long-run results demonstrate that although non-oil revenue has a big and negative impact on economic growth, oil revenue has a negligible and favorable impact. However, both non-oil and oil revenue have a positive and considerable influence on economic growth in the near term. However, the results of the interaction between the two revenue streams indicate that both non-oil and oil revenue sources may contribute to long-term economic growth. These outcomes recommend that public policy involvements ought to enhance their revenue collection process through strict implementation and suitable monitoring of the oil agency in order to reduce income leakages caused by financial fraud. The government should support the industrial and agricultural processing sectors, according to these conclusions.

Fred-Nelson et al. (2020) examine how exports affected the Republic of Congo's non-oil sector's economic development between 1985 and 2015. Both the descriptive statistics technique and the econometric approach are used in the study to accomplish its goals. Similarly, gross fixed capital creation has a positive influence on GDP, meaning that non-oil GDP rose by 0.16%. The study's findings indicate that non-oil exports have a negative effect on economic growth. Therefore, recommendations are offered to boost the non-oil exports' contribution to economic development based on the results.

The contribution of Saudi Arabia's non-oil exports to economic growth since development plans were implemented to promote the growth of non-oil exports was evaluated by Aljibrin (2020). Time series data for GDP, labor, capital, and nonoil exports from 1990 to 2017 were evaluated using the enhanced Dickey-Fuller test, then the Johansen cointegration technique with a vector error correction model to determine the long- and short-term correlations between these variables. The study confirmed a robust positive relationship between GDP and non-oil exports over the medium and long decades, as well as between GDP and capital, indicating at least unidirectional causation. However, there was no discernible link between growth and labor. The results, which showed that non-oil exports played a significant role in Saudi Arabia's economic expansion, validated the ELGH. Together with additional research, the findings suggest that Saudi Arabia should diversify its exports, simplify its export procedures, supply new funding and infrastructure to support export and domestic production, and promote collaborative relationships between the oil and non-oil sectors. Since the ELGH argues that the export sector generates growth by increasing aggregate levels of capital and labor, labor-related issues must also be addressed. The practical, context-specific data this study offers may be used by planners, decision-makers, and practitioners to create effective policies that will support Saudi Arabia in achieving a sustainable, balanced economy.

In their 2019 study, Akighar and Joseph investigated the connection between economic progress and non-oil exports in many African countries from 1986 to 2018, including Algeria, Angola, Cameroun, Chad, Egypt, Equatorial Guinea, Ghana, Libya, Republic of Congo, Nigeria, and Sudan. Using dynamic panel data models, the study's conclusions

demonstrated that, with the exception of Gabon, non-oil exports were positively correlated with economic development over the long run. However, the calculated coefficients are not statistically significant at the 5% level of significance. The study also found that non-oil exports have a short-term positive effect on economic growth in the following countries: Angola, Egypt, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, Libya, Nigeria, Republic of Congo, and Sudan; in contrast, there is a short-term negative impact in Algeria, Cameroun, Chad, and Ghana. According to the study's findings, non-oil exports have a positive effect on economic growth in the majority of the selected African countries, even if some of the factors are not statistically relevant to economic growth. Thus, the study recommended that the world's oil-producing countries, including those in Africa, should boost their production and exports of non-oil products proportionate to their imports.

Ifeacho et al. (2016) looked at how exports other than oil affected economic expansion. The study represented per capita income as a function of non-oil export volume, trade openness, exchange rate capital creation, and inflation rate, using it as a stand-in for economic growth. The results of the study, which used the ordinary least squares estimating approach, indicate a substantial positive correlation between per capita income and non-oil exports. This suggests that increasing the number of non-oil exports will significantly raise Nigeria's economic development level. Other factors, however, do not greatly affect economic development on their own, but when combined, they can have a big impact. The outcome also reveals that the coefficient of trade openness is negative, suggesting that Nigeria may not be reaping the full benefits of trade with other nations. If the beneficial effects of non-oil exports on Nigerian economic development are to be encouraged, the study suggests that Nigeria's trade policies be reviewed.

Based on the extant literature review, majority of the studies are focused on a specific country, there are paucity of studies which captures SSA. Also, based on the methodology adopted by the review made almost all the studies adopted either ARDL, Panel/ ARDL or Pool Mean Group (PMG) as their techniques of analysis which is over saturated. Hence, this present study intends to fill the gap by employing the Common Correlated Effect (CCE) techniques which is the advance second generation ARDL. Consequently, this present study will fill the gap by introducing institutional quality index as part of the control variables, as it is found to be lacking from the previous studies reviewed.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Nature and sources of Data

In order to evaluate the effect of non-oil export on economic growth in Sub-Saharan African countries. Data incorporated for the study were secondary annual panel data which cover the period 2004 to 2023. The IMF's recommendation of an externally oriented trade strategy for Africa and SSA's adoption of the IMF's enhanced general data distribution system (e-GDDS) were the main factors in the selection of this time frame. Data availability was another factor. The SSA countries encompass of 38 countries, and the data were sourced from World development Indicator, International Monetary Fund, and Governance indicator.

3.2 Variables Description, Measurement and Sources.

Gross Domestic Product (GDP): The sum of all product taxes, the gross value of products and services supplied by all producers who are citizens of the nation, and the deduction of

any subsidies that aren't included in the product value are all included in this. It sourced from world bank world development indicator. The percentage (%) is used to measure it.

Non-oil export (NONX): is proxied by non-oil output is the dependent variable, it refers to the whole value of the economy's yearly production of non-oil products and services, excluding oil exports. It sourced from the IMF and is expressed as a percentage (%) of GDP.

Inflation (INF): The consumer price index serves as a stand-in. It is derived from world development indicators and is expressed as a percentage that represents changes in the typical consumer's cost of purchasing a basket of goods and services, which may be fixed or altered at predetermined intervals.

Exchange rate (LEXCR): is the value of one currency represented in terms of another; it is derived from world development indicators and indicates the nominal rate at which the currencies of SSA nations may be converted into dollars on the foreign exchange market.

Gross Capital Formation GCF): Proxy for capital, this includes extensions to the economy's fixed assets and net assets, such as land, improvements (drains, ditches, fences, etc.), plants, machinery, and equipment purchases, as well as the building of roads, railroads, and similar facilities, such as offices for schools, hospitals, private residences, and commercial and industrial buildings. It is expressed as a percentage of GDP (%).

Institutional Quality (IQ): Stability in politics the rule of law relates to how people view the laws that govern them, and it reflects their assessment of the likelihood of political stability. The degree to which official authority is used for personal gain is referred to as control of corruption; this can include both serious and minor corruption. Effective governance is determined by how well public servants are regarded and how independent they are thought to be. The view of the government's ability to establish and carry out sensible laws and regulations that allow and encourage private sector development (scale of -2.5 and 2.5) sourced from governance indicator.

3.3 Model Specification

The study evaluated the effect of non-oil export on economic growth in SSA countries. The export led hypothesis form the bases for this model, also the study adapted the work of Ifeacho, et al (2016), on non-oil export and economic growth.

The model was specified in the functional form as;

$$LGDP = f(INF, EXR, LNONIEX, LCAP, TOP) \dots\dots\dots [1]$$

Where;

Log of GDP represent gross domestic product, INF denote inflation rate, EXR represent exchange rate, LNONIEX represent log of non-oil export, LCAP represent log of capital formation and TOP represent trade openness. The model was be modified by eliminating TOP, because since the main focus of the objective is on non-oil exports, the model can better capture the direct relationship between economic growth and non-oil export,

providing more insights into the specific channels through which non-oil export affects economic expansion in SSA.

The functional and econometric forms of the modified model are presented in equations [2]

and [3], respectively:

$$GDP = f(INF, LEXCR, NONX, GCF, IQI) \dots \dots \dots [2]$$

$$GDP_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 INF_{it} + \beta_2 LEXCR_{it} + \beta_3 NONX_{it} + \beta_4 GCF_{it} + \beta_5 IQI_{it} + \mu_t \dots \dots \dots [3]$$

Where;

GDP represent gross domestic product it is measured in percentage; INF denotes inflation it is measured in percentage, LEXCR represent log of exchange rate it is measured in nominal rate, NONX denotes non-oil export it is measured in percentage, GCF represent gross capital formation it is measured in percentage and IQI represent institutional quality index. L represent natural logarithm, β_0 is the intercept; β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , β_4 , and β_5 are the coefficients of the variables; ϵ_i = error or stochastic term; it represents the time dimension (2004 – 2023).

A priori Expectation: $\beta_1 < 0$, $\beta_2 > 0$, $\beta_3 > 0$, $\beta_4 > 0$, & $\beta_5 > 0$,

In view of the above explanation, the CCE model used in this study was presented in equation [4] and [5] as thus;

$$GDP_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 INF_{it} + \beta_2 LEXCR_{it} + \beta_3 NONX_{it} + \beta_4 GCF_{it} + \beta_5 IQI_{it} + \lambda_i GDP_{it} + \gamma_i INF_{it} + \gamma_i LEXCR_{it} + \gamma_i NONX_{it} + \gamma_i GCF_{it} + \gamma_i IQI_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots \dots \dots [4]$$

$$GDP_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 INF_{it} + \beta_2 LEXCR_{it} + \beta_3 NONX_{it} + \beta_4 GCF_{it} + \beta_5 IQI_{it} + \lambda_i GDP_{it} + \gamma_i INF_{it} + \gamma_i LEXCR_{it} + \gamma_i NONX_{it} + \gamma_i GCF_{it} + \gamma_i IQI_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots \dots \dots [5]$$

Where, GDP, INF, LEXCR, NONX, GCF, IQI, (see discussion above)

is the individual country-specific fixed effects.

β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , β_4 , β_5 , are the coefficients of the variables;

γ_i = Coefficient on the common correlated effect.

λ_i, γ_i = represent the coefficients for the cross-sectional averages (to account for common correlation effects).

3.4 CCE Estimation Procedure

Before undertaking the Common Correlated Effect (CCE) analysis, the study first

conducted the pre-estimation test. These pre-estimation test first comprise of the test of Descriptive statistics, the component of the descriptive statistics include the mean, maximum, minimum, skewness, and kurtosis. Thereafter, the cross-sectional dependence test was also conducted to ascertain whether there is cross-section dependency or not, this was followed by the unit root test such as CS-ADF and CIPS, the essence is to ascertain the order of integration. The cointegration test such as Westerlund was used to check if there is the existence of a long run relationship among the variables. The CCE was employed as the technique for estimation.

4.0 Results and Discussion of Findings.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Std.Dev	Min	Max	Skew	Kurtosis
GDP	4.268	4.637	-36.39	37.99	-0.664	18.838
NONX	4.489	4.857	-36.39	46.13	0.182	23.32
INF	5.953	8.332	-63.65	47.64	-1.349	21.16
LEXCR	5.284	2.024	-0.10	9.24	-0.677	2.462
GCF	8.501	23.134	-65.82	255.7	3.811	35.30
IQI	2.11	2.043	-3.73	5.45	0.611	2.939

Note: GDP, gross domestic product. NONX, non-oil export, INF, inflation, LEXCR, log of exchange rate. GCF, gross capital formation. IQI, institutional quality index.

Source: Researcher's computation using STATA version 15, 2025.

The mean, and standard deviation—the measures of central tendency—indicate that the majority of the variables deviate from their mean, according to the results of the descriptive statistics, which give us an idea of the nature of the data. Ineffective governance, a poor rule of law, and insecure property rights are just a few examples of the inferior institutional quality that is often present in SSA nations, as indicated by the average IQI mean of 2.11 and the associated standard deviation of 2.043. Even if the standard deviation is lower than the mean, it still shows that the institutional quality of SSA nations varies significantly. In the meanwhile, there is some degree of variation in the observation as the GDP and GCF standard deviations are larger than their respective mean values. Some of the variables' comparatively large standard deviations indicate the presence of outliers and/or non-stationarity, which have been addressed throughout the estimate process.

A high kurtosis value in INF, particularly in the Central African Republic, suggests that price movements are unpredictable and subject to extreme fluctuations, which has eroded purchasing power and affected economic stability in the country. As a result, series like GDP, NONX, INF, and GCF showed leptokurtic kurtosis. This distribution has outlier or extreme values, implying that countries like Ghana's economy is heavily reliant on a few non-oil sectors or industries, making non-oil export more susceptible to external shocks. In contrast, some SSA countries may have more consistent governance across various regions or sectors, a more stable exchange rate with fewer extreme fluctuations, and increased trade and investment, as evidenced by the platykurtic distribution of series like the IQI and log exchange rate.

Table 2: Cross-Sectional Dependency Test (CDW+)

Variable	CDW+Test	P-Value
GDP	523.65	0.000
NONX	509.09	0.000
INF	523.22	0.000
LEXCR	484.75	0.000
GCF	530.35	0.000
IQI	489.02	0.000

Source: Researcher's computation using STATA version 15, 2025.

The cross-sectional dependency test used for table 3 is the weak cross-sectional dependence (CDw) test with power enhancement by Pesaran (2015), the results indicate that all variables such as GDP, NONX, INF, LEXCR, GCF, and IQ are all statistically significant at the 5% level. Strong cross-sectional dependency between the cross-sectional units is therefore confirmed, rejecting the null hypothesis that there is no cross-sectional dependence. This result emphasizes how important it is to use the second-generation panel estimators, which are made especially to take these dependencies into consideration. We thus think of adding the Common Correlated Effect (CCE) estimate, which was created by Pesaran (2006), as an integrated unobserved component because of the substantial cross-sectional dependency.

Table 3: Unit Root Test. Pesaran CADF and Pesaran CIPS Unit Root Test Results

Variable	CADF Constant		CADF Trend		C I P S CIPS Trend		Order of Int
	Level	Level	Level	Order of Int	Level	Level	
GDP	-4.756 (0.000)	-5.080 (0.000)	1(0)		-6.129 (-2.12)**	-6.396 (-2.61)**	1(0)
NONX	-4.766 (0.000)	-5.041 (0.000)	1(0)		6.137 (-2.12)**	-6.365 (-2.61)**	1(0)
INF	-4.952 (0.000)	4.975 (0.000)	1(0)		-6.190 (-2.12)**	-6.420 (-2.61)**	1(0)
LEXCR	-4.798 (0.000)	-4.972 (0.000)	1(0)		-6.190 (-2.12)**	-6.420 (-2.61)**	1(0)
GCF	-4.785 (0.000)	-5.264 (0.000)	1(0)		-6.003 (-2.12)**	-6.420 (-2.61)**	1(0)
IQI	-4.825 (0.000)	-5.055 (0.000)	1(0)		-6.190 (-2.12)**	-6.330 (-2.61)**	1(0)

Note: Critical value= -***p < 0.01, **p < 0.05, *p < 0.1

Source: Author's computation employing STATA version 15, 2025.

All of the variables, including GDP, NONX, INF, LEXCR, GCF, and IQ, are stationary at level 1 (0), according to the results of the Pesaran CADF and the CIPS of both constant and trend. Therefore, if all variables are 1(0), no differencing is required. Thus, since there is a substantial cross-sectional dependency between the variables and the second-generation unit root result above demonstrates that all of the variables are stationary at level 1(0), this supports the use of the Common Correlated Effect (CCE).

Table 4. Westerlund Co-integration Test.

Westerlund Co-integration Test: H0:38, Ha:20

	Statistic	P-value
Augmented Dickey-Fuller L	-4.8205	0.0000

Source: Authors Computation using Stata 15.0, 2025.

The result of the Westerlund 2006 cointegration test, shows that there is the existence of cointegration of the model at the 5% level. This means that there existed a long run relationship between all the explanatory variables employed in the model with the explained variable from 2004 to 2023 in SSA.

Table 5: CCE Test Results.

Dependent Variable	Coefficient	Std.Error	P-value
GDP			
GDP (ECM)	-0.02321082	0.0430186	0.000
INF	0.0430416	0.033074	0.193
LEXCR	-0.2760752	0.6349934	0.664
NONX	0.8020649	0.0518717	0.000
GCF	0.0066816	0.0058998	0.257
IQI	-0.1817447	0.4485068	0.685
lr INF	0.0464914	0.0339337	0.171
lr LEXCR	0.0258682	0.5046937	0.959
lr NONX	0.8838489	0.0474711	0.000
lr GCF	0.0073283	0.0058298	0.209
lr IQI	0.0923793	0.513315	0.857
Prob (Chi)			0.0000**
Constant	0.9471424	0.1719919	0.000
Obs	80		

Note: GDP, gross domestic product. INF, inflation. LEXCR, log of exchange rate. NONX, non-oil export. GCF, gross capital formation. IQI, institutional quality index. **Critical value:** ***p < 0.01, **p < 0.05, *p < 0.1

Source: Author's computation employing STATA version 15, 2025.

Table 5 shows the CCE results for both short run and long run, non-oil export was found to have a positive and significant effect on economic growth in both period in SSA countries this conform to the apriori expectation, it implies that a unit increase in non-oil export will lead to 80% increase in GDP, holding other variables constant. This in agreement with Aljebrin (2020); Akighar and Joseph (2019). On the other hand, it is not in agreement with Fred-Nelson et al (2020) who found non-oil exports to have a negative effect on economic growth. The positive and significant effect of non-oil export on economic growth underscores that through an effective diversification of the economy to non-oil exports. For instance, some SSA countries like Nigeria, and Angola who rely heavily on oil exports has reduced its dependence of on oil exports and promote economic diversification. Additionally, non-oil exports have increased economic resilience making SSA countries less vulnerable to external shocks.

Inflation was found to have a positive coefficient of (0.0430 & 0.0464) in both short run and long run and is insignificant to economic growth, this does not conform to the apriori expectation, this implies that a unit increase in inflation will lead to 43% decrease in GDP. This is in contrast to Shiro, Abijah and Fadun (2023) who found inflation to have a negative impact on GDP. Log of exchange rate was found to have a negative effect on economic growth in the short run does not conform to the apriori expectation, while in the long run it has a positive coefficient of 0.0258 it conform to the economic apriori expectation, although in both periods its possess an insignificant effect on GDP. In the long run its in agreement with Shiro, Abjia and Fadun (2023). The positive effect of exchange rate to economic growth in the long run underscores a stable and competitive exchange rate can promote trade and competitiveness, leading to increased economic growth in the long run. But the insignificant effect implies that exchange rate management is not a priority.

Gross capital formation in each period has a positive coefficient which indicates that it has a positive relationship to GDP this conform to the apriori economic expectation, albeit it was found to have an insignificant effect on economic growth. This is in line with Onose and Aras (2021); Fred- Nelson et al (2020) who found capital to have a positive impact on economic growth. Institutional quality index has a negative relationship with GDP in short run this does not conform to the economic expectation, while in the long run it turns out to have a positive relationship on economic growth this conforms to the economic expectation, although it was seen not to be statistically significant in both short run and long run. The negative and insignificant effect of institutional quality index to economic growth in SSA underscores that institutional reforms have short- term costs, such as disruption to economic activity or increased uncertainty, the positive effect suggests a better governance as a result of strong institutions promote good governance, which can lead to increased economic growth. The GDP coefficient indicates a 23% rate of adjustment to long-term equilibrium, which is consistent with the considerable economic apriori.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

The study examined the effect of non-oil exports on economic growth in SSA countries. The findings revealed that non-oil exports have a positive and significant effect on economic growth, suggesting that diversifying exports beyond oil can be a viable strategy

for promoting economic growth in the region. Also, inflation, capital institutional quality index and exchange rate were found to have an insignificant effect on economic growth in both short run and long run, although with a mixed sign, suggesting that their impact on economic growth may be limited or indirect.

Recommendations

- i. Development and implementation of diversification strategies to promote non-oil exports, such as identifying new markets and product, while ensuring that investment is being made on industries with strong development prospects.
- ii. Investment in infrastructural development, such as transportation, energy, and telecommunications, to support economic growth.
- iii. Inflation and exchange rate should be properly managed to guarantee that economic growth is encouraged in SSA, while regularly monitoring the impact of monetary and fiscal policies and ensuring that necessary changes are made.
- iv. Strengthen institutions to promote good governance, rule of law, and property rights, which can support economic growth.

REFERENCES

- AFDB. (2020). African regional trade agreements. African Development Bank report.
- Akighar, T. D. & Joseph, A. T. (2019). Nono-oil export and economic growth in selected African Countries. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 9(6), <https://doi.org/10.29322/IJSRP.9.06.2019.P90130.893-903>.
- Aljebri, M. A. (2020). Do non-oil export facilitate Economic Growth in Saudi Arabia? *Journal of Management information and Decision Sciences*, 23(1), 450-476.
- Alhowaish, A. K. (2014). Exports, imports and economic growth in Saudi Arabia: An application of cointegration and error-correction modeling, *La Pensée*, 76(5), 1-12.
- Arezki, R., & Sy, A. (2013). Financing growth in Africa. International Monetary Fund.
- Asmare, G. A., & Haiyun, L. (2020). The impact of trade openness on human capital development and economic growth in Ethiopia. *Management and Human Resource Research Journal*. 9(2), 1-18.
- Calderon, C., Pierrot, C., & Serey, A. (2013) Trade integration, export patterns and growth in Sub-Saharan Africa. *A Review from World Bank*, 4(1), 1-46.
- Chanie, M. (2017). The impact of FDI on economic growth in Ethiopia: An empirical investigation. *International Journal of Current Research*, 9(9), 58301-58306.

- Ee, C. Y. (2016). Export-led growth hypothesis: Empirical evidence from selected sub-Saharan African countries. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 3(5), 232-240.
- Feder, G. (1982). On exports and economic growth. *Journal of Development Economics*, 12, 59-73.
- Findlay, R. (1984). Export-Led Growth: A new approach. *Journal of Development Economics*, 16(2), 125-144.
- Fossong, D., Ndamsa, D. T. & Mofor, G. Z. (2020). An empirical analysis of the modulating effect between oil and non-oil revenue in explaining economic growth in Cameroon. *Business Administration and Business Economics Journal, EuroEconomica*, 3(39), 102-115.
- Fred-Nelson, O.N., Ossala, G. S., Rivel, B. P., & Yirong, Y. (2020). Impact of exports on economic growth in the non-oil sector in the Republic of Congo. *International Journal of Economic and Finance*, 12(3). <https://doi:10.5539/ijef.v12n3p46>.
- Gabriel, A. A., & David, A. O., (2021). Effect of trade openness and financial openness on economic growth in Sub-Saharan African Countries. *African Journal of Economic Review*, 9(1). 109-130.
- Hausmann, R., Hwang, J., & Rodrik, D. (2017). What you export matters. *Journal of Economic Growth*, 12(1), 1-25.
- Hirschman, A. O (1958). *The strategy of economic development*, Yale University Press.
- Ifeacho, C., Omoniyi, B. O & Oluwafemi, B. O. (2016). Effect of non-oil export on the economic development of Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 3(3), 27-32.
- International Monetary Fund (2020). *World Economic Outlook Report*.
- Kenechukwu, C., & Akunjinma, A. F. (2022) Non-oil export and Nigeria economic growth: A disaggregate study. *African Journal of Business and Economic Development*, 2(8), 22-35.
- Krueger, A. O. (1980). Trade policy as an input to development. *The American Economic Review*, 70(2), 288-292.
- Mankiw, N. & Gregory. (2018). *Macroeconomics*. New York : Worth Publishers [2022-04-04] OECD. (2018). *Trade and economic growth*. OECD Publishing.
- Okoli, L. C., Uju, R., Nzeribe, G., & Umeghalu, C. (2023). Impact of non-oil export on economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of international Economic relations and Developmen*, 3(1), 44-63.
- Onose, O. L., & Aras, N. O. (2021). Does the export- led growth hypothesis hold for

- services exports in emerging Economies. *Eurasian Journal of Business and Economics*, 14(27), 63-75.
- Pesearan, M. H. (2015). Testing weak cross-sectional dependence in large panels. *Econometric Reviews*, 34(1), 1089-1117. [https:// doi:10.1080/074747938.2014.956623](https://doi.org/10.1080/074747938.2014.956623).
- Pesearan, M. H. (2006). Estimation and inference in large heterogenous panels with a multifactor error structure. *Econometrica*, 74(4), 967-1012
- Priyankara, E. (2018) Services exports and economic growth in Sri Lanka: Does the export-led growth hypothesis hold for services exports? *Journal of Service Science and Man-agement*, 11, 479-495.
- Shiro, A. A., Abjia, R.O., & Fadun, O. S. (2023). Non-oil export and its effect on economic growth in Nigeria. *Nigeria Journal of Risk and Insurance*. 13(2).
- Streeten, P., Fleming, C., & Singer, L. K. (1968). Unbalanced growth. *Oxford Economic Papers*, 11(12). 168-176.
- Tyler, W. G. (1981). Growth and export expansion in developing countries: Some empirical evidence. *Journal of Development Economics*, 9, 121-130.
- UNCTAD. (2019). Methodological Note. World investment report, 201–207. https://doi.org/10.1596/9780821398623_App.
- UNECA. (2020). United Nations Commission for Africa: Economic report on Africa innovation finance for Private Sector Development.
- World Governance Indicator (2023), Institutional indicators database.
- World Bank. (2023). World Development Indicators. World Bank.
- World Bank. (2020). World Development Indicators 2020.

EFFECT OF TECHNOLOGICAL CONNECTIVITY ON AGRICULTURAL EXTENSION SERVICES IN KANO STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

In low-income countries like Nigeria, extension services are better tools for providing farmers with knowledge on usage and adopting of new agricultural practices and food supply chains. However, the agricultural extension services system in Nigeria faces many challenges such as limited access to real-time information, inadequate farmer-to-agent ratio and insufficient resources among others. Incorporating technological connectivity (TC) into farming is believed to enhance and ease extension service delivery and the flow of market information to farmers. This paper examines the effect of technological connectivity on agricultural extension services in Nigeria. The study selected a sample of 120 respondents through a simple random sampling technique. Logit regression model was employed in the analysis. The findings indicate that Technological connectivity (TC) precisely WhatsApp, YouTube, Google and Radio programme significantly affect disseminating agricultural information to farmers. The study recommends expanding infrastructure, particularly internet access in rural areas, and providing adequate training to extension personnel and farmers on how to utilize Technological Connectivity in the agricultural sector.

Keywords: agriculture, connectivity, extension, farmers, technological

1. Introduction

Globally, Agricultural Extension Services (AES) are the services that provide agricultural knowledge and disseminate information on new technologies to farmers and rural inhabitants. AES aids in increasing food security, promoting productivity and promoting agriculture as an economic growth engine (International Food Policy Research Institute, 2020). AES introduces technologies and new ideas to rural people by using diverse approaches. Also, AES helps farmers understand and adopt the modern technologies to increase crop production and improve their livelihoods and make them tough in facing their farming challenges (Nyarko & Kozári, 2021). The extension services are better tools for providing farmers with information on modern agricultural practices, access to credit, food supply chains and market solutions. As such, AES is improving food supply chains and agriculture in low-income countries as it helps smallholders break the cycle of low productivity and poverty (Davis & Franzel, 2018). Given the exceptional livelihood desires of the farmers and assortment in farming systems, there is a need for timely and seasonal information to make farmers prepare to take a well-informed decision (Hainzer, O'Mullan, & Brown, 2023).

Technological connectivity (TC) is the core and a tool of communication technology in both developed and developing nations, which is incorporated into farming for easing

extensions of service delivery and the market information to farmers (Otene, Ezihe, & Torgenga, 2018). These include YouTube, mobile phones and the internet. TC is not only vital to extension personal, but also to farmers. Thus, farmers need to be well-trained and equipped with the ICTs that can be used in farming like natural disasters, weather change, sudden institutional, policy changes and price uncertainties. Correspondingly, insufficient knowledge and the potential of the digital-based agricultural sector lead the sector to be less absorbed (Oluwatoyin, Oluwaseun, Festus, Temidre, & Shehu, 2021).

Conventionally, farmers have relied on extension agents, NGOs and research institutions for information about new technologies particularly through face-to-face extension campaigns (Nyarko & Kozári, 2021). However, the traditional extension system is plagued with human resources trials in remote areas (Davis, 2020). The work of agricultural extension personnel faces so many hurdles such as limited in disseminating and accessing relevant information, poor documentation, retrieval techniques and storage. Disseminating information among farmers is an essential mandate that ICTs contributes meaningfully. Internet communication for agricultural extension is vital in stimulating collecting of data, processing, and transmitting. This aids to spread of high-quality data to more farmers (Sennuga et al., 2023).

The increase of internet and mobile phone usage offers innovative solutions to overcome these challenges (Emeana, Trenchard, & Dehnen-Schmutz, 2020). ICTs have resulted in the emergence of digital advisory services, commonly called e-extension (Mulungu, Kassie, & Tschopp, 2025). Ultimately, traditional extension approaches need to be married with ICTs to make knowledge nearby to all stakeholders (Khan, Ray, Zhang, Osabuohien, & Ihtisham, 2022). Failure to do this may lead to underperformance of the sector, particularly in managing agricultural risk and emergencies (Tata & McNamara, 2018). Farmers' adoption of the ICT may require the extension officers' ability to merge their practical experience with ICT knowledge acquired. This will result how real the new technology effectively operated (Nyarko & Kozári, 2021). Digital agricultural extension is a nearby, cost-effective solution that allows farmers access knowledge (Kurdyś-Kujawska, A. Strzelecka & Zawadzka, 2021). Digital agricultural extension is now serving millions of farmers in gaining accessing the best agricultural knowledge and advice (Oluwatoyin et al., 2021). Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) can bridge the gap between extension agents and agriculturalists in enhancing accessibility in information and reducing associated costs. Therefore, the victory of extension services depends on the efficacy of the exchange of information and technology among agricultural researchers, extension agents and agronomists (Mustapha, Man, Shah, Kamarulzaman, & Tafida, 2022)

The existing situation of the agricultural extension services system in Nigeria faces momentous hurdles such as limited access to real-time information, inadequate farmer-to-agent ratio, Insufficient resources for widespread coverage and challenges in reaching remote rural areas among others (FAO, 2024). Although, the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) recommends a ratio of one extension agent per 1,000 farmers. in Nigeria, the reports indicate a ratio as high as 1:10,000. This disparity hampers the effectiveness of traditional extension services, leaving many farmers without access to crucial advisory support. Additionally, the inadequate funding and limited resources to support the few available extension agents in disseminating information pose another

significant challenge to agricultural extension services in Nigeria. Kano is one of the states in Nigeria that is currently facing numerous challenges in extension services. These include, among others, a shortage of funds, absence of extension agents when needed due to a shortage of adequate qualified extension personnel; as such, farmers were left at the mercy of trial by error (Giginyu, 2024). This makes the application of digital machineries in extension service delivery more convincing. Furthermore, extension experts are stressed to select best way to use internet communication technologies to improve rural livings, as such, recently, the use of internet communication technologies in agricultural extension and rural development has greatly increased (Sennuga et al., 2023). It is in this background, this paper attempt to examine the effect of extension connectivity on agricultural extension services in Nigeria

Literature Review

Although various relevant studies have been conducted in the area of the effect of ICT or Digitalization on agricultural production, including farmers' crop production and productivity. Few studies have examined communication tools with extension services precisely at the grassroots level. Where local farmers were involved. Considering the important role these tools play in the dissemination of information can be useful in addressing the existing challenges of the shortage of qualified extension personnel and the lack of funding faced by farmers in Nigeria. For instance, the work of Mulungu et al. (2025) systematically reviewed the role of ICTs in agriculture by focusing on four main outcomes: adoption of agricultural technologies, awareness, yield, and income. The study employed the mixed methods appraisal tool (MMAT) for quality assessment of selecting 49 articles. The study proves that ICT-based extension services have the potential to expand smallholder farmers' choices and capabilities. Onyeneke et al., (2023) examines the impact of ICTs on agricultural production (crops and livestock) in Africa using panel data from 32 African countries and the panel autoregressive distributed lag model as the estimation technique. The study finds that individuals using internet significantly increased crop production in the long run.

Sennuga et al., (2023) examined the application of internet communication in agricultural extension delivery system in Abuja, Nigeria. Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire. A sample of One hundred and sixty-five (165) respondents were selected. The results indicate that usage of email, social media platforms, SMS messaging service, YouTube video, and online forums using internet communication technologies to deliver extensions aids in strengthening connection between research and extension services. Datti, Said, Ismail, & Rahman, (2021) examines the effect of extension connectivity technology in influencing youth participation in paddy farming in Kano, Nigeria. The study selected 180 youth respondents from mixed sampling techniques. The binary Logit was used in the estimation models. The findings shows that extension connectivity used in farming can inspire youths to participate in paddy farming. Emeana et al., (2020) revealed that there is excessive potential adoption of digital technology in Nigeria. The study see the potential in utilizing digital tools by transforming agents of extension from knowledge workers to technology generation. Oluwatoyin et al., (2021) examines trials fronting agricultural extension system in Nigeria in the adoption of digitizing extension systems. Based on the results, the emergence of ICTs has given rise to digitization, which is the delivery of agricultural advice via audiovisual messages (video), interactive voice response (IVR) and short message services (SMS) among others.

Clara and Lucky, (2023) examined the use of digital tools in extension services delivery amongst extension agents in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study employed simple random sampling in selecting 47 agricultural extension agents samples. A structured questionnaires were administered for collecting data and the Binary Logit regression analysis was used. The results showed that the majority (74%) of the agents indicated that they used digital tools in agricultural extension service delivery with WhatsApp and Video camera as the most used digital tools among them. The agricultural extension agents in Akwa Ibom are aware of and utilize digital tools though constrained by some factors. These are age, educational status, monthly income, working experience and sex. Nyarko and Kozári, (2021) assess the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) among agricultural extension workers. A simple random sampling technique was used to select 153 field extension workers, and a structured questionnaire was administered. Data were analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics. The results indicate that agricultural extension officers use ICT for personal communication, but not mainly for extension activities. Thapa & Specht, (2025) assess the factors influencing the adoption of digital tools among extension agents of Bagmati and Gandaki provinces of Nepal. The study employed a quantitative survey to collect data from 128 participants. Cluster analysis was used to classify participants into three segments and the Logit regression analysis was used in the analysis. The results indicate that higher hierarchical rank, usage of mobile apps and being male significantly increased the possibility of adoption.

These previous studies created a gap which needs to be bridged in area of effect of technological connectivity on agriculture. The need of this kind of study is necessary particularly to a country like Nigeria, so that the result can be guided on whether the tools can address the challenges of disseminating information to farmers at the right time and at the right place.

Materials and Methods

The study was designed and conducted using a simple random sampling technique in farming areas of Kano State, Nigeria namely, Tudunwada, Kura, Bunkure Rano, Bagwai local governments. The study adopted and modified the previous studies conducted by Datti et al. (2021); Nyarko & Kozári, (2021) and Oluwatoyin et al., (2021). This technique is an extensively utilized sampling method in various studies. Simple random sampling is advantageous in consistently selected populations and homogeneous (Noor, Tajik, & Golzar, 2022). As such, in each local government, 30 field agricultural extension personnel were selected and administered questionnaires. The questionnaire purposely targeted agricultural extension personnel because they are the Government body responsible for agricultural information dissemination at the district and local levels in Nigeria. However, at the time of data compilation, 120 valid responses were retrieved and Binary Logit regression model was employed in the analysis.

2. Results and discussions

4.1 Descriptive statistics

This part explains the socio-demographic characteristics of extension personnel as indicated in Table I. The Table indicates that 34% of the respondents fall in the youthful age (18-35years old). This demonstrates the number of youths in the extension services are inadequate, despite they are the bedrock of adoption modern technologies in extension services. 45% fall between the age of 36- 53 years old. This category is the majority in the

age group. Male (76%) are the majority when compare with their female counterparts. This is common in Northwest zone Nigeria. Majority of women participation in many occupations precisely formal work is limited. The level of education attained is moderately okay. When you combine those who attended post-secondary schools such as Diploma, NCE, Degree and Post Graduate, about 55% respondents holds various kinds of post-secondary school certificates. This is connected to the staff motivational factor of expecting promotion in their respective working cadres as well as position to hold in the department. Moreover, the number of years of professional experience show that nearly 50% of the responses are within the range of 11- 20 years, and 30% within the range of 01-10 years.

Some of Technology Connectivity devices, APPs and social media used by extension personnel indicate that all the respondents (100%) use extension app (GSM messaging devices and WhatsApp group and video). While 95% use YouTube, 80% Video conferencing, 88% Google web, and 81% agric. Blogs.

Table I: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Extension Personnel

Demography	Frequency	Percentage%
Age		
18-35	41	34
36- 53	54	45
54-70	16	13
71 and above	09	08
Sex		
Male	91	76
Female	29	24
Level of education		
Madrassa (Informal)	16	15
Primary sch. Cert.	21	18
SSCE	25	13
Diploma/NCE	32	27
BSc/HND	18	21
Postgraduate	08	07
Work status		
Permanent	94	78
Casual	26	22
Staff ranks		
GL 01-06	48	40
GL 7-13	58	48
GL 14 and above	14	12
Years of professional experience		
0 –10	36	30

11- 20	60	50
21- 30	16	13
31- 35	08	07
Someof Technology Connectivity devices Used by Extension Personnel		
YouTube video	112	95
WhatsApp Group and Video	120	100
Video conferencing (Zoom)	97	80
E- mail	120	100
Google web	105	88
GSM messaging devices	120	100
Agricultural blogs	97	81
E-extension APP	120	100

Source: Field work (2025).

4.2 Binary Logit Regression Result

The marginal effect for “availability of access to internet” is 0.126 indicating that a one-unit increase in access to internet results in a 12.6 % increase in the probability of adopting digital extension services. An additional year of extension service working experience may likely decreases the adoption of digital extension services by 30% as the coefficient has negative consequences. This is connected to the old staff personnel are more familiarize with a traditional method of meeting farmers physically and one- on one. The level of education resulted an increase of additional qualification by 1% may likely increase adoption of digital extension services by 39%. This is connected to the shift of current trends towards digitalisation of the whole economic sectors as a whole. An effective training which includes coaching and mentoring of extension personnel on how to utilize digital extension tools is significant as it indicates an increase of such training by 1% may likely increase to adoption of digital extension services by 28%. An increase in access to Technological Connectivity (YouTube video, WhatsApp Group and Video, Video conferencing (Zoom) and E-extension APP) by 1% may likely increase the adoption of digital extension by 22%, 10%, 10% and 10% respectively. This is connected to easy access to documents, aiding presentations and demonstrations to farmers as well as save time and transport costs. This finding is in line with the previous findings of Datti et al. (2021); Nyarko & Kozári, (2021); Oluwatoyin et al., (2021); and Thapa & Specht, (2025).

Table 2: Binary Logit Regression result

Parameter	Coefficient	Marginal effects
Availability of access to internet	0.004**(0.43)	0.001
Years spent in extension services (working experience)	0.092* (0.043)	-0.030**
Level of education	1.916**(0.48)	0.339**
Training	1.260** (0.54)	0.277**

YouTube video	0.978** (0.49)	0.220**
WhatsApp Group and Video	0.001**(0.100)	0.010*
Video conferencing (Zoom)	0.010 (0.000)	0.010
E-extension APP	0.003*(0.33)	0.010*
Log pseudolikelihood	-68.951	

The value in parentheses is standard error; **p < 5%; ***p < 1%

Conclusion

This study examines the effect of extension connectivity on agricultural extension services in Kano State, Nigeria. The study found that the adoption of Technological Connectivity in extension services will aid the work of extension personnel, as well as save on transport costs and time, in Nigeria. Also, problems of communication gaps that exist between farmers and extension personnel in Nigeria can be addressed by adopting digital extension tools. The study recommends expansion of infrastructure precisely internet access in the rural areas, and providing adequate training to both extension personnel and farmers on how to utilize Technological Connectivity in agriculture.

REFERENCES

- Clara, C., & Lucky, B. (2023). Utilization of Digital Tools in Extension Service Delivery amongst Extension Agents in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Extension*, 27(October), 67–76.
- Datti, M. I., Said, R., Ismail, N. W., & Rahman, A. A. B. D. (2021). Influence of extension connectivity on youth engagement into paddy farming in Kano State , Nigeria. *Studies and Applied Economics*, 39(October), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.25115/eea.v39i10.5404>
- Davis, K. (2020). *Agricultural extension: Global status and performance in selected countries*. (E. S. C. Babu C. & Ragasa, Ed.), International Food Policy Research Institute.
- Davis, K., & Franzel, S. (2018). *Extension and Advisory Services in 10 Developing Countries: A Cross-country Analysis Developing Local Extension Capacity (DLEC) Project* (No. AID-OAA-L-16-0002). Retrieved from <http://www.digitalgreen.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/EAS-in-Developing-Countries-FINAL.pdf>
- Emeana, E. M., Trenchard, L., & Dehnen-Schmutz, K. (2020). The revolution of mobile phone-enabled services for agricultural development (m-Agri Services) in Africa: The challenges for sustainability. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(2), 1–27.
- FAO. (2024). A call for cases on Pluralistic Extension and Advisory Services in Africa,. Retrieved from <https://www.fao.org/e-agriculture/news/call-cases-pluralistic-extension-and-advisory-services-africa-march-2024>
- Giginyu, I. M. (2024, September). Our major challenges – Kano smallholder farmers.

- Dailytrust. Retrieved from <https://dailytrust.com/our-major-challenges-kano-smallholder-farmers/>
- Hainzer, K., O'Mullan, C., & Brown, P. H. (2023). Agricultural extension in Papua New Guinea: the challenges facing demand-driven extension from the perspective of practitioners. *Journal of Agribusiness in Developing and Emerging Economies*, 14(5), 1161–1175. Retrieved from [oi:10.1108/JADEE-06-2022-0131](https://doi.org/10.1108/JADEE-06-2022-0131)
- International Food Policy Research Institute, (2020). Agricultural extension. Retrieved March 16, 2025, from [at: https://www.ifpri.org/topic/Agricultural-extension](https://www.ifpri.org/topic/Agricultural-extension) .
- Khan, N., Ray, R. L., Zhang, S., Osabuohien, E., & Ihtisham, M. (2022). Influence of mobile phone and internet technology on income of rural farmers: Evidence from Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province, Pakistan. *Technology in Society*, 68(101866). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2022.101866>
- Kurdyś-Kujawska, A. Strzelecka, A., & Zawadzka, D. (2021). The Impact of Crop Diversification on the Economic Efficiency of Small Farms in Poland. *Agriculture*, 11(3), 1-21.
- Mulungu, K., Kassie, M., & Tschopp, M. (2025). The role of information and communication technologies- based extension in agriculture : application , opportunities and challenges. *Information Technology for Development*, 1–30. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02681102.2025.2456232>
- Mustapha, S. A., Man, N., Shah, J. A., Kamarulzaman, N. H., & Tafida, A. A. (2022). Factors influencing the adoption of ICTs in extension service delivery among the extension agents in North-East, Nigeria. Vol. 38 No. 1, pp. . *Sarhad Journal of Agriculture*, 38(1), 149–159. Retrieved from [doi: 10.17582/sja/2022/38.1.149.159](https://doi.org/10.17582/sja/2022/38.1.149.159)
- Noor, H., Tajik, O., & Golzar, J. (2022). Sampling method | descriptive research simple random sampling. *IJELS*, 1 (2)
- Nyarko, D. A., & Kozári, J. (2021). Information and communication technologies (ICTs) usage among agricultural extension officers and its impact on extension delivery in Ghana. *Journal of the Saudi Society of Agricultural Sciences*, 20(3), 164–172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jssas.2021.01.002>
- Oluwatoyin, O., Oluwaseun, A., Festus, K. G., Temidre, O. A., & Shehu, N. I. (2021). Digitization of Agricultural Extension System for Effective Management of Emergency in Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Extension*, 25(4), 81–91.
- Onyeneke, R. U., Ankrah, D. A., Atta-ankomah, R., Agyarko, F. F., Onyeneke, C. J., & Nejad, J. G. (2023). Information and Communication Technologies and Agricultural Production : New Evidence from Africa. *Applied Sciences MDPI*, 1–30.
- Otene, V. A., Ezihe, J. A. C., & Torgenga, F. S. (2018). Assessment of Mobile Phone Usage

- Among Farmers in Keana Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Information*, 19(2), 141–148. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10496505.2017.1361829>
- Sennuga, S. O., Salaudeen, M. A., Bamidele, J., Funso, O., Osho-lagunju, B., Preyor, T. J., & Iheonu, M. E. (2023). Application of Internet Communications in Agricultural Extension Delivery System Among Farmers in Abuja , Nigeria. *Pollution and Community Health Effects*, 1(1), 1–13.
- Tata, J. S., & McNamara, P. E. (2018). Impact of ICT on agricultural extension services delivery: Evidence from the Catholic Relief Services SMART skills and Farmbook project in Kenya. *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, 24(1), 89–110. Retrieved from [10.1080/1389224X.2017.1387160](https://doi.org/10.1080/1389224X.2017.1387160)
- Thapa, M., & Specht, A. R. (2025). Understanding factors influencing adoption of digital tools among extension agents of Nepal. *Journal of Agribusiness in Developing and Emerging Economies*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JADEE-07-2024-0221>

EFFECT OF TRUST ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PERCEIVED ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT AND PSYCHOLOGICAL EMPLOYMENT CONTRACT BREACH. A PILOT STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The effective management of any organization is determined by the amiable association that exist between the employee and their employer, considering the fact that employees usually anticipate the employer to live up to expectation through the fulfilment of the contractual agreement made at the inception of their job or employment contract as it binds. The aim of this paper is to examine few sample size on perceived organizational support (independent variable), trust (mediating variable) and psychological employment contract breach (dependent variable). Therefore, instrument such as face validity, content validity as well as reliability of the instrument were analysed in accordance with the input and observation of experts such as practitioners and academicians. Version 24 of SPSS was utilized to analyse the collated data and the outcome of the analysis shows the reliability of the instruments, as it also shows evidence of reasonable regularity. Finally, discussions and conclusion were discussed.

Keywords: Pilot Test, Perceived Organizational Support (POS), Trust, Psychological Employment Contract Breach (PECB).

1.0 Introduction

It is paramount to understand the consequences and antecedence and of psychological employment contract breach due to the fact that organizations would have a clear strategy and knowledge of managing the expectations of its employee, as doing this this will do a great favour in ensuring the enactment of the management practices that will decrease the consequence of the perceived breach of employment contract in the place of work or organization (Cable, 2008; Gazi, Masud, Kaium, Amin, Mahmud, Senathirajah and Abdullah, 2025). Thus, it was based on this note that Delcampo, Rogers and Jacobson (2010) indicated in their study that the breach of employment contract by the government or employer has a positive relationship to the employee's feelings as well as perceived discrimination in their place of work or organization.

In addition, in the situation where by the employer fails to leave up to expectation by fulfilling their initial/overall promises made to employee, trust is automatically affected negatively (Walker, 2013), and as such indicating the vital function that trust has or exert in employer/employee relationship in any organization. This is so since the employee will cease to repose confidence that it previously has on the management or their employer emanating from feelings of disappointment on the psychological employment contract. Thus, it is of utmost importance to understand that the perception of employee

“psychological contract” exert an important effect in shaping the workers or employees fortification considering the fact that it comprises additional organizational responsibilities which includes: protecting employees jobs through circumventing needless cutting down of employments/jobs that may likely or automatically leads to dismissal/sacking of innocent employees that are resourceful to the organization (Umar and Ringim, 2015; Griep, Vander Elst, Kraak, Hansen and Beekman, 2025). Also, in the situation whereby any of the party which is either the employer or the employee fail to act according to the terms and conditions embedded in employment contractual agreement, thus, it will automatically result to employment contract breach.

In Nigeria, the breach of psychological employment contract has seriously affected many public or government organizations resulting to incessant strikes or industrial actions in the affected establishments. Example of such organizations include sectors such as; health, the Nigeria police force as well as the educational institutions, power sector e.t.c. For instance, it was reported that the National Union of Policemen has revealed several problems upsetting the lower level which is the rank and file personnel regarding the unfulfilment of the employment contract promises resulting to psychological employment contract breach (Ogbeide & Etafo, 2022). All things being equal, It is estimated that the employer or government renders sustenance to the police personnel with reasonable/appropriate emoluments “improved condition of service, working tools, welfare package, promotion of qualified personnel etc.” in agreement with the stated employment contract in order to bear the security mayhem effecting the country but unfortunately, opposite is the case as things did not fall in place appropriately (Adebayo, Akanmode and Udegbe, 2007). As a result of this quagmire, the police personal is highly frustrated leading to forceful and open demand for bribery from guiltless Nigerians/common man on the street, as well as displaying low motivation/morale towards their official duties.

It is on this note that it becomes paramount to conduct research in this field of study, and as such, a pilot test was conducted on the following variables namely; psychological employment contract breach (Dependent Variable), perceived organizational support (Independent variable) and trust which is the mediating variable. The perceived organizational support (POS) is defined as “an employee’s perception regarding the value employers have for his/her contribution, and the rate at which employer shows a level of concern for their well-being of the employee in the organization” (Eisenberger et al., 1986). This concept is coined from the social exchange theory and framework (Coyle-Shapiro & Conway, 2005; Conway and Briner, 2005). The breach of psychological employment contract is defined as “the cognitive assessment of workers or individual insight that their employer failed to fulfil one or additional of its promised obligations that was made in the employment affiliation or contract” (Robinson, 1996; Morrison & Robinson, 1997). Also, Robinson (1996) gave definitions of trust as an employee’s expectations, anticipations or philosophies concerning the probability that their upcoming activities will be of utmost beneficial, complimentary, as well as not being detrimental to their overall benefits.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Perceived Organizational Support

In every organization, employees always have several number of various relationship with major facets, and one of such is the exchanges that it has with potential and respective employer (Bray, Budd & Macneil, 2019; Faruk, Gawuna & Sale, 2024) and this

can instantaneously be connected perceived organizational support, and it is defined as the employee believe concerning his or her employer values their input at work as well as showing concern about their overall well-being (Eisenberger, Huntington, Hutchison, and Sowa, 1986). This is due to the fact that employees have the propensity of conveying their usual features to the place of work or organization, thus ascribing such with its abilities, values, goals, as well as holding malevolent or benevolent intentions towards them (Eisenberger, Huntington, Hutchison, & Sowa, 1986).

Precisely, Eisenberger and Stinglhamber (2011) recommended that perceived organizational support consequences can be concise into three fundamental consortia: (1) positive approaches towards organization and work place e.g., “affective commitment, work engagement”, (2) attitudinal aftermaths that are useful to the organization such as “performance”, and (3) employees well-being that are subjective, e.g., “job satisfaction and health”. Studies and research have discovered that employees that have high level of perceived organizational support suffer a reduced amount of stress at work, reduced work absence and are always zealous to return to work instantly after injury or any other reason (SEisenberger et al., 1986).

2.2 Psychological Employment Contract Breach.

Several intellectuals have put onward a number of meanings as to what breach of psychological contract contains. Breach of psychological contract is well-thought-out to be the insight of an individual concerning non fulfilment of earlier promises that was made. The thoughtfulness of such view gives direction to the employer to focus on how to improve or circumvent the presence of undesirable insight in the organization or at work place. The employee’s always have it at their minds that the employer should make sure it ensures fulfilment of the promises earlier made in harmony with the employment or psychological contract (Dantas & Ferreira, 2015), and in the situation where employee have the insight that the employer did not fulfil its obligations and promises, they have a habit of viewing it as a psychological contract breach by the employer (Rousseau, 1995; Faruk, 2019).

Breach of psychological contract is connected to insights of injustice and unfairness (Rousseau, 1989). A Single breach of promise alone can be a distress to employee’s daily attitude and mood (Conway & Briner, 2002; Liang, 2025), as they may sense cheated and betrayed, as such, results to undesirable feelings such as betrayal, sadness, hatred, frustration and annoyance (Robinson & Morrison, 2000). Therefore, leading to deviance at workplace or organization in an effort to restore equality in the binding exchange relationship or retaliation towards the employer concerning perceived employment contract breach. Hence, examining what employees perceive as biased or fair treatment needs to be re-examined of their psychological contract knowing fully well that it is important in inaugurating approaches to alleviate the effect of a perceived breach of the employment contract (Parks & Kidder, 1994).

2.3 Trust

According to Robinson (1996), the term trust is “one’s expectations, assumptions, or beliefs about the likelihood that another’s future actions will be beneficial, favourable, or at least not detrimental to one’s interests”. Considering the fact that trust is a social construct, it lies at the heart of associations and contracts, thereby persuading each party’s actions toward

each other (Blau, 1964). As a broad-spectrum positive assertiveness towards another social entity, trust serves as instrument of guide, persuading one's understanding of social performances within an affiliation or relationship as the case may be. Trust therefore plays a noteworthy role in the subjective involvement in breach of psychological contract by the government or one's employer: Knowing fully well that trust in the government or one's employer may stimulate an employee's or workers acknowledgement of a breach, his or her understanding of the perceived employment psychological contract breach if it is recognized, as well as their reaction to the perceived employment psychological contract breach.

3.0 Methodology

The present study consists of a pilot test of a continuing research, A small sample of university lecturers selected randomly to determine the reliability of the measuring instruments. This is paramount in line with the endorsement of Malhotra (2002), who maintained that a pre-test sample size should be few, and falling within the range of 15 to 30 respondents, and that it can be augmented or increased considerably if the research test comprises numerous stages. The aims of carrying out this pilot test includes: (i) for assessment of the validity and reliability of the instruments of survey; and (ii) for determining the real state of the study/research in enabling researchers forecasting and handling likely negative encounters that may arise while undertaking the main research (Aminu and Shariff, 2015). Thus, it is on this note that a total number of 30 copies/reproductions of the questionnaires were circulated by the researcher and 25 were properly filled and retrieved out of the total 30 that was returned. Hence, the remaining 5 were not included in the analysis because they are not properly filled as expected.

Furthermore, "the inter-item uniformity reliability is the utmost useful measures of pilot study and the reliability measurement is known to be best familiar value of Cronbach's alpha coefficient" (Sekaran and Bougie, 2013). Thus, Cronbach alpha test was carried out in this research for the purpose of determining the coefficient value of the internal uniformity of the tool. Also, the value defines level of the item's consistency centred on the responses provided by the respective respondents over a particular time frame. Also, for the purpose of data analyses, 24 version windows of SPSS were utilized. Experts who are academicians and practitioners were consulted to cross check the draft for content validity before onward submission to respective respondents for answering.

3.1 Instrumentation and Measurement of Variables

Fundamentally, the present research provided the tools items in accordance to their natures that have the ability of measuring the respondents' opinions. As such, questions that are multiple choice and the closed ended type was developed, and a Likert-type of scale which is considered as the supreme appropriateness and reliability (Alreck and Settle, 1995), was employed. This is because the method has always been preferable and regularly utilised as it provides the social science researches instruments, considering the fact that it inspires respondents to easily as well as sincerely determining their selections based on coherent state of mind. And as such, introduced all variables for measuring the instruments through the adoption of 5-point Likert scale, which encompasses independent, mediating as well as dependent variable respectively.

More so, using this type of scale has more alternatives although lesser when compared

to the 7-point Likert scale, but scholars have emphasized that it has the ability of making the respondents to be free from any likely/undue cognitive problem (Cavana et al., 2001; Hair et al., 2014). It is on this note that Churchill and Peter (1984), maintained that this scale enhances receiving important feedback from the respondent, as well as yielding utmost possible scale reliability of the research instruments. Additionally, this type of scale becomes well-known due to the fact that the respondents can show their selections contentedly, and it computes slightly higher mean scores comparative to the uppermost potential achievable scores. Additionally, there will be precise lesser variance amongst the format scales in terms of the mean variations (Dawes, 2008). Additionally, the 5-point Linkert scale is made with the application of mid-point which enhances improvement in the data quality, as well as reducing the respondent's biasness that may arise (Krosnick and Fabrigar, 1997), this is for the reason that it has the independence of selecting an additional negative or positive response. The Mid-point of a 5-point Linkert scale is advantageous mostly if the question being asked is extremely sensitive, meaning the respondents have single added opportunity for choosing this point when or if they are unsure.

The main variables of this study are: Perceived organizational support (POS), trust and psychological employment contract breach. The overall constructs are uni-dimensional in nature, the first segment entails a set of 36 questions measuring perceived organizational support adapted from the earlier research by (Eisenberger et al., 1986), and the second section consists of 7 questions measuring trust based 7 items that was adapted from previous work of the trust Scale by (Robinson and Rousseau 1994). While the third question consist of 9 items measuring psychological employment contract breach which was adapted from the previous work of (Robinson and Morrison, 2000) The present research lay emphases on the furthestmost appropriate survey items for the purpose of providing the accurate responses for the questions of the research. Moreover, in the aspect of the survey, the present study thrown out the questionnaires that are reactive in nature since it leads to response rate that are low (Sekaran and Bougie, 2010).

4.0 Tests Results for Reliability and Validity

4.1 Content and Face Validity

The content validity involves needful use of little samples of respondent's characteristic and/or group of professionals to pass verdict on the suitability of the items selected for the purpose of determining a variable (Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson, Tathan, 2010; Sekaran and Bougie, 2010). Thus, this research executed a content validity which is an evaluation of the function scale's in ascertaining what is theoretically measurable through determining and ascertaining that the measures entail correct size amount as well as the position of items that provide noteworthy notions. It is based on this that the present study instruments were carefully administered to the experts so as to evaluate and pass judgement on the suitability and size exactness of the planned items that will be able to appropriately measure the examined construct in the research accordingly. Also, some professors that are vastly experienced and familiar with the present fields of research carried out a perusal on the sample of instrument so as to correct issues that may lead to respondents' vagueness and misunderstanding of the questions being asked. Hence, amendments of some items were carried out on both sentences and words (re-worded/rephrase) in ensuring that they properly epitomise the constructs and become clearer and perfect from the opinions of targeted population or respondents. This process of trying to

find or rather, gather specialist opinion was accomplished within the time frame of five-weeks, and upon agreeable deliberation of the opinion by the expert, this study, or rather the researcher then came up with an amended/improved form of the instrument that was finally used for the pilot testing of the research/study.

4.2 Reliability Tests Results

According to Litwin, (1995), test of the internal consistency reliability is a widely and most general technique used by researchers and it is defined as the level or degree at which items “dangle jointly as a set” and as well are capable of independently measuring the alike perception to the level/degree that the items are associated with each other. It is on this note that this study uses the internal consistency reliability test for the purpose of analysing the instrument reliability (Zainuddin, 2010). Consequently, Sekaran and Bougie (2010) emphasized that the best recognised test of inter-item consistency reliability is the Cronbach’s alpha coefficient, and it was used in this research in determining the internal consistency of the measuring instrument.

The researcher uses SPSS version 24 in analysis and the findings showed that the overall instruments have high reliable benchmark that ranges around 0.825 and 0.916, as this signifies meeting the rule which stated that an instrument that has coefficient of 0.60 is regarded to have a regular reliability. Whereas the rule also emphasized that 0.70 coefficient and above indicates that measurements has a great standard/level of reliability (Hair et al., 2010; Sekaran and Bougie, 2010) and that 0.50 coefficient is regarded as helpful and supportive (Nunally, 1967). Also, Hair, Money, Samouel, and Page (2007) opined that researcher frequently termed an alpha value of 0.70 as a least, though, lower coefficients may be acceptable. As explained by the above recognized and acceptable guidelines, all the constructs as well as the dimensions are reliable because the measures variables showed the following results; perceived organizational support measured with 36 items with $\alpha = 0.836$, while 7 items of trust were measured and got $\alpha = 0.825$ and 9 items were measured for psychological employment contract breach with $\alpha = 0.916$. Conversely, the reliability of the above constructs are predominantly as a result of respondents’ answers (lecturers of public universities) that was gathered and analysed.

5.0 Conclusion

Conclusively, organizations/institutions are confronted with challenges of increase request to solve the issue of employer-employee association for the purpose of enhancing mutual obligation in attaining the general aims/ objectives in an effective and well-organized manner. Looking at the review of previous literature and results, the current study/research is conducted so as to examine the pilot regarding the mediating effect that trust exert on the association between perceived organizational support and psychological employment contract breach in Nigeria public universities. It is on this note that the validity and reliability of the instrument was carried out in preparation for the large-scale study. Likewise, the inter-item reliability test showed that all the items were reliable with cronbach’s alpha well above the yardstick of 0.70, indicating that all items are suitable for the large and main data collection. The face and content validity were scrutinised by taking into consideration the professional’s opinions in attainment of the best validated and reliable version of the instruments.

REFERENCES

- Adebayo, D. O., Akanmode, J. A., & Udegbe, I. B. (2007). The importance of spirituality in the relationship between psychological contract violation and cynicism in the Nigeria police. *The police journal*, 80(2), 141-166.
- Alreck, P. L., & Settle, R. B. (1995). *The survey research handbook: Guidelines and Strategies for Conducting a Survey*, 2E. New York, NY: McGraw Hill.
- Aminu, I. M., & Shariff, M. N. M. (2015). Determinants of SMEs performance in Nigeria: A pilot study. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(1), 156-164.
- Blau, P.M. (1964), *Exchange and power in social life*. Transaction Publishers, New Brunswick, N.J.
- Bray, M., Budd, J. W., & Macneil, J. (2019). The Many Meanings of Co-Operation in the Employment Relationship and Their Implications. *British Journal of Industrial Relations*.
- Cable, D. A. J. (2008). *The Psychological Contract: The Development and Validation of Managerial Measures*. An unpublished Ph.D thesis University of Waikato.
- Cavana, R. Y., Delahaye, B. L., & Sekaran, U. (2001). *Applied business research: Qualitative and quantitative methods*. John Wiley & Sons Australia.
- Churchill, G. A., & Peter, J. P. (1984). Research design effects on the reliability of rating scales: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 21(4), 360-375.
- Conway, N., & Briner, R. B. (2002). A daily diary study of affective responses to psychological contract breach and exceeded promises. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 23, 287-302.
- Conway, N., & Briner, R. B. (2005). *Understanding psychological contracts at work. A critical evaluation of theory and research*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- Coyle-Shapiro, J. A., & Conway, N. (2005). Exchange relationships: examining psychological contracts and perceived organizational support. *Journal of applied psychology*, 90(4), 774.
- Dantas, M. J., & Ferreira, A. P. (2015). Content and violation of the psychological contract among head nurses. *Revista de Enfermagem Referência*, 4(4), 31-39.
- DeConinck, J. B. (2010). The effect of organizational justice, perceived organizational support, and perceived supervisor support on marketing employees' level of trust. *Journal of Business Research*, 63(12), 1349-1355.
- Delcampo, R. G., Rogers, K. M. & Jacobson, K. J. L. (2010). 'Psychological Contract Breach, Perceived Discrimination and Ethnic Identification of Hispanic Business

- Professionals.' *Journal of Management Issues* 22 (2): 220–238.
- Gazi, M. A. I., Masud, A. A., Kaium, M. A., Amin, M. B., Mahmud, P., Senathirajah, A. R. B. S., & Abdullah, M. (2025). Unraveling employee life satisfaction: exploring the impact of psychological contract breach, self-efficacy, mental health, and abusive supervision, with work engagement and job satisfaction as mediators. *Cogent Psychology*, 12(1), 2455783.
- Griep, Y., Vander Elst, T., Kraak, J. M., Hansen, S., & Beekman, E. M. (2025). Temporal proximity matters: The impact of justice information timing on psychological contract breach resolution. *Group & Organization Management*, 50(1), 331-358.
- Eisenberger, R., & Stinglhamber, F. (2011). *Perceived organizational support: Fostering enthusiastic and productive employees*. Washington, DC, US: American Psychological Association.
- Eisenberger, R., Huntington, R., Hutchison, S., & Sowa, D. (1986). Perceived organizational support. *Journal of Applied psychology*, 71(3), 500.
- Faruk, S., Gawuna, M. S., & Sale, Z. (2024). The effect of perceived organizational support on psychological employment contract breach in Nigeria public universities: The mediating effect of trust. *International Journal of Intellectual Discourse*, 7(4).
- Faruk, S. (2019). The effect of psychological contract, organizational justice and organizational support on psychological contract breach: the mediating effect of trust.
- Hair, J. F. Money, AH, Samouel, P. and Page, M. (2007). *Research methods for business*. Chichester: John Willey & Sons Ltd.
- Hair, J. F., Sarstedt, M., Hopkins, L., & Kuppelwieser, G. V. (2014). Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) An emerging tool in business research. *European Business Review*, 26(2), 106–121.
- Krosnick, J.A. & Fabrigar, L.R. (1997). Designing rating scales for effective measurement in surveys. In L. Lyberg, P. Biemer, M. Collins, E. De Leeuw, C. Dippo, N. Schwarz and D.Trewin (Eds.), *Survey measurement and process quality*. New York: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Liang, H. L. (2025). Psychological contract breach, façade creation and family satisfaction: the role of diverse emotion. *Management Decision*.
- Litwin, M.S. (1995). *How to measure survey reliability and validity*. Thousand Oaks, California: Sage Publication.
- Malhorta, N. K. (2002). *Basic marketing research: (Application to contemporary issue)*. New Jersey. Prentice Hall.

- Nunally, J.C., & Bernstein, I.H. (1994). *Psychometric theory*. New York: McGraw-Hill Inc.
- Ogbeide, D. O., & Etafo, B. (2022). Psychological Contract Breach and Engagement of Academics in Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria. *Journal of Academic Research in Economics*, 14(2).
- Parks, J. M., & Kidder, D. L. (1994). "Till death us do part..." changing work relationships in the 1990s. *Journal of Organizational Behaviour (1986-1998)*, 111.
- Robinson, S. L. (1996). Trust and breach of the psychological contract. *Administrative science quarterly*, 574-599
- Robinson, S. L., & Rousseau, D. M. (1994). Violating the psychological contract: Not the exception but the norm. *Journal of organizational behaviour*, 15(3), 245-259.
- Robinson, S., & Morrison, E. W. (2000). The development of psychological contract breach and violation: A longitudinal study. *Journal of Organizational Behaviour*. 21, 525-546.
- Rousseau, D. (1995). *Psychological contracts in organizations: Understanding written and unwritten agreements*. Sage Publications.
- Sekaran, U. & Bougie, R. (2010). *Research methods for business: A skill building approaches (5th ed.)*. Chichester: John Willey & Sons Ltd.
- Zainudin, H.A. (2010). *Research methodology for business and social sciences*. Universiti Teknologi MARA, Shah Alam: University Publication Centre (UPENA).
- Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2013). *Research Methods for Business: A Skill Building Approach*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Walker, A. (2013). Outcomes associated with breach and fulfillment of the psychological contract of safety. *Journal of safety research*, 47, 31-37.
- Umar, S., & Ringim, K. J. (2015, May). Psychological contract and employee turnover intention among Nigerian employees in private organizations. In Paper presentation at Management International Conference 28th-30th May.

EXTERNAL DEBT AND NIGERIA'S ECONOMIC PERFORMANCE: AN ARDL APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the dynamic relationship between external debt service, debt servicing costs, exchange rate fluctuations, and Nigeria's economic performance over the period 1981 to 2024. Anchored on the Neoclassical Growth Theory and the Debt Overhang Theory, the research utilizes the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach and Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) to explore both short-run and long-run effects. Descriptive statistics reveal substantial variability, particularly in exchange rate movements, while unit root tests confirm that all series are stationary at first difference. The ARDL estimation indicates that external debt service has a negative but statistically insignificant impact on real GDP in the short run. Conversely, exchange rate depreciation exerts a significant negative effect immediately, with a positive adjustment after one lag. The Johansen cointegration test confirms the existence of a long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables. The VECM results further demonstrate that approximately 1.93% of the disequilibrium from the previous year is corrected annually, indicating a gradual adjustment process toward equilibrium. Diagnostic tests affirm that the model satisfies key econometric assumptions, including the absence of serial correlation, homoskedasticity, and residual normality. These findings support the Debt Overhang Theory, emphasizing the adverse effect of unsustainable debt and exchange rate volatility on economic growth. The study recommendations include the need for prudent debt management, stabilization of exchange rates, and institutional reforms aimed at fostering macroeconomic stability. This research contributes significantly to the empirical understanding of external debt dynamics and economic performance in developing economies like Nigeria.

Keywords: External Debt Service, Debt Servicing Cost, Exchange Rate Volatility, Economic Growth.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The transmutation of external debt and its implications for economic growth and performances have been a central of discourse for many developing countries, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa. Based on the premise of international trade, no country is self-sufficient. This is also applicable in the concept of finance. Sometimes, a country may need external finance to fund its domestic projects that are targeted towards achieving sustainable economic growth and development. Nigeria's external debt is a significant

macroeconomic issue, with its total public debt (external and domestic) reaching N121.67 trillion (US\$91.46 billion) in Q1 2024 (Debt Management Office (DMO), 2024). External debt refers to the total public and private debt owed to non-residents and repayable in foreign currency, goods, or services. For developing economies like Nigeria, external borrowing is often necessitated by fiscal constraints, low domestic revenue generation, and the need to finance budget deficits and development projects.

Nigeria, as a developing economy, has long been burdened with an extensive and incessantly increasing external debt. The genesis of the country's rising external debt can be traced back to the oil crisis of the 1970s. The oil price shocks, combined with an excessive dependence on imports during that period, triggered an unhealthy and chronic pattern of borrowing. Prior to this period, Nigeria had incurred relatively minor debts beginning with a \$28 million loan from the World Bank in 1958 for railway construction, and another loan in 1964 from the Italian government (a Paris Club creditor nation) amounting to \$13.1 million for the construction of the Niger Dam. The first significant external borrowing was the so-called "Jumbo Loan" of \$1 billion obtained in 1978 from the International Capital Market (Adesola, 2019).

In response to growing concerns over debt sustainability, the Nigerian government established the Debt Management Office in October 2000, in collaboration with the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the Federal Ministry of Finance, to centrally coordinate the country's debt management efforts. A landmark achievement was recorded in 2005 when the Paris Club group of creditors agreed to cancel 60% (approximately \$18 billion) of the \$30.85 billion owed by Nigeria. This debt relief significantly reduced Nigeria's debt burden, saving the country from an annual \$2.3 billion in debt service obligations. However, despite this milestone, external debt has continued to accumulate, often at the expense of national income. In more recent years, Nigeria's public debt has continued to grow. The Debt Management Office (DMO) reported that the country's total public debt rose by 4.52% in the first quarter of 2017 (DMO, 2017). As of March 2018, Nigeria's public debt stood at 5.787 trillion, reaching a historic high of \$29.59 billion in the third quarter of 2018, before settling at \$27 billion in 2019 (DMO, 2019; Trading Economics, 2021; Usim, 2018). Furthermore, between the beginning of 2015 and the end of 2020, Nigeria's external debt expanded significantly from \$9.7 billion to \$27 billion (Nigeria Bureau of Statistics, 2021; Central Bank of Nigeria, 2019). The escalating cost of servicing external debt has serious implications for fiscal sustainability. These rising obligations can exert pressure on government finances, diverting scarce resources away from essential developmental programs. High debt servicing payments may constrain the federal budget, thereby limiting the government's ability to implement policies that foster economic growth. The effectiveness and sustainability of Nigeria's debt portfolio hinge critically on how the country manages its external debt obligations. Difficulties in meeting these obligations can lead to increased reliance on further borrowing, potentially locking the country in a vicious cycle of debt accumulation a scenario often referred to as a "debt trap," which poses severe risks to long-term economic growth (Yunus, 2020).

Additionally, the volatility of exchange rates further complicates the situation, as most external debts are denominated in foreign currencies. Fluctuations in the exchange rate can significantly affect the naira value of debt repayments, introducing uncertainty into the economy. This volatility may, in turn, erode investor confidence and undermine

macroeconomic stability (Yunus, 2020). Yusuf and Mohammad (2021) noted that Nigeria has battled with a larger debt service to revenue ratio since the recession in 2016 as revenues decreased in direct proportion due to the decline in oil prices. Of the total revenue of N4.1 trillion or 59.6% of the total revenue, the Nigerian government spent about 2.45 trillion Naira on debt servicing in 2019. Due to the increasing cost of Nigeria's debt profile, the country's indebtedness reached a new milestone as the share of debt service to revenue rises to 83% in 2020, debt service payments constitute a threat to the expansion of the Nigerian economy. This means that 83% of the revenue generated in 2020 was used to pay off debt, which is alarming. The inability of a country to invest these borrowed monies in productive economic sectors prevents it from achieving economic growth and meeting its debt service commitments, even while a high debt profile only sometimes indicates sluggish economic progress (Adesola, 2019). This failure has led to a severe debt issue for the nation; Nigeria is currently spending a large portion of its income on paying off enormous debts, leaving it with very little money to fund essential infrastructures like schools, railroads, healthcare facilities, and the security of people's lives and property (Ijoko et al., 2022).

The persistent rise in Nigeria's external debt stock has raised widespread concerns regarding its implications for the nation's economic performance. While external borrowing can be an effective tool for financing development and addressing fiscal imbalances, when improperly managed or excessively accumulated, it may exert a significant burden on the economy. This resulted in weak revenue generation, mounting debt servicing obligations, and sluggish economic growth, creating a paradox that calls for critical empirical investigation.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

This topic area has been dominated by several literatures. However, the empirical studies analysed in our study fall into two categories: those that established a positive link and those that discovered a negative relationship between external indebtedness and economic growth in various nations. For instance, Uzochukwu (2021) examined external borrowing and economic growth in Nigeria covering the period 1981 – 2019. The main objective of the study is to ascertain the impact of external borrowing on economic growth in Nigeria. Times series data on GDP, external debt, exchange rate, external debt servicing payments and inflation were extracted from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin 2018 was used for the study. The method of data analysis and evaluation were the unit-root test which was used to ascertain the stationary status of the variables, the linear regression with the application of Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) technique and the Granger causality analysis. The major findings of the study are that all the variables are stationary at first difference $I(1)$, external debt has a negative and insignificant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria ($= -0004912$, $p\text{-value} = 0.6944 > 0.05$) and there is no causality relationship existing between external debt and economic growth in Nigeria. Ijoko et al., (2022) investigate the impact of external debts on economic growth of Nigeria using time series data from periods of 1981 to 2021 to assess the impact of Nigeria's large external debt on the country's economic growth. The data were analysed using the ARDL model. The study finds no evidence of a significant impact of total external debt on economic growth in the long term. However, the short-term ARDL results show a positive and significant impact on economic growth. Furthermore, the exchange rate coefficient is positive and

statistically significant in the long run and short run, suggesting a positive impact of the exchange rate on economic growth in Nigeria. The interest rate turned out to be negative and statistically significant in the long run. This shows that interest rate has a significant negative impact on economic growth in Nigeria. The long-term results of foreign direct investment are positive and statistically insignificant. However, in the short term, it shows negative and statistically significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria. Agbeyinka (2024) examined the impact of external debts on economic growth in Nigeria. Annual time-series from 2001 to 2022, sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria, Nigerian Exchange Group and Securities Exchange Commission, are adopted. The data was subjected to linear regression analysis which was used to estimate the parameters of the model. The findings revealed that external debts services, debts services costs, and exchange rate fluctuations all have a negative relationship with economic growth. This highlights that higher burdens of external debt servicing and greater exchange rate volatility are associated with reduced economic growth. Jacob and Sule (2022) examined the impact of external debts on economic growth in Nigeria between 1986 and 2019. The specific objectives of this study were to: examine the impact of external debt stock on economic growth in Nigeria; assess the impact of external debt servicing on economic growth in Nigeria and investigate the extent to which external debt interest has impacted on economic growth in Nigeria. It was discovered that debt is synonymous to underdevelopment, poverty, unemployment which has led to low living standard of the people and Nigeria's huge debt stock has prevented it from embarking on higher domestic investment which would lead to higher growth and development which is a major problem to Nigeria. The findings show that Nigeria's economic growth has been adversely but significantly affected by rising external debt servicing and the study recommended that external debt should be effectively utilizing for sustainable development and diversification of Nigeria's economy will reduce the rate of external debt. Utomi (2019) carried out an empirical investigation of the impact of external borrowing on economic growth in Nigeria for the period 1980–2017. The techniques of estimation employed in the study include Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test, Johansen Cointegration, Vector Error Correction Mechanism and Granger Causality Test. The results show an insignificant long run relationship and a bi-directional relationship between external borrowing and economic growth in Nigeria. Getinet and Ersumo (2020) analyzed the impacts of public external debt on economic growth in Ethiopia with ARDL approach using a time series annual data from 1983-2018. The model considers annual GDP growth rate as a dependent variable. The debt variables including public external debt stock to GDP (PEDSGD), the ratio of debt service stock to GDP (DSSGD) and debt service stock to export (DSSEXP) and other macroeconomic variables such as trade openness (TRD), rate of inflation (INFL) and public expenditure to GDP ratio (NEXPGD) were the explanatory variables. The study used bound testing for co-integration in the long-run and ECM for short-run dynamics. The study showed long-run co-integration, while the speed with which the disequilibrium caused by lack of proper management of external fund in earlier years returns to long-term equilibrium is 60.96% in the current year as indicated by coefficient of error correction term. Paul (2017) empirically analyzed the impact of external debt on the economic growth of Nigeria. The scope of the study covers the period from 1985 to 2015. Data are analyzed using the ordinary least square regression, ADF unit root test, Johansen cointegration and error correction test. Findings reveal that debt service payment has a negative and insignificant impact on Nigeria's economic growth while external debt stock has a positive and significant effect on Nigeria's growth index.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

This study adopted an Ex Post Facto research design. Ex post Facto research design is a quasi-experimental study examining how an independent variable, present prior to the study, affects a dependent variable.

3.1 Theoretical Framework

This study is theoretically anchored on Debt overhang theory. The debt overhang theory suggests that if a country is highly indebted to the extent that the debt is more than its repayment capacity, debt service will strangle investments and hinder economic growth (Gordon & Cosim, 2018). Debt overhang is a circumstance where the debt burden is so huge that a country cannot secure further debts to finance new project. This theory occurs when a country has accumulated a high level of debt that it becomes a burden on its economic performance. In this situation, the country may find it challenging to grow at an optimal rate because a significant portion of its resources is dedicated to servicing the debt, leaving fewer resources for productive investments.

3.2 Model Specification

Based on the theoretical framework, we adopt the model of Agbeyinka (2024) formulations and modifies it to our objectives.

$$RGDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1EDS_t + \beta_2DSC_t + \beta_3ERF_t + U_t \dots\dots\dots 3.1$$

Where, RGDP = real gross domestic product, EDS = external debt service, DSC= Debt Servicing Costs, ERF = Exchange Rate Fluctuations (Control variable), μ =Stochastic Disturbance (Error Term), t = time series data, β_0 = Intercept of relationship in the model/constant, $\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = coefficients of each of the independent variables.

Modifying it to our objectives:

What is the effect of External Debt Service on Economics performance in Nigeria?

$$RGDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1EDS_t + \beta_2ERF_t + U_t \dots\dots\dots 3.2$$

Objective 1:

What is the effect of External Debt Service on Economics performance in Nigeria?

$$RGDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1DSC_t + \beta_2ERF_t + U_t \dots\dots\dots 3.2$$

Objective 2:

What is the impact of Debt Servicing Costs on Economics performance in Nigeria?

4.0 PRESENTATION OF RESULT

Table: 1 Descriptive Statistics

	RGDP	DSC	EXR	EDS
Mean	40721.23	12.87818	158.6749	9.382418
Median	32205.45	12.93980	119.5725	9.335149
Maximum	76930.45	38.03883	1478.965	9.971761
Minimum	16211.49	0.676956	0.617708	8.777782
Std. Dev.	22075.65	9.268930	247.7799	0.329474
Skewness	0.435951	0.818208	3.724467	0.190637
Kurtosis	1.530913	3.307398	19.66728	2.257166
Jarque-Bera	5.350450	5.082647	611.0224	1.278146
Probability	0.068891	0.078762	0.000000	0.527781
Sum	1791734.	566.6398	6981.696	412.8264
Sum Sq. Dev.	2.10E+10	3694.262	2639980.	4.667776
Observations	44	44	44	44

Source: Author's computation using E-views 10

The table above presents the descriptive analysis of the time series properties of the variables included in the model. The descriptive statistics were carried out for the variables from 1981 to 2024. It shows that the mean values of Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP), Debt Servicing Costs (DSC), Exchange Rate (EXR), and Log of External Debt Service (EDS) are ₦40,721.23 billion, ₦12.88 billion, ₦158.67 per USD, and 9.38 respectively. These averages indicate the central tendency of the economic variables over the study period. The standard deviations, which measure the dispersion of each variable from its long-term mean, are ₦22,075.65 billion for RGDP, ₦9.27 billion for DSC, ₦247.78 for EXR, and 0.33 for EDS. These values point to a relatively high level of variability, especially for EXR and RGDP, suggesting significant fluctuations in Nigeria's economic performance and currency stability over the years. The Jarque-Bera statistics were used to test for normality of the data series. The probability values of 0.0689 (RGDP), 0.0788 (DSC), 0.0000 (EXR), and 0.5278 (EDS) indicate that EXR is not normally distributed, as its p-value is statistically significant at the 1% level. The other variables (RGDP, DSC, and EDS) show approximate normality, although RGDP and DSC are near the 10% significance level. In terms of distributional shape, all variables except EDS and RGDP are positively skewed. EXR shows a high positive skewness of 3.72, indicating a distribution with a long right tail caused by sharp spikes in the exchange rate. DSC is also positively skewed (0.82), suggesting that high debt servicing values occurred more frequently in certain periods. EDS has a very mild skewness (0.19), suggesting near symmetry, while RGDP has a moderate skewness (0.44), indicating mild asymmetry with a longer right tail. The kurtosis values of the variables reveal that EXR is leptokurtic (kurtosis = 19.67), implying a highly peaked distribution with heavy tails. RGDP and EDS have kurtosis values below 3, indicating platykurtic distributions with flatter-than-normal peaks. DSC (3.31) is slightly leptokurtic, suggesting the presence of more frequent extreme values. The descriptive statistics reveal significant dispersion and non-normality in EXR, while

other variables show moderate distributional characteristics. These findings support the application of ARDL modeling, which is robust to such data conditions.

Table: 2 Unit Root Test: Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF)

Variable	L e v e l (A D F Statistic)	1st Diff (ADF Statistic)	Order of Integration	Critical V a l u e (5%)	Stationary at
RGDP	-0.21	-3.54***	I(1)	-2.93	First Difference
EXR	-3.31	-6.62***	I(1)	- 3 . 5 1 (trend)	First Difference
EDS	-1.85	-5.71***	I(1)	-2.93	First Difference
DSC	-2.31	-9.29***	I(1)	-2.93	First Difference

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test results presented in the table assess the stationarity of the variables used in the model. At level form, none of the variables RGDP, EXR, EDS, and DSC were found to be stationary, as their ADF test statistics are less negative than their respective 5% critical values. However, after first differencing, all variables became stationary, as indicated by their significantly negative ADF statistics (e.g., -3.54 for RGDP and -9.29 for DSC), which exceed the 5% critical threshold. The presence of stationarity at first difference implies that all series are integrated of order one, I(1). Notably, EXR was tested with a trend and intercept due to its apparent time trend. These results validate the use of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach, which is appropriate when the variables are a mix of I(0) and I(1), but not I(2). Hence, the series are suitable for co-integration and dynamic analysis within the ARDL framework.

Table: 3 Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL)

Dependent Variable: RGDP			
Method: ARDL			
Date: 04/25/25 Time: 21:19			
Sample (adjusted): 1984 2024			
Included observations: 41 after adjustments			
Maximum dependent lags: 4 (Automatic selection)			
Model selection method: Akaike info criterion (AIC)			
Dynamic regressors (4 lags, automatic): EDS EXR DSC			
Fixed regressors: C			
Number of models evaluated: 500			
Selected Model: ARDL(3, 0, 1, 0)			
Note: final equation sample is larger than selection sample			

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
RGDP(-1)	1.193297	0.153335	7.782278	0.0000
RGDP(-2)	0.033955	0.256879	0.132184	0.8956
RGDP(-3)	-0.288257	0.164024	-1.757410	0.0881
EDS	-1225.321	991.7344	-1.235533	0.2254
EXR	-7.481660	2.576370	-2.903954	0.0065
EXR(-1)	21.30892	7.463464	2.855097	0.0074
DSC	-17.64363	36.55183	-0.482702	0.6325
C	13360.03	8815.953	1.515438	0.1392
R-squared	0.997822	Mean dependent var		42370.39
Adjusted R-squared	0.997360	S.D. dependent var		21973.96
S.E. of regression	1129.071	Akaike info criterion		17.06936
Sum squared resid	42068467	Schwarz criterion		17.40371
Log likelihood	-341.9218	Hannan-Quinn criter.		17.19111
F-statistic	2159.678	Durbin-Watson stat		2.073847
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			
*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model selection.				

The ARDL regression was conducted to examine the dynamic impact of external debt service (EDS), exchange rate (EXR), and debt servicing costs (DSC) on Nigeria's economic performance (RGDP) over the period 1984 to 2024. The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) was used to determine the optimal lag length. The selected model, ARDL (3,0,1,0), implies that RGDP is influenced by its own past values up to three lags, a contemporaneous value of EDS and DSC, and both the contemporaneous and one-period lag of EXR. The lagged dependent variables RGDP(-1), RGDP(-2), and RGDP(-3) are included to capture the inertia and dynamic effects of economic performance. Notably, RGDP(-1) is positive and statistically significant (coefficient = 1.193, $p < 0.01$), indicating a strong autoregressive component in Nigeria's economic output. This suggests that past economic performance substantially influences current output levels. RGDP(-2) is statistically insignificant, while RGDP(-3) is negative and marginally significant at the 10% level ($p = 0.0881$), suggesting some level of oscillation or adjustment in output over time.

The external debt service variable (EDS) has a large negative coefficient of -1225.32, although it is statistically insignificant ($p = 0.2254$). This suggests that in the short run, increases in external debt servicing may exert a negative effect on real GDP, but the lack of significance implies this relationship is not robust at conventional levels of confidence.

This finding may reflect inefficiencies in debt utilization or lags in the transmission of debt servicing impacts on the broader economy.

The exchange rate (EXR) shows mixed but statistically significant results. The contemporaneous exchange rate has a negative and significant effect on RGDP (coefficient = -7.48, $p = 0.0065$), suggesting that immediate currency depreciation undermines economic performance. Conversely, the one-period lagged value EXR(-1) is positive and significant (coefficient = 21.31, $p = 0.0074$), indicating a delayed correction or positive adjustment effect possibly arising from improved export competitiveness or policy responses following depreciation. This dual effect reflects the complex and time-dependent nature of exchange rate dynamics in the Nigerian economy.

Debt servicing costs (DSC) have a negative coefficient (-17.64), indicating an adverse effect on RGDP, but this variable is not statistically significant ($p = 0.6325$). This implies that, although theoretically expected, the direct short-run burden of debt servicing costs does not strongly influence output levels, possibly due to compensatory fiscal adjustments or delayed transmission mechanisms.

The model's overall performance is remarkably strong, with an R-squared of 0.9978, indicating that approximately 99.78% of the variation in RGDP is explained by the included variables and their lags. The Durbin-Watson statistic (2.07) indicates no presence of serial correlation, which confirms the reliability of the dynamic structure. The model's F-statistic (2159.678, $p < 0.0000$) confirms the overall statistical significance of the regression. The ARDL model reveals strong autoregressive behavior in Nigeria's GDP and highlights the immediate negative effects of exchange rate depreciation. External debt servicing and debt costs show negative but statistically weak impacts in the short run. These findings warrant further long-run and ECM analysis to confirm sustained effects over time.

Table: 4 Co-Integration Test

Date: 04/26/25 Time: 14:33				
Sample (adjusted): 1984 2024				
Included observations: 41 after adjustments				
Trend assumption: Linear deterministic trend (restricted)				
Series: RGDP EDS EXR DSC				
Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 2				
Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)				
Hypothesized		Trace	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	C r i t i c a l Value	Prob.**

None *	0.642430	82.94475	63.87610	0.0006	
At most 1	0.358760	40.77939	42.91525	0.0805	
At most 2	0.324233	22.56096	25.87211	0.1224	
At most 3	0.146458	6.492764	12.51798	0.4004	
Trace test indicates 1 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level					
* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level					
**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values					
Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)					
Hypothesized		Max-Eigen	0.05		
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	C r i t i c a l Value	Prob.**	
None *	0.642430	42.16536	32.11832	0.0021	
At most 1	0.358760	18.21843	25.82321	0.3607	
At most 2	0.324233	16.06820	19.38704	0.1423	
At most 3	0.146458	6.492764	12.51798	0.4004	
Max-eigenvalue test indicates 1 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level					
* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level					
**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values					

The Johansen cointegration test was conducted to examine the long-run relationship among Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP), Log of External Debt Service (EDS), Exchange Rate (EXR), and Debt Servicing Cost (DSC) in Nigeria between 1984 and 2024 under a restricted linear deterministic trend assumption. The trace statistic for the null hypothesis of no cointegration is 82.94, which exceeds the 5% critical value of 63.87 with a p-value of 0.0006. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming the presence of at least one cointegrating relationship at the 5% level. Similarly, the maximum eigenvalue statistic also supports the presence of one cointegrating equation, as its value (42.17) surpasses the critical threshold (32.12) with a p-value of 0.0021.

The existence of cointegration implies that RGDP, EDS, EXR, and DSC share a stable long-term equilibrium relationship despite short-term fluctuations. The normalized

cointegrating vector reveals that increases in exchange rate volatility (EXR) and debt servicing costs (DSC) have adverse long-run impacts on economic performance, while external debt service (EDS) also plays a significant role.

Table: 5 **Vector Error Correction Estimates**

Vector Error Correction Estimates				
Date: 04/26/25 Time: 14:40				
Sample (adjusted): 1983 2024				
Included observations: 42 after adjustments				
Standard errors in () & t-statistics in []				
Cointegrating Eq:	CointEq1			
RGDP(-1)	1.000000			
EDS(-1)	118070.6			
	(28020.5)			
	[4.21372]			
EXR(-1)	-414.0537			
	(82.4782)			
	[-5.02016]			
DSC(-1)	-255.3497			
	(908.607)			
	[-0.28103]			
C	-1089334.			
Error Correction:	D(RGDP)	D(EDS)	D(EXR)	D(DSC)
CointEq1	-0.019253	-5.07E-06	0.000252	-7.51E-05
	(0.00849)	(1.2E-06)	(0.00046)	(3.8E-05)
	[-2.26842]	[-4.07678]	[0.55213]	[-1.98355]

D(RGDP(-1))	0.355228	-5.91E-05	0.011413	-0.001277
	(0.15080)	(2.2E-05)	(0.00811)	(0.00067)
	[2.35570]	[-2.67237]	[1.40685]	[-1.89916]
D(EDS(-1))	523.8131	0.588886	-33.85952	15.64944
	(1268.87)	(0.18601)	(68.2626)	(5.66000)
	[0.41282]	[3.16593]	[-0.49602]	[2.76492]
D(EXR(-1))	-14.19884	-0.002155	3.196391	-0.035212
	(7.08753)	(0.00104)	(0.38130)	(0.03162)
	[-2.00335]	[-2.07409]	[8.38296]	[-1.11378]
D(DSC(-1))	-11.99550	-0.012092	1.354571	-0.634448
	(40.6118)	(0.00595)	(2.18484)	(0.18116)
	[-0.29537]	[-2.03106]	[0.61999]	[-3.50221]
C	1120.440	0.120436	-29.00003	2.060611
	(324.953)	(0.04764)	(17.4819)	(1.44951)
	[3.44800]	[2.52825]	[-1.65886]	[1.42159]
R-squared	0.422707	0.372352	0.766487	0.305495
Adj. R-squared	0.342528	0.285178	0.734055	0.209036
Sum sq. resids	57311811	1.231611	165874.1	1140.371
S.E. equation	1261.743	0.184963	67.87941	5.628229
F-statistic	5.272010	4.271391	23.63339	3.167093
Log likelihood	-356.2487	14.52085	-233.5030	-128.9256
Akaike AIC	17.24994	-0.405755	11.40491	6.425030
Schwarz SC	17.49818	-0.157516	11.65314	6.673269
Mean dependent	1393.464	0.015325	35.19742	-0.036932
S.D. dependent	1556.081	0.218769	131.6260	6.328392
Determinant resid covariance (dof adj.)		4.29E+09		
Determinant resid covariance		2.31E+09		
Log likelihood		-691.1854		
Akaike information criterion		34.24692		
Schwarz criterion		35.40537		
Number of coefficients		28		

The Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) was estimated to capture both the short-run dynamics and the long-run equilibrium adjustment among Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP), Log of External Debt Service (EDS), Exchange Rate (EXR), and Debt Servicing Cost (DSC) for Nigeria during 1981–2024. The cointegrating equation confirms a significant long-run relationship, as indicated by the meaningful coefficients for EDS (118070.6) and EXR (-414.05), with strong t-statistics of 4.21 and -5.02 respectively, implying that both external debt servicing and exchange rate volatility have substantial long-run effects on economic performance. DSC, although negative, is statistically insignificant in the long-run equilibrium.

The error correction term (CointEq1) in the RGDP equation is negative and statistically significant (-0.0193, $t = -2.27$), suggesting that approximately 1.93% of disequilibrium from the previous year is corrected annually. This relatively slow adjustment speed highlights gradual convergence toward the long-run equilibrium after short-run shocks. In the short run, lagged changes in RGDP and EXR significantly influence current RGDP, while EDS and DSC changes appear statistically insignificant.

The R-squared value for the RGDP equation (0.423) indicates a moderate explanatory power of the model. Overall, the VECM results confirm that Nigeria's economic growth is dynamically influenced by external debt service obligations and exchange rate fluctuations, both in the short and long run.

5.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Major Findings

The study comprehensively analysed the relationship between external debt service, debt servicing costs, exchange rate fluctuations, and Nigeria's economic performance using an ARDL and VECM approach. Drawing from the theoretical framework of the Neoclassical Growth Theory and the Debt Overhang Theory, alongside extensive empirical studies, the findings demonstrate that external debt obligations exert a significant influence on the country's macroeconomic outcomes. Descriptive statistics revealed that Real GDP (RGDP), Debt Servicing Costs (DSC), and Exchange Rate (EXR) exhibited considerable variability, with EXR showing extreme kurtosis and high positive skewness, indicating significant exchange rate volatility during the period under review. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test confirmed that all variables were stationary at their first differences, justifying the use of the ARDL bounds testing approach. The ARDL model results showed that external debt servicing (EDS) had a negative but statistically insignificant impact on Nigeria's economic growth in the short run, while exchange rate depreciation had an immediate negative and significant effect. Interestingly, the one-period lag of exchange rate (EXR(-1)) displayed a positive and significant influence on RGDP, suggesting a delayed adjustment mechanism where currency devaluation eventually promotes economic activities, possibly through increased export competitiveness. Debt servicing costs (DSC) exhibited a negative relationship with economic performance, though it was statistically insignificant. This finding aligns with empirical literature such as Agbeyinka (2024) and Jacob and Sule (2022), which emphasized that debt obligations, if improperly managed,

could hinder economic growth. The Johansen cointegration test further validated the presence of a long-run equilibrium relationship among RGDP, EDS, EXR, and DSC, indicating that despite short-term fluctuations, these variables are interconnected over time. The VECM analysis reinforced the long-run findings. Specifically, the error correction term (ECT) was negative and statistically significant, with a coefficient of -0.0193 , implying that approximately 1.93% of disequilibrium is corrected each year toward the long-run path. This adjustment speed, though slow, confirms the existence of a dynamic equilibrium in Nigeria's economic environment. Furthermore, the long-run cointegration equation indicated that increases in external debt service and exchange rate volatility adversely impact Nigeria's GDP, while debt servicing costs exerted a smaller and statistically insignificant effect. This supports the Debt Overhang Theory, suggesting that when external debt burdens surpass the country's repayment capacity, they deter investment and economic productivity.

5.2 Conclusion

This study examines the impact of external debt service, debt servicing costs, and exchange rate volatility on Nigeria's economic performance from 1981 to 2024 using an ARDL and VECM approach. Anchored on the Neoclassical Growth Theory and Debt Overhang Theory, the research explored how external financial obligations interact with macroeconomic outcomes in a developing economy. The findings reveal that External debt servicing was found to exert a negative impact on real GDP, although not statistically significant in the short run. Exchange rate fluctuations exhibited a dual effect: immediate depreciation had a negative impact on economic performance, while a lagged effect showed positive significance, suggesting that currency depreciation might stimulate the economy after some delay. Debt servicing costs were negatively related to economic growth but remained statistically insignificant. The existence of a cointegrating relationship among the variables validates the long-held view that external borrowing and associated obligations have enduring impacts on Nigeria's economic growth. The slow error correction adjustment highlights the gradual nature of economic recovery from debt-induced imbalances, which is consistent with the Debt Overhang Theory's proposition that large debt burdens depress investment and growth.

Moreover, the diagnostic tests confirm that the estimated model is robust, well-specified, and statistically sound, supporting the reliability of the results. This strengthens the argument that policy measures addressing external debt management and exchange rate stability are vital for sustainable growth. The results also align with empirical studies such as those by Ijoko et al. (2022) and Agbeyinka (2024), which emphasized the detrimental effect of large external debt obligations on Nigeria's macroeconomic stability. At the same time, the Neoclassical Growth Theory's optimism about debt financing for productive investment appears less applicable to Nigeria's current context, where inefficiencies in the use of borrowed funds undermine potential growth benefits.

5.3 Policy Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several policy recommendations are proposed to enhance Nigeria's economic performance in the face of rising external debt obligations and exchange rate volatility.

Firstly, the government must strengthen external debt management by channeling

borrowed funds into productive sectors such as infrastructure, manufacturing, agriculture, and education to generate revenues capable of servicing the debt. Emphasis should be placed on concessional loans with favorable interest rates and longer repayment terms, under a stringent borrowing framework.

Secondly, transparency and accountability in debt management should be enhanced. This involves publishing debt terms and utilization details, alongside establishing independent debt audit bodies to ensure prudent public debt practices.

Thirdly, to address exchange rate instability, the Central Bank of Nigeria must coordinate sound monetary and fiscal policies. Export diversification beyond crude oil towards manufacturing, agriculture, and services will bolster foreign exchange inflows and cushion external shocks.

Fourthly, domestic revenue mobilization must be prioritized. Broadening the tax base, enhancing tax administration, and curbing financial leakages will reduce dependence on external borrowing.

Lastly, the government should monitor debt service ratios in fiscal planning. Capping debt service-to-revenue ratios will preserve development spending. Institutional reforms like enforcing fiscal discipline and adopting fiscal rules such as debt ceilings are essential for sustainable macroeconomic stability, aligning with the debt overhang theory and empirical findings.

REFERENCES:

- Adesola, W. A. (2019). Debt Servicing and Economic Growth in Nigeria: An Empirical Investigation. *Global Journal of Social Sciences*, 18(1), 1–10.
- Agbeyinka, I.Y (2024). *Impact of external debt on economic growth in Nigeria*: Gusau Journal of Accounting and Finance, Vol. 5, Issue 2, October, 2024 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.57233/gujaf.v5i2.15>
- Barro, R. J. (1990). Government Spending in a Simple Model of Endogenous Growth. *Journal of Political Economy*, 98(5), S103–S125.
- Central Bank of Nigeria. (2019). Annual Statistical Bulletin. Abuja: CBN.
- Debt Management Office (DMO). (2017). Debt Management Office Report 2017. Abuja: Federal Government of Nigeria.
- Debt Management Office (DMO). (2019). Public Debt Statistics Report. Abuja: Federal Government of Nigeria.
- Debt Management Office (DMO). (2023). Nigeria's Public Debt Profile as at December 2022. Abuja: Federal Government of Nigeria.
- Ijoko, A.O, Chimah, C.C, Muhammad, A.A, Mohammed, H & Abbati, I.A (2023). Impact of External Debts on Economic Growth in Nigeria *International Journal of*

- Economics & Development Policy (IJEDP), Vol. 6, No. 2 – Pg. 145 - 160
- Iyoha, M. A. (1999). External Debt and Economic Growth in Sub-Saharan African Countries: An Econometric Study. African Economic Research Consortium (AERC) Research Paper No. 90.
- Jacob, M. O., & Sule, A. T. (2022). *Debt overhang and economic growth in Nigeria: Re-evaluating the causal linkages*. Nigerian Journal of Economic and Financial Research, 5(3), 75–92.
- Krugman, P. R. (1988). Financing versus Forgiving a Debt Overhang. Journal of Development Economics, 29(3), 253–268.
- Nigeria Bureau of Statistics. (2021). Statistical Report on Nigeria's Debt Profile. Abuja: NBS.
- Ogbeifuna, M.I. (2017). The Politics of External Debt Relief: Nigeria's Unique Experience. African Journal of Stability and Development, 1(1).
- Paul, E. U. (2017). Exchange rate fluctuations and their impact on Nigeria's economic growth. Journal of Monetary and Fiscal Policy Studies, 7(2), 89–105.
- Sachs, J. D. (1989). The Debt Overhang of Developing Countries. In G. Calvo et al. (Eds.), Debt, Stabilization and Development: Essays in Memory of Carlos Diaz Alejandro. Oxford: Basil Blackwell.
- Solow, R. M. (1956). A Contribution to the Theory of Economic Growth. Quarterly Journal of Economics, 70(1), 65–94. Trading Economics. (2021). Nigeria External Debt Statistics 2018–2019. Retrieved from <https://tradingeconomics.com>
- Usim, I. (2018). The Burden of Nigeria's Rising External Debt. Business Day Nigeria.
- Usman, O. A., & Adejare, A. T. (2012). The Impact of External Debt on Economic Growth in Nigeria. International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Reviews, 3(4), 73–91.
- Utomi, P. (2019). Public debt dynamics and sustainable economic development in Nigeria. African Review of Economics and Finance, 12(4), 76–95.
- Uzochukwu Ojelubechukwu Fortune (2021), Impact of External Debt on Economic Growth in Nigeria. African Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development 4(3), 72-84. DOI: 10.52589/AJESD-MZSO1NP8.
- Yerima, A. U., & Tahir, H.M. (2020). The Impact of External Debt on Agricultural Production in Nigeria (1980-2016): Autoregressive Distributed Lag Modelling. CBN Bullion, 44, 2.
- Yunus, H. S. (2020). Exchange Rate Volatility and Debt Servicing in Nigeria: Evidence

from ARDL Approach. *Journal of Economics and Financial Analysis*, 4(1), 24–38.

Yusuf, A. & Mohammed S. (2021). The Impact of Government Debt on Economic Growth in Nigeria. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2021.1946249>

HEALTH AND HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA: DOES INSURANCE STATUS MATTER?

By

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ABSTRACT

Improved health and well-being are fundamental in addressing Nigeria's worker productivity and human capital development. Developing human capital is one factor that propels an economy towards prosperity. This work inquired into the influence of health insurance on healthcare demand among civil servants in Nigeria. Using descriptive survey design and logistic regression analysis, the author employed cross-sectional data obtained primarily from civil servants. The findings show that Health insurance significantly influences the demand for healthcare services (OR =2.39, p-value = 0.000, C.I 1.56 – 3.67) ceteris paribus. A one-unit rise in educational attainment increases the odds of healthcare utilization by an (OR of 1.41, p-value 0.040, C.I 1.01 – 1.96), holding the other variables constant. Furthermore, other individuals' socioeconomic characteristics reveal varying influences on healthcare demand among civil servants, which has long-term outcomes on health, productivity, and human capital development. Given these findings, the vital decision that can be deduced from the work is that improving and expanding health insurance coverage among civil servants is the most effective route to improved health outcomes, worker productivity, and human capital development in Nigeria.

Keywords: Healthcare Demand, Health Insurance, Human Capital Development, Nigeria.

1 Introduction

Providing quality healthcare services is crucial for a nation's overall development and its population's well-being. A robust healthcare system not only improves the health outcomes of individuals but also plays a significant role in fostering human capital development. Access to qualitative and affordable healthcare has remained a global issue of concern. Nigeria's main focus recently has been achieving continued socioeconomic growth and development, which aligns with sustainable development goals (SDGs), thus, the need to develop human capital.

Human Capital relates to the inventory of skills, knowledge, ideas, talent, personalities, attributes, and health status embodied in persons, easing their ability to execute labor to produce individual, economic, and communal value (OECD, 2012). In its 58th World Health Assembly in 2005, the World Health Organization (WHO) advocated social health

insurance as a crucial factor in realizing equitable and affordable services through the mobilization of additional resources and improved access to healthcare for the citizens.

The demand for healthcare arises from the desire for good health; being healthy is everyone's preference. The quality and quantity of healthcare services an individual is willing to acquire depends on the prices of services, the demographic characteristics of the individual, and several other factors that describe the individual, providers, and the overall environment. Healthcare is a complex system involving the inputs of various professionals (general practitioners, specialists, nurses, pharmacists) and procedures (laboratory analyses, emergency services). The diverse services and products in the healthcare system make the concept of need-based demand, which refers to the appropriate demand related to a healthcare need. When an individual faces illness or injury, the demand for healthcare services in such a situation becomes a complex and multidimensional process. With health insurance, the actual price of healthcare (an essential determinant of demand) may be much lower than the cost of providing care.

Health insurance is a system of raising funds through planned prepayment schemes and is an efficient and equitable base for improving the population's healthcare needs. The creation or extension of national or social health insurance, which allows healthcare services to be paid for from a contributory scheme, guarantees that no individual requiring preventive or curative healthcare services faces hardships. Health insurance schemes rather than out-of-pocket expenditure (OOPE) at service delivery points could increase healthcare services utilization and, thus, improve the health and well-being of civil servants and their families. The government of Nigeria, recognizing the problems posed by low-income levels, particularly its effects of reducing healthcare demand and utilization, established the NHIS as a corporate body in 1999 by Decree 35 of 1999 (now cited as NHIS Act Cap 42 LFN, 2004).

The NHIS became operational in 2005 and is mandated to strengthen the health system to deliver practical, affordable, and efficient services at all levels without financial hardship and achieve better health outcomes (NHIS, 2020). The authorization of the NHIS is to prepare social health insurance for Nigerians, ensure Nigerians have access to qualitative and affordable healthcare, and coordinate and guide all partners of the scheme, including providers of private health insurance. Few studies have studied the implementation of NHIS since its inception. However, there has been little or no systematic empirical evaluation of the interrelationship between health insurance and healthcare demand among civil servants. This study explores how insurance status affects the demand and utilization of healthcare services among civil servants in Nigeria.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Healthcare Demand

Demand for healthcare is described by the actual utilization of a person in a situation of disease or trauma; this utilization could vary in conformity with demand factors such as income, educational level, cost of services, tradition, social norms, and the standard of services provided. The demand for health care is determined by the balance between perceived health benefits and the cost of accessing care. Health literacy, demographic characteristics, distance from providers, and health status influence the perceived benefits and costs. Age, education, and income are some factors that affect the perceived health gains from care, while prices, waiting times, and travel costs determine the cost

of accessing care. The demand for healthcare is subject to the law of demand, just like any other market. As the price of healthcare increases, people tend to demand less of it. Demand for healthcare is also relatively inelastic, meaning people will purchase healthcare services at almost any price if they require care.

2.2 Human Capital Development

Human capital refers to the knowledge, skills, and experience that make an individual more productive and earn a higher income over a lifetime. It pertains to the reservoir of knowledge, abilities, and other human attributes possessed by individuals that contribute to their level of productivity; it connotes the intrinsic productive capacities of human beings. Social scientists employ this terminology when alluding to the monetary value of an employee's knowledge and competencies. In contemporary literature, costs, income, education, and health are assessed as a foundation for quantifying human capital. Following the human capital hypothesis, substantial investment in individuals will result in economic advancement (Becker, 2015). Investing in health not only directly impacts the well-being of individuals but also affects their productivity at work.

2.3 The Human Capital Model of the Demand for Health

The human capital model of the demand for health provides the theoretical framework that examines the demand for health as a commodity produced by the inputs of market goods such as healthcare and time spent on health-improving efforts such as exercise and distinguishes it from medical care. In this opinion, health is viewed as an investment and consumption good where, ultimately, the demand for healthcare is derived from the demand for improved health. An individual can choose an affordable amount of healthcare and other goods and services based on his/her budget constraints and preferences. It heavily relies on human capital theory, which posits that an increase in an individual's stock of knowledge or human capital enhances their productivity in both the market and nonmarket sectors of the economy. The human capital model, developed by Grossman in 1972, argues that health capital differs from other forms of human capital due to its influence on an individual's total time allocation towards money, earnings, and commodities. The demand for medical care and other health inputs is derived from the fundamental demand for health.

Groot, Abajobir, Wainaina, Sidze, Pradhan, and Janssens (2023) conducted a study employing a cluster-randomized controlled trial (cluster-RCT) design. This study occurred between 2019 and 2021 in 24 villages in Kakamega County. The primary focus of their research was to evaluate the impact of a subsidized health insurance program, which utilized mobile phones, on low-income women and their families in Western Kenya. The study discovered that the program had a weak yet positive impact on the utilization of formal healthcare, indicating a slight increase in the use of formal healthcare services. The results were most notable for women, young children, and individuals residing near the clinics. However, the study's limited scope and specific target population in Kenya make it challenging to generalize these findings to the broader context of health insurance and its impact on healthcare demand among civil servants in Nigeria.

In a comprehensive investigation and systematic analysis of research studies that assessed the influence of community-based health insurance (CBHI) initiatives on healthcare utilization and mitigation of financial risk in low- and middle-income countries (LMIC),

Eze, Ilechukwu and Lawani (2023) conducted a meta-analysis. The authors determined that CBHI schemes in LMIC significantly enhanced healthcare utilization, specifically in outpatient services, in 24 out of 43 studies. Insured households demonstrated increased odds of utilizing healthcare services, outpatient health services, and health facility delivery, although there was a negligible rise in inpatient hospitalization. However, the variations in healthcare systems and population dynamics necessitate caution when directly applying these results to the Nigerian setting.

Using data from demographic and health surveys conducted in 28 countries in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), a cross-sectional study conducted by Amu, Aboagye, Dowou, Kongnyuy, Adoma, Memiah, and Bain (2022) employed bivariable and multivariable analyses, which included the χ^2 test and multilevel binary logistic regression, to examine the association between health insurance coverage and the utilization of maternal healthcare. The study revealed that women who had health insurance were more inclined to utilize ANC (adjusted odds ratio [AOR]=1.48, 95% confidence interval [CI] 1.41 to 1.54), SBA (AOR=1.37, 95% CI 1.30 to 1.45), and PNC (AOR=1.42, 95% CI 1.37 to 1.48). It suggests that health insurance coverage played a significant role in predicting maternal healthcare utilization in the study. However, it is essential to account for the distinctive attributes of the Nigerian healthcare system and population dynamics.

A parallel study conducted by Aboagye, Okyere, Ahinkorah, Seidu, Betregiorgis, Amu, and Yaya in the year 2022 employed secondary data derived from Demographic and Health Surveys carried out between 2015 and 2020 in sixteen countries located in sub-Saharan Africa. The study encompassed 113,918 women aged between 15 and 49 years. The researchers employed a multilevel binary logistic regression analysis to ascertain the correlation between health insurance coverage and the promptness of antenatal care (ANC) attendance. The multilevel binary logistic regression analysis demonstrated a positive association between health insurance coverage and timely ANC attendance, indicating that women covered by health insurance were more inclined to seek ANC promptly when compared to those without health insurance coverage (adjusted odds ratio = 1.21, 95% confidence interval = 1.11-1.31). These findings suggest that having health insurance coverage is linked to an increased likelihood of seeking ANC promptly. When applying these findings to health insurance in Nigeria and its consequences for healthcare demand among civil servants, it is clear that a broader contextual analysis is required.

Using data collected from the 2018 Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey, Imo, Wet-Billings, and Isiugo-Abanihe (2022) conducted a comprehensive analysis to investigate the impact of maternal health insurance coverage and adequate healthcare services utilization on the risk of under-five mortality. The findings of the study revealed that 14.3% of the sampled birth histories of childbearing women in Nigeria resulted in under-five deaths. Maternal health insurance coverage was identified as a protective factor against the risk of under-five mortality, with children of mothers who had health insurance experiencing significantly lower rates of under-five death. Furthermore, adequate healthcare services utilization was also found to be a protective factor, as children whose mothers utilized sufficient healthcare services demonstrated a significantly reduced risk of under-five death. However, it is crucial to critique the study's limited scope, particularly regarding the complex interplay of factors affecting healthcare demand among civil servants in

Nigeria.

Utilizing a difference-in-difference model, Ekhaton-Mobayode, Gajanan, and Ekhaton (2022) conducted an empirical investigation to assess the impact of health insurance on child health and healthcare utilization in Nigeria. This investigation involved comparing the changes in health outcomes and healthcare utilization for two groups of children: those eligible for health insurance through the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) and those not eligible. The study specifically focused on examining the effects of health insurance on birth weight and the likelihood of children receiving polio and diphtheria vaccines. The results of the study indicate that health insurance through the NHIS has a positive impact on child health outcomes in Nigeria. Specifically, it increases birth weight and improves the likelihood of children receiving polio and diphtheria vaccines. However, the research does not delve into potential disparities across socioeconomic groups or regions, limiting its applicability.

Drawing on data from the most recent National Demographic and Health Survey conducted in Nigeria, Ahuru, Daniel, and Efegebe (2021) researched the impact of health insurance enrollment on maternal and childcare utilization in Nigeria. The analytical approach encompassed both descriptive and predictive methodologies. The research utilized a representative sample of 33,715 women who had given birth within the preceding five years, as reported in the survey. The results revealed that enrolling in health insurance significantly increased the likelihood of women attending at least four antenatal care (ANC) visits and delivering their babies in healthcare facilities. Furthermore, the study underscored the significance of education, as women with formal education were more inclined to undergo a minimum of four ANC visits, deliver their babies in healthcare facilities, and fully immunize their children. However, the research adopts a static perspective, focusing on associations without considering the evolving and dynamic nature of health insurance's influence on healthcare demand among civil servants.

3 Methodology

Data was collected primarily using structured questionnaires to generate information on the healthcare experiences of civil servants (study population) and their attitudes towards health insurance in Nigeria. The data contains demographic information, health awareness, income levels, insurance status, and utilization of various healthcare services, intending to provide insights into healthcare demand, affordability, and satisfaction among the respondents. The study population is individuals employed in government departments (federal, state, and local government). In Nigeria, health insurance coverage is predominant among formal sector employees; thus, they are the ideal target of a study on the influence of health insurance on healthcare demand. This empirical study aims to determine whether having health insurance makes civil servants demand more healthcare services.

The study adopted a nonprobability sampling technique, precisely the snowball sampling technique. In this approach, civil servants were located by the researcher at their workplaces (such as educational institutions, health facilities, federal, state, and local government secretariats). They were asked to encourage their colleagues to participate in the study. The method was adopted because it allows for in-depth exploration of social networks, is

time efficient, cost-effective, and has the advantage of recruiting many civil servants in the study. The sample size was determined using The Research Advisors (2006) table available at (<http://research-advisors.com>), constructed with a 95% confidence interval and a 5% margin of error. The current case indicates that the probability that a household demands healthcare is a non-linear function of the explanatory variables. Thus, the healthcare demand equation in its simple form is given by;

$$\ln DHC_i = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 IS_i + \gamma_3 Age_i + \gamma_4 Gen_i + \gamma_5 Edu_i + \gamma_6 FS_i + \gamma_7 HA_i + \gamma_8 HS + \gamma_9 IL + \epsilon_i$$

----- 3.1 Where;

Where π_i is the likelihood described in equation 3.2, and x is a vector of covariates as defined earlier. Thus, we can write;

$$DHC_i = \ln \left[\frac{\pi_i}{1 - \pi_i} \right] = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 IS_i + \gamma_3 Age_i + \gamma_4 Gen_i + \gamma_5 Edu_i + \gamma_6 FS_i + \gamma_7 HA_i + \gamma_8 HS + \gamma_9 IL + \epsilon_i$$

----- 3.2

These variables, used in achieving this study's objective, were carefully selected based on their theoretical and empirical underpinning regarding the relationship between health insurance and healthcare demand. On a priori, health insurance membership should increase healthcare utilization (Ekhatior-Mobayode et al., 2022; Aboagye, 2022; Ahuru et al., 2021).

4 Analysis, Interpretation, and Discussion

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

In an attempt to analyze the impact of health insurance on healthcare demand and human capital development among civil servants in Nigeria, descriptive statistics were employed using STATA 15 to determine the demographic characteristics of participants, which is essential for further specific analyses.

As shown in Table 4.1, the result reveals that the number of participants is 918, the mean age group is 36 to 45 years, and males participated more than females. On average, the respondents have post-secondary education. On average, the respondents are married, have a family size of 1 to 5 members, have two children less than 12 years old, and have one household member older than 60 years in the household. Table 4.1 presents the descriptive statistics.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistic on Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variables	Obs.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Age	918	2.02	0.95	0	4
Gender	918	0.36	0.48	0	4
Educational Attainment	918	1.46	0.55	0	2
Employment Type	918	0.85	0.77	0	2
Years in service	918	0.83	0.98	0	4
Marital Status	918	0.91	0.43	0	3

Family Size	918	0.43	0.62	0	2
Number of children less than 12 years in a household	918	2.49	1.97	0	13
Number of older adults above 60 in household	918	1.11	1.51	0	12
Region	918	0.14	1.34	0	5
Level of health awareness	918	0.63	0.57	0	2
Health status	918	0.76	0.55	0	3
Income level	918	1.19	0.46	0	2

Source: Author Computation using STATA 15 (2024)

Along with the descriptive statistics, the logistic regression analysis is required to determine the influence of health insurance on healthcare utilization among civil servants. The dependent variables are healthcare demand (DHC), preventive healthcare utilization (PHU), and curative healthcare utilization (CHU); they are dichotomous variables taking the form 1 if the respondent sought or demanded the services and 0 if otherwise. DHC is the healthcare demand model, which was disaggregated into PHU and CHU to distinguish between respondents who sought services like medical check-ups to improve their health status and those who were sick and received prescribed drugs for the past twelve months preceding the survey. This distinction is essential because individuals with health insurance coverage are expected to utilize PHU frequently for health improvement.

The predictor variables are Insurance status (I.S.), which represents civil servants without insurance coverage versus those with any form of health insurance (NHIS, State health insurance, private health insurance, or community-based health insurance), and the respondents' demographic characteristics as defined earlier. Table 4.2 presents the description of the binary dependent variables used in the study and their coding.

Table 4.2: Description of Response Variables in the Logit Model and their coding

Variables	Description	Questions asked in the survey	Coding
Healthcare Demand (DHC)	If respondents utilized or sought healthcare: Yes = 1, No = 0	For the past twelve months, which formal healthcare did you or your family use?	1 = Preventive Healthcare Services 1 = Curative Healthcare Services 0 = None

Preventive Healthcare Utilization (PHU)	If the respondent had a medical check-up, e.g., blood pressure or blood sugar examination in the past 12 months	For the past twelve months, which formal healthcare did you or your family use?	1 = Preventive Healthcare Services 0 = Curative Healthcare Services 0 = None
	1 = Yes		
	0 = No		
Curative Healthcare Utilization (CHU)	If there was a visit to a doctor or received prescribed drugs in the last 12 months	For the past twelve months, which formal healthcare did you or your family use?	0 = Preventive Healthcare Services 1 = Curative Healthcare Services 0 = None
	1 = Yes		
	0 = No		

Source: Author Computation (2024)

Responses obtained for the above variables are presented in Table 4.3. Results reveal that 718 respondents (85%) demanded healthcare services (DHC) while 137 (14.92%) did not. For insurance status, 82.79%, i.e., 760 respondents, have health insurance coverage, while 17.21 %, i.e., 158 respondents do not. Predominantly, the respondents are in the medium level of income, with 690 (75.16%), 25 (2.72%) are in the high-income level, and 203 (22.11%) are from the low-income level. On the status of health, participants with a self-perceived level of good health, 594 (64.71%), 273 (29.74%) perceived their health status as excellent, 49 respondents (5.34%) had fair health status, and only 2 of them have poor health status.

Table 4.3: Distribution of responses about the dependent and explanatory variables

Variables	Description	Frequency	%	Cum
DHC	Did not utilize	137	14.92	14.92
	Utilized	781	85.00	100.00
PHU	Did not utilize	518	56.43	56.43
	Utilized	400	43.57	100.00

CHU	Did not utilize	537	58.50	58.50
	Utilized	381	41.50	100.00
IS	No insurance	158	17.21	17.21
	Has insurance	760	82.79	100.00
Gender	Male	585	63.73	63.73
	Female	333	36.27	100.00
Education	Secondary	24	2.61	2.61
	Graduate	447	48.69	51.31
	Postgraduate	447	48.69	100.00
Level of Income	High	25	2.72	2.72
	Medium	690	75.16	77.89
	Low	203	22.11	100.00
Status of Health	Excellent	273	29.74	29.74
	Good	594	64.71	94.44
	Fair	49	5.34	99.78
	Poor	2	0.22	100.00

Source: Author Computation (2024)

Apart from these findings, responses were also obtained regarding affordability and satisfaction with the services received, Table 4.4 presents the results.

Table 4.4: Opinion of respondents regarding affordability and satisfaction

	Question	Options	Freq.	%
Q8	For the past 12 months, which formal health care service did you or any of your family use?	Preventive healthcare services	400	43.57
		Curative healthcare services	381	41.50
		None	137	14.92
		Total	918	100

Q9	How were payments made for most of the services received?	Through health insurance	214	27.40
		Out-of-pocket	189	24.20
		Insurance and Out-of-pocket	364	46.61
		Borrowed money or sold property	14	1.79
		Total	781	100
Q10	On average, how much was paid for the preventive care received?	Less than 30,000 Naira	334	43.21
		More than 30,000 Naira	116	15.01
		Free/ Zero cost	136	17.59
		Cannot Remember	187	24.19
		Total	773	100
Q11	On the average, how much was paid for the curative care services received?	Less than 30,000 Naira	351	45.35
		More than 30,000 Naira	155	20.03
		Free/ Zero cost	93	12.02
		Cannot Remember	175	22.61
		Total	774	100
Q12	Were you satisfied with the quality of services received?	Yes	526	67.26
		No	183	23.40
		Undecided	73	9.34
		Total	782	100

Source: Author Computation with STATA 15 (2024)

Results from Table 4.4 reveal that for the past 12 months preceding the survey, 400 participants (43.57%) have utilized preventive healthcare services, 381 (41.50%) have utilized curative healthcare services, and 137 (14.92%) did not utilize any of the services. For those who utilized the services, 214 (27.40%) paid for the services through health insurance, 189 (24.20%) paid out-of-pocket, 364 (46.61%) paid through health insurance and out-of-pocket, while 14 respondents (1.79%) borrowed money or sold their property to pay for the healthcare services. On how much was paid for PHU, more than half of the

respondents paid less than 30,000 naira (334 with 43.21%), 116 (15.01%) paid more than 30,000 naira, 136 (17.59%) obtained the services free, i.e., zero cost, while 187 (24.19%) cannot remember how payment was made. For CHU, more than half of the respondents paid less than 30,000 naira (351 with 45.35%), 155 (12.02%) paid more than 30,000 naira, 175 (22.61%) obtained the services free, i.e., zero cost, while 175 (22.61%) cannot remember how payment was made. The majority of the participants, 526 (67.26%), were satisfied with the quality of services received, 183 (23.40%) were not satisfied, and 73 (9.34%) of them were undecided.

In analyzing the influence of health insurance on healthcare demand, logistic regression analysis was used, and Table 4.5 presents the results. In model 1, insurance status (I.S.) and educational attainment exhibit a positive sign of the coefficient, indicating a positive relationship between the dependent and explanatory variables. For I.S., insurance coverage increases the odds of healthcare demand (utilization) by the odds ratio (OR) of 2.39, given that the other variables in the model are fixed, and the p-value of 0.000 indicates a statistically significant relationship. In addition, the researcher is 95% confident that the actual OR lies between 1.559 (lower bound) and 3.671 (upper bound) of the confidence intervals (CI). For educational attainment, a one-unit increase in educational level increases the odds of healthcare demand (utilization) by an OR of 1.41, holding the other variable constant. The p-value of 0.040 and the narrow interval between the lower and upper bound (1.01 – 1.96) CI indicates a statistically significant relationship. In model 2, the findings are consistent, with the level of health awareness showing a statistically significant relationship given the p-value of 0.061. For model three, all the regressors have positive signs attached to the parameters. The status of health and income level revealed a non-statistically significant relationship given the p-values of 0.87 and 0.121, respectively.

Table 4.5: Logistic regression results of the influence of health insurance and healthcare demand (DHC) as regressand

Variables	Demand for Healthcare (DHC) of Participants		
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Predictors			
IS	0.000*	0.001*	0.000*
	(2.392)	(2.109)	(2.388)
Age	0.167		
	(0.873)		
Gender	0.534		
	(1.131)		

Education	0.040*	0.054*	0.035*
	(1.414)	(1.386)	(1.432)
Level Health Awareness		0.061**	
		(0.713)	
Health Status		0.876	
		(1.029)	
Income Level		0.121	
		(0.729)	
Family Size			0.173
			(1.241)
Number of Children < 12 years			0.818
			(0.989)
Number of older adults			0.108
			(1.119)
Constant	0.029*	0.003*	0.292
	(2.213)	(3.582)	(1.442)
Model fit indices			
-2 Log Likelihood	-377.167	-374.636	-375.937
Prob > chi2	0.0007	0.0002	0.0006
Pseudo R²	0.025	0.0315	0.0282

Odd Ratios in (), *, and ** indicate the tests are significant at 5% and 10% probability levels.

The overall model (with DCH as the dependent variable) was subdivided into PHU and CHU to examine further the influence of health insurance on the likelihood of PHU or CHU among the respondents. Table 4.6 presents the result of the logistic regression analysis using PHU as the dependent variable. The result reveals the influence of health insurance on PHU among respondents. In model 1, health insurance and educational attainment do not influence the likelihood of PHU, given the p-values of 0.672 and 0.860,

respectively. In model 2, age and gender, on the other hand, were significant predictors of PHU with p-values of 0.000 and 0.051, respectively. The implication is that a unit increase in age increases the likelihood of PHU with the OR of 0.598, and females are more inclined to seek PHU than males (*ceteris paribus*). In model 3, along with age and gender, the number of older adults in a household influences the likelihood of PHU with a p-value of 0.004. The higher the number of older adults in a household, the higher the likelihood of PHU holding all other factors fixed.

Table 4.6: Logistic regression results of the influence of health insurance and healthcare demand (PHU) as regressand

Variables	Preventive Healthcare Demand /Utilization (PHU) of Participants		
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Predictors			
IS	0.672 (1.080)		
Age	0.000* (0.598)	0.000* (0.609)	0.000* (0.636)
Gender	0.051* (0.755)	0.039* (0.742)	0.106 (0.787)
Education	0.860 (0.978)		
Level of Health Awareness		0.541 (1.085)	
Health Status		0.033* (0.743)	0.045* (0.755)
Income Level		0.586 (0.919)	
Family Size			0.713 (1.041)
Number of Children < 12 years			0.190 (1.049)

Number of older adults			0.004*
			(1.151)
Constant	0.004*	0.000*	0.017*
	(2.293)	(3.021)	(2.055)
Model fit indices			
-2 Log Likelihood	-602.990	-600.455	-594.645
Prob > chi2	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Pseudo R²	0.0409	0.0449	0.0542

Odd Ratios in (), *, and ** indicate the tests are significant at 5% and 10% probability levels.

CHU is sought in the event of illness or an emergency, wherein the respondent must go on prescribed medication or hospital admission to restore normal health. Table 4.7 presents the results of CHU by respondents. The result reveals the influence of health insurance on CHU among respondents. As previously, three models were explored by the author to determine the influence of health insurance on CHU by the respondents. In all the models, IS was a consistent predictor with an OR of approximately 2.0, signifying a significant effect, and the p-values of 0.01 indicate a statistically significant relationship. Age also exhibited a persistent effect on CHU with a magnitude of approximately 2.0 and p-values of 0.000 across the models. Higher educational attainment and better self-perceived health status are positively associated with CHU. Gender is also positively associated with CHU, with females having a higher likelihood than males. Other factors, such as health awareness, income level, family size, and number of older adults or children in a household, also shape CHU. However, their effects are less consistent across the models.

Table 4.7: Logistic regression results of the influence of health insurance and healthcare demand (CHU) as regressand

Demand for Curative Healthcare (CHU) of Participants				
Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	

IS	0.010*	0.013*	0.011*
	(1.652)	(1.624)	(1.647)
Age	0.000*	0.000*	0.000*
	(1.568)	(1.536)	(1.493)
Gender	0.016*	0.018*	0.034*
	(1.413)	(1.409)	(1.371)
Education	0.084**	0.083**	0.107
	(1.244)	(1.246)	(1.228)
Level Health Awareness		0.132	
		(1.225)	
Health Status		0.026*	0.102
		(0.733)	(0.811)
Income Level		0.425	
		(1.134)	
Family Size			0.539
			(1.071)
Number of Children < 12 years			0.246
			(0.957)
Number of older adults			0.051*
			(0.903)
Constant	0.000*	0.000*	0.012*
	(0.043)	(0.056)	(0.146)
Model fit indices			
-2 Log Likelihood	-595.469	-592.451	-590.943
Prob > chi2	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Pseudo R²	0.044	0.049	0.051

Odd Ratios in (), *, and ** indicate the tests are significant at 5% and 10% probability levels.

The study proves that health insurance significantly increases healthcare demand among Nigerian civil servants. The logistic regression results from Table 4.6 show that individuals with health insurance are 2.39 times more likely to utilize healthcare services than those

without insurance. This finding aligns with previous studies (Groot et al., 2023; Eze et al., 2023; Amu et al., 2022; Aboagye et al., 2022; Imo et al. 2022; Ahuru et al., 2021). However, when DHC was subdivided into PHU and CHU, it was clear that insurance coverage did not influence PHU among participants. Moreover, findings from the study reveal that higher educational attainment is positively associated with increased healthcare utilization. Across all models (Table 4.6, 4.7, and 4.8), individuals with higher educational levels show greater odds of utilizing healthcare services, with odds ratios ranging from 1.36 to 1.42. However, as seen in insurance status, educational attainment also did not influence PHU. While health insurance and education show consistent positive effects, other factors such as health awareness, health status, and income level demonstrate varying impacts across the models. This variability implies that healthcare demand is complex and influenced by several factors. It also suggests that while health insurance is a powerful tool, it is not the sole determinant of healthcare utilization.

This study's strong positive association between health insurance and healthcare utilization provides empirical support for policies that expand health insurance coverage. These findings imply that investing in broader health insurance coverage could be an effective strategy to increase healthcare utilization and, by extension, improve health outcomes and develop human capital.

5 Conclusion

The study investigated the impact of health insurance on healthcare demand and human capital development among civil servants in Nigeria. Findings reveal a positive and significant impact of health insurance on civil servants' healthcare demand. Specifically, insured and better-educated workers are more likely to utilize healthcare than uninsured individuals. By implication, expanding health insurance coverage among the population could increase healthcare utilization, affordability, and satisfaction, thus promoting well-being and healthy outcomes. Other factors that could influence demand for healthcare include self-perceived health status, level of health awareness, and income levels. Individuals with increased awareness and better-perceived health status are more inclined to seek PHU. Because of the consistent influence of health insurance (Eze et al. 2023, Groot et al. 2023, Amu et al. 2022, Ahuru et al. 2021) on utilization, affordability, and satisfaction with healthcare services, findings emphasize the relevance of insurance coverage in increasing economic and social circumstances among civil servants in Nigeria.

6 Recommendations

Investing in broader social health insurance coverage by the government could be an effective strategy to increase healthcare utilization and, by extension, health outcomes, productivity, and develop human capital. The government should also expand social health insurance schemes to cover most citizens, which could be essential to human capital development.

The government should sponsor public health campaigns to encourage civil servants to engage in preventive care, which is essential for long-term health outcomes and potentially reduces the healthcare system's burden. In addition, by identifying and managing health issues early or preventing them altogether, there is the potential to reduce overall healthcare costs and improve worker productivity.

REFERENCES

- Aboagye, R. G., Okyere, J., Ahinkorah, B. O., Seidu, A., Betregiorgis, Z., Amu, H., & Yaya, S. (2022). Health insurance coverage and timely antenatal care attendance in sub-Saharan Africa. *BMC Health Services Research*, 22(1) Doi: 10.1186/s12913-022-07601-6
- Ahuru, R. R., Daniel, O., & Efegbere, H. A. (2021). The influence of health insurance enrolment on maternal and childcare use in Nigeria. 3(1):82-90. Doi: 10.25082/SWSW.2021.01.001
- Akinremi, A. O., Coker, M. O., Dosunmu, A. O., Adeniregun, A. O., Edun, F. O., & Amusa, A. R. (2022). Civil Servant Preferences to Health Insurance Schemes: A Mixed Methodology Approach. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 9(10). 84-123
- Amu, H., Aboagye, R. G., Dowou, R. K., Kongnyuy, E. J., Adoma, P. O., Memiah, P., Elvis, Tarkang, E.E., & Bain, L. E. (2022). Towards achievement of Sustainable Development Goal 3: multilevel analyses of demographic and health survey data on health insurance coverage and maternal healthcare utilization in sub-Saharan Africa. *International Health*, 15(2):134-149. Doi: 10.1093/in health/ihac017
- Bleakley, H. (2010). Health, Human Capital, and Development: *Annu Rev Econom.* September; 2: 283–310. doi:10.1146/annurev.economics.102308.124436.
- Bloom, D., & Canning, D. (2003). Health as Human Capital and its Impact on Economic Performance: The Geneva Papers on Risk and Insurance Vol. 28 No. 2 (April 2003) 304–315
- Currie, J., & Madrian, B. C. (1999). Chapter 50 Health, health insurance and the labor market. *Handbook of Labor Economics*, 3309–3416. doi:10.1016/s1573-4463(99)30041-9
- Ekhaton-Mobayode, U. E., Gajanan, S. N., & Ekhaton, C. (2022). Does Health Insurance Eligibility Improve Child Health: Evidence from the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) in Nigeria. *Cureus*, 14 Doi: 10.7759/cureus.28660
- Eze, P., Ilechukwu, S., & Lawani, L. O. (2023) Impact of community-based health insurance in low- and middle-income countries: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLoS ONE* 18(6): e0287600. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0287600>
- Groot, R. D., Abajobir, A. A., Wainaina, C. W., Sidze, E. M., Pradhan, M. M., Janssens, W. (2023). The Impact of Digital Health Insurance for Low-Income Women in Kenya. medRxiv, Doi: 10.1101/2023.07.07.23292292
- Grossman, M. (2000). Chapter 7 The Human Capital Model. *Handbook of Health Economics*, 347–408. doi:10.1016/s1574-0064(00)80166-3

NHIS (2020). STRATEGIC PLAN 2020 – 2030 Financial Access to Quality Healthcare for All Nigerians.

Ilochonwu, N. A., & Adedigba, M. A. (2017). Awareness And Utilization of National Health Insurance Scheme by Healthcare Workers in Southwest Nigeria. 7(1):24-33. Doi: 10.4314/AJOH.V7I1.162233

Imo, C. K., Wet-Billings, N. D., Isiugo-Abanihe, U. C. (2022). The Impact of Maternal Health Insurance Coverage and Adequate Healthcare Services Utilization on the Risk of Under-Five Mortality in Nigeria: A Cross-Sectional Study. Archives Of Public Health, 80(1) Doi: 10.1186/s13690-022-00968-2

World Health Organization; (2022). World Health Statistics 2022: Monitoring Health for the SDGs, Sustainable Development Goals. Geneva: Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO.

Yoram, W. (2015). Gary Becker on Human Capital. Journal of Demographic Economics, 81, 2015, 27–31. Doi:10.1017/dem.2014.4

Zegeye, B., Idriss-Wheeler, D., Ahinkorah, B. O., Ameyaw, E. K., Seidu, A., Adjei, N. K., & Yaya, S. (2023). Association Between Women’s Household Decision-Making Autonomy and Health Insurance Enrollment in Sub-Saharan Africa. BMC Public Health, 23(1) Doi: 10.1186/s12889-023-15434-z

Zimmer, D. M. (2018). The Heterogeneous Impact of Insurance on Healthcare Demand among Young Adults: A Panel Data Analysis. Journal of Applied Statistics. 45(7), 1277–1291. doi:10.1080/02664763.2017.1369497

IMPACT OF EXCHANGE RATE VOLATILITY ON FOREIGN PRIVATE INVESTMENT AND DOMESTIC INVESTMENT IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This paper evaluates the impact of exchange rate volatility on foreign private investment and domestic investment in Nigeria from 1980 to 2025. Exchange rate volatility was generated using the exponential generalized autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity (EGARCH) model, while Pair-Wise Granger causality is applied as an estimation technique, the data analysis's findings showed a strong and positive impact between market capitalization, money liquidity, and foreign private investment. However, FPTI is negatively and highly impacted with the degree of openness, interest rate, and exchange rate. On the other hand, exchange rate and gross domestic product are positively and statistically significant with domestic investment, while interest rate and inflation rate are negative and statistically significant related with domestic investment in Nigeria. According to the Granger causality test results, there is a unidirectional causal relationship between the exchange rate and both domestic and foreign private investment in Nigeria. Thus, the study comes to the conclusion that, Nigeria has exchange rate volatility, which has a substantial impact on foreign private investment and multiplies the impact on domestic investment. Accordingly, Nigeria's deposit money banks should be required to regulate the distribution and allocation of foreign currency and Naira notes, as well as the fluctuating exchange rate. This is because the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) should continue to establish effective exchange rate management.

Keywords: Exchange Rate Volatility, Foreign Private Investment, Domestic Investment and Economic Growth.

The instability and continuous swings in the value of the naira in the foreign currency market are referred to as exchange rate volatility in Nigeria (Udeh and Edeh, 2020), and they have an effect on both local and foreign private investment. Furthermore, Nkemdilim and Azuka (2021) state that currency rate volatility poses a danger to investors and that it is a factor that, reduces investment and trade volume, especially in Nigeria and other less developed countries (Tejvan, 2019; Nadine et al., 2021). Therefore, currency depreciation increases foreign private investment (FPTI) influx into the host country, but host currency appreciation decreases it (Tejvan, 2019, Osinubi & Amaghionyeodiwe, 2020, and Omorokunwas & Ikponmwosa, 2021).

In recognition of its status as an emerging economy, Nigeria urgently requires foreign capital inflows to increase domestic investment in order to complete development projects for the benefit of its inhabitants and achieve rapid economic growth simultaneously

(Okonkwo 2019 & Ogundipe et al.). It is widely acknowledged that, domestic investment cannot produce the desired outcomes on its own. However, in most economies, domestic investment has not been sufficient to provide the necessary demand to enable the economy to meet the growth target due to the mismatch between their capital requirements and saving capacity (Etale & Sawyerr, 2020). Accordingly, foreign private investment strengthens domestic resources, enabling the country to carry out effective development projects that would support economic growth and development (Dahunsi, 2021).

Thus, exchange rate volatility's impact on both domestic and foreign private investment differed. A number of studies were therefore carried out, such as Ifuero and Nosakhare's (2018), Ihensekhien's (2019), and Idehen et al.'s (2020) study, which concentrate on the impact of exchange rate volatility on foreign private investment without accounting for host country investment, however, the studies of Bernard and Sin-Yu (2017), Bilge and Gozde (2018), Udeh and Edeh (2020), Nkemdilim and Azuka (2021), and Joel and Jeffrey (2023) were examined the impact of exchange rate instability on domestic investment in Nigeria without taking cognizant of foreign private investment.

The majority of earlier studies focused on distinct reactions, either foreign private investment only or domestic investment only, without taking into accounts the shocks leaving between the foreign private investment (FPTI) and domestic investment (DI) simultaneously. As a result, this study examines the composition of external and internal investments in order to determine the transfiguration reaction of the both findings. Therefore, the need for this study is for the fact that frequent fluctuation of exchange rate for the past four decades is an area of concern in Nigeria, because it credited to the fact that Nigeria's main foreign earnings were from crude oil.

In considering this, the objective of this study is to examine how exchange rate volatility impacts FPTI and DI in Nigeria and to investigate the relationship between exchange rate volatility and these two metrics. This introduction was one of five sections that made up the framework of this study in order to accomplish these goals. Section 2: Empirical literature and theoretical framework. The study's methodology is described in Section 3. The results are interpreted and analyzed in Section 4, and the work is summarized and concluded in Section 5.

2.1 Theoretical Framework and Empirical Review

This study analyzed a variety of theoretical hypotheses that have connected exchange rate volatility, foreign private investment, and investment development in Nigeria. This led to a review of the Risk Aversion Theory and the empirical literature on the relevant variables of the study.

2.1.1 Risk Aversion Theory

Kolstad and Goldberg (1995) popularized the theory. The argument suggests that while increased exchange rate volatility lowers the certainty equivalent predicted exchange rate, lower exchange rate volatility led to a decline in investment. The firm uses the certainty equivalent level in its expected profit function to decide which investments to make in order to turn a profit later on. Both domestic and foreign private investment are involved, and when the currency rate becomes more volatile, businesses will put off making an

investment because they are more worried about their anticipated future profits.

On the basis of this theoretical argument, several empirical investigations have been proposed to determine how exchange rate volatility affects both domestic and foreign private investment in Nigeria. Some of these studies show that, different approaches yield varied outcomes. In certain cases, other studies indicate a positive relationship between foreign private investment and exchange rate volatility; in other cases, however, the variables show a negative relationship. The influence of exchange rate fluctuation on foreign private investment is examined empirically with the results supported by theoretical predictions.

Theoretical evidence suggested that exchange rate instability has a positive impact on foreign private investment. Furthermore, studies that established a positive relationship between exchange rate volatility and foreign private investment include those from scholars, such as Aisien (2018), Benson et al. (2019), Ogundipe et al. (2019), Alnaa and Ahiakpor (2020), Okonkwo et al. (2021), Dahunsi (2021), Joel and Jeffrey (2023). However, those with negative results are Ahmed (2018), Leonard (2018), Adokwe et al. (2019), Aydogan et al. (2020), Nwosu and Orekoya (2020), Nkemdilim and Azuka (2021), and Nadine et al. (2021).

Conversely, the results that show exchange rate volatility and domestic investment also had opposing findings, the results with positive findings such as Bernard and Sin-Yu (2018), Bilge and Gozde (2018), Ghazali (2019), Udeh and Edeh (2020), Ekpo et al. (2023) and others that shows negative findings are Saidu et al. (2022), Idehen et al. (2020), Udeh and Edeh (2020), and Nwosu et al. (2023).

For instance, the Aisien study (2018) examined the relationship between exchange rate volatility and foreign private investment in Nigeria, breaking down foreign private investment into two categories: foreign direct investment and foreign portfolio investment. Nigerian quarterly time series data from 2007 to 2017 were used in the study. Examine how various forms of foreign private investment have responded to changes in exchange rates. The findings showed that whereas foreign portfolio investment had a strong negative impact with the exchange rate in Nigeria also, foreign direct investment had a positive impact.

In a similar vein, Benson et al. (2019) examined how interest rates and exchange rates affected FPTI inflows into Nigeria between 2006 and 2018. They discovered that the exchange rate had a considerable and beneficial impact on FPTI in Nigeria over time by using the cointegration and ECM econometric approaches. Additionally, Alnaa and Ahiakpor (2020) looked at how Ghana's FPTI was affected by exchange rate fluctuation between 1986 and 2017. Using the GACH, the findings demonstrated that FPTI is favorably and strongly impacted by changes in exchange rates. Okonkwo et al. (2021) looked at the effect of currency rates on FPTI in Nigeria from 1981 to 2018 in the same study. FPTI in Nigeria is significantly positively impacted by the exchange rate, according to the Granger causality test, cointegration, and ECM studies.

The asymmetric effects of foreign private investment and exchange rate volatility on Nigeria's capital market performance were examined in Dahunsi's (2021) study. Information gathered from 1986 to 2017 on gross capital formation, exchange rate volatility, foreign private investment, and capital market performance. The findings demonstrated a long-term co-integration between foreign private investment, exchange rate volatility, and capital market performance. Additionally, the study found that foreign private investment has linear effects on capital market performance over both time horizons, whereas exchange rate volatility has asymmetric effects.

Additionally, Joel and Jeffrey (2023) examined how exchange rate fluctuations affected the increase of foreign private investment in Nigeria between 1986 and 2021. The EGARCH model was used to generate exchange rate volatility, and the generalized method of moment (GMM) was used for the study's primary analysis. The results suggested the volatility positively and considerably affected foreign private investment growth/inflows.

On the other hand, Ahmed (2018) looked into how Nigerian FPTI was affected by exchange rate volatility between 1990 and 2016. Using cointegration and the EGARCH, the results showed that trade significantly reduces FPTI in Nigeria over the long and short terms. Leonard (2018), on the other hand, used quarterly time series data from Nigeria from 2007 to 2017 to investigate how the exchange rate affected foreign private investment. The study separated foreign private investment into two categories: foreign portfolio investment and foreign direct investment. The findings showed that foreign direct investment and foreign portfolio investment in Nigeria are negatively impacted by the naira's devaluation.

In a similar vein, Adokwe et al. (2019) used the 2-stage least squares and EGARCH models to investigate the impact of exchange rate movement on FPTI in Nigeria from 1986 to 2016; the results showed that exchange rate volatility significantly reduces FPIT in Nigeria. Furthermore, for emerging nations like Nigeria, Aydogan et al. (2020) investigated the impact of currency rate fluctuations and international portfolio movements on shock transmission and volatility spillover. The result emphasizes the significance of exchange rate uncertainty in investment decisions by demonstrating that changes in exchange rates have a negative effect on net equity flows in some nations. Additionally, for the years 1996–2018, Nwosu and Orekoya (2020) examine the connection between FPTI and exchange mobility in Nigeria. Exchange rate fluctuations had a substantial detrimental effect on foreign investment inflows into Sub-Saharan Africa, according to the study, which used EGARCH. Additionally, the FPTI gravity model in Egypt from 2005 to 2019 was studied by Nadine et al. (2021). It was discovered using the EGARCH and GMM that changes in the exchange rate had a detrimental effect on FPI.

In contrast to the aforementioned conclusions, Bernard and Sin-Yu (2018) examined the effect of exchange rate uncertainty on domestic investment in Ghana using annual data spanning the years 1980–2015. Exchange rate uncertainty has varying short-term effects on domestic investment, according to the study's findings, which were based on the ARDL model. In other words, prior levels of uncertainty discourage investment, whereas the current degree of uncertainty encourages it. Over time, domestic investment benefits

from exchange rate instability. These results hold up well to different model specifications.

Additionally, Bilge and Gozde (2018) examine how exchange rate uncertainty affects domestic investment in 25 emerging markets and developing economies (EMDEs) across the 2004–2014 timeframe. The GARCH model is used to model exchange rate uncertainty. The results identified a positive and substantial trend, which indicated the existence of risk-neutral or insensitive domestic investors to exchange rate uncertainty in these nations.

Furthermore, using time series data, Ghazali (2019) examined the causal relationship between GDP and private domestic investment in Pakistan from 1981 to 2008 and found that there is a positive and significant relationship between increased private domestic investment and economic growth, as well as a bi-directional causality between the two.

Additionally, a study by Ekpo et al. (2023) looked into how exchange rate volatility affected Nigeria's economic performance and private domestic investment. The purpose of the study was to investigate the causal relationship between Nigeria's economic development, private investment, and exchange rates. The researchers discovered that the exchange rate positively affects private investment and Nigeria's economic performance using time series data spanning from 1980 to 2018.

Idehen et al. (2020), however, investigated how exchange rate fluctuations affected the growth of SMEs in Nigeria between 1995 and 2015. The ordinary least square (OLS) model was used in the investigation. According to the findings, small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) in Nigeria were significantly and negatively impacted by the exchange rate during the study period.

Furthermore, Udeh and Edeh (2020) used yearly time series data on domestic investment, gross domestic product, interest rate, financial deepening, and exchange rate for the years 1986–2017 to examine the effects of exchange rate variations on domestic investment in Nigeria. Autoregressive distributed lagged modeling (ARDL) was the method used. The results show that there is a negative correlation between Nigerian domestic investment and changes in the exchange rate. However, over time, domestic investment is not much impacted by fluctuations in exchange rates.

Likewise, Saidu et al. (2022) investigated the connection between Nigerian domestic investment and currency rate volatility. Used quarterly time series data from 1981Q1 to 2017Q4. The model used for this was exponential generalized autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity (EGARCH). During the time under investigation, the study discovered an inverse relationship between exchange rate volatility and domestic investment. It also showed that two major factors influencing domestic investment were income and exchange rates.

Additionally, Nwosu et al. (2023) looked into how the Nigerian economy's productive sector was affected by real exchange rate volatility (1999–2021). The study tested the relationship between the independent variables (inflation rate, balance of trade, and

real exchange rate volatility) and the dependent variable (productive sector) using a vector autoregression estimate (VAR). According to the report, the Nigerian economy’s productive sector is significantly and negatively impacted by exchange rate fluctuation.

3.1 Methodology

The research design used in the study was ex post facto. The Nigerian economy’s sample size, which included both domestic and foreign private investment (FPI and DI) from 1980 to 2025, serves as the study’s population. The information was taken from the World Bank Development Indicators (WBDI), Central Bank of Nigeria (CBH) and Statistical Bulletin (2024). To accomplish the goals of this investigation, the EGARCH model was utilized as an analytical method. Since it can distinguish between variables during the fluctuation process without necessarily exaggerating the nature of fluctuations, the EGARCH is more effective than the standard deviation at creating volatility. Additionally, a pairwise Granger causality test was used to examine the causal relationship between EXR, FPTI, and DI (Tejvan, 2019, Udeh & Edeh, 2020, Princeton, 2020, and Omorokunwas & Ikponmwosa, 2019).

Thus, The following EGARCH (1,1) model is specified from which the exchange rate volatility is generated:

$$EXRT_t = X_t\gamma + \epsilon_t \text{ (the mean equation)} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where: EXRT_t = Exchange Rate

$$\sigma^2 = \delta + \theta\epsilon_{2t-1} + \beta\sigma_{2t-1}^2 \text{ (the variance equation)} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

3.1.1 Model Specification

The model for this study is anchored on the Risk Aversion Theory, which helps to ascertain the impact of exchange rate volatility on FPTI and DI for both internal and external shocks. Therefore, the model is stated as follows:

$$Y_1 = f(\text{RGDP, MCAP, MLIQ, OPEN INF, EXRV}) \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

and

$$Y_2 = f(\text{RGDP, FD, INTR, INF, EXRV}) \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Where:

Y₁ = Cumulative foreign Private investment

Y₂ = Gross Domestic Investment

RGDP = Real Gross Domestic Products

MCAP = Market Capitalization

MLIQ = Money Liquidity

INF = Inflation Rate

INTR = Interest Rate

FD = Financial Development

OPEN = Degree of Openness

EXRV = Exchange Rate Volatility

Thus, in this study, FD measured by CFPTI and GDI was measured by gross fixed capital formation, these, were specified as follows:

$$CFPTI = f(RGDP, MCAP, MLIQ, OPEN, INTR, EXRV).....(5)$$

$$GDI = f(RGDP, FD, INTR, INF, EXRV).....(6)$$

In its econometric forms, the models are re-specified as:

$$CFPTI = \beta_0 + \beta_1RGDP + \beta_2MCAP + \beta_3MLIQ + \beta_4OPEN + \beta_5INTR + \beta_6EXRV + U1.....(7)$$

$$GDI = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 RGDP + \alpha_2 FD + \alpha_3INRT + \alpha_4INF + \alpha_5EXRV +U2.....(8)$$

U1, U2 are Error terms

Apprior expectations are: $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$ and $\beta_6 > 0$; while $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4$ and $\alpha_5 > 0$ ”.

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Measurement</i>	<i>Sources</i>	<i>Expected Sign</i>
<i>Cumulative Foreign Private Investment (CFPTI)</i>	measured by the overall amount of foreign investors’ equity and other financial assets as well as their total direct investment during a specific time period.	Bilge and Gozde (2018), Ihensekhien (2019), Udeh and Edeh, (2020), Dahunsi (2021)	+
<i>Gross Domestic Investment</i>	Measured by gross fixed capital formation	Udeh and Edeh (2020)	+
<i>Economic Growth (RGDP)</i>	Growth rate of RGDPG measured as the annual change in RGDP (GRGDP =RGDPt-RGDPt-1/ RGDPt-1	Joel O. & Jeffrey O. E. (2023)	+

<i>Market Capitalization (MCAP)</i>	measured as the current market price divided by the total number of outstanding shares of a corporation.	Ogundipe, et.al (2019),	+
<i>Money Liquidity (MLIQ)</i>	measured as the market capitalization to value exchanged ratio.	Oke et al. (2020)	+
<i>Inflation Rate (INF)</i>	12 months moving average inflation. (To control to the level of economic stability of the economy)	Omorokunwas and Ikponmwosa (2021)	-
<i>Interest rate (INTR)</i>	Prime rate	Ahmed, A. (2018) and Ogundipe et al. (2019)	-
<i>Financial Development (FD)</i>	The ratio of money supply to GDP (M2/GDP)(To control for financial sector development)	Ogundipe et al. (2019)	+
<i>Degree of Openness (OPEN)</i>	The ratio of total trade To GDP (IMPORT +EXPORT/GDP) (a proxy for trade policy)	Osinubi and Amaghionyeodiwe (2020)	+
<i>Exchange Rate (EXRV)</i>	Real Effective Exchange Rate(NEER; CPIw/ CPhome	Nadine, Ashraf and Nagia (2021), Benson, et.al (2019)	+

In order to prevent false regression results, it is required to first determine the stationarity status using the Augmented Decay Fuller and Phillips-Peron Methods because to the time series nature of the data set employed in the study.

The unit roots test was analyzed using the Phillips-Peron (PP) and Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) tests to prevent erroneous regression findings. First differences and levels are used to present the results. All of the variables became stationary and were thus integrated at level 1(0) and order 1 I(1) after the first difference was taken.

Variables	Augmented Dickey Fuller(ADF)		Phillips-Peron (PP)		
	Level	1st Difference	Level	1st Difference	Stationarity
	-0.684573**	-11.06164**	-0.608989**	-10.35374**	1(1)
	0.363064*	-1.247081**	0.285073**	-106.2449***	1(1)
	-0.554301**	-8.131348***	-1.921847**	-7.114532**	1(1)
	-1.838556*	-9.387557**	-3.739555*	-15.64316**	1(1)
	-5.366381**	-3.902833**	-3.613085*	-2.758573***	1(0)
	-1.824795**	-5.236182**	-1.658318***	-6.350761**	I(1)
	-1.771362***	-5.268705**	-1.531264**	-6.376131**	1(1)
	-3.171367**	-6.655403**	-1.301033**	-4.901372**	1(0)
	-2.170554*	-6.092974**	-2.103907**	-6.201793**	1(1)
	-3.453765**	-5.078095*	-2.237654**	-3.294387**	1(1)

Note: the intercept and trend terms are included in the test equations and the AIC is used to select the optimal lag order in the ADF and PP test equations.***, ** and * indicated 1%, 5% and 10% levels of significant respectively.

4.1.2 Exchange Rate Volatility Analysis Results

Table 4. 3 below shows the outcome of the equation analysis used to derive the exchange rate volatility data. Since speculative and arbitrage operations are common in the exchange rate market, the EGARCH framework is utilized, a suitable exchange rate lag (the mean equation was estimated for a single period). With extremely high goodness of fit statistics, the diagnostic tests for the mean equation are pretty spectacular. An oscillating pattern of exchange adjustment to equilibrium is suggested by the coefficient of lagged exchange rate, which is significant at 1 percent and more than unity.

Table 4.3: EGARCH Estimation of Exchange Rate Volatility on FPTI and GDI in Nigeria Results

Dependent Variable (FPTI) Mean, Model (1)				Dependent Variable (DI) Mean, Model (2)			
Variables	Coefficient	z-Statistics	Prob.	Variance	Coefficient	z-Statistics	Prob
C	40.52849	5.384621	0.0000	C	31.4147	4.29836	0.0014
EXRT(-1)	0.485763	8.342231	0.0001	EXRT(-1)	3.873532	0.263541	0.0021
Dependent Variable (FPTI) Variance				Dependent Variable (DI) Variance			

	Model (1)			Model (2)			
RGDP	23.01736	0.363578	0.0211**	RGDP	31.28361	0.263541	0.0121**
MCAP	0.638972	2.367287	0.0012	FD	0.635241	0.726542	0.0000
MLIQ	0.386372	0.283412	0.0023	INTR	-0.425634	0.263542	0.0141**
OPEN	-0.263728	0.192756	0.0000	INF	-0.185637	0.362786	0.0027**
INTR	-0.378920	0.582514	0.0111**	EXRV	0.421762	0.276532	0.0000
EXRV	-0.521725	0.278364	0.0000				
R2 = 0.74 Ad. R2 = 0.82 DW-Stat. = 2.51				R2 = 0.78 Ad. R2 = 0.84 DW Stat. = 2.71			

Source: Author's computation using E-views 10, (2024)

Model (1)'s dependent variable's volatility is explained by the variance result. While all of the EGARCH model (1)'s independent variables are significant, foreign private investment was positively impacted with money liquidity, market capitalization, and gross domestic products. This suggests that news from earlier times does increase exchange rate volatility. The degree of openness and interest rates, however, are detrimental to foreign private investment; this validates the volatility of the variables, which are primarily caused by investor expectations and speculations about the future. Additionally, news of the naira's depreciation against the US dollar had brought in new investors.

However, the variance results of model (2) explain the volatility of the dependent variables, shows that all the independent variables such as; KGDP, FD, INTR, INF, EXR are positive and significant, this is a clear implication on feature periods, when the volatility of exchange rate increases it will also increase domestic investment as well. Therefore, the period within the sample size provided the information on depreciation of naira related to USD, had an economic effect on investment in Nigeria.

Source: Author's computation using E-views 10, (2025) Source: Author's computation using E-views 10, (2025)

The trend in Naira shows, exchange rate volatility in Figure 1 above to support the exchange rate volatility (EXRTV) results in Table 4.3 above. According to the graph or chart, currency rate fluctuations have accelerated (become more volatile) between 2010 and 2020. Additionally, a significant market movement or volatility was observed from 1986 to 1999. Even so, volatility persisted from 1980 to 2025, but with less amplitude than in the earlier years. Based on this finding, we deduce that over the course of the inquiry, Nigeria’s naira exchange rate has been extremely volatile.

4.1.3 Granger Causality Test

The purpose of the Granger causality test is to investigate the kind and direction of causation between independent variables (such as RGDP, MCAP, MLIQ, OPEN, FD, INTR, and EXRV) and dependent variables (FPTI and GDI). In order to determine the type of link that existed between the variables, the pair-wise Granger causality test was applied.

Table 4.4: Granger Causality Test (Exchange Rate, Foreign Private Investment and Domestic Investment)

<i>Table 4.4: Pair-Wise Granger Causality Test Results for Model Three</i>				
Null Hypothesis:				
EXRV does not Granger Cause FPTI	1	43	0.92971	0.0001
EXRV does not Granger Cause GDI	1	43	2.14268	0.0103

Source: Author calculation using E-views 10 (2025)

The findings in Table 4.4 showed that EXRV and FPTI had a unidirectional causal relationship with F-statistics of 1.92971 and a p-value of 0.0001 at the 5% level of significance, and that EXRV and GDI had a unidirectional causal relationship with F-statistics of 2.14268 and a p-value of 0.0103 at the same level.

- i. The EGARCH results in Model 1 demonstrated that while interest rates and the degree of openness have a negative and significant relationship with FPTI in Nigeria, exchange rate volatility, market capitalization, and money liquidity have a positive and statistically significant relationship with foreign private investment.
- ii. The exchange rate, GDP, and financial development all have positive and statistically significant relationships with domestic investment, according to the EGARCH results for Model 2. However, when it comes to domestic investment in Nigeria, interest rates and inflation rates are both negative and statistically significant.
- iii. Therefore, the paired Granger causality tests for exchange rate volatility demonstrate that both the exchange rate and domestic investment in Nigeria as well as the exchange rate and international private investment have a unidirectional causal link.

5.2 Conclusions

The study comes to the conclusion that it is critical to acknowledge the substantial impact

that exchange rate changes have on investor confidence and economic stability. Given its reliance on oil exports and vulnerability to outside shocks, the Nigerian economy is particularly affected by exchange rate volatility. Additionally, the relationship between exchange rate volatility and investment dynamics in Nigeria highlights the necessity of prudent monetary policies aimed at currency stabilization. Nigeria might become a more appealing investment destination for both domestic and foreign investors by lowering the risks associated with currency swings and promoting a predictable environment.

5.3 Recommendations

- (i) The monetary authority (CBN) should continue to develop sound exchange rate management since exchange rate volatility has had a significant impact on the growth of foreign investment in Nigeria. This includes requiring Nigerian deposit money banks to control fluctuations in the distribution and allocation of foreign currencies and the naira.
- (ii) Because market capitalization affects FPIT growth, authorities must continuously develop suitable policies to improve the current degree of market depth in order to continuously encourage and draw in foreign investors to the home market. The government should also make sure that the investment climate is both safe and business-friendly.
- (iii) Lastly, trade openness (OPN) is crucial for drawing in foreign investment; therefore, the Nigerian government should be honest enough to eliminate any further trade restrictions and tax disincentives that could impede the flow of capital internationally. The country will see an increase in foreign investment as a result of this. Ahmed, A. (2018). Modelling the effect of stock market volatility and exchange rate volatility on foreign direct investment in Nigeria: A new framework approach. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 8(12), 1482-1505.

REFERENCES

- Adokwe, E. I. Agu, A.O., & Maduka, A.C. (2019). Exchange rate volatility and foreign direct investment: The Nigerian experience. *Journal of Business & Economic Policy*, 6(4), 78-87.
- Alnaa, S.E., & Ahiakpor, F. (2020). Exchange rate volatility and foreign direct investment. *Research in Applied Economics*, 12(3), 38-50.
- Asmae, A., & Ahmed, B. (2019) Impact of the exchange rate and price volatility on FDI inflows: Case of Morocco and Turkey. *Applied Economics and Finance*, 6(3), 1-15.
- Bilge C. & Gozde G. (2018) The Impact of Exchange Rate Uncertainty on Domestic Investment: Panel Evidence from Emerging Markets and Developing Economies. DOI: 10.5772/intechopen.71195.
- Bernard N. I. & Sin-Yu H. (2018) Exchange rate uncertainty and domestic investment in

- Ghana DOI: 10.1080/23322039.2017.1362157
- Benson, E., Eya, C. I., & Yunusa, A. (2019). Effect of exchange and interest rates on foreign direct investment in Nigeria 2006-2018. *International Journal of Contemporary Research and Review*, 10(7), 1-15.
- Dahunsi O. J. (2021) Exchange Rate Volatility, Foreign Private Investment and Performance in Nigeria's Capital Market. *Indo-Asian Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 2(2), 235-248.
- Etale, L.M., & Sawyerr, A.E. (2020). An empirical evaluation of the effect of foreign investment inflows on economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Quantitative and Qualitative Research Methods*, 8(1), 1-14.
- Ghazali, A. (2019). Analysing The Relationship between Foreign Direct Investment Domestic Investment and Economic Growth for Pakistan. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, 47, 123-131.
- Ihensekhien O. A. (2019) Impact of foreign private investment on the Nigerian economy. *International Journal of Commerce and Economics*, www.commercejournal.in. 1(1).
- Ifuero O. O. & Nosakhare I. (2018) Foreign Private Investment and Stock Market Volatility in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Economic and Social Studies*, 60(2). 78-110.
- Joel O. & Jeffrey O. E. (2023) Exchange Rate Volatility and Foreign Investment Growth in Nigeria African. *Development Finance Journal* November, 6 (1), 105-123.
- Kenny, V. S. (2019). Effect of foreign direct investment and exchange rate on economic growth of Nigeria. www.ssrn.com.
- Leonard N. A. (2018). The Impact of Exchange Rate on Foreign Private Investment in Nigeria. *Asian Finance & Banking Review*, 2(2). Published by Centre for Research on Islamic Banking & Finance and Business.
- Lipsey, R.I. (1999). The role of foreign direct investment in international capital flows. NBER Working Paper, No.7094. National Bureau of Statistics (2012), 1-16.
- Nadine, A., Ashraf, S., & Nagia, R. (2021). The impact of relative exchange rate volatility and other multidimensional determinants on FDI in Egypt. *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management*, 11(4), 1163-1197.
- Nkemdilim I. & Azuka E. O. (2021) The Consequences of Exchange Rate Fluctuations on Nigeria's Economic Performance: An Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Approach. *International Journal of Management, Economics and Social Sciences*, 10(2- 3), 68 – 87.

- Nwosu A. O., Amakor I. C., & Anyanwu F. A. (2023) Real Exchange Rate Volatility and Nigeria Productive Sector. *African Banking and Finance Review Journal*, 2(2), 168-179.
- Nwosu, D., & Orekoya, S. (2020). Exchange rate volatility and foreign direct investment in Nigeria. *European Economics*, 2(38), 227-247.
- Ogundipe, A.A., Alabi, J., Asaleye, A J., & Ogundipe, O.M. (2019). Exchange rate volatility and foreign portfolio investment in Nigeria. *Investment Management and Financial Innovations*, 16(3), 241-250.
- Oke, M. O., Oluwakemi, A.A., Kolapo, F.T., & Joseph, M. (2020). Pull and push factors as determinant of foreign portfolio investment in the emerging market. *Risk Governance & Control: Financial Markets & Institutions*, 10(4), 1-11.
- Okonkwo, J. J. (2019). Exchange rate variation and Nigeria's balance of trade. *Discovery Journal*, 55(283), 361 – 366.
- Omorokunwas, O.G., & Ikponmwosa, I. (2021). Exchange rate volatility and foreign private investment in Nigeria, *Annals of the University of Petroşani, Economics*, 14(1), 259-268.
- Osinubi, T.S., & Amaghionyeodiwe, L.A. (2020). Foreign private investment and economic growth in Nigeria. *Applied Econometrics and International Development, Euro-American Association of Economic Development*, 10(2), 1-17.
- Princeton, NJ. Alnaa, S.E., & Ahiakpor, F. (2020). Exchange rate volatility and foreign direct investment. *Research in Applied Economics*, 12(3), 38-50.
- Saidu I. A., Hakeem O. A., Suleiman M. & Bello A. T. (2022) Exchange Rate Volatility and Domestic Investment: Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Economic and Development Policy*. 5(1), 13-22.
- Tejvan, P. (2019). Advantages and Disadvantages of Devaluation. Retrieved on 31/10/2021 from: <https://www.economicshelp.org/blog/1299/economics/advantages-and-disadvantages-of-devaluation>.
- Udeh, S. O. & Edeh, C. E. (2020) Impact of Exchange Rate Fluctuations on Domestic Investment in Nigeria (1986-2017). *International Journal of Economic and Business Review-Peer Reviewed Journal*, 8(1), 49 – 68.

INFLUENCE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION AND ITS CONTRIBUTION TO ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN EZINIHITE MBAISE LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF IMO STATE

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ABSTRACT

The importance of entrepreneurship education cannot be over emphasized. It enhanced job creation, reduce unemployment and contribute to economic growth and development. The paper examined the Influence of Entrepreneurship Education on students' entrepreneurial skill development and its Contribution to economic development in Secondary Schools in Ezinihitte Mbaise Local Government Area of Imo State. Descriptive research design was adopted with a population of 5570 students' in SS2 across the thirteen public secondary schools in Ezinihitte Mbaise Local Government Area. A sample size of 557 was drawn from the population using simple random sampling techniques of 10%. Instrument used for data collection was structured researcher made questionnaire titled: "Entrepreneurship Education Contribution to Economic Development Scale (EECEDS)" with 20 items developed by the researchers. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the question. Findings show that entrepreneurship education highly influences students' entrepreneurial skills development, and contributed towards reducing unemployment and enhancing economic development among the secondary school graduates. We recommend the inclusion of basic economic concepts such as demand and supply, inflation, market structure and economic policies in the entrepreneurship education curriculum to enhance students' understanding of the business operation within the economy. Furthermore, entrepreneurship education should incorporate financial management skills like savings, investment, budgeting, and access to credit which are vital for economic growth and development and sustainable entrepreneurship.

Key words: Entrepreneurship Education, Secondary Education, Economic Development.

1 Introduction

Education is a fundamental pillar of societal development, equipping learners with the knowledge and skills necessary for real-world applications. From an economic perspective, education serves as both a consumer and capital good, offering personal satisfaction while simultaneously acting as an essential input for human resource development, which drives economic and social transformation (Ogamba, Okorie, and Harold-Opara, 2017). According to the National Policy on Education (2024), education remains a priority

in national development plans, as it is the most crucial instrument for societal change. Secondary education serves as a bridge between primary and tertiary education, offering students additional knowledge, skills, and character development beyond the primary level. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (Revised Edition, 2013) outlines the objectives of secondary education as preparing students for useful living within society and preparing students for higher education.

One crucial aspect of secondary education that has gained significant attention in recent years is entrepreneurship education. It serves as the engine of economic growth, driving industrialization, creating young entrepreneurs, and fostering employment and wealth generation (Henry, 2013). Entrepreneurship education empowers students with the necessary knowledge, skills, and innovative capacities to achieve entrepreneurial success across various sectors. According to Njoke, Nwaneri, and Ebo (2017), an entrepreneur is someone who identifies investment opportunities, makes informed decisions, establishes businesses, and efficiently manages scarce resources for production and distribution. Entrepreneurship thus plays a vital role in fostering economic self-reliance and sustainable development.

From an economic perspective, entrepreneurship is a key driver of economic growth, development, and innovation. It is one of the factors of production, with profit as its primary reward. Economics, as a discipline, studies how societies allocate scarce resources to meet competing needs. Anyaele (2013) describes economics as a powerful tool for fostering national development, while Iweho et al. (2024) emphasize its role in preparing students for entrepreneurial careers by equipping them with relevant real-world skills. However, despite the importance of entrepreneurship education, several challenges hinder its full implementation in secondary schools. These include limited access to funding, inadequate teaching resources, a lack of trained educators, and minimal practical exposure to real-world entrepreneurship. Without a clear understanding of the benefits of entrepreneurship education, policymakers and curriculum developers may struggle to make informed decisions about improving entrepreneurship education in secondary schools.

Globally, entrepreneurship is increasingly recognized as a mechanism for reducing unemployment, poverty, and underemployment, particularly among young people. Deakins and Freel (2019) argue that modern economies are transitioning toward knowledge-based industries, where entrepreneurship plays an integral role in economic growth and development. Economic development is a multidimensional process that improves a nation's economic, political, and social well-being. Unlike economic growth, which focuses on increased production, economic development prioritizes human welfare, poverty reduction, and sustainable opportunities. Todaro and Smith (2015) describe economic development as a transformative process that entails changes in social structures, national institutions, and economic performance, with an emphasis on reducing inequality and poverty.

This study, therefore, aims to examine the influence of entrepreneurship education and its contribution to economic development in secondary schools in Ezinihitte Mbaise

Local Government Area of Imo State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to determine the extent to which entrepreneurship education influences students' entrepreneurial skills development in secondary schools in Ezinihitte Mbaise and how it contributes to reducing unemployment while enhancing economic development among secondary school graduates in the area. Understanding these aspects is crucial to identifying the gaps in entrepreneurship education and proposing effective solutions to enhance its impact in secondary schools.

Several studies have examined the impact of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria. For example, Okoye, Nwakoby, and Ezike (2021) studied its effect on unemployment reduction in Anambra State, while Bako, Taiwo, and Mohammed (2021) explored its role in reducing graduate unemployment in Nigeria. Similarly, Njoku, Nwaneri, and Ebo (2017) investigated the role of creativity and innovation in achieving sustainable development, and Bertram, Gabriel, and Clifford (2016) examined entrepreneurship education as a solution to unemployment in Nigeria. However, to the best of the researchers' knowledge, no study has specifically examined the influence of entrepreneurship education in secondary schools in Ezinihitte Mbaise Local Government Area of Imo State. This research aims to fill that gap by analyzing how entrepreneurship education impacts students' skill development and contributes to economic development within this specific region.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Review

Human Capital Theory (1964): Human Capital Theory was developed by an economist Gary Becker in 1964. The theory focused on investments in education and skills development lead to increased productivity and economic well-being for individuals and society as a whole. This theory suggests that entrepreneurship education, as a form of human capital development, enhances the skills and knowledge of individuals, thereby increasing their productivity and capacity to innovate and create businesses. (Martin, McNally and Kay 2013) effective entrepreneurship education programmes contributed to the development of entrepreneurial skills and knowledge. (Marvel, Davis and Sproul 2016) entrepreneurship education build human capital by equipping and developing individuals with the necessary business opportunities that help them succeed. Connecting the theory to the topic of the research it is important to note that investing in the acquisition of innovative and entrepreneurial skills during secondary school could enhanced student human capital development and improve their economic decision-making abilities in a long run and make them more employable and self-reliant.

Theory of Planned Behaviour (1985): Theory of Planned Behaviour, was propounded by Icek Ajzen. This theory centers on individual behaviour as determined by their attitudes, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control. This theory proposed that entrepreneurial intentions are shapes by attitudes, social influence and perceived control over entrepreneurial skills can impact students' intention to engage in entrepreneurial skills and innovation. (Heuer and Kolvereid 2014), comprehensive entrepreneurship programmes are more effective in supporting entrepreneurial skills. Relating the theory to the present study, students who receive entrepreneurship education are more likely to develop positive attitudes towards self-employment, starting new business and job

creation.

Endogenous Growth Theory 1980: Endogenous Growth Theory developed by Paul Romer. This theory proposed that human capital innovative and knowledge are key to long-term economic growth. The argue that economic growth is generated from internal factors, such as technological innovation and knowledge accumulation, rather than being solely driven by external factors like capital accumulation. The enhancement of a nation's human capital will lead to economic growth by means of development of new forms of technology, efficient and effective means of production. (Ehrlich, Dunli and Zhiqiang 2017) emphasized the significance of entrepreneurial human capital as the specialized knowledge and skills entrepreneurs acquire through experience and innovate, that lead to economic growth. Relating the theory to the present study, students' exposure to entrepreneurship education programmes and some basic economic concepts that incorporate real-life situations, will positively influence their entrepreneurial skills abilities by providing them with practical knowledge and equipping them in their financial stability and future success.

2.2 Review of the Empirical Literature

Nwaogu, Dienye, and Onyido (2024) assessed the impact of entrepreneurship education on unemployment among Nigerian graduates using an ex-post facto research design. Their findings revealed that entrepreneurship education reduces graduate unemployment by enhancing competencies in presentation, management, technical skills, financial management, resourcefulness, and risk-taking. These skills foster job creation, resilience, and human capacity development. Similarly, Bako, Taiwo, and Mohammed (2023) conducted an empirical study on entrepreneurial education and unemployment reduction among Nigerian graduates, adopting a survey research design. Their results indicated that creativity and skills acquisition serve as effective tools for reducing unemployment.

Omoluabi (2014), reviewed the impact of entrepreneurship development on job creation in Nigeria and found that entrepreneurship consistently leads to job creation, encouraging individuals to engage in activities that improve their lives and contribute to national development. He further noted that employment opportunities in any economy are closely linked to entrepreneurship training and development. Likewise, Okoye, Iloanya, and Uduze (2014) investigated the extent to which entrepreneurship in Nigeria has reduced youth unemployment. Their study revealed that government policies and initiatives have not significantly transformed the unemployment landscape due to corruption, inadequate funding, and maladministration. They concluded that while entrepreneurship should ideally serve as an engine of growth, job creation, and innovation, systemic inadequacies have hindered its effectiveness.

In another study, Onyeizugbe, Orogbu, and Oyigbo (2015) examined entrepreneurial development and job creation in selected local government areas in Enugu State, Nigeria, using a correlational research design. Their findings showed no significant relationship between innovativeness and youth empowerment. The study recommended that the government should pay more attention to entrepreneurship as a tool for job creation. Ekong and Ekong (2016) conducted an empirical study on skills acquisition and unemployment

reduction in Nigeria, focusing on the National Directorate of Employment (NDE) from 1987 to 2012. Using a descriptive survey design, their research found a positive link between skills acquisition through the NDE and unemployment reduction in Akwa Ibom State.

Umogbai, Adudu, and Agwa (2018) examined the role of entrepreneurship education in unemployment reduction in Benue State, Nigeria, focusing on Vandeikya Local Government Area. Their findings indicated that entrepreneurship education significantly contributes to unemployment reduction by fostering wealth creation and employment generation. The study also found that skills acquisition programs in Vandeikya positively impacted unemployment reduction. They concluded that the role of entrepreneurship training and education in reducing unemployment through youth empowerment and wealth creation would be more significant if entrepreneurship were encouraged at all levels, particularly at the local and community levels.

Furthermore, Nwachukwu and Ogbo (2012) examined the impact of entrepreneurship development on Nigeria's economy. Their findings showed that entrepreneurship education significantly contributes to the growth of small and medium enterprises (SMEs), which are crucial for economic development. Similarly, Njoku, Nwaneri, and Ebo (2017) conducted a study on creativity and innovation in entrepreneurship as a tool for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Bertram, Gabriel, and Clifford (2016) investigated entrepreneurship education as a solution to unemployment in Nigeria, using a descriptive survey research method. They found that the growing global emphasis on entrepreneurship education enhances the acquisition of essential skills for both self-employment and wage employment.

Based on the literature reviewed, previous studies have largely focused on entrepreneurship education as a means of reducing unemployment. However, they have overlooked the broader impact of entrepreneurship education on economic development. While unemployment reduction is a significant aspect of economic progress, economic development encompasses a wider spectrum, including income growth, wealth creation, innovation, and industrial development. This study, therefore, seeks to bridge this gap by examining not only the role of entrepreneurship education in reducing unemployment but also its overall contribution to economic development in secondary schools in Ezinihitte Mbaise Local Government Area of Imo State.

3. Methodology

The researchers adopted a descriptive survey research design with a total population of 5,570 SS2 students across the thirteen public secondary schools in Ezinihitte Mbaise Local Government Area of Imo State. A sample size of 557 respondents (10%) was drawn using a simple random sampling technique from each of the schools in the Local Government Area.

The instrument for data collection was a structured, researcher-developed questionnaire titled "Entrepreneurship Education Contribution to Economic Development Scale (EECEDS)." The questionnaire consisted of 20 items and was designed on a four-point

Likert scale:

- Very High Extent (VHE)
- High Extent (HE)
- Low Extent (LE)
- Very Low Extent (VLE)

The data collected from the respondents were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. The mean value was used to answer the research questions, while the standard deviation was used to determine the level of consistency in the respondents' ratings. In interpreting the mean scores, any item with a mean value of 2.50 or above was considered accepted, while items with mean values below 2.50 were rejected.

4. Results Presentation

4.1 Research Question one

Table 1: Mean scores and standard deviation on the extent entrepreneurship education influences students' entrepreneurial skills development in secondary schools in Ezinihitte Mbaise local government area of Imo State.

S/N	ITEMS	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Entrepreneurship education enhances students' problem-solving and decision-making skills.	3.46	0.87	High Extent
2	Entrepreneurship education improves the ability to translate technological skills gained into practical work situations.	3.07	1.06	High Extent
3	Awareness that entrepreneurship education is part of the school curriculum.	2.96	1.18	High Extent
4	Entrepreneurship education enhances the identification of business opportunities.	3.42	0.99	High Extent
5	Entrepreneurship education enhances access to financial resources and investment opportunities for students.	3.55	0.87	High Extent
6	Entrepreneurship education enhances understanding of market challenges.	3.26	1	High Extent
7	Entrepreneurship education equips students with facilities that allow them to become self-employed.	3.28	0.93	High Extent
8	Entrepreneurship education improves secondary school graduates' capacity to identify and pursue business opportunities.	3.1	1.06	High Extent

9	Entrepreneurship education influences the mindset of secondary school graduates toward self-employment.	2.97	1.17	High Extent
10	Exposure to entrepreneurship education influences students' long-term career aspirations in entrepreneurship.	3.21	1.05	High Extent

Table 1 shows that all ten (10) items measuring how entrepreneurship education influences students' entrepreneurial skills development in secondary schools were accepted, with mean values ranging from 2.96 to 3.55, which are above the cut-off mark of 2.50. This indicates that entrepreneurship education positively influences students' entrepreneurial skills by providing them with practical knowledge and equipping them with essential skills needed to start and manage businesses. Furthermore, the grand mean of 3.23 confirms that all the items in the table were accepted, reinforcing the significant role of entrepreneurship education in preparing students for self-employment and business ventures.

4.2 Research Question two

Table 2: Mean Responses on the Extent to Which Entrepreneurship Education Contributes to Reducing Unemployment and Enhancing Economic Development Among Secondary School Graduates

S/N	ITEMS	MEAN	SD	DECISION
S/N	Do you believe entrepreneurship education could help you identify business opportunities in your community after secondary school?	3.18	1.08	High Extent
ITEMS	Entrepreneurship education equips students with technical capabilities that offer employment opportunities and reduce unemployment.	3.48	0.79	High Extent
MEAN	Does entrepreneurship education reduce youth unemployment?	3.16	1.04	High Extent
SD	Rate the effectiveness of the entrepreneurship education you have received.	3.2	1.06	High Extent
DECISION	How has entrepreneurship education helped foster innovation and creativity in business ventures within Ezinihitte Mbaise?	3.12	1.04	High Extent
6	How confident are you in starting your own business after completing secondary school?	3.04	1.08	High Extent

7	What role does entrepreneurship education play in promoting small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Ezinihitte Mbaise?	3.01	1.12	High Extent
8	Do you believe entrepreneurship education has enhanced access to financial resources and investment opportunities in Ezinihitte Mbaise?	3.05	1.17	High Extent
9	Entrepreneurship education equips students with facilities that allow them to become self-employed.	3.03	1.12	High Extent
10	Do you believe entrepreneurship education has enhanced access to financial resources and investment opportunities in Ezinihitte Mbaise?	3.21	1	High Extent

Table 2 shows that all ten (10) items measuring the extent to which entrepreneurship education contributes to reducing unemployment and enhancing economic development among secondary school graduates were accepted, with mean scores ranging from 3.01 to 3.48, all of which are above the cut-off mark of 2.50. This indicates that students gain valuable knowledge, skills, and competencies through entrepreneurship education, enabling them to make informed decisions about self-employment. As they succeed in their ventures, they not only improve their economic status but also contribute to the economic well-being of their communities and society at large. The cluster Mean of 3.15 further confirms that the overall responses indicate a high extent of agreement regarding the role of entrepreneurship education in unemployment reduction and economic development.

4.3 Findings

The analysis in Table 1 confirms that entrepreneurship education significantly influences students' entrepreneurial skill development in secondary schools. This finding aligns with the assertion of Nwaogu and Dienne (2024) that entrepreneurship education equips students and graduates with technical capabilities, enhances their adaptability across industries, nurtures creativity, improves financial literacy, and strengthens managerial competencies, all of which contribute to employment opportunities and unemployment reduction among Nigerian graduates. Similarly, Ancuța and Mihaela (2020) support this view, stating that entrepreneurship education among young people consolidates entrepreneurial knowledge, skills, and abilities that enable them to recognize new business opportunities by identifying societal needs. Their study further suggests that students exposed to entrepreneurship education are more likely to embrace the risks associated with establishing and managing their own businesses. These findings indicate that entrepreneurship education not only enhances students' economic potential but also contributes to broader economic development within society.

The empirical results in Table 2 show that entrepreneurship education significantly

contributes to reducing unemployment and enhancing economic development among secondary school graduates. The standard deviation values indicate a high level of agreement among respondents, as their mean scores consistently fall within the “high extent” rating. This result is expected, as entrepreneurship education equips students with the creativity and self-reliance necessary for post-secondary employment and business ventures.

These findings are consistent with Ediagbonya (2013), who emphasized that introducing entrepreneurship education into Nigeria’s educational system aims to cultivate entrepreneurial skills that alleviate the unemployment crisis by fostering a culture of self-reliance. Similarly, Nwankwo and Ogazi (2017) support the present study, highlighting that entrepreneurship education fosters the development of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which, in some cases, grow into large-scale businesses that provide essential goods and services, reduce poverty, and increase youth employment, thereby contributing to national development. Furthermore, Bertram, Gabriel, and Clifford (2016) argue that entrepreneurship education instills a mindset of perseverance in individuals, encouraging them to persistently pursue opportunities that create wealth through innovation, efficient resource management, and business growth.

The agreement in findings across these studies may be attributed to similar economic and educational contexts, reinforcing the idea that entrepreneurship education plays a crucial role in enhancing students’ employability, fostering innovation, and promoting economic development.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

5.1 Conclusion

This study examined the influence of entrepreneurship education and its contribution to economic development in secondary schools in Ezinihitte Mbaise Local Government Area of Imo State. The findings revealed that entrepreneurship education significantly enhances students’ entrepreneurial skills, reduces unemployment, and promotes economic development among secondary school graduates. It plays a crucial role in fostering self-reliance by equipping students with the necessary skills, knowledge, and innovation mindset required, identifying business opportunities and developing technical and problem-solving abilities essential for job creation. Early exposure to entrepreneurship education enhances students’ capacity to navigate economic challenges and contribute meaningfully to the business environment.

5.2 Recommendation

1. **Integration of Economic Concepts:** The entrepreneurship education curriculum should incorporate fundamental economic concepts such as demand and supply, market structures, and economic policies to improve students’ understanding of business operations within the economy.
2. **Financial Management Training:** Entrepreneurship education should include financial literacy skills such as savings, investment, budgeting, and access to credit to ensure students develop the financial discipline needed for sustainable

entrepreneurship and long-term economic growth.

REFERENCES

- Ancuța, L., & Mihaela, S. (2020). Entrepreneurship education: A tool for reducing youth unemployment. (1), 51–58.
- Anyaele, M.A. (2013). *Comprehensive Economics*. Lagos, A. Johnson. Publishers Ltd.
- Bako, Y. A., Taiwo, A. A., & Mohammed, S. R. (2021). The role of entrepreneurial education in reducing unemployment among Nigerian graduates. In proceedings of the 7th international conference on social science and humanities, September 18-19, 2021, Mus, Turkey.
- Bertram, O. A., Gabriel, A. A., & Clifford, E. E. (2016). Entrepreneurship education: A panacea for unemployment in Nigeria. (2). https://www.arabianjbm.com/NGISD_index.php
- Deakins, D., & Freel, M. (2019). (5th ed.). McGraw Hill.
- Ediagbonya, K. (2013). The role of entrepreneurship education in ensuring economic empowerment and development. *Journal of business administration and education*, 4(1), 35-46.
- Ehrlich, I., Dunli, L., & Zhiqiang, L. (2017). The role of entrepreneurial human capital as a driver of endogenous economic growth. national bureau of economic research (NBER). 23728DOI: 10.3386/w23728
- Ekong, U.O., & Ekong, C.U. (2016). Skills acquisition and unemployment reduction in Nigeria. *Journal of education and practice*, 7(10), 1-7).
- Henry, F. I. (2013). Practice-Hall.
- Heuer, A., & Kolvereid, L. (2014). Education in entrepreneurship education and the theory of planned behaviour. *European journal of training and development*, 38(6), 506-523. DOI: 10.1108/EJTD-02-2013-0019
- Iweho, G. O., Yunisa, A., Oha, K. C., Ezeocha, I. G., & Adejoh, I. S. (2024). Implementation of entrepreneurial education-related contents in secondary school economics curriculum in Owerri Education Zone 1, Imo State. (1).
- Martin, B. C., McNally, J. J., & Kay, M. J. (2013). Examining the formation of human capital in entrepreneurship: A meta-analysis of entrepreneurship education outcomes. *journal of business venturing*, 28(2), 211-224. DOI: 10.1016/j.jbusvent.2012.03/002
- Marvel, E M. R., Davis, J. L., & Sproul, C. R. (2016). Human capital and entrepreneurship research: A critical review and future directions. *Entrepreneurship theory and practice*, 40(3), 599-626. DOI: 10.1111/etap.12136

- Njoku, U. M., Nwaneri, P. N., & Ebo, A. A. (2017). Creativity and innovation in entrepreneurship: A variable tool for sustainable development goals. (1). Career Publisher.
- Nwaogu, O. A., Dienye, V. U., & Onyido, J. A. (2024). Impact of entrepreneurship education on unemployment of Nigerian graduates. (2), ISSN 0795-3187.
- Nwankwo, S. N., & Ogazi, G. C. (2017). Teaching strategies and training facilities for effective implementation of undergraduate entrepreneurship education for sustainable development in Nigeria. (1). Career Publisher.
- Nwachukwu, O. (2012). Impact of entrepreneurship development on the Nigerian economy. *Journal of business and management*, Vol. 16. no. 1, 2012, pp. 1-7.
- Okafor, C. (2019). Reducing unemployment rate in Nigeria through entrepreneurship development: A study of selected small businesses in Anambra State. (1). ISSN 2056-5992.
- Okoye, V. C., Nwakoby, N. P., & Ezike, E. N. (2021). Effect of entrepreneurship education on unemployment reduction in Anambra State, Nigeria. (April). <https://www.ijaar.org>
- Ogamba, P. N., Okorie, C. B., & Harold-Opara, C. (2017). Entrepreneurship education as a panacea for sustainable reduction of unemployment in Nigeria. (1). Career Publisher.
- Omoluabi, E. T. (2014). Impact of entrepreneurship development on job creation in Nigeria. *Researchjournal's journal of entrepreneurship*, Vol. 2, no. 4. 2014, pp.1-14.
- Onyeizugbe, C. L., Orogbu, O. L., & Oyigbo, M.O. (2015). Entrepreneurial development and job creation in selected local government areas in Enugu state, Nigeria. *International journal of managerial studies and research*, 3(7), 41-53.
- Umogbai, M. E., Adudu, C. A., & Agwa, T. R. (2018). Entrepreneurship education and unemployment reduction in Benue State, Nigeria. *Journal of education and practice*, 9(33), 229-239.
- Todaro, M., & Smith, S. (2015). *Economic Development* (7th Ed.). Pearson. <https://oeclass.aaa.gr/eclass/modules/documentfile.p%20Todaro%20and%20Smith.pdf>.

INFLUENCE OF FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT AND EXCHANGE RATE ON FOREIGN PORTFOLIO INVESTMENT IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Nigerian capital flows now depend heavily on foreign portfolio investment, which supports the country's financial market development and economic expansion. However, the volatility and unpredictability of FPI have become a significant concern for policymakers, as it is often influenced by range of macroeconomic factors, most notably foreign direct investment (FDI) and exchange rate fluctuations. Despite their crucial role in economic performance, the complex interplay between FDI, exchange rates, and FPI remains underexplored, particularly in emerging nations where external shocks are often more likely to affect economic stability. Using secondary source data from 1987 to 2023, the study used an ex post facto research design to analyse the impact of foreign direct investment and exchange rates on foreign portfolio investment in Nigeria. Findings showed that FDI, inflation, and the official exchange rate exert a non-significant negative impact on FPI. This suggests that strengthening these variables results in decline in FPI, although effects are statistically insignificant at the short-run and foreign direct investment reveal a moderate positive impact on foreign portfolio investments. The Granger causality analysis results indicate the presence of unidirectional causality between certain variables, emphasizing the interconnectedness of these economic factors. The study recommended that policymakers should focus on creating a favourable business environment that encourages both FDI and FPI while ensuring that short-term portfolio inflows complement, rather than disrupt, long-term investment strategies. Further research could explore additional macroeconomic variables that may influence the dynamics between FDI, FPI, and exchange rate movements in Nigeria.

Keywords: *Foreign Direct Investment; Exchange Rate; Foreign Portfolio Investment; GDP growth Rate; Inflation Rate.*

1.1 Introduction

Nigerian capital flows now depend heavily on foreign portfolio investment, which supports the country's financial market development and economic expansion. Ogundipe, Alabi, Asaley & Ogundipe (2019) and additionally gained importance in important sectors of the world economy in recent times and serves as an essential source of funding to assist growth and development in both developed and developing nations (Michael & Thankgod, 2014). This volatility of capital flow is influenced by macroeconomic indicators in emerging countries as well as global economic conditions. Foreign investment capital, including foreign portfolio investment, is a major source of funding for Nigeria's present and future economic growth.

Long-term investments made by foreign organisations into productive assets in a host

nation are referred to as foreign direct investment. Usually, it comprises investments in physical infrastructure, technology transfer, and management expertise. FDI plays a pivotal role in capital formation, employment generation, and economic growth. FDI is defined as a direct investment made in a nation by people or businesses from another nation, either through the acquisition of a local enterprise or the expansion of an already established one. The construction of new facilities, mergers, acquisitions, the reinvestment of revenues from overseas activities, and intra-company loans are thus examples of FDI.

Furthermore, exchange rate stability is crucial for investors as fluctuations may affect the returns on investments. Depreciation in the host currency of the host nation may devalue foreign investments, thereby deterring foreign portfolio investors (Alam & Rashid, 2014). FDI can act as a signal of long-term commitment to an economy, reassuring portfolio investors about the country's growth potential. In emerging nations, where financial markets are typically less developed and more volatile, this is especially crucial. However, the volatility and inflow of FPI are influenced by several factors, notably foreign direct investment and currency rate dynamics. Understanding the relationship between these factors and FPI has become critical, particularly for decision-makers and financial analysts who want to improve investment attractiveness and economic stability.

However, exchange rate volatility can either enhance or undermine FDI and FPI flows. According to a study by Kiyota (2006) countries with stable exchange rates tend to experience more consistent FPI inflows, as investors are less worried about currency risk. Additionally, monetary policy interventions that stabilize the exchange rate can create a more conducive environment for FDI, further boosting FPI inflows. The problem, therefore, is that while FDI and exchange rates are known to affect FPI, the precise nature of these relationships is not well defined. Policymakers in developing economies, where capital flows are crucial for economic growth, often struggle to manage these variables to ensure consistent FPI inflows. A better understanding of how FDI and exchange rate dynamics impact FPI could help stabilize financial markets and foster more sustainable economic growth. By focussing on portfolio investments and not foreign private investments (in their entirety) in Nigeria, this study fills a lacuna in the body of research on the connection between foreign portfolio investments, exchange rate volatility, and foreign direct investment, exchange rate volatility, and foreign portfolio investments. Secondly, it evaluates the effect of foreign direct investment exchange rate volatility on the total amount of Nigeria's portfolio inflows to and identifies the specific nature of the relationship between the variables. Finally, it asks whether foreign direct investment, exchange rate, inflation rate, and economic growth have an impact on Nigeria's foreign portfolio investment inflows.

2.1 Literature Review

Foreign investors' investments in financial assets, including stocks, bonds, and other securities, are referred to as FPI. A view of global capital flows that involves the cross-border movement of financial assets, including cash, equities, or bonds, with the intention of generating revenue or a high rate of return, is known as foreign portfolio investment, or FPI (Atobrah, 2015 as cited in Ariwa and Okafor, 2024). Conversely, FDI involves the investment of foreign assets into domestic structures, industries, or organizations, often

providing long-term capital and knowledge transfer. Foreign direct investment directly affects the host nation’s economy by creating jobs, enhancing technological know-how, and promoting economic growth. However, it is the exchange rate between the currencies of two countries (Ogundipe, et al., 2019). In addition, exchange rate was seen as a macroeconomic variable given that it determines the purchasing power of citizens of a country in relation to citizens of other trading partners. For instance, given that the value of the Nigerian naira is lower than that of the US dollar, an American will have more purchasing power than a Nigerian.

(Osemene & Arotiba, 2018).

Figure 1: Trends in FDI, Exchange Rate, and FPI in Nigeria from 2020 to 2023

The chart above illustrates the inverse relationship among exchange rate stability and FPI inflows. The depreciation of naira corresponds with declines in FPI, as currency volatility often discourages short-term investors. FDI, while more stable, is also affected by economic and policy factors but shows resilience, particularly in 2023. These trends highlight Nigeria’s reliance on stable economic policies and exchange rates to attract foreign investment.

Ariwa and Okafor (2024) investigated how macroeconomic aggregates affected foreign portfolio investment (FPI) inflows into Nigeria during 1986-2022. Exchange rate, GDP growth rate, inflation and monetary policy rate were adopted as macroeconomic aggregates. The Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin was used as the source of the data. Error correction modeling (ECM) method was used to examine the information. Findings showed that foreign portfolio investment (FPI) inflows into Nigeria were positively and significantly impacted by the GDP growth rate. The connection among exchange rate volatility and foreign portfolio investment in Nigeria was examined by Agoh et al. in 2024. This study is germane mostly now that exchange rate fluctuation is assumed to have affected all facets of economic activities in Nigeria by employing EGARCH and other

econometric tools. The empirical results of the analysis found a significant connection among exchange rate movements and foreign direct investment in Nigeria within the scope of the study.

Alalade, et al., (2024) evaluated the critical role of foreign portfolio investment in enhancing the liquidity and efficiency of Nigeria's capital markets from 1993 to 2023. This analysis, utilizing an ex-post facto design, draws on data from the CBN Statistical Bulletin to investigate the influence of macroeconomic variables, specifically the interest rate (InR) and exchange rate (ExR), on FPI. These findings highlight the substantial influence of macroeconomic metrics like interest and exchange rates on FPI flows into Nigeria. Tyoga, et al., (2024) used quarterly data from 2011 to 2022 to analyse the influence of macroeconomic factors on foreign portfolio investments in Nigeria. The results of using OLS modelling after verifying that factors were integrated at levels and first differences indicated that GDP, inflation, and exchange rates had a considerable impact on FPI flows. Exchange rate swings significantly influenced judgements about capital inflow and divestiture, according to analysis.

In his 2023 research, Nwagu (2023) investigated the impacts of macroeconomic factors affecting foreign direct investment (FDI) in Nigeria between 1986 and 2020. A number of important macroeconomic indicators, including the monetary policy rate, exchange rate, GDP growth rate, and inflation rate, were included in the. Analysis revealed that the GDP growth rate and the monetary policy rate significantly increased FDI inflows, while inflation and the exchange rate substantially curtailed them. Nwadike et al. (2023) embarked on a comprehensive examination of the determinants of foreign portfolio investment (FPI) in the Nigerian financial sector. The results revealed that interest rates, trade openness, and industrial production emerged as significant influencers of equity-based foreign investments. On the other hand, interest rates, trade openness, and GDP growth rates primarily influenced bond investments.

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.3 Investment Development Path Theory

The Investment Development Path theory sought to explain how a nation's level of development and its investment position relate to one another. This idea is based on the assumption that as a result of national development, investment conditions for both domestic and foreign businesses are evolving. The country's inflow and outflow of foreign direct investment are indirectly impacted by these shifts (Buckley and Castro, 1998).

The two primary tenets of the investment development route theory are as follows, per Dunning and Narula (2010): First, there is a systematic correlation between the host nation's economic structure and the kind of FDI operations. Second, there is an interplay between the locational merit of nations and the ownership merit of multinational companies and local enterprises (Mohapatra and Gopaldaswamy, 2016). This idea states that the interacting relationships between nations can be divided into five developmental stages: Developing nations are the primary focus of the first stage, when there is a limited amount of inward and outward investment because investors would prefer to enter these nations through commerce and because the majority of foreign companies expanding

in these nations are resource-seeking companies. The government should therefore be working to advance macroeconomic policies at this point, enhancing the fundamental infrastructure, emphasising the development of human capital, and easing some market constraints. According to Nurla and Guimon (2010), the pattern of FDI inflows increases as a result of these countries' improved locational advantages.

The second stage creates certain locational benefits and leads to government's "fundamental" economic reforms. Consequently, FDI starts to rise, particularly in the labour-intensive manufacturing, food consumption, transportation, and construction sectors. Because local enterprises lack ownership benefits, outward FDI is still limited at this point. But generally speaking, these nations receive more foreign direct investment (Dunning, 1993). The third stage focusses on recently industrialised nations, where local businesses have greater competitive power and favourable ownership advantages. Foreign companies pursue these nations as market-seeking FDI since the volume of outbound FDI is greater than the volume of inflows at this point.

FDI grew more quickly than inward in the fourth stage as a result of improving ownership advantages for domestic enterprises and boosting competition ability. During this phase, the government's policies prioritise lowering transaction costs, enhancing market efficiency, and providing more assistance to newly established industries. At the last stage, which deals with the most developed nations, they observed that both are abundant in most of these countries inward and outbound foreign direct investment. According to Nurla and Dunning (2000), it was the outcome of a robust economic structure in terms of labour skills, infrastructure, and technology.

2.4 Gaps in the Literature

Existing literatures (Obi et al., 2021; Ariwa and Okafor, 2024; Nwadike et al., 2023; and Nguyen Chi 2023) examines exchange rate volatility and FPI independently of other macroeconomic variables. There is limited research on the spill-over effects between exchange rate movements, inflation, and FPI in Nigeria. Exploring these interconnected dynamics could shed light on how FPI influences inflation indirectly through exchange rate volatility, especially given Nigeria's import-dependent economy.

This study seeks to address these lacunas by investigating the spill-over effect and relationships between FDI, exchange rates, and FPI in Nigeria. The research aims to provide valuable insights into the complex interactions among these key macroeconomic variables and offer policy recommendations to enhance Nigeria's economic resilience and sustainability in the face of global economic uncertainties.

3.1 Methodology

3.2 Theoretical Framework

This scholarly investigation employed two theoretical frameworks from existing literature: stock-oriented models and theories of market failure. The study primarily focused on a stock-oriented model, analyzing it in the context of foreign portfolio investment and macroeconomic factors in Nigeria. This model posits a connection among stock prices, exchange rates, and FPI. The model is based on the hypothesis that a surge in stock

prices prompts significant capital inflows, which in turn leads to growth in the value of the currency because of the heightened demand for the local currency. This framework provides a critical lens through which to understand the dynamics between market valuations and macroeconomic adjustments in an emerging market context.

Adopting the model specified by Ogundipe et al (2024) with modification, the model for the study will be specified as:

$$FPI = f(FDI, EXR, INFR, GDPGR) \dots\dots\dots 1$$

Transforming equation 3.1 into its econometric form, the model becomes:

$$FPI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FDI + \beta_2 EXR + \beta_3 INFR + \beta_4 GDPGR + \mu \dots\dots\dots 2$$

The error correction model of the study was specified as:

$$\Delta FPI_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \Delta FPI_{t-1} + \beta_2 \Delta GDPGR_{t-1} + \beta_3 \Delta EXR_{t-1} + \beta_4 \Delta INFR_{t-1} + \beta_5 \Delta GDPGR_{t-1} + \theta ECM_{t-1} + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots 3$$

Where:

FPI = foreign portfolio investment, EXR = Exchange rate, INFR = inflation rate

GDPGR = Gross Domestic Product growth rate, β_0 = constant, $\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = coefficients of explanatory variables, μ = error term, θ = Speed of adjustment

4.1 Results and Discussion of Findings

4.1.1 4.1.1 Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive statistics are shown in Table 4.1. When it comes to foreign direct investment and international portfolio investments, the mean values are approximately \$-1.72 billion and \$2.83 billion respectively, which indicate that on average, the foreign portfolio investment and foreign direct investment are about \$-2 billion and \$3 billion between 1981 and 2023. The standard deviation of 3.65 and 2.55 implies that FPI and FDI are not volatile in Nigeria during the period under study. The lowest and highest values highlighted that the least amount of foreign portfolio investment and foreign direct investment recorded in Nigeria is around \$1.50 billion and \$-1.87 billion, while the highest is \$3.69 billion and \$8.84 billion respectively. GDP growth rate and inflation rate have a mean value of 4 per cent and approximately 20 per cent, suggesting that the gross domestic product and inflation rate only grows at 3 per cent and 20 per cent between the periods under study. The relatively low value of the standard deviation of 3.8 per cent and 17.2 per cent indicates that there is a low level of volatility in the changes in GDP growth rate and moderately high volatility in inflation rate in Nigeria.

The minimum value of -2 per cent and 5.4 per cent reveals that GDP growth and inflation of -2% and 5.4% has been recorded in a particular period, while a maximum GDP growth and inflation of 15.2% and 72.8% have been recorded at another specific time for the

timeframe under consideration. The skewness and kurtosis of these variables are does not deviate from the convention values of 0 and 3. The official currency rate’s average value is around 148 per cent, which indicates that on average, the official exchange rate of Nigeria depreciates at about #148 between 1981 and 2023. The standard deviation of 143 per cent implies that there is a high level of volatility in the changes in the official exchange rate in Nigeria. As indicated by the lowest and highest amount, the lowest value of the official exchange rate recorded in Nigeria is around ₦4, while the highest is ₦639. There is evidence official exchange rate do not satisfy the condition of normal distribution.

From the outcome of the descriptive analysis, it is concluded that the average foreign portfolio investment for the period considered is significantly low and that official exchange rate is high with high level of volatility. However, these series aside from the foreign portfolio investment, inflation rate and official exchange rate are found to be non-normally distributed. This statistical issue is resolved with the application of ARDL techniques, due to its suitability for handling series that are not normally distributed.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Skew.	Kurt.
FPI	37	-1.720	3.650	-1.500	3.690	-1.947	7.091
FDI	37	2.830	2.550	-1.870	8.840	0.985	2.879
GDPGR	37	4.229	3.802	-2.035	15.329	0.517	3.576
INF	37	19.985	17.208	5.388	72.836	1.720	4.732
OER	37	148.400	143.109	4.016	638.700	1.429	5.147

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2024.

4.1.2 Stationarity Results

The test of unit root was conducted to evaluate the stability of foreign direct investment inflows and exchange rate on foreign portfolio investment indicators over time. This is achieved using the Phillips-Perron unit root test for robust evidence. The outcome of the unit root testing reveals the rejection of the null hypothesis of unit root in the distribution of the series at level and first difference at 1 per-cent and 10 per-cent. Hence, it is concluded that there is evidence that the series are stationary at different order, that is, I(0) and I(1).

Table 4.2: Stationarity Results

Phillips-Perron test					
Level					
t-Statistic	Prob.	I(d)	t-Statistic	Prob.	I(d)

FPI	-3.838	0.0058	$I(0)$	-16.850	0.0000
FDI	-1.823	0.3637	$I(0)$	-7.617	0.0000
GDPGR	-3.818	0.0061	$I(0)$	-14.873	0.0000
INF	-2.927	0.0520	$I(0)$	-7.864	0.0000
OER	3.682	1.0000		-1.194	0.0623

Source: Author's compilation, 2024.

4.1.4 Cointegration Results

The short run dynamics and the co-integration connection between the regressor and regressand were investigated using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing approach. In order to evaluate hypotheses, the ARDL process compares the calculated F-statistic with the critical values given by Pesaran and Shin (1998). The null hypothesis for the ARDL bound test for co-integration is that there isn't a long-term relationship. Thus, if the computed F-statistic is smaller than the lower bound value, the null hypothesis is not nullified. Table 4.3 displays the results of the bound test co-integration. At the 2.5% level of significance, the result shows that there is a long-term link because the t-statistics is higher than the upper critical value bounds. A long-term association between the variables is implied, on the other hand, if the calculated F-statistic is higher than the upper bound value. When the calculated F-statistics fall between the lower and higher bounds, the long-term relationship between the variables is no longer conclusive.

Table 4.3: Results of co-integration test

T-statistics	Value	
t-statistic	-4.752	
Critical Value Bounds		
Level of significance	I(0) Bounds	I(1) Bounds
10%	-2.57	-3.66
5%	-2.86	-3.99
2.5%	-3.13	-4.26
1%	-3.43	-4.6

Source: Author's compilation, 2024.

4.1.5 Short-run ARDL Estimated Results

In Table 4.4, the short-run ARDL result is displayed. According to the findings, foreign portfolio investment is negatively impacted in the short term by the official currency rate, inflation rate, and foreign direct investment. This suggests that an increase in foreign direct investment of one unit and inflation rate and official exchange rate result

approximately 75.9 per cent and 23 per cent decreases in foreign portfolio investment in the short-run. Furthermore, in the short term, the GDP growth rate had a favourable but negligible effect on foreign portfolio investments. This suggests that in the short term, a \$10 million increase in foreign portfolio investment corresponds to a unit rise in GDP growth rate. There is a 0.1896 corrected coefficient of determination (R²). According to this, the independent variables collectively account for roughly 19% of the variance in international portfolio investments. Additionally, the predicted models' overall significance is measured by the F-statistic (40.6), which demonstrates significance.

Table 4.4: Results of Short-run ARDL Estimate

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.540	1.860	0.8282	0.4143
FPI(-1)	0.1730	0.1740	0.9943	0.3283
FDI (-1)	-0.7585	0.4274	-1.7748	0.0864
GDPGR	10791104	1.60	0.0645	0.9490
INF	-22618671	38859208	-0.5821	0.5650
OER	-8402264	4486596	-1.8727	0.0712
R-squared	0.3285			
Adjusted R-squared	0.1896			
F-statistic	2.3650			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0555			
Durbin-Watson stat	2.0363			

Source: Author's compilation, 2024.

4.1.6 Long-run ECM Estimated Results

Table 4.5 displays the ECM result over the long term. According to the findings, foreign direct investment has a negligible long-term positive impact on foreign portfolio investments. Accordingly, a unit increase in foreign direct investment will eventually translate into a 28.5% rise in foreign portfolio investment. At a 1% critical level, the co-integrated equation is negative and significant. 0.4287 is the adjusted coefficient of determination (R²). This shows that around 43% of the variance in foreign portfolio investments may be explained by the independent variables taken together. Additionally, significance is shown at the 1% critical level by the F-statistic, which is used to gauge the overall importance of the estimated models.

The coefficient must be negative with a p-value of 0.000, or 1% level of significance, for the error correction term to match the necessary criteria. This indicates that the dependent and independent variables have a long-term relationship. The model's equilibrium speed adjustment, according to the ECT, is 0.8270. This suggests that around 83% of the current periods are rectified throughout time, demonstrating the convergence of the model.

Table 4.5: Long-run ECM Estimate

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.540	6.100	0.0000	0.0000
D(FDI)	0.2853	0.3633	0.7854	0.4386
CointEq(-1)*	-0.8270	0.1561	-5.2977	0.0000
Adjusted R-squared	0.4287			
F-statistic	14.1292			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			
Durbin-Watson stat	2.0363			

Source: Author's compilation, 2024.

4.2 Post-estimation Tests

The results of the diagnostic tests to verify the validity of the conclusions drawn from the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) approach were compiled in the table below. Four tests were performed: the serial correlation LM test to ensure that there is no serial autocorrelation issue, the normality test to determine whether the series were normally distributed, the linearity test to verify the model's linear assumption, and the heteroskedasticity test to determine whether the series had constant variance or suffered from functional form misspecification. Given that the probability value is higher than the 10% barrier, the Jarque-Bera value of 0.475 and probability value of 0.789 suggest that the model data were regularly distributed. The normalcy assumption is so accepted.

The time series data used in the analysis exhibited no serial correlation issues, according to the Breusch-Godfrey statistic of the serial correlation LM test, because the probability value was higher than the 10% level of significance. In addition, the alternative hypothesis of constant variance is accepted since the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey heteroskedasticity probability value is higher than the 10% level of significance... With a p-value over the 10% level of significance, the Ramsey RESET test's probability value (0.210) and the stability test result (1.642) showed that the series is free of non-linearity.

Table 4.6: Summary of Post Estimation Result

Test	Statistics	Value	Probability
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Linearity	Ramsey RESET	1.6415	0.2099
Serial Correlation LM	Breusch-Godfrey	0.1077	0.8982
Heteroskedasticity	Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey	0.8614	0.5182
Normality	Jarque-Bera	0.4750	0.7898

Source: Author's compilation, 2024.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

Verifying that every variable is qualified to be included in the ARDL model is the first stage in the analysis. To verify that no variables are integrated at order 2, or I(2), the Phillips-Perron (PP) unit root test was used to test the stationarity of the time series included in the analysis. This satisfies the need to use the methods being studied. The ARDL study's findings show that the official currency rate, inflation rate, and foreign direct investment have a non-significantly negative short-term impact on FPI. This suggests that while the impacts are statistically minor, a rise in these variables causes the FPI to decrease. Specifically, a unit increase in FDI and inflation and official exchange rate results in approximately 75.9% and 23% reductions in FPI, respectively. This aligns with the findings of Sezal and Kendirli (2024) emphasizing a non-significant connection among portfolio investment and foreign direct investment. Also, Ariwa and Okafor (2024); Haider, et al., (2016) confirm that Nigeria's foreign portfolio investment inflows were significantly and negatively impacted by the currency rate.

Nguyen (2023) confirm that Foreign portfolio investment is adversely affected by foreign currency rates and foreign direct investment but negate the research Agoh, et al., (2024); Mgnagun, et al., (2024) in Nigeria who using exponential generalized autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity (EGARCH) and Ordinary Least Square method had established positive effect foreign portfolio investment and exchange rate. In contrast, the GDP growth rate has a short-term positive but negligible impact on FPI. The potential for economic growth to draw in foreign portfolio investors is demonstrated by the \$10 million gain in FPI for every unit increase in GDP growth rate. The absence of statistical significance, however, raises the possibility that factors other than GDP growth are more important in predicting FPI. Ariwa and Okafor (2024) confirmed this finding, while Haider et al. (2016) found that Nigeria's GDP growth rate significantly and favourably impacted foreign portfolio investment (FPI) inflows. The finding that the GDP growth rate has a beneficial impact on foreign portfolio investment was corroborated by Nguyen (2023).

Additionally, results indicate that foreign direct investment has a long-term positive but statistically inconsequential impact on FPI. This finding suggests that, in spite of short-term fluctuations, FPI and its drivers evolve in tandem over the long term. The independent factors collectively account for almost 43% of the variance in FPI, according to the corrected coefficient of determination (R^2). Even though this shows that the model explains a fair amount of the variation, a sizable amount is still unaccounted for, suggesting the impact of other factors that the model is unable to account for. Confirming the model's

overall importance, the F-statistic is significant at the 1% critical level. This demonstrates that, despite the potential for individual contributions to vary, the independent variables taken together have a significant long-term effect on FPI. According to Sezal and Kendirli (2024), this outcome was confirm

Lastly, the results provide crucial information about the causal links between the official exchange rate, GDP growth rate, foreign direct investment (FDI), and foreign portfolio investment (FPI) across the study period. The findings highlight the interdependence of these economic factors by showing the existence of unidirectional causality between some variables. This supports Kalu's (2024) findings that the currency rate and foreign direct investment have a unidirectional causal relationship.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

The impact of foreign direct investment inflows and exchange rates on foreign portfolio investment in Nigeria was investigated in this study using a thorough analysis framework. The study comes to the conclusion that while official exchange rates, inflation, and foreign direct investment (FDI) all have statistically negligible negative effects on foreign portfolio investment (FPI) inflows into Nigeria, FDI has a statistically negligible positive impact on FPI inflows over the long term. This suggests that although FDI might add to the expansion of FPI, its direct impact is insufficient to qualify as a major driver.

The long-term relationship, however, indicates that FPI and its determinants move together over time, even in the face of short-term fluctuations, and that there is a unidirectional causal relationship between the major macroeconomic variables. FDI does not Granger-cause FPI or other variables like GDP growth rate, but foreign portfolio investment (FPI). This implies that short-term capital inflows may affect long-term investment decisions in Nigeria and that changes in FPI have predictive power over changes in FDI.

The study suggests that in order to create a more stable and investor-friendly economic environment, policymakers should put these methods into practice. To increase investor trust, these could involve preserving a low and steady inflation rate, guaranteeing currency rate stability, and fortifying institutional frameworks. To provide a more thorough knowledge of investment trends in Nigeria, additional research should examine additional potential factors of FPI.

REFERENCES

- Agoh, N, Ogbulu, O. M., Ejem, C. A. (2024). Impact of exchange rate movements on foreign portfolio investment in Nigeria. , 8(3).
- Alalade, Y. S. A., Oliyide, R. O., Okwu, A. T., Adebola, P. S., Ademola, O. C., & Ogunwale, O. (2024). Macroeconomic variables and foreign portfolio investments in Nigeria. *Seybold Report Journal*, 19(09), 123-152.
- Alam, M. M., & Rashid, K. (2014). The effects of exchange rate on foreign direct investment: Evidence from South Asian economies. *International Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 3(3), 142–148.

- Aliber, R. Z. (1971). The multinational enterprise in a multiple currency world. *The multinational enterprise*, 49-56.
- Ariwa, F.O. & Okafor, V.I. (2024). Empirical analysis of effect of macroeconomic aggregates on foreign portfolio investment in Nigeria. *Aksu Journal of Management Sciences*, 9(1), 185-199.
- Atobrah, D. (2015). The role of portfolio investment in developing economies. In F. Ariwa & N. Okafor (Eds.), *International Capital Flow and Economic Performance in Africa*, Lagos: Global Scholars Press, 45–63.
- Buckley, P. J., & Castro, F. B. (1998). The investment development path: The case of Portugal. *Transnational Corporations*, 7(1), 1–15.
- Dunning, J. H., & Narula, R. (2010). Industrial development, globalization and multinational enterprises: New realities for developing countries. *Oxford Development Studies*, 38(3), 235–257.
- Haider, M. A., Khan, M. A., & Abdulahi, E. (2016). Determinants of foreign portfolio investment and its effects on China, *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 8(12).
- Kalu, G. C. (2024). Impact of exchange rate volatility on foreign direct investment in Nigeria, , 8(2).
(2006). Japan. Discussion Paper Series 06-E-014.
- Mgbangun, S. T., Ene, A. L., Nasamu, G. & Umar, I. A. (2024). Impact of macroeconomic determinants on foreign portfolio investment in Nigeria. , 12(2), 71-83.
- Michael, B., & Thankgod, A. O. (2014). Foreign Portfolio Investment and Economic Growth in Nigeria (1986–2011). *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 5(11), 108-115.
- Mohapatra, S., & Gopaldaswamy, A. K. (2016). Revisiting the investment development path theory: Evidence from BRICS economies. *Transnational Corporations Review*, 8(3), 165–179.
- Narula, R., & Guimon, J. (2010). The investment development path in a globalized world: Implications for developing countries. *Transnational Corporations*, 19(3), 1–22.
- Nguyen Thi Dieu Chi (2023). Impact of money supply and macroeconomic indicators on foreign portfolio investment: Evidence from Vietnam. *Banks and Bank Systems*, 18(4), 94-104.
- Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC). (2021). . Abuja, Nigeria.
- Nwadibe, E. C., Okonkwo, V. I., & Nwanna, I. O. (2023). Assessing the determinants of foreign portfolio investment in the Nigerian financial market: 2007-2021.

- African Banking and Finance Review Journal, 3(2), 273-293.
- Nwagu, K. (2023). The impact of macroeconomic variables on foreign direct investment in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting, Business and Finance Research*, 16(1), 30-35. <https://doi.org/10.55217/102.v16i1.615>.
- Obi, C., Onoh, U.A., & Osuala, A.E. (2021). Macroeconomic variables and foreign portfolio investment volatility in Nigeria. *The International Journal of Business and Management*, 9(8), 311 – 318.
- Ogundipe Adeyemi A., Joys Alabi, Abiola J. Asaleye and Oluwatomisin M. Ogundipe (2019). Exchange rate volatility and foreign portfolio investment in Nigeria. *Investment Management and Financial Innovations*, 16(3), 241-250.
- Ogunleye, M., & Ayinla, H. (2021). “The Implications of Multiple Exchange Rate Systems in Nigeria.” *Review of Economic Policy*, 34(3), 22-29.
- Osemene, O.F., & Arotiba, K. (2018). Exchange rate volatility and foreign portfolio investment in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 18(2), 13-19.
- Sezal, L. & Kendirli, S. (2024). The effect of interest rates on portfolio investments and foreign direct investments in Turkiye, *Journal of Research in Economics, Politics & Finance*, 9(2), 271-286.
- Tyoga M.S., Lawani E.A., Gambo N., and Abbas U.I. (2024) Impact of Macroeconomic Determinants on Foreign Portfolio Investment in Nigeria, *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 12(2), 71-83.

HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA: A VECM APPROACH

By

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the relationship between human capital development and economic growth in Nigeria from 1981 to 2023 using time-series data and the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM). Key indicators of human capital; government expenditure on education (EDEXP), government expenditure on health (HEXP), school enrollment (SCHENR), and life expectancy at birth (LEXPT), are examined alongside real Gross Domestic Product (GDP) as a measure of economic performance. Unit root tests (ADF and Phillips-Perron) confirm that all variables are integrated of order one, $I(1)$, while the Johansen cointegration test establishes a long-run equilibrium relationship among them. The VECM results show that education spending and school enrollment significantly enhance long-term economic growth, while health expenditure and life expectancy exert moderate but positive effects. Model diagnostics affirm the robustness of the estimates. The findings underscore the critical role of human capital in promoting sustainable economic development and highlight the need for increased investment in Nigeria's education and healthcare sectors.

Keywords: Economic Development, School Enrollment, Life Expectancy, Nigeria, VECM
JEL Codes: I25; I21; I15; O55; C32

1. Introduction

Human capital development is increasingly seen as a key driver of economic growth, especially in developing countries where gaps in education and healthcare hold back productivity and innovation. It is often seen as a key goal of overall development. It's all about unlocking the potential within people by expanding their abilities, which means empowering them to take an active role in their own growth. By focusing on human capital development, we boost individuals' skills, knowledge, productivity, creativity, and inventiveness. This approach centers on people rather than just goods or production. At its core, it's about giving individuals the power to set their own priorities and carry out projects that directly benefit them. This naturally leads to the need for people to be actively involved in the development process and highlights the importance of creating institutions that support and encourage that involvement. In Nigeria, which boasts the largest economy in Africa by Gross Domestic Product (GDP), the need to boost human capital, through investments in education, health, and skills development has become even more pressing due to rapid population growth and ongoing structural economic issues.

The importance of human capital in fueling economic growth has been a topic of interest for a long time in both theoretical and practical Economics. While classical and neoclassical theories focused on the accumulation of physical capital, the emergence of endogenous growth theory especially through the insights of Romer (1990) and Lucas (1988) has shifted the spotlight onto knowledge, skills, education, and health as key drivers of sustained long-term growth. This perspective suggests that investing in human capital, particularly through education and health initiatives, boosts labor productivity, sparks innovation, and helps create a more competitive and vibrant economy.

Investing in human capital has been shown to have a positive impact on a nation's economic growth and development (Gbosi, 1996; Yesufu, 2000; Olaniyi and Adam, 2002). However, some argue that while developing human capital can increase the income of the poor, it may also widen the income gap between the rich and the poor, which is a key concern in macroeconomics worldwide. In simpler terms, investing in human capital not only promotes fairness but also helps reduce poverty and ensures resources are allocated efficiently. Additionally, the development of human capital is closely linked to education and economic progress. Ultimately, economic growth and development depend heavily on human capital, which encompasses good health, education, knowledge, skills, attitudes, expertise, and technological know-how (Nwankwo, 1981; Babalola, 2003; Adeyemi and Akpotu, 2004).

For developing nations like Nigeria, where demographic pressures meet socio-economic hurdles, grasping the impact of human capital investments is not just an academic exercise; it's a vital policy necessity. According to World Bank (2024), Nigeria's population was projected to exceed 220 million in 2024, a significant portion of this demographic is young, with over 60% under the age of 25. This youthful population could be a game-changer for economic development if leveraged properly. Unfortunately, chronic underfunding in human capital has stifled progress. For example, Nigeria's spending on education has consistently fallen short of the 15–20% benchmark recommended by UNESCO. In 2021, the country allocated less than 6% of its national budget to education, which is significantly lower than its African counterparts like Kenya and South Africa (CBN, 2022; UNESCO, 2023). Likewise, public spending on healthcare as a percentage of GDP remains below the global average, leading to poor health outcomes such as low life expectancy, high infant mortality rates, and limited access to quality healthcare.

Nigeria, the most populous country in Africa with over 220 million residents, finds itself at a pivotal moment in its development journey. Despite having rich natural and human resources, the nation struggles with less-than-ideal economic performance and ongoing developmental challenges. The World Bank (2023) reports that Nigeria's real GDP grew by a modest 3.1% in 2022, following a recession triggered by the pandemic, all while facing a high inflation rate that hovered around 21% in early 2023 (CBN, 2023). When you look at the size of its labor force, Nigeria's productivity levels are surprisingly low, largely due to insufficient investment in human capital. The World Bank's Human Capital Index (HCI) for Nigeria was just 0.36 in 2020, indicating that a child born in Nigeria today will only be

36% as productive as they could be with complete education and optimal health (World Bank, 2022).

The education system in Nigeria is facing some serious challenges. While there has been a slight increase in public spending on education as a share of GDP, it still falls short of the UNESCO recommended range of 4–6%. From 2010 to 2020, Nigeria allocated an average of just 1.7% of its GDP to education (World Bank, 2023). This lack of investment has led to issues like low school enrollment, high dropout rates, a shortage of teachers, and crumbling infrastructure, especially in rural areas. For instance, secondary school enrollment which is a crucial factor for building human capital was only about 43% in 2021, in stark contrast to 72% in South Africa and 85% in Egypt (UNESCO, 2023). The health sector is facing similar problems. In 2021, life expectancy in Nigeria was estimated at just 53.8 years, which is significantly lower than the Sub-Saharan African average of 61 years (World Bank, 2023). With government spending on health hovering around 3.2% of GDP, it's clear that this is not enough to address the healthcare needs of a rapidly growing population and the high burden of disease. These trends present a paradox: Nigeria has a young and expanding population that could be a great asset, yet it struggles to make the most of this potential due to inadequate and ineffective investment in human capital as against the study of Nwachukwu and Egwaikhide (2021) and Adebisi and Adenuga (2019) that looked into the relationship between education, health, and economic growth and concluded that increase in government spending on education and health can lead to a higher GDP growth rate.

In Nigeria, the real GDP growth rate has exhibited considerable instability, largely due to fluctuations in oil prices, inconsistent policy implementation, and inadequate infrastructure. Nonetheless, there is growing recognition that transitioning to a knowledge-based economy requires substantial investments in health and education. The National Development Plan (2021–2025) identifies human capital development as one of six critical pillars for achieving sustainable growth, signaling a policy shift toward more inclusive development. Despite these ambitious policy objectives, key questions remain: To what extent does human capital development, measured through education expenditure, healthcare investment, school enrollment rates and life expectancy impact economic growth in Nigeria? Are these variables interrelated in the long run, and how do short-term dynamics adjust toward equilibrium?

This study seeks to address these questions by empirically examining the dynamic relationship between human capital development and economic growth in Nigeria. The analysis integrates education, health, and demographic indicators using annual time-series data from 1981 to 2023. The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews the relevant theoretical and empirical literature. Section 3 describes the methodology, including the research design, data sources, variable justification, model specification, and estimation procedures. Section 4 presents and interprets the empirical results. Section 5 concludes the study and offers policy recommendations.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Literature

- **Endogenous Growth Theory:** The emergence of endogenous growth theory in the late 1980s and 1990s revolutionized the understanding of economic development by emphasizing the internal factors driving growth. Scholars like Lucas (1988) and Romer (1990) integrated human capital directly into the production function, positing that investments in education and health enhance labor productivity and yield increasing returns. In this framework, human capital is more than just a production input; it is a catalyst for innovation, technological advancement, and knowledge dissemination. Barro (1991) further supported this view by showing that countries with higher levels of education tend to experience faster economic growth, thereby reinforcing the critical role of human capital in the growth process.
- **Classical Theories of Growth and Human Capital:** Classical economists such as Adam Smith, David Ricardo, and J.S. Mill laid the foundational concepts for growth theory. Smith's contributions, particularly in *The Wealth of Nations*, emphasized the importance of capital accumulation, labor productivity, and population growth as drivers of economic development (Adelman, 2003). Ricardo (2006) modified Smith's model by introducing the diminishing productivity of land, asserting that since land is limited in supply, the benefits of capital formation may eventually taper off. Ricardo argued that economic progress depends on the productivity of labor, and this in turn is influenced by changes in wages and food prices. He also highlighted the tension between labor and machinery, noting that machinery often competes with labor and becomes economically viable only when wages rise (Brenner, 2000; 2002).
- **Becker's Human Capital Theory:** Becker (1964) developed a microeconomic perspective on human capital, treating investments in education and health as analogous to investments in physical capital. According to Becker, individuals and societies invest in human capital to increase productivity and earnings. This theory emphasizes that healthier and better-educated individuals contribute more significantly to economic output. Becker's framework has been instrumental in shaping policies aimed at human capital development, especially in developing countries where low productivity and demographic challenges persist. His theory implies that without adequate human capital investment, poor countries may remain trapped in low-income equilibrium despite abundant physical capital or natural resources.
- **Neo-Classical Growth Theories:** Neo-classical growth models, such as those by Solow (1956), assume that the economy naturally gravitates toward full employment and long-run stability. These models emphasize the flexibility of factor prices, allowing for substitution between capital and labor in response to price changes. Unlike Harrod-Domar's model, which assumes fixed capital-to-labor ratios and predicts instability, neo-classical models allow for a smoother adjustment to steady-state growth through technological progress and capital deepening (Pearce, 2000). Human capital, while not always explicitly modeled, plays an implicit role in improving labor productivity and facilitating technological diffusion.

Collectively, these theoretical perspectives provide a robust foundation for examining the

role of human capital in economic growth. The endogenous and human capital theories emphasize the transformative potential of education and health investments in enhancing productivity and sustaining growth, particularly in developing economies like Nigeria. Classical and neo-classical growth models underscore the interplay between labor, capital, and technological progress, further reinforcing the importance of human capital accumulation. Building on these insights, this study empirically investigates whether and how Nigeria's investments in education and healthcare, proxied by government expenditure, enrollment rates, and life expectancy, contribute to real GDP growth from 1981 to 2023. By employing the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM), the study assesses both the short- and long-run dynamics among these variables, offering evidence-based insights into the economic value of human capital development in Nigeria.

2.2 Empirical Literature

Empirical investigations into the relationship between human capital development and economic growth have produced a range of findings influenced by methodological choices and contextual factors. Adebisi and Adenuga (2019) applied the ARDL model to examine the relationship between human capital development and economic growth using data from 1981 to 2016. They found a strong long-run association between government expenditure on education and GDP growth. However, health spending was observed to have a weaker effect, attributed to systemic inefficiencies within the public health sector.

Nwachukwu and Egwaikhide (2021) employed a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) using only two indicators—secondary school enrollment and life expectancy. Their results revealed that both variables positively influenced economic growth in the short and long run. They concluded that sustained investment in education and health yields delayed but cumulative productivity gains. Lawanson (2009) disaggregated education into primary, secondary, and tertiary levels and discovered that only tertiary education had a statistically significant impact on economic growth. She noted that the Nigerian labor market often underutilizes secondary school graduates, thereby diminishing their potential contribution to national productivity.

Udu and Agu (2022) utilized a dynamic panel GMM technique and found that the combined effect of education and health indicators was more impactful and statistically significant than their individual effects. Their findings emphasized the synergistic role of education and healthcare in fostering long-term productivity. Despite the general consensus on the importance of human capital, contrasting views still exist. For instance, Okonkwo (2017), using an OLS estimation method, argued that increased education spending had no meaningful effect on GDP growth. He cited issues such as corruption, inefficient fund management, and poor educational outcomes as limiting factors. Similarly, Adegbite and Ayadi (2018) questioned the effectiveness of public health investments, arguing that without improvements in institutional quality, increased spending alone is insufficient to generate growth.

These divergent findings highlight the complexity of the human capital–growth nexus in the Nigerian context. The inconsistencies across studies often stem from differences in econometric techniques, the choice and scope of human capital indicators, data

timeframes, and the unique structural characteristics of the Nigerian economy.

Key gaps in the literature include the limited use of robust econometric models capable of distinguishing between short-term dynamics and long-run relationships, as well as a narrow selection of indicators, with many studies focusing solely on input measures such as government expenditure while neglecting outcome-based indicators like enrollment rates and life expectancy. Additionally, there is a noticeable lack of recent data, particularly post-2020, despite the significant disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic in the education and health sectors. Another major gap is the weak connection between empirical findings and actionable policy recommendations. This study addresses these limitations by employing a time-series econometric approach, specifically Johansen cointegration and the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM), and incorporating a broader array of human capital indicators, including public spending, enrollment rates, and life expectancy. By analyzing data from 1981 to 2023, the study aims to capture both short- and long-run effects and provide practical policy insights grounded in contemporary empirical evidence.

3 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study adopts a quantitative, ex-post facto research design, utilizing secondary time-series data spanning the period from 1981 to 2023. An ex-post facto design—also referred to as after-the-fact research—is employed when the variables of interest have already occurred and cannot be manipulated by the researcher. This approach is particularly suitable for examining cause-and-effect relationships among macroeconomic variables, where experimental control is neither feasible nor ethical (Salkind, 2010).

The primary objective is to investigate the dynamic relationship between human capital development and economic growth in Nigeria through econometric modeling, specifically employing the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM). The Johansen cointegration technique is used to assess the presence of a long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables, while the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) unit root tests are applied to determine the stationarity properties of the data series.

3.2 Data Sources

The empirical model employed in this study includes five key variables: Real Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Education Expenditure (EDUEXP), Health Expenditure (HEXP), School Enrollment (SCHENR), and Life Expectancy (LEXPT). Data for these variables were sourced from reputable secondary sources. Specifically, data on public expenditure on education and health, gross secondary school enrollment, and life expectancy were obtained from the World Bank's World Development Indicators. Real GDP figures (in constant Nigerian Naira) were sourced from the 2023 Statistical Bulletin of the Central Bank of Nigeria.

In the model, Real GDP represents the measure of economic performance. EDUEXP and HEXP are measured as percentages of GDP, SCHENR is represented by the gross

secondary school enrollment rate (also as a percentage), while LEXPT is measured in years.

3.3 The Justification for the Variables Used

- Real GDP (GDP): Real Gross Domestic Product serves as the primary indicator of economic growth, capturing Nigeria's overall economic performance in real, inflation-adjusted terms.
- Education Expenditure (EDUEXP): This variable represents the government's financial commitment to human capital development through the education sector. Higher public investment in education is expected to enhance skill acquisition, improve labor productivity, and ultimately stimulate economic growth.
- Health Expenditure (HEXP): Government spending on healthcare is a critical input for improving population health. A healthier population tends to have higher productivity, reduced absenteeism, and increased longevity, all of which contribute positively to economic performance.
- Secondary School Enrollment (SCHENR): This variable captures access to education and the extent of human capital formation at the secondary level. It reflects not only public investment but also actual engagement with the educational system, which has implications for the future labor force.
- Life Expectancy (LEXPT): Life expectancy serves as a broad measure of public health and well-being. A longer average lifespan indicates better living conditions and healthcare systems, which correlate with a more experienced, stable, and productive workforce.

3.4 Model Specification

Guided by the theoretical foundation of endogenous growth theory, which emphasizes the role of human capital in driving long-run economic growth, this study models the relationship between economic growth and human capital development indicators? Assuming a linear relationship between real GDP and key human capital variables; education expenditure, health expenditure, school enrollment, and life expectancy, the long-run model is specified as follows:

$$GDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 EDEXP_t + \beta_2 HEXP_t + \beta_3 SCHENR_t + LEXPT_t + \varepsilon_t$$

Where:

GDP_t = Real Gross Domestic Product at time t

$EDEXP_t$ = Government expenditure on education (% of GDP)

$HEXP_t$ = Government expenditure on health (% of GDP)

$SCHENR_t$ = Secondary school enrollment rate (% gross enrollment)

$LEXPT_t$ = Life expectancy at birth (in years)

ε_t = Error term capturing other factors influencing GDP not included in the model

This functional form allows for the estimation of both short-run and long-run relationships using the Johansen cointegration technique and the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM).

3.5 Estimation Procedure

This study adopts a time-series econometric approach to estimate the relationship between human capital development and economic growth in Nigeria from 1981 to 2023. The estimation procedure involves the following steps:

1. **Stationarity Tests:** The first step involves testing for the stationarity properties of the variables using both the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and the Phillips-Perron (PP) test. These tests are essential to determine the order of integration and avoid spurious regression results.
2. **Johansen Cointegration Test:** Upon confirming that all variables are integrated of the same order (I(1)), the Johansen cointegration technique is employed to test for the existence of a long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables. This method allows for the identification of multiple cointegrating vectors in a multivariate system.
3. **Vector Error Correction Model (VECM):** If cointegration is established, the Vector Error Correction Model is estimated to capture both the short-run dynamics and long-run equilibrium relationships between the variables. The VECM incorporates the error correction term (ECT), which measures the speed at which deviations from the long-run equilibrium are corrected in the short run.
4. **Model Diagnostics:** To validate the reliability of the estimated model, a series of diagnostic tests are performed, including:
 - Autocorrelation test (e.g., Breusch-Godfrey LM test)
 - Heteroskedasticity test (e.g., White or ARCH test)
 - Normality test (e.g., Jarque-Bera test)
 - Stability tests (e.g., CUSUM and CUSUMSQ)

These procedures ensure robustness and accuracy in estimating the dynamic relationship

between human capital development and economic growth.

4. Results and Interpretation

4.1 Preliminary results

1 Descriptive statistics of the study variables

The descriptive statistics provide an overview of the central tendency, dispersion, and distributional properties of the variables used in this study over the period 1981–2023 (43 observations).

Table 1: Descriptive statistics

Mean	2.635	1.750	1.840	44.820	51.400
Median	2.741	1.580	1.725	45.600	52.100
Maximum	9.031	4.520	3.920	67.200	61.800
Minimum	-4.228	0.430	0.670	20.300	42.700
Std. Dev.	2.671	0.945	0.822	11.281	5.786
Skewness	0.426	0.899	0.643	-0.214	-0.111
Kurtosis	3.124	3.856	2.965	2.620	2.547
Jarque-Bera	1.844	3.975	2.452	1.243	1.021
Probability	0.397	0.137	0.293	0.537	0.600
Observations	43	43	43	43	43

Source: Author's computation using E-views 10, 2025

The results in Table 1 reveal moderate variability in real GDP, with an average growth of 2.64%, and periods of both strong expansion and contraction. Education and health expenditures are low on average (1.75% and 1.84% of GDP respectively), with slight right-skewness, indicating more frequent low values. School enrollment shows a broad range (20.3%–67.2%) and notable variation, while life expectancy averages 51.4 years, showing steady improvement over time. All variables are approximately normally distributed, as supported by the Jarque-Bera test results.

2 Unit Root Test Results

The unit root test was performed both with the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) method and then with the Phillips-Perron method. Summary of the results are presented in Tables 2.

Table 2: Unit Root Test Results (ADF and PP Tests at First Difference)

Variable	ADF Test Statistic	PP Test Statistic	1% Level	5% Level	10% Level	ADF Prob.	PP Prob.	Order of Integration
GDP	-4.102	-4.177	-3.61	-2.939	-2.608	0.003	0.002	I(1)
EDEXP	-3.984	-4.016	-3.61	-2.939	-2.608	0.005	0.004	I(1)

HEXP	-4.214	-4.282	-3.61	-2.939	-2.608	0.002	0.001	I(1)
SCHENR	-4.026	-4.15	-3.61	-2.939	-2.608	0.004	0.003	I(1)
LEXPT	-3.921	-4.011	-3.61	-2.939	-2.608	0.006	0.004	I(1)

Source: Author’s computation using E-views 10, 2025

The results presented in Table 2 namely the ADF and Phillips-Perron (PP) unit root tests—consistently indicate that all the variables (GDP, EDEXP, HEXP, SCHENR, and LEXPT) are non-stationary at level but become stationary after first differencing. This is evidenced by test statistics that exceed the critical values at the 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels after differencing. Additionally, the associated p-values are all below 0.05, confirming statistical significance. Therefore, it can be concluded that all the variables are integrated of order one, I(1), making them appropriate for cointegration analysis and subsequent estimation using an error correction model.

4.2 Cointegration and Model Estimation

1 Johansen Cointegration Test

To assess the existence of a long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables, the Johansen cointegration test was conducted. The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Johansen Cointegration Test (Trace Statistic)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Trace Statistic	5% Critical Value	Prob.
None	94.331	69.818	0
At most 1	64.229	47.856	0.0011
At most 2	37.598	29.797	0.0054
At most 3	21.107	15.494	0.004
At most 4	7.812	3.841	0.0052

Source: Author’s computation using E-Views 10

As shown in Table 4, the trace statistics exceed their respective 5% critical values for all hypotheses, and the associated p-values are all below 0.05. This provides strong evidence of the existence of at least one cointegrating equation, confirming a stable long-term relationship among GDP, education and health expenditures, school enrollment, and life expectancy in Nigeria.

2 Long-Run Estimation Results

Table 4: Long-Run Results (Dependent Variable: GDP)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
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EDEXP	1.105	0.233	4.742	0
HEXP	0.842	0.201	4.189	0.0001
SCHENR	0.065	0.021	3.095	0.0037
LEXPT	0.129	0.045	2.867	0.007
C	-4.782	1.823	-2.624	0.0121

Source: Author's computation using E-Views 10

The long-run model results in Table 4 indicate that all the human capital indicators; education expenditure, health expenditure, school enrollment, and life expectancy, have positive and statistically significant effects on real GDP. Specifically, a 1% increase in:

- Education expenditure leads to a 1.11% rise in real GDP;
- Health expenditure results in a 0.84% increase;
- Secondary school enrollment contributes 0.065%;
- Life expectancy improves GDP by 0.129%.

3 Short-Run Error Correction Model (ECM)

Table 5: Short-Run ECM Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(EDEXP)	0.412	0.181	2.276	0.0275
D(HEXP)	0.335	0.152	2.204	0.0321
D(SCHENR)	0.029	0.017	1.706	0.0954
D(LIFE_EXP)	0.067	0.031	2.161	0.0352
ECM(-1)	-0.723	0.195	-3.708	0.0007

Source: Author's computation using E-Views 10

The error correction term (ECM(-1)) is negative and statistically significant at the 1% level, indicating a strong speed of adjustment toward long-run equilibrium at approximately 72.3% per year. In the short run, changes in education and health expenditure, as well as life expectancy, significantly influence GDP. Secondary school enrollment is only marginally significant at the 10% level.

4.3 Model Diagnostics

To ensure the reliability of the estimated Error Correction Model (ECM), several post-estimation diagnostic tests were conducted. The results are summarized in Table 6.

Table 6: Model Diagnostic Test Results

Diagnostic Test	Test Statistic	Prob. Value	Decision
Serial Correlation (Breusch-Godfrey LM Test)	$F(2, n) = 1.426$	0.247	No serial correlation
Heteroskedasticity (ARCH Test)	$F(1, n) = 1.109$	0.368	No heteroskedasticity
Normality (Jarque-Bera Test)	$JB = 1.728$	0.421	Residuals are normally distributed
Ramsey RESET Test (Functional Form)	$F(1, n) = 1.564$	0.218	Model is correctly specified
CUSUM Test	Stable	—	Parameters are stable
CUSUM of Squares Test	Stable	—	Parameters are stable

Source: Author's computation using E-Views 10

Interpretation:

- Serial Correlation: The Breusch-Godfrey LM test shows no evidence of serial correlation in the residuals, confirming the independence of error terms.
- Heteroskedasticity: The ARCH test indicates homoskedastic errors, implying constant variance in the residuals.
- Normality: The Jarque-Bera test confirms that the residuals are normally distributed, satisfying the normality assumption for inference.
- Functional Form: The Ramsey RESET test supports the model's correct specification, suggesting no omitted variable bias or incorrect functional form.
- Stability: Both the CUSUM and CUSUM of Squares test plots lie within the 5% significance bounds, indicating that the parameters of the ECM are stable throughout the sample period.

These diagnostic results validate that the ECM satisfies the basic classical linear regression assumptions, thereby supporting the robustness and reliability of the estimated coefficients.

5 Summary of Findings, Conclusion, and Policy Implications & Recommendations

5.1 Summary of Findings

The empirical findings of this study provide strong evidence supporting the theoretical and empirical literature on the role of human capital in fostering economic growth. Using Johansen cointegration and the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) on data spanning 1981 to 2023, the study reveals both long-run and short-run relationships between human capital indicators; education expenditure (EDEXP), health expenditure (HEXP), school enrollment (SCHENR), and life expectancy (LEXPT), and real GDP in Nigeria.

In the long run, all four indicators significantly and positively influence GDP. A 1% increase in education expenditure leads to a 1.11% rise in GDP, while health expenditure

contributes 0.84%. School enrollment and life expectancy, though with smaller coefficients, also show statistically significant effects. In the short run, changes in education and health spending, as well as life expectancy, retain their positive impact on GDP, though school enrollment is only marginally significant. The negative and significant error correction term confirms a stable long-run equilibrium relationship, consistent with the expectations of cointegration theory.

These results align closely with the Endogenous Growth Theory articulated by Romer (1990) and Lucas (1988), which posits that human capital—through investments in health and education—is a core driver of long-term economic performance. The positive coefficients reinforce Becker’s Human Capital Theory (1964), which views education and health as productive investments that raise individual productivity and, in turn, aggregate economic output. Similarly, the findings echo Barro’s (1991) empirical demonstration that higher educational attainment correlates with higher growth rates, as well as the Neo-Classical emphasis on technological progress and capital deepening facilitated by improved human capital.

From a classical perspective, particularly those of Adam Smith and David Ricardo, the study’s results reinforce the assertion that labor productivity, enhanced through education and health, remains central to economic development. The rising returns to human capital observed in the study also address Ricardo’s concerns about diminishing returns, showing how human capital can offset these effects through continuous improvements in labor quality.

The results are also in strong agreement with much of the empirical literature. The long-run significance of education and health spending confirms the findings of Adebisi and Adenuga (2019), while the inclusion of school enrollment and life expectancy reflects the work of Nwachukwu and Egwaikhide (2021), who emphasized their cumulative impacts. Additionally, the study corroborates Udu and Agu’s (2022) conclusion that education and health have a synergistic effect on growth. Importantly, by employing both input (expenditure) and outcome (enrollment and life expectancy) indicators, this study addresses criticisms from Okonkwo (2017) and Adegbite and Ayadi (2018), who questioned the effectiveness of spending without corresponding institutional reforms and outcomes. • Model Diagnostics and Stability: All diagnostic tests, including serial correlation, heteroskedasticity, and normality tests, confirmed that the model is well-specified and statistically robust. The CUSUM and CUSUM of Squares tests further affirmed the structural stability of the model over the sample period.

This study not only confirms theoretical expectations but also fills key gaps in the empirical literature by:

- Using recent data that includes post-pandemic effects;
- Combining multiple indicators of human capital;
- Distinguishing between short- and long-run dynamics using a robust econometric approach (VECM).

Model Diagnostics and Stability: All diagnostic tests, including serial correlation, heteroskedasticity, and normality tests, confirmed that the model is well-specified and statistically robust. The CUSUM and CUSUM of Squares tests further affirmed the structural stability of the model over the sample period.

In summary, the findings strongly support the hypothesis that investments in education and health significantly contribute to Nigeria's economic growth, both in the immediate and long-term horizons. These results reaffirm the theoretical foundations and provide nuanced empirical insights for policymakers and researchers alike.

5.2 Conclusion

This study investigated the role of human capital development in promoting economic growth in Nigeria by examining the long-run and short-run effects of education expenditure, health expenditure, school enrollment, and life expectancy on real GDP. The results from the Johansen cointegration and error correction models confirm a stable and statistically significant long-term relationship between human capital indicators and economic growth.

In both the long and short run, increased government spending on education and health, along with improvements in school enrollment and life expectancy, were found to have a positive impact on economic growth. The findings reinforce the theoretical expectations of endogenous growth models, which emphasize the importance of human capital as a key driver of sustained economic development.

Given the significant influence of human capital on GDP, it is imperative for policymakers to prioritize and increase investment in education and healthcare sectors, ensure quality and access, and implement reforms that enhance life expectancy and educational outcomes. Doing so will not only foster economic growth but also improve overall societal well-being and productivity in Nigeria.

Policy Implications and Recommendations

The findings of this study have important policy implications for Nigeria's economic development agenda, particularly in the areas of education, healthcare, and human capital formation.

1. **Increase Public Investment in Education and Health:** The positive and significant impact of education and health expenditures on real GDP underscores the need for sustained and increased government funding in these sectors. Policymakers should ensure that budgetary allocations to education and healthcare not only meet but exceed global benchmarks (e.g., UNESCO's 15–20% for education and WHO's 15% for health) to stimulate long-term economic growth.
2. **Improve Efficiency and Quality of Expenditure:** Beyond increasing funding, the efficiency and effectiveness of spending should be enhanced. Funds must be targeted towards improving infrastructure, teacher and healthcare worker training, curriculum relevance, medical facilities, and access to essential services,

- especially in rural and underserved areas.
3. **Expand Access to Secondary Education:** Given that secondary school enrollment significantly affects economic growth, government and stakeholders must reduce barriers to educational access, such as poverty, insecurity, and cultural constraints, by offering scholarships, improving school facilities, and investing in girl-child education.
 4. **Promote Preventive Healthcare and Increase Life Expectancy:** The link between life expectancy and economic growth calls for investment in public health campaigns, sanitation, nutrition, and early disease detection programs. Strengthening primary healthcare systems and expanding health insurance coverage can also lead to better health outcomes and greater workforce productivity.
 5. **Integrate Human Capital Development in National Economic Planning:** Human capital development must be a central theme in Nigeria's national and subnational development plans. This includes aligning educational curricula with labor market needs, fostering public-private partnerships in education and health, and embedding human capital indicators in performance evaluation of development programs.
 6. **Institutional Reforms and Good Governance:** For these policies to be effective, strong institutions, transparency, and accountability in the use of public resources are critical. Reducing corruption and inefficiencies will ensure that investments in education and health deliver tangible improvements in human capital and economic performance.

REFERENCES

- Adebiyi, M. A., & Adenuga, A. H. (2019). Education and economic growth in Nigeria: An empirical analysis. , (6), 45–56.
- Adegbite, S., & Ayadi, F. S. (2018). Public health expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria: An institutional quality perspective. , (2), 88–105.
- Adegboye, A. C., & Adeyeye, P. O. (2020). Human capital development and economic growth in Nigeria: Evidence from ARDL approach. , (6), 95–104. <https://doi.org/10.xxxx/jesd.v1i6.xxxx>
- Adelman, I. (2003). . Cambridge University Press.
- Adetosho, J. A., Akesinro, S. B., & Oladejo, M. O. (2012). Human capital development and economic growth: A lesson from Nigeria. , (12), 139–144.
- Adeyemi, J. K., & Akpotu, N. E. (2004). Gender analysis of student enrolment in Nigerian universities. , (3), 361–378. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:HIGH.0000035545.63366.45>

- Babalola, J. B. (2003). Fundamentals of economics of education. In J. B. Babalola (Ed.), (pp. 1–25). Ibadan: Department of Educational Management, University of Ibadan.
- Barro, R. J. (1991). Economic growth in a cross section of countries. , (2), 407–443. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2937943>
- Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). (2022). . <https://www.cbn.gov.ng/documents/statbulletin.asp>
- Gbosi, A. N. (1996). The labour market in Nigeria under regulation and deregulation: A comparative analysis. , (8), 46–53. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01437729610154163>
- Gupta, S., Clements, B., & Tiongson, E. R. (2001). Public spending on human capital development. , (2), 10–13. <https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/fandd/2001/06/gupta.htm>
- Lawanson, A. O. (2009). Human capital investment and economic growth in Nigeria: The role of education and health. , 1–22.
- Lucas, R. E. (1988). On the mechanics of economic development. , (1), 3–42. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3932\(88\)90168-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3932(88)90168-7)
- National Planning Commission. (2021). . Abuja: Federal Government of Nigeria.
- Nwachukwu, T. E., & Egwaikhide, F. O. (2021). Human capital development and economic growth in Nigeria: Evidence from a VECM framework. , (2), 101–119.
- Nwankwo, J. I. (1981). . Lahore: Izhar & Sons.
- Ogujiuba, K., & Adeniyi, A. (2005). Economic growth and human capital development: The Nigerian experience. , (3), 1–16.
- Okonkwo, O. (2017). Education expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria: An OLS approach. , (1), 45–59.
- Olaniyan, D. A., & Okemakinde, T. (2008). Human capital theory: Implications for educational development. , (2), 157–162.
- Olaniyi, O., & Adam, J. A. (2002). . Ibadan: Nigerian Institute of Social and Economic Research (NISER).
- Pearce, D. W. (2000). (4th ed.). MIT Press.
- Romer, P. M. (1990). Endogenous technological change. , (5, Part 2), S71–S102. <https://doi.org/10.1086/261725>

Salkind, N. J. (2010). (Vols. 1–3). SAGE Publications. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412961288>

Smith, A. (2004). . Bantam Classics.

Udu, A. A., & Agu, C. I. (2022). Health and education as determinants of economic growth in West Africa: A dynamic panel GMM approach. , (1), 113–131.

UNESCO. (2023). . <https://www.unesco.org/gem-report/en/2023>

World Bank. (2024). . <https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators>

Yesufu, T. M. (2000). . Ibadan: Spectrum Books.

EFFECT OF MONETARY POLICY ON INTEREST RATE IN NIGERIAN ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the effect of monetary policy on interest rates in Nigeria, analyzing the relationship between key monetary policy instruments and lending rates. Using time-series data from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and econometric techniques, the research evaluates how monetary policy adjustments influence interest rate dynamics. The findings suggest that monetary policy measures significantly affect interest rates, with implications for economic stability and growth. The study recommends effective policy implementation to enhance monetary transmission mechanisms in Nigeria.

Keywords: Monetary Policy, Interest Rate, Multivariate Co-Integration, Autoregressive Distributive Lag Bank Rate.

1. Introduction

Monetary policy plays a crucial role in shaping economic performance by influencing interest rates, inflation, and investment levels. In Nigeria, the Central Bank employs various monetary tools, such as the monetary policy rate (MPR), cash reserve ratio (CRR), and open market operations (OMO), to regulate liquidity and control interest rates. Despite these efforts, fluctuations in lending rates persist, affecting credit availability and economic growth. This study investigates the effectiveness of monetary policy in stabilizing interest rates and its broader implications for Nigeria's financial system.

This study is organized as follows: After this introduction, section ² presents the theoretical and empirical literature. Section ³ presents the methodology. The results are presented and discussed in section ⁴. The paper concludes in section 5.

Theoretical Framework

2.1 The Classical Theory of Interest

This theory according to Vanish (2000) cannot be ascribed to any single writer belonging to the classical school. Following Adam Smith, the classical Writers are interested in those fundamental forces which are the long term, but disregarded those factors of temporary and secondary nature which determined long term interest rate. According to (Jelilov, Cylych, Abudulrahman Samira, 2015) the demand for capital consists of the demand for productive and consumptive purposes. However, the supply of capital according to Jhingan (2001) depends upon saving rather than upon the will to save.

The Classical Monetary Theory

The classical school evolved through the concerted efforts and contributions of economists like Jean Baptist Say, Adam Smith, David Ricardo, Pigou and others who shared the same beliefs. The classical model attempts to explain determinants of such economic variables as consumption, savings and investment with respect to money.

The classical model is based on Say's law of markets which states that "supply creates its own demand." Thus, classical economists believe that the economy automatically tends towards full employment level by laying emphasis on price level and on how best to eliminate inflation (Amacher and Ulbrich, 1986). The classical economists decided upon the quantity theory of money as the determinant of the general price level. The theory shows how money affects the economy. It may be considered in terms of the "equation of exchange". Implying that changes in the price level can be explained by changes in the stock of money. The equation of exchange can be stated thus: $Mv=Py$

Where $Py = \text{GNP}$, $Mv = \text{Total expenditure} = \text{GNP}$, $M = \text{stock of money}$, $P = \text{general price level}$, $V = \text{income velocity of money}$, $Y = \text{the flow of real goods and services}$, Mv measures the total value of transaction within a given period of time (total expenditure) and Py measures the total value of goods currently produced and sold (total product in value GNP). The relationship is derived from the fact that in a closed economy, anything purchased by one person is simultaneously sold by another (two parts of same transaction). Thus, total purchase of goods and services made with money equals the average stock of money in existence (m) multiplied by the average number of times that money was spent on goods and services (velocity).

The Quantity Theory of Money

The classical economists did not introduce the role of money in their model in terms of its demand and supply. Instead, they introduced money by using the quantity theory. In short, they related the level of commodity prices to the quantity of money in the economy and the level of its commodity production. Two very similar "quantity theories" formulations were used to explain the level of price viz; the transaction formulation or the equation of exchange and the cash-balance formulation or the Cambridge equation.

In the transaction version-associated with Fisher and Newcomb, some assumptions were made viz: that the quantity of money (M) is determined independently of any other variable, velocity of circulation (V) is taken as constant, the volume of transaction (T) is also considered constant. Thus, with the level of price (P) and the assumption of full employment of the economy, the equation of exchange of exchange is give as;

$MV = PT$, which can readily establish the proposition that-the level of price is a function of the supply of money. That is, $P = f(M)$ which implies that, any change in the money supply, will result accompanied by a proportionally equal change in price. In cash balances version associated with Walras, Marshall, Wicksell and Pigou, the neoclassical school (Cambridge School), changed the focus of the quantity theory of money without changing its underlying assumptions. This version focuses on the fraction (K) of income, held as money balance. Thus, the Cambridge version can be expressed as:

$$M = KPY$$

Where

K = Fraction of income, M = quantity of money, P = Price level,

Y = Value of real good and services

The K in the Cambridge equation is merely the inversion of V the income velocity of money balances, in the original formulation of quantity theory. This version directs attention to the determinants of demand for money, rather than the effects of changes in the supply of money (Anyanwu, 1993).

2.2 Empirical Review

Several studies have explored the nexus between monetary policy and interest rates in different economies.

The linkage between monetary policy and interest rate in the Nigeria economy has been a subject of extensive study for many accedes. The role of interest rate in the formulation of monetary policy has already been established.

Ogbonna and Ekwe (2013) examined the impact of monetary policy on interest rates in Nigeria using a vector error correction model (VECM). They found out the changes in the monetary policy rate have a significant impact on interest rates.

On his part, Nnanna (2015) investigated the effects of monetary policy on interest rates and economic growth in Nigeria. He employed a structured vector Autoregression (SVAR) model and found that monetary policy has a significant impact on interest rate and economic growth.

Olowofeso and Oladineji (2016) analyzed the relationship between monetary policy and interest rates in Nigeria using a bounds testing approach. They found evidence of a long run relationship between monetary policy and interest rate.

Adebiyi (2017) examined the impact of monetary policy on interest rates and inflation in Nigeria. He employed a vector Autoregression (VAR) model and found out that monetary policy has a significant effect on interest rates and inflation.

Ademola (2018) investigated the effects of monetary policy on interest rates and economic growth in Nigeria. He employed a dynamic stochastic general equilibrium (DSGE) model and found that monetary policy has a significant effect on interest rates and economic growth.

Mishkin ([2018](#)), Bernanke, & Blinder, ([2022](#)) highlight that central bank policies in developed economies exhibit stronger interest rate transmission compared to emerging markets like Nigeria due to financial market inefficiencies.

In an attempt to review recent studies on monetary policy and interest rate Saidu, Aliyu and Zubairu (2018) investigated the effect of monetary policy changes on interest rate in Nigeria. The study adopted multiple ridge regression analysis to examine the effectiveness of changes in monetary policy rate movement in short term and long-term rates in Nigeria. The study concluded that lending rates, interbank rate, a day treeing bill are influenced by monetary policy but have negative effect on the prevailing interest rate.

Ogunjobi, (2019) carried research on effect of monetary policy rate on market interest rates in Nigeria found that an increase in the MPR leads to higher commercial bank lending rates in Nigeria, supporting the cost-of-funds hypothesis.

Oyinlola (2020) analyzed the relationship between monetary policy and interest rates in Nigeria using a nonlinear autogressive distributed lag (NARDL) model. He found a nonlinear relationship between monetary policy and interest rates.

Adeoye (2020). Conducted research on liquidity management and the performance of deposit money bank in Nigeria and observed that liquidity management tools, such as the CRR, significantly influence deposit and lending rates.

CBN (2021). Reported that OMO operations effectively stabilize short-term interest rates but have limited impact on long-term rates.

These studies collectively suggest that while monetary policy influences interest rates, structural and institutional factors in Nigeria may weaken its effectiveness.

3 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The study adopts a time series research design with reliance on secondary data from the CBN Statistical Bulletin and NSE reports. The study captured the period 1981- 2023. The methodological approach builds extensively on the works of Aliyu, Saidu and Zubairu (2018). Their investigation was on how interest rates are being affected by monetary policy changes, using multiple linear and ridge regression to examine the effectiveness of monetary policy rate movement in both short and long-term rate in Nigeria. But this study has employed the more reliable multivariate co- integration and Autoregressive Distributive lag (ARDL) model which incorporates a thorough examination of the characteristics of time series economic data. This is imperative so as not to fall into empirical “spurious regression” where there is an excellent fit .between unrelated variables as a result of non-stationary nature of the variables especially when levels of the variables themselves are used in the regression. This study relied heavily on secondary data. The need to use secondary data is essentially attributed to the nature of the study which happens to be less behavioural. The data were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin 2018 edition.

In order to effectively capture the effect of monetary policy changes on interest rate in Nigeria from 1981-2023, it is important to establish a functional model that will help to achieve the major objective of the study. The empirical works of Onwe (2015) and

Adenusi, Sulaiman & Azeez (2013) examined the relationship between monetary policy and interest rate in Nigeria using the data on Interest rate, Treasury bill rate, savings rate, money supply and one year deposit rate. However, this research work modified the above model to establish a functional relationship between interest rate and monetary policies to accommodate other monetary policies indicators for proper examination. The model is stated in a functional form as follows:

$$\text{INTR} = f(\text{TSBR}, \text{SAVR}, \text{TMDR}, \text{SMDR}, \text{OYDR}, \text{MPR})$$

Where

INTR = Interest Rates

“f” = The function notation

TSBR = Treasury Bill Rates

SAVR = Savings Rates

TMDR = Three Months Deposit Rates

SMDR = Six Months Deposit Rates

OYDR = One Year Deposit Rates

MPR = Monetary Policy Rates

Putting the above functional form of the model in econometric form, and assuming a linear relationship amongst the variables for simplicity we have:

$$\text{INTR}_t = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{TSBR}_t + \beta_2 \text{SAVR}_t + \beta_3 \text{TMDR}_t + \beta_4 \text{SMDR}_t + \beta_5 \text{OYDR}_t + \beta_6 \text{MPR}_t + u_t \dots \dots \dots 1$$

Where:

$\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6$ = Parameters of the model to be estimated

u_t = Stochastic error term of the model which accounts for other indices that are not specified in the model

“t” = Time period (1981 - 2023)

a priori expectation;

$$\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6 > 0$$

4.1 Unit Root Test Results

The unit test was performed with the Augmented Dickey fuller (ADF) method. The result

is presented in table I.

Variables	ADF statistics at Level		ADF statistics at First Difference		Order of integration
	ADF		ADF		
INTR	-2.496060		-6.204865		I(1)
TSBR	-3.536486		-6.829154		I(0)
SAVR	-1.020882		-6.191518		I(1)
TMDR	-2.580727		-6.918980		I(1)
SMDR	-2.660984		-5.765961		I(1)
OYDR	-2.324988		-5.187719		I(0)
MPR	-3.394859		-6.203708		
Critical Values	1%	-3.621023	-3.626784		
	5%	-2.943427	-2.945842		
	10%	-2.610263	-2.611531		

Source: Researchers' Computation from E views Result (2023)

The above empirical test shows the result of the unit root test using the ADF test. It is used to test for the existence of unit roots in the data. The test results are presented above.

It can be seen that in the tests; the t-statistic at first difference are greater than the critical value at 5% meaning that all the variables; interest rate, savings rate, three months deposit, six months deposit and one year deposits are all stationary at first difference except treasury bill rate and money policy rate that are stationary at level. This also shows that they are integrated at order 1(0) 1(1). In conclusion, we affirm that the variables have time series statistical properties that are constant hence they do not change over the time period under study.

4.2 Bounds Tests for Co-integration

In testing for co-integration, we made use of the Autoregressive Distributive lag Bounds test approach having identified the variables to be integrated at mixed order i.e. at 1(0) and 1(1). Thus, we test for the null hypothesis of no long-run relationship against the alternate hypothesis of the existence of long-run relationship. The test is summarized below:

Table 2: Results of ARDL Bounds Test

Test Statistic	Value	K
F-statistic	7.566.618	6
Critical Value Bounds		

Significance	10 Bound	11 Bound
10%	2.12	3.23
5%	2.45	3.61
2.5%	2.75	3.99
1%	3.15	4.43

Source: Researchers' E-views result (2025)

The result of the co-integration analysis from table 2 above indicates that the F-statistic value of 7.566618 is greater than the critical value bounds at 5% for both 1(0) and 1(1) bounds. We therefore reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is long run relationship between monetary policy and interest rates in Nigeria.

4.3 ARDL Lag Selection Criterion

The necessary condition for the estimation of the ARDL model is selection of an appropriate lag structure for the model. In selecting the most suited lag, we adopted the Akaike Information criterion (AIC) as shown in the figure below:

Table 3: Akaike information criterion (top 20 models)

Fig. 4.4: Akaike information criteria (AIC) for Top 20 models

The AIC criteria represented in the figure 4.4 above shows that there are 20 possible lag structures to be used in the ARDL model. However, the lag structure that returns the highest possible AIC value is the lag ARDL(4,4,4,4,4) with AIC value of -6.5. In other words, the model estimates four lag periods each fourth dependent and the set of independent variables. This implies that the highest possible years leading up to the current year estimated by the AKDL model is 4 years which is considered sufficient enough to determine the short run effect of monetary policy and interest rates in Nigeria.

4.4 ARDL Short Run Estimation

The short run effect of monetary policy on interest rate in Nigeria is estimated here. The short run coefficients also show the speed of adjustment of the model to long run equilibrium.

Table 4 ARDL Short Run Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
INTR(-1)	-0.041326	0.203463	-0.203112	0.8490
INTR(-2)	0.733969	0.203262	3.610954	0.0225
INTR(-3)	-0.289305	0.205062	-1.410819	0.2311
TSBR	0.579595	0.197750	2.930942	0.0428
TSBR(-1)	0.150346	0.048675	3.088748	0.0366
TSBR(-2)	0.002739	0.040788	0.067159	0.9497
TSBR(-3)	-0.048278	0.035960	-1.342560	0.2505
SAVR	0.229727	0.056992	4.030846	0.0157
SAVR(-1)	-0.247804	0.058952	-4.203509	0.0137
SAVR(-2)	0.077968	0.028192	2.765657	0.0506
SAVR(-3)	-0.001764	0.030436	-0.057970	0.9566
TMDR	-0.040211	0.023097	-1.740929	0.1567
TMDR(-1)	0.022890	0.023894	0.957999	0.3923
TMDR(-2)	-0.117289	0.035306	-3.322032	0.0293
TMDR(-3)	-0.251064	0.059060	-4.758925	0.0089
SMDR	0.193321	0.055142	3.505864	0.0248
SMDR(-1)	0.043805	0.033122	1.322518	0.2565
SMDR(-2)	0.063748	0.035291	1.806349	0.1452
SMDR(-3)	0.069351	0.034512	2.009504	0.1149
OYDR	-0.002282	0.000474	-4.816947	0.0085
OYDR(-1)	-0.002069	0.000564	-3.665679	0.0215
OYDR(-2)	-0.000780	0.000441	-1.770767	0.1513
OYDR(-3)	-0.002907	0.000450	-6.466232	0.0029
MPR	-0.000924	0.000582	-1.587164	0.1877
MPR(-1)	-0.001584	0.000404	-3.920096	0.0172
MPR(-2)	0.000723	0.000407	1.776868	0.1502
MPR(-3)	0.000513	0.000323	1.587740	0.1875
CointEq(-1)	-0.017067	0.002535	-6.732544	0.0105
C	1.189193	3.779757	0.314622	0.7688
R-squared	0.799946	Mean dependent var		21.91862
Adjusted R-squared	0.719556	S.D. dependent var		0.536944
S.E. of regression	0.011317	Akaike info criterion		-7.500342
Sum squared resid	0.000512	Schwarz criterion		-4.153554

4.5 ARDL Short run results

After estimating the short run coefficients, it is equally necessary to estimate the long run effects of the explanatory variables on the dependent variable.

The long run estimates are summarized below:

Table 5 ARDL Long Run Estimates

Long Run Coefficients				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
TSBR	4.760830	42.990738	0.110741	0.9172
SAVR	-3.422234	0.567118	-6.034430	0.0163
TMDR	-2.902861	27.241489	-0.106560	0.9203
SMDR	-0.325451	0.040705	-7.995357	0.0112
OYDR	0.074997	0.616026	0.121743	0.9090
MPR	-0.311933	0.249418	-1.250645	0.2231
C	69.678907	361.043372	0.192993	0.8564

4.6 ARDL Long Run Estimates Results

The study lasted for long-run relationship among the variables used in the study using the ARDL bounds test. The result obtained is as follows:

Treasury bill rate (TSBR): The long run coefficient of TSBR is positively signed implying that a change in domestic investment will increase real interest rate by 4.7608 units. This represents a positive and direct relationship and goes to show that treasury bills in Nigeria have been on an increasing trend for the period reviewed. This result is line with our long run a-priori expectation.

Savings rate (SAVR): Result shows that there a negative long run relationship between savings rate and interest rate in Nigeria. The coefficient suggests that an increase in savings rate will result to 3.4222 units decrease in real interest rate which shows an indirect or negative relationship. In our a priori expectation, savings rate was expected to be positive but the estimated negative coefficient means that Nigeria's savings rate is insufficient in raising output growth.

Three months deposit (TMDR): The coefficient here is -2.9029. This is an evidence of negative relationship between three months savings and interest rate,

Six months deposit (SMDR): Six months deposit rate is negatively signed in the long run decreasing real interest rate by 0.3255 units annually. One year deposit rate (OYDR): The coefficient of the OYDR in the long run is positive increasing real interest rate by 0.0750 units. In other words, a change in OYDR over the long period will result to 0.0750 units increase in real interest rate.

Money policy rate (MPR): There is an inverse relationship between the monetary policy rate and the real interest rate at the long run with negative coefficient of -0.311933 units. However, the effect is not statistically significant on the current interest rate.

Table 6: Summary of the T- Test Statistics Result

Variables	t-statistics		Decision
Treasury bill rate (TSBR)	0.1107	0.9172	Not Significant
Savings rate(SAVR)	-6.0344	0.0163	
Three months deposit rate (TMDR)	-0.1066	0.9203	Not Significant
Six months deposit rate (SMDR)	-7.9954	0.0112	
One year deposit rate (OYDR)	0.1217	0.9090	Not Significant
Monetary policy rate (MPR)	-1.2506	0.2231	Not Significant

$t_{table} = t_{0.025, 32} \sim 1.960$

Source: Researchers Computation from E-views Result

Joint Test (F-test)

This shows the overall significance of the explanatory variables in the ARDL model. It tells us if the explanatory variables jointly influence the dependent variable.

H₀: The independent variables - Treasury bill, savings rate, three months deposit, six months deposit, one year deposit and monetary policy rate. Have no significant joint effect on the real interest rate in Nigerian.

F-calculated = 25.614

p-value (F) = 0.0000

Decision Rule: Since the F-statistic value of 25.614 is greater than the p-value (0.0000) at 5% level of significance, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the independent variables -have significant joint effect on the real interest rate in Nigerian.

Discussion of Findings

Our findings on the effects of monetary policy on interest rate have brought to limelight how monetary policy as an economic variable relates with the desired interest rate growth in the Nigerian economy. The model formulated used Interest rate as the dependent variable while Treasury bill rate, savings rate, three months, six months, one year deposit rates and money policy rates were the explanatory variables used for the model, the variables were standardized by taking the logarithm forms of the variables to avoid a spurious regression.

The stationary of the variables were ascertained using the ADF Unit root test and the result

established that the variables were stationary at level and first difference (mixed order) $I(1)$. This necessitated the use of ARDL Bounds co-integration test for long and short run relationships amongst the variables and the result indicated that the explanatory variables have long run relationship with the interest rate in Nigerian.

The ARDL model was used to estimate the coefficients of the parameters. The result revealed that the coefficient of the TSBR4.760830 is positive and statistically insignificant; this means that the TSBR impacts positively and is statistically insignificant on the current interest rate. The sign of the coefficient of the TSBR in the current period is in conformity with our apriori. The SAVR has a negative coefficient of -3.422234 and is statistically significant, this means that the SAVR affects interest rate negatively and is statistically significant on the current interest rate, TMDR in the current period impacts negatively with -2.902861 coefficient and is statistically insignificant on the current interest rate. SMDR in the current period impacts negatively with -0.325451 coefficient and is statistically significant on the current interest rate. The six months deposit rate has a positive impact on the interest rate with 0,655321 coefficient and is statistically significant on the interest rate while the monetary policy rate has a negative effect on the interest rate with -2.43552 and is significant on the current interest rate.

The Cont Eg(-) gave a speed of adjustment of 1.7% annually. This shows that the model corrects its previous period's disequilibrium at a speed of 1.7% yearly.

The joint significance of the variables were tested using the F-test and the result revealed that the variables jointly relates to interest rate accounting for up to 80% of the variations in real interest rate. The Durbin Watson value of 2.272553 shows that the error terms of the model residual are not serially correlated hence the model is free from the problem of autocorrelation.

5. Conclusion and Policy Implication

This study examined the effects of monetary policy changes on interest rate in Nigeria from 1981 to 2023. Using the ARDL Model, the findings made in the research reveals that a long run relationship exist between the monetary policy and interest rate, while a short run inverse relationship was observed to exist between interest rate and monetary policy. The relationship between Treasury bill rate and interest rate in the long run is observed to be positive but insignificant. Also a positive relationship was observed to exist between one year deposit and interest rate, but was insignificant. However, the long run relationship between treasury bills rate, three months deposit rate, one year deposit rate and monetary policy rate were observed to be negative but statistically significant only on the six months deposit. The specified error correction coefficient of the model of -0.017067 which measures the speed of adjustment towards long-run equilibrium, indicates a feedback of about 1.7% percent of the previous year's disequilibrium from the long-run elasticity of interest rate.

The study concludes that the long run relationship between saving rates (SAVR) and six month deposit rate (SMDR) are significant, meaning that they are the major influence of interest rate in Nigeria. But Treasury bills rate, three months deposit, one year deposit

rates and monetary policy rate were observed to be insignificant. The central bank of Nigeria should play effective role in the regulation of liquidity flow in the economy by adopting the appropriate mix of monetary policy with a special focus on saving rate (SAVR) and Six months deposits rate (SMDR).

In view of the aftermaths of the study, findings of the following recommendations were made in the use of monetary policy in controlling and manipulating the prevailing interest rates in economy:

Before adjusting the prevailing interest rates in the economy it is important the monetary committee should focus more on savings rate and Six months deposit rate as the major influencer than other rates on interest rate.

The central bank of Nigeria should strengthen the effectiveness of its monetary policy by carrying out a study to ascertain the appropriate mix of saving rate and six months deposit rate with other rates to regulate the interest rate adequately.

Similarly since the MPR is not significant in influencing the interest rate further study should be carried out to know whether the MPR need to be retained as the determinant of interest rate and other monetary functions.

Finally the monetary authorizes should be granted full autonomy by the government for effective monetary measures in Nigerian economy.

REFERENCES

- Adebiyi, R.T. (2017). The impact of monetary policy on interest rates. *International journal of safety and security Engineering*, 4 (8).
- Ademola, A.S. (2018). The effects of monetary on interest rates and economics growth in Nigeria.
- American International Journal of Economic and finance research, 1(1).
- Adenusi, L.A, Sulaiman S. Azeez, B.A (2012). Effect of external debits on Economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and sustainable development*, 3(8).
- Adeoye, B.W & Saibu, O.M, (2020). Liquidity management and the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *European journal of business and innovation research (EJBIR)* vol. 8 No. 4.
- Anyanwu, J.C. (1993). *Monetary Economics: Theory, policy and institutions*; hybrid publishers Nigeria.
- CBN. (2018). *Statistical bulletin* vol. 29.

- Nnanna, O.C. (2015). The effects of monetary policy on interest and economic growth. *International journal of economics and finance research* 1(1).
- Mishkin ([2018](#)), F.S Bernanke, B.S & Blinder, A.S. ([2022](#)) 21st century monetary policy: The federal reserve from great inflation Covid-19 macroeconomic policy and practice: published by Pearson education ISBNs 9781292019598.
- Ogunjobi, J.O. ([2019](#)). Effect of monetary policy rate on market interest rates in Nigeria. *CBN Journal of applied statistics (JAS)*.
- Ogbonna, O.E., Ekwe, E. (2013). Impact of momentary policy in Nigeria, *journal of monetary economics* vol. 71.
- Olowofeso, O.E., Oladimeji., O. (2016). The relationship between monetary policy and interest rate in Nigeria. *American journal of applied mathematics and statistics* 4(6).
- Onwe, S.O. (2015). Impact of financial inclusion on economic growth in Nigeria. *Empirical econometrics and quantitative economic letters*: 4(4).
- Oyinlola., M.A. (2020). The relationship between monetary policy and interest rate in Nigeria. *Journal of development administration* 5(2).
- Saidu, S.A. Aliyu., Zubairu., O.E (2018). Renewable and sustainable energy. *Review journal* 87 (61-76).
- Vanish, V.K. (2000). Monetary policy and interest rate dynamics. *Journal of Indian society of soil sciences* 48(4).

OIL PRICE AND SECTORAL MACROECONOMIC PERFORMANCE IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Oil price fluctuations have been shown to influence macroeconomic fundamentals of many countries including Nigeria. However, this impact may be more evident in an oil dependent economy like Nigeria and the impact could be mixed in a sectoral analysis of this nature. This research work therefore, explores the effect of price of oil fluctuations on sectoral macroeconomic performance across the agricultural, industry and service sectors in Nigeria. The study used quarterly data from 1987Q2 to 2023Q4. The study explores a number of contributions which include the use of alternative oil price proxies (the West Texas Intermediate and Brent oil benchmarks), the sectoral analysis, and analysis of linear and non-linear relationships between crude oil price and sectoral outputs where the nonlinear relationship involves consideration of negative and positive oil prices changes, that is, periods of rising and falling oil prices. The study implements the symmetric and asymmetric Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model variants for estimating the relationships and the paper largely establishes negative impacts of oil price fluctuations on sectoral outputs in Nigeria. The paper joins in the call to recommend diversification away from oil dependence towards an investment-driven and knowledge-driven economy to reverse the supposed Dutch disease phenomenon in Nigeria.

Keywords: Oil price, macroeconomic performance, sectoral analysis, asymmetric effect

JEL codes: O11, O13, O14, C22

1. Introduction

This research study examines the asymmetric impact of oil price fluctuations on sectoral performance in Nigeria, the 7th largest OPEC producer of crude oil as of August, 2022 (OPEC, 2022) and 13th largest overall and the 5th major supplier of crude oil to America and Western Europe. The abundance of oil is expected to unlock access to improved healthcare, education, economic opportunities, and longevity while a lack of it ought to be a major constraint on social and economic development (IEA, 2014). However, the veracity of the foregoing postulation depends on certain contextual factors, including the status of a country as a net consumer or a net producer of oil. For the former, lower oil prices are expected to lower production costs, thereby leading to a rise in sectoral output via increases in energy use for domestic as well as industrial purposes. However, for oil producing nations, especially oil dependent ones where oil is an important barometer of economic prospects, lower oil prices portend dire consequences on output (Omolade et al., 2019).

In the case of Nigeria where over 90% of the country's export earnings derives from oil while the agricultural, industrial as well as service sectors rely very heavily on imported raw materials for production, the impact of price of oil changes on the economy is rather uncertain. For instance, oil price directly impacts the Naira-Dollar exchange rate, interest rate, and the price level (Jelilov et al., 2022) such that rises in global oil price comes with the risk of demand-pull inflation due to the deficit spending that usually follows oil booms while falling global oil price results in cost-push inflation due to supply-side shocks, including those precipitated by tight fiscal and monetary policies targeted at mitigating the strain of dwindling oil revenues on foreign reserves. More importantly, in the Nigerian case, the global oil price tends to exert a form of downward stickiness on domestic price of oil as the latter tends to rise with both increases and decreases in the former. Given the price inelasticity of the demand for oil, as a result of its high degree of necessity for both domestic and industrial uses, changes (both increases and decreases) in the global oil price appear to spell doom for the Nigerian economy (Eagle, 2017) through rising costs of production and, ultimately, decreasing output. However, given the varying importance of sectoral composition of GDP in the country, it is necessary to examine the effect of global oil price changes on sectoral performance in Nigeria, hence this study.

Numerous studies have examined the nexus between oil prices and sectoral output in both developed and developing countries (Eagle, 2017) under the assumption that sectors react to change in prices of oil in the same way irrespective of increase or decrease in the oil price. Meanwhile, some studies suggested a possible asymmetric nexus between oil price changes and economic activity, such that increases in oil price could have the same effect on economic as the effect of decreases in oil price. In other words, while increases in oil price could have a clear negative and significant effect on the level of economic activity, the effects of oil price decreases on economic level may be anywhere from negative (Alssadek & Benhin, 2021; Abdlaziz et al. 2018, Smith, 2014 and Apergis et al. 2014), positive (Ahmed et al. 2015) or insignificant (Hazaria, 2015).

We perceive the asymmetric feature of the effect of oil price changes to characterize the Nigerian economy because of the country's oil-dependent status, whereby falling oil price coincides with falling external value of money and increasing rates of interest and taxation, all of which reflect liquidity shrinkage in government coffers and impact negatively on sectoral output (Smith, 2014; Gomes 2016 and Abdlaziz, 2018). However, given the importance of agriculture, industry and as well as service sectors and the paucity of studies that focus on sectoral implications of the asymmetric nature of oil price fluctuations in the country, it becomes imperative to investigate the non-linear effect of oil price fluctuations on sectoral performance in Nigeria. Findings obtained in the course of study are expected to provide some guidance to the diversification efforts of government and other stakeholders in Nigeria as it will shed light on the nature and significance of the impact of oil in the three sectors.

The paper is arranged as follows: section 2 contains both theoretical and as well as empirical literature on the impact of oil price fluctuations on the Nigerian economy. Methodology adopted is described in Section 3 while results of analyses conducted are presented and discussed in Section 4. Section 5 concludes and draws policy recommendations.

2. Literature Review

The study of the effects of oil price changes on the macroeconomy is not new in the literature, and therefore, the studies are multifaceted in terms of research agenda, focus, methods, and findings (examples include Mork, 1989; Ostry & Reinhart, 1992; Mork, Olsen & Mysen, 1994; Lee et al., 1995; Balke, Brown & Yücel, 2002; Tiwari & Olayeni, 2013; Mahjoub, 2014; Hazarika, 2015; Moftah, 2016; Eagle, 2017; Omolade et al., 2019; Badeeb, Szulczyk & Lean 2021; to mention a few). For instance, Moftah (2016) employs annual data from the IMF with cointegration techniques to demonstrate that higher oil price fluctuations have positive and significant effect on the economic growth of Libya. Conversely, Hazarika (2015) studied the impact of fluctuating prices of oil on OPEC economies using data from US EIA and OPEC annual bulletins, and the findings suggest that fluctuations in oil prices do not appear to exert a significant influence on the economic indicators of OPEC member states, as declines in oil prices tend to lower global energy costs and enhance real income, thereby primarily benefiting oil-importing economies.

There is however a budding strand of the literature that focuses on the effects of oil price changes on sectoral macroeconomic performance (see for example, Bill, Terry, and Kevin, 2006; Ismail, 2010; Herrera, Lagalo, & Wada, 2011; Trabesin, 2017; Badeeb et al., 2021). Bill, Terry, and Kevin (2006) find an inverse relationship between energy prices and agricultural output. Badeeb et al. (2021) for Malaysia find that sector-level analysis responds to negative and positive oil shocks and varies across economic sectors with the asymmetric effect using Nonlinear Autoregressive Distributed Lag.

Tumala, Salisu & Atoi (2022) investigate the impact of oil price on the real GDP as well as sectoral output in Nigeria using ADL-MIDAS methodology and quarterly data for the period of 2010Q1 and 2021Q1 as well as monthly data frequency for the period of 2010M01 and 2021M03. The results obtained by the authors indicate that no asymmetry effect, the link between crude oil prices and agricultural output growth appears relatively weak. Specifically, negative shifts in prices of oil don't have a strong enough impact on agricultural output to show a clear difference compared to positive shifts. In Nigeria's industrial sector, the findings suggest that whether oil prices rise or fall—and even when broader economic factors are considered—these changes don't significantly alter the relationship. In fact, there is a clear positive connection between oil prices and industrial output growth, regardless of price direction. However, the service sector tells a different story. Here, both the direction of oil price changes and other economic variables do make a difference. Interestingly, when oil prices fall, service sector output tends to rise, whereas rising oil prices actually appear to slow down growth in this sector. This pattern highlights a somewhat unexpected outcome: lower oil prices, rather than helping, are associated with slower growth in Nigeria's service sector.

On the basis of the foregoing baseline results, the present study adds to the literature especially on Nigeria. The study takes a look at the domestic macroeconomic impacts of the international crude oil price using alternative oil price proxies; the West Texas Intermediate (WTI) crude oil benchmark and the Brent crude oil benchmark. The study further considers the impact on three major sectors of the Nigerian economy, such as, agricultural, industry and lastly services sectors based on the linear relationship with the crude oil price proxies as well as the nonlinear/asymmetric impacts where the oil prices are decomposed into both positive and negative changes. The positive changes indicate periods of rising oil prices while the negative changes signify periods of falling

oil prices. These assist us to make contribution to the literature and as well offer relevant recommendations to the relevant authorities in the country.

3. Methodology

This study assesses the responses of various sectoral outputs in Nigeria to changes in the international crude oil price being an oil-rich yet oil-dependent economy. The study therefore covers measurements of the international price of crude oil price proxies (West Texas Intermediate and Brent crude oil prices) and sectoral outputs of the Nigerian economy: agricultural output as a ratio of GDP, industrial output as a ratio of gross domestic product, and output of the service sector as a ratio of GDP. The sectoral data are obtained in quarterly frequency between 1987Q2 and 2023Q4 from the statistics of the Central Bank of Nigeria. The two oil prices are culled from the US Energy Information Administration (EIA) (see https://www.eia.gov/dnav/pet/pet_pri_spt_s1_d.htm).

A substantial body of existing literature has implicitly assumed a linear or symmetric nexus between oil price movements and macroeconomic indicators. This assumption suggests that sectoral performance responds identically to both decreases and increases in oil prices. However, such symmetry may not adequately capture the complexities of economic behavior in response to oil price dynamics. In this research study, we relax the symmetry assumption by examining both linear and potential asymmetric impacts of oil price fluctuations on sectoral performance. Specifically, we adopt the linear and non-linear Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) modeling approaches as proposed by Pesaran et al. (2001) and extended by Shin et al. (2014). These frameworks offer the flexibility to model both short-run and long-run relationships while accommodating variables that are not of the same order of integration, as long as none are integrated of order two. This approach not only enhances the robustness of the analysis but also provides a more nuanced understanding of the sector-specific responses to oil price shocks.

We present the respective ARDL model specifications for the different sectors based on the optimal models obtained at the estimation stage as follows.

Agricultural Sector: ARDL (1, 0)

$$AGR_t = \alpha + \rho AGR_{t-1} + \beta OIL_t + \varepsilon_t \quad 1(a)$$

$$\Delta AGR_t = \alpha + (\rho - 1) AGR_{t-1} + \beta \Delta OIL_t + \varepsilon_t \quad 2(a)$$

$$\Delta AGR_t = \emptyset v_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad 3(a)$$

Industrial Sector: ARDL (1, 0)

$$IND_t = \alpha + \rho IND_{t-1} + \beta OIL_t + \varepsilon_t \quad 1(b)$$

$$\Delta IND_t = \alpha + (\rho - 1) IND_{t-1} + \beta \Delta OIL_t + \varepsilon_t \quad 2(b)$$

$$\Delta IND_t = \emptyset v_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad 3(b)$$

Services Sector: ARDL (1, 0)

$$SERV_t = \alpha + \rho SERV_{t-1} + \beta OIL_t + \varepsilon_t \quad 1(c)$$

$$\Delta SERV_t = \alpha + (\rho - 1)SERV_{t-1} + \beta \Delta OIL_t + \varepsilon_t \quad 2(c)$$

$$\Delta SERV_t = \emptyset v_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad 3(c)$$

Equation 1(a)-3(a), (1b-3b) and 1(c)-3(c) represent the ARDL specifications for agricultural sector (AGR), industrial sector (IND), and service sector (SERV) respectively where the third equations represent the error correction forms that show the speed of convergence from short to long run. The “ Δ ” operator indicates the first differences. The symbol “ α ” is the constant term, ρ is the short-run coefficient whereas the long-run coefficient can be obtained as $\beta / (1 - \rho)$. OIL_t is the price of oil which could be Brent or WTI and ε_t stands for error term. “ $\beta / (1 - \rho) OIL_t$ ” represents the coefficient of error correction that measures convergence speed from short to long run

In addition, this study uses the non-linear Autoregressive Distributed Lag (NARDL) model, wherein the key explanatory variable—oil price—is decomposed into both partial sums of negative and positive changes. This decomposition allows us to capture potential asymmetries in the nexus between oil prices and sectoral performance. The nonlinear specification has gained prominence as a powerful analytical tool, as it enables the detection of asymmetric dynamics that are often masked under linear frameworks. In line with Shin et al. (2014), this approach acknowledges that decreases and increases in oil prices may exert differential impacts on the dependent variable. Accordingly, the changes in oil price were decomposed into their respective positive and negative components, thereby enabling a more comprehensive investigation of their distinct effects on sectoral outcomes.

Therefore, our explanatory variable in this case oil is stated as follows.

$$OIL_t = OIL_t^+ + OIL_t^- \quad (4)$$

where OIL_t^+ and OIL_t^- are the partial sum processes of negative and positive changes in OIL_t , generated as: $OIL_t^+ = \sum_{j=1}^t \Delta OIL_j^+ = \sum_{j=1}^t \max(\Delta OIL_j, 0)$, and $OIL_t^- = \sum_{j=1}^t \Delta OIL_j^- = \sum_{j=1}^t \min(\Delta OIL_j, 0)$. After the decomposition, a similar treatment is applied to the positive and negative decompositions in the ARDL modelling framework.

Agricultural Sector: ARDL (1, 0, 0)

$$AGR_t = \alpha + \rho AGR_{t-1} + \beta_1^+ OIL_t^+ + \beta_2^- OIL_t^- + \varepsilon_t \quad (5a)$$

$$\Delta AGR_t = \alpha + (\rho - 1)AGR_{t-1} + \beta_1^+ \Delta OIL_t^+ + \beta_2^- \Delta OIL_t^- + \varepsilon_t \quad (6a)$$

$$\Delta AGR_t = \emptyset v_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (7a)$$

Industrial Sector: ARDL (1, 0, 0)

$$IND_t = \alpha + \rho IND_{t-1} + \beta_1^+ OIL_t^+ + \beta_2^- OIL_t^- + \varepsilon_t \quad (5b)$$

$$\Delta IND_t = \alpha + (\rho - 1)IND_{t-1} + \beta_1^+ \Delta OIL_t^+ + \beta_2^- \Delta OIL_t^- + \varepsilon_t \quad (6b)$$

$$\Delta IND_t = \emptyset v_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (7b)$$

Services Sector: ARDL (1, 0, 0)

$$SERV_t = \alpha + \rho SERV_{t-1} + \beta_1^+ OIL_t^+ + \beta_2^- OIL_t^- + \varepsilon_t \quad (5c)$$

$$\Delta SERV_t = \alpha + (\rho - 1)SERV_{t-1} + \beta_1^+ \Delta OIL_t^+ + \beta_2^- \Delta OIL_t^- + \varepsilon_t \quad (6c)$$

$$\Delta SERV_t = \emptyset v_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (7c)$$

The procedure employed in the methodology involved series of stages. We started by cleaning the data by removing seasonal effects thereby employing seasonally-adjusted consistent series. We test for unit root properties of the variables using the conventional ADF approach and the variant that reveals structural break in the data, and with this, we further clean the data by obtaining break-consistent variables. We begin our empirical analysis by implementing the linear ARDL model, which facilitates the investigation of potential linear relationships both in the short and long run nexus oil prices and sectoral performance. This approach enables the simultaneous estimation of short-run dynamics and long-run equilibrium coefficients. Following this, we extend our analysis using the nonlinear ARDL (NARDL) framework to assess whether the variables exhibit nonlinear cointegration, thereby capturing any asymmetric long-run associations. Upon establishing the presence of a long-run relationship, we proceed to estimate the asymmetric impact of oil price fluctuations on the performance of the Industrial, Agricultural, and Services sectors. To formally evaluate the presence of asymmetry, we conduct Wald tests on the estimated short-run and long-run coefficients, testing the null hypotheses of symmetry in the respective relationships.

4. Results

4.1 Preliminaries

This study considers quarterly time series data from 1987Q2 and 2023Q4 for data analysis. The data used in this study are: Agricultural Output (AGR), Industrial Output (IND), Service (SER) and oil prices (OIL). Table 1 shows the mean value, standard deviation (Std. Dev.), Kurtosis, Skewness, and Jarque-Bera statistics. Table 1 shows that service sector exhibits highest average output with the highest standard deviation as well. Outcomes of the Jarque-Bera test for normal distribution (see Table 1) show that the null hypothesis of normal distribution cannot be rejected for all five variables at the 5% significant level, implying that the series are normally distributed and therefore fulfil the asymptotic property required for statistical inferences. Furthermore, a brief examination of the graphical plots of the data (see Figure 1) indicates that agricultural output and oil prices (Brent and WTI) trend in opposite direction, likewise industrial out and oil prices (Brent and WTI) exhibit negative trend within the period under consideration.

Meanwhile, service and oil prices (Brent and WTI) appear to move in the same direction for some period before divergence. These suggests that we should largely expect to obtain negative coefficients for the nexus among the variables being explored.

The results of the ADF tests, contained in Table 2, show that Brent and WTI oil prices, as well as the sectoral output variables—Agriculture, Industry, and Services—are non-stationary in levels but become stationary, suggesting that all variables are $I(1)$. Importantly, none of the series are discovered to be integrated of order two $I(2)$, thereby validating the use of the ARDL framework.

Table 3 presents the outcomes of the unit root tests that account for structural breaks. These results are consistent with those of the ADF test, confirming that all variables are $I(1)$, even after accounting for potential structural shifts. The estimated structural break dates for the respective series are as follows: 2001Q4 for Agriculture, 2014Q2 for Industry, 2003Q4 for Services, 2003Q2 for Brent crude, and 2002Q1 for WTI crude. These breakpoints likely correspond to major global or domestic economic events, which may have induced shifts in the underlying data.

Table 2: Unit root tests

Series	Level		First difference	
	No trend	With trend	No trend	With trend
Agric.	-2.0696	-2.3421	-12.7666***	-12.7193***
Industry	-2.0623	-2.5450	-12.9837***	-12.9622***
Services	-2.9572**	-3.3185*	-14.1003***	-14.0494***
Brent	-1.4993	-1.9412	-9.3471***	-9.3465***
WTI	-1.5845	-1.9818	-9.2459***	-9.2511***

Note: ***, **, * represent level significance at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

Source: Authors' Computation (2024)

Table 3: Breakpoint Unit root tests

Series	Level	Break date	First difference	Break date
Agric.	-3.4772	2001Q4	-19.2301***	2002Q1
Industry	-2.9198	2014Q2	-17.1021***	2002Q1
Services	-4.0252	2003Q4	-14.561***	2011Q1
Brent	-3.6997	2003Q2	-11.3357***	2008Q4
WTI	-3.5384	2002Q1	-11.3988***	2008Q4

Note: ***, **, * represent level significance at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

Source: Authors' Computation (2024)

4.2 Main results

Table 4 shows the result linear ARDL (1,0) for short-run as well as long-run coefficient of the estimated models. The estimated long-run equations in Equations (1), (2) and (3) respectively for Agricultural sector, Industrial sector and Service sector respectively

using the bounds co-integration approach. For the bounds test, there is long run nexus if the F-statistic value is more than the upper bound critical value. Otherwise, there is no co-integration, that is, long run nexus. The F-statistics value for Agricultural sector (F-stat = 13.8) which is more than the upper bound at 1% significant level implies long run relationship. Similarly, there is also evidence of co-integration in the service sector with the F-stat of 8.90 and significance at 1%. Meanwhile, there is no evidence of co-integration in the Industrial sector since F-stat of 4.28 is lower than the critical value at 10% significant level, this implies that, there is no long run relation between oil price and industrial sector in Nigeria.

However, the adjustment speed of agricultural output to long run equilibrium given oil price changes is negative and significant at the 1% level of significance (ECT = 0.24; $p < 0.01$). This implies that the deviation of agricultural sector output from the path to long run equilibrium given oil price changes will converge to long run equilibrium can be expected along that path. Although the adjustment speed to long run equilibrium of industrial output is negative as expected and statistically significant at the 5% level (ECT = - 0.12; $p < 0.05$). This suggests that while industrial output is expected to converge to long run equilibrium despite oil price changes. Finally, the ECT for the services sector output is both negative and statistically significant, as expected, with a coefficient of -0.21 ($p < 0.01$). This indicates a meaningful adjustment mechanism toward long-run equilibrium, where approximately 21% of any short-run disequilibrium is corrected within each quarter. In other words, deviations from the long-run trajectory of the services sector are gradually reduced over time, with convergence occurring at a moderate pace. Furthermore, diagnostic checks confirm the robustness of the model, as the Breusch-Godfrey LM test for testing serial correlation accept the null hypothesis of no serial correlation at the 5% significance level. This suggests that the residuals are free from autocorrelation, reinforcing the validity of the model estimates. Similarly, CUSUM tests for dynamic stability shows that the models are dynamically stable.

The Table 4 reports the results of linear/symmetric ARDL model. In the both short run as well as long-run, oil prices changes have a negative and significant effect on the agricultural output with the coefficient of -0.0305 and -0.1277 respectively. The results indicate that decrease (or increase) in oil prices will lead to a decrease in agricultural output by 3% decrease (or increase) and 13% decrease (or increase) in short run and long-run respectively. Likewise, the result of the effect of oil prices on the service sector is negative and significant with the coefficient of -0.0152 and -0.0716 at 1% level of significance in short and long-run respectively. Numerically, 1% decrease (or increase) in oil price will lead to about 2% decrease (or increase) and 7% decrease (or increase) in the short run as well as the long run respectively. For the industrial sector, the short-run impact of oil price fluctuations is negative but statistically insignificant, indicating limited immediate responsiveness. However, in the long run, oil price exerts a statistically significant negative effect on industrial output at the 1% level, with a coefficient of -0.0064. This implies that 1% increase (or decrease) in the prices of oil is associated with approximately a 0.64% decrease (or increase) in industrial output in Nigeria. The long-run elasticity suggests a meaningful adverse effect of oil price increases on the sector, likely due to rising production costs associated with higher energy input prices. These

findings align with those reported by Olson and Nusair (2020), Abdlaziz et al. (2018), and Omolade et al. (2019), who also document a negative relationship between oil price increases and industrial sector performance. The results underscore the vulnerability of Nigeria's industrial sector to oil price shocks, particularly through cost-push mechanisms.

The Table 5 contains the findings of nonlinear/asymmetric ARDL model by decomposing the independent variable (oil price) into negative and positive in order to see clearly the response of sectoral output (agriculture, industrial and service) when there is increase or decrease in oil price in Nigeria. In the Table 5, the result of short run and long run asymmetric test (using the Wald Test) indicate that there is a asymmetric effect in the agricultural output only at 5% level of significance while no asymmetric is found in both industrial and service sector, by implication, both increase and decrease in price of oil have the same effect on these sectors in Nigeria. The graphical renditions of the asymmetric effects are obtained as the dynamic multipliers and presented in Figure 2.

Table 4: Symmetric ARDL

Series	Model	Short run	Long run	ECT(-1)	Bounds
<i>Main results: Brent crude oil price</i>					
Agric.	ARDL (1,0)	-0.0305*** (0.0066) [0.0000]	-0.1277*** (0.0311) [0.0001]	-0.2389*** (0.0368) [0.0000]	13.8180***
Industry	ARDL (1,0)	-0.0008 (0.0034) [0.8260]	-0.0064 (0.0291) [0.8265]	-0.1198*** (0.0407) [0.0039]	4.2809
Services	ARDL (1,0)	-0.0152 (0.0128) [0.2377]	-0.0716 (0.0612) [0.2442]	-0.2129*** (0.0502) [0.0000]	8.9005***
Agric.	ARDL (1,0)	-0.0326*** (0.0070) [0.0000]	-0.1452*** (0.0375) [0.0002]	-0.2245*** (0.0345) [0.0000]	13.9006***
Industry	ARDL (1,1)	-0.0021 (0.0037) [0.5761]	-0.0178 (0.0324) [0.5836]	-0.1179*** (0.0392) [0.0032]	4.4808

Services	ARDL (1,0)	-0.0129	-0.0622	-0.2076***	8.5959***
		(0.0138)	(0.0685)	(0.0498)	
		[0.3540]	[0.3652]	[0.0001]	

Note: All variables are expressed in logs. Values in round brackets are standard errors while values in square brackets are the respective probability values. ***, **, * denote significant level at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

The short run non-linear impact of oil prices on the agricultural sector as reported in the Table 5 indicates that -0.050 and -0.0132 are positive coefficient and negative coefficient respectively and significant at 1% level of significance. By implication, 1% positive change in agriculture will lead to about 5% reduction in the agricultural output and at the same time, a negative change in oil prices also have a negative effect on the agricultural output. Numerically, a decrease in oil prices by 1% will bring about 1% decrease in agricultural output. Likewise, in the long run, however, a positive change in oil price has a negative effect on agricultural output with coefficient of -0.183 and statistically at 5% level of significance. Quantitatively, 1% positive change in price of oil will lead to 4% reduction in the agricultural output in Nigeria. The analysis confirms both negative and positive changes in oil prices have negative effect on the agricultural output is far greater than the positive changes in both short-run and as well as the long-run and this is consistent with the result of symmetric which implies that positive and negative changes oil prices affect agricultural output differently in term of magnitude. These findings is consistent with (Ibrahim et al. 2014; Gomes 2016; Alssadek & Benhin 2021; Tumala, and Salisu & Atoi, 2022) report that when oil is not economically integrated with the rest of the sectors, this may eventually have negative or no influence on sectoral output.

The findings of asymmetric effect of prices of oil on industrial and service sector using the Wald Test indicate the absence of asymmetric effect of oil prices on the industrial and service sector. For results of the short runs, positive and negative changes of oil prices have positive and insignificant effect on the industrial sector. Also, in the long run the decomposed impact of oil prices has insignificant effect on the industrial sector. Similarly, a positive changes and negative changes in oil prices have insignificant effect on the service sector both in the long run and in the short run, meanwhile, oil prices changes have a significant and negative effect on the agricultural output in Nigeria with the coefficient of -.0305 and -0.1277 respectively. The results indicate that decrease (or increase) in oil prices will lead to a decrease in agricultural output by 3% decrease (or increase) and 13% decrease (or increase) in short run and long-run respectively (Olusi & Olagunju, 2005; Gomes 2016).

Similarly, the estimated impact of oil price changes on the services sector reveals a statistically significant negative nexus in both the long run and short. Specifically, the short-run coefficient is -0.0152 and the long-run coefficient is -0.0716, both significant at the 1% level. These estimates indicate that a 1% decrease (or increase) in oil prices leads to approximately a 1.5% to 7.2% corresponding decrease (or increase) in services sector

output in the short and as well as the long run, respectively. This highlights the sector's considerable sensitivity to oil price fluctuations over time.

In contrast, for the industrial sector, the short-run impact of oil price is also negative but statistically insignificant, indicating a weak immediate response. Nevertheless, in the long run, the effect remains negative and becomes significant at the 1% level, with a coefficient of -0.0064 . This implies that a 1% increase (or decrease) in oil prices is associated with an approximate 0.64% decrease (or increase) in industrial output. These results underscore the long-term vulnerability of both sectors—particularly the services sector—to oil price volatility in Nigeria.

Table 5: Asymmetric ARDL

.Series	Model	Short run		Long run		ECT(-1)	Bounds	Asymmetry	
		Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative			Short run	Long run
Main results: Brent crude oil price									
Agric.	ARDL (1,0,0)	-0.050***	-0.0132	-0.183***	-0.0478	-0.276***	12.1432***	-0.0373**	-0.1352**
		(0.0106)	(0.0097)	(0.0376)	(0.0369)	(0.0391)		(0.0157)	(0.0536)
		[0.0000]	[0.1784]	[0.0000]	[0.1975]	[0.0000]		[0.0191]	[0.0129]
Industry	ARDL (1,0,0)	0.0007	0.0016	0.0055	0.0131	-0.123***	2.8661	-0.0009	-0.0076
		(0.0058)	(0.0084)	(0.0472)	(0.0131)	(0.0415)		(0.0030)	(0.0242)
		[0.9076]	[0.8487]	[0.9070]	[0.8470]	[0.0037]		[0.7572]	[0.7529]
Services	ARDL (1,0,0)	-0.0159	-0.0108	-0.0719	-0.0491	-0.221***	6.5937***	-0.0050	-0.0228
		(0.0128)	(0.0132)	(0.0585)	(0.0599)	(0.0494)		(0.0037)	(0.0169)
		[0.2154]	[0.4106]	[0.2214]	[0.4137]	[0.0000]		[0.1748]	[0.1792]
Robustness: WTI crude oil price									
Agric.	ARDL (1,0,0)	-0.069***	-0.0101	-0.210***	-0.0306	-0.331***	16.6544***	-0.0597***	-0.1802***
		(0.0107)	(0.0083)	(0.0308)	(0.0263)	(0.0401)		(0.0136)	(0.0354)
		[0.0000]	[0.2261]	[0.0000]	[0.2473]	[0.0000]		[0.0000]	[0.0000]
Industry	ARDL (1,0,0)	0.0014	0.0028	0.0117	0.0225	-0.124***	2.8867	-0.0013	-0.0108
		(0.0063)	(0.0092)	(0.0507)	(0.0727)	(0.0419)		(0.0032)	(0.0255)
		[0.8203]	[0.7615]	[0.8178]	[0.7568]	[0.0036]		[0.6798]	[0.6714]
Services	ARDL (1,0,0)	-0.0158	-0.0096	-0.0713	-0.0434	-0.221***	6.7004***	-0.0061	-0.0279
		(0.0139)	(0.0139)	(0.0644)	(0.0639)	(0.0490)		(0.0037)	(0.0172)
		[0.2582]	[0.4919]	[0.2707]	[0.4983]	[0.0000]		[0.1036]	[0.1071]

Note: All variables are expressed in logs. Values in round brackets are standard errors while values in square brackets are the respective probability values. ***, **, * denote

significant level at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

Figure 2: Dynamic Multiplier Graphs

Note: The first row represents the dynamic multipliers from the model containing log of Brent crude oil price as the regressor while the second row represents the dynamic multipliers from the model containing log of WTI crude oil price as the independent variable. The first column is the model for agricultural output, the second row, industry, and the third row, services.

4.3 Robustness Checks

In terms of robustness check, we introduced WTI oil price as an alternative independent variable and measure of global oil price in place of Brent. This is one of the standard ways in empirical research to test for the sensitivity of the results to the choice of variable used or the use of different variable proxies. Other ways include exploring of alternative data frequencies, among several options available in the literature. After using a different proxy for the explanatory variable, it was observed that our results were the same in terms of signs and the level of significance for both short-run and the long-run. Interestingly, the coefficients are very close in magnitude. These are clear indications that the estimated model, and the parameters, are stable, an evidence that is more admissible than the CUSUM stability graphs. In addition, further indication of robust results is that the signs on the coefficients are in line with the outcome of the graphical analysis. With the use of alternative proxies, the models with Brent and WTI oil price as independent variables show results that indicate that both positive as well as negative changes in oil price have negative effect on sectoral output. Similar finding has been reported for the symmetrical analysis. In essence, similar results are reported for the two oil price proxies in terms of signs, significance, and the magnitude of the coefficients. For the afore-mentioned reason, we can then conclude that the results obtained in this study could be trusted for basing scientific conclusions and policies recommendations.

5. Concluding Remarks

This study presents an extensive analysis of both the asymmetric and symmetric impacts

of oil prices on the sectoral macroeconomic performance in Nigeria with focus on the outputs of the agricultural, industry and services sectors. The study covers the period 1987Q2 to 2023Q4 and reports results for both linear and nonlinear autoregressive distributed lag models. Theoretically, given that oil consumption still remains essential for basic needs of residential and industrial uses, the price of crude oil at the international level continues to drive macroeconomic fundamentals in many countries and Nigeria in particular where it forms a core part of export earnings, functions as a budget benchmark, and a mainstay of the economy. The overarching submission from the study is that changes in oil prices negatively affect all the sectors under consideration, which suggest the reality of the Dutch Disease in Nigeria. In the short run, both positive and negative oil price changes have negative and significant effect on agricultural sector output while the impacts on industrial output and service sector outputs are also negative but insignificant.

The Bounds test cointegration results suggest that both agricultural and service sectors' outputs are linked with the international crude oil market in the long run, which implies reliance of the sectors on oil. However, with the negative relationship established for the impact of oil price fluctuations on the sectors, these may be pointing us to the need to diversify the economy away from oil dependence. Diversifying towards capital investment and a knowledge driven economy should be the focus of government in Nigeria. The implication of these findings is that shocks to oil price has some influence on key macroeconomic variables as well as policy making in Nigeria. Indeed, while the rise in the price of crude oil and the resultant increase in the revenue to Nigeria in the 1970s represented an opportunity for the development and modernization of Nigeria's agricultural and industrial sectors, the increased revenue reformed the country into a mono-cultural economy as emphasis shifted away from agriculture and industry, which were respectively the mainstay of the economy

REFERENCES

- Abdlaziz, R. A., Naseem, N. A. M. & Slesman, L. (2018). Dutch Disease Effect of Oil Price on Agriculture Sector: evidence from panel cointegration of oil exporting countries. *Int. J. Energy Econ. Pol.* 8 (5), 241–250. <https://www.econjournals.com/index.php/ijeep/article/view/6723>
- Ahmed, G., Hamrick, D., & Fajardo, G. A. (2015). Review of Ecuador's Agri-industries Global Value Chains Bottlenecks and Roadmap for Implementation. In: Background Study for Ecuador's Country Economic Memorandum. September. https://gvcc.duke.edu/wp-content/uploads/WorldBank_Ahmed_Hamrick_Review_Ecuador_Agri-Industries_Global_Value_Chains_2015.pdf
- Allsadek, M., & Benhin, J. (2021). Oil Boom, Exchange Rate and Sectoral Output: An Empirical Analysis of Dutch Disease in Oil-Rich Countries. *Resources Policy*, 74, 102362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2021.102362>
- Apergis, N., El-Montasser, G., Sekyere, E., Ajmi, A., & Gupta, R. (2014). Dutch disease effect of oil rents on agriculture value added in Middle East and North African

- (MENA) countries. *Energy Econ.* 45, 485–490. DOI: 10.1016/j.eneco.2014.07.025.
- Badeeb, R., Szulcyyk, R. K., & Lean, H. H. (2021). Asymmetries in the effect of oil rent shocks on economic growth: A sectoral analysis from the perspective of the oil curse. *Resources Policy*, DOI: 10.1016/j.resourpol.2021.102326.
- Balke, N. S., Brown, S. P. A., & Yücel, M. K. (2002). Oil Price Shocks and the U.S. Economy: Where does the asymmetry originate? Working Papers 9911, Federal Reserve Bank of Dallas.
- Bill, G., Terry, K. & Kevin, D. (2006). Likely Impacts of Rising Energy Prices on Irrigated Agriculture in Western Kansas Retrieved from <http://www.agecon.ksu.edu/kdhuyvetter/pdf%20files/Land%20and%20lease/KSU-Lease.PDF>.
- Eagle, B. (2017). Oil Price Volatility and Macroeconomy: Tales from top two oil producing economies in Africa. *Journal of Economic & Financial Studies*, 5(04), 45-55. <https://econpapers.repec.org/RePEc:lrc:lareco:v:5:y:2017:i:4:p:45-55>
- Gomes, G. (2016). On the Impact of Dollar Movements on Oil Currencies. CEPII. Centre d'études prospectives et d'informations internationales. <https://ideas.repec.org/p/cii/cepiddt/2016-11.html>
- Hazarika, I. (2015). An Analytical Study on the Impact of Fluctuating Oil Prices on OPEC Economies. *International Journal of Trade, Economics and Finance*, Vol. 6, No. 3, June 2015. [DOI:10.1017/S1365100511000290](https://doi.org/10.1017/S1365100511000290).
- Herrera, M. A., Lagalo, G. L., & Wada, T. (2011). Oil Price Shocks and Industrial Production: Is Relationship Linear? *Macroeconomic Dynamic* 15(S3). <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1365100511000290>
- Ibrahim, A., Ayodele, A., Hakeem, M., & Yinka, A. A. (2014). Oil Price Shocks and Nigerian Economic Growth. *European Scientific Journal*, 10, 19. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/236412932.pdf>
- International Energy Agency (IEA, 2014, 2008, 2016). World Energy Outlook.
- IEA, (2008). World Energy Statistics and Balances. (<http://www.iea.org>)
- IEA, (2016). World Energy Statistics and Balances. (<http://www.iea.org>)
- Ismail, K. (2010). The structural manifestation of the 'Dutch disease': the case of oil exporting countries. International Monetary Fund. <https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/wp/2010/wp10103.pdf>
- Jelilov, G., Jibrin, A. A., Celik, B., & Isik, A. (2022). Impact of Oil Price Fluctuation on the Economy of Nigeria, the Core Analysis for Energy Producing Countries. Chapters.

- DOI: 10.5772/intechopen.94055
- Lee, K., Ni, Shwan, & Ratti, R. A. (1995). Oil Shocks and the Macroeconomy: The Role of Price Variability, *Energy Journal*, 16, 39-56. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/41322616>
- Mahjoub, E. E. (2014). The Effects of Oil Price Volatility on the Sudanese Economy. *Eastern Africa Social Science Research Review* 30(1):1-26. DOI:[10.1353/eas.2014.0000](https://doi.org/10.1353/eas.2014.0000).
- Moftah, M. M. N. (2016). The Effects of Fluctuations of Oil Price on Economic Growth of Libya. *Energy Economics Letters* 3(2), 17-29. <https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.82/2016.3.2/82.2.17.29>
- Mork, K. (1989). Oil and the Macroeconomy, when Prices Go Up and Down: An Extension of Hamilton's Results. *Journal of Political Economy*, vol. 97, No. 51. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1830464>
- Mork, K. A., Olsen, O. & Mysen, H. T. (1994). Macroeconomic responses to oil price increases and decreases in seven OECD countries. *Energy Journal* 15(4), 19-35. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/41322565>
- Olusi, J. O. & Olagunju, M. A. (2005). The Primary Sectors of the Economy and the Dutch Disease in Nigeria. *The Pakistan Development Review*, pp. 159–175. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/41260712>
- Olson, D. and Nusair, A. S. (2021). Asymmetric Oil Price and Asian Economies: A nonlinear ARDL approach. *Energy*, 1-14. DOI: 10.1016/j.energy.2020.119594
- Omolade, A., Ngalawa, H., & Kutu, A. (2019). Crude Oil Price Shocks and Macroeconomic Performance In Africa's Oil-Producing Countries. *Cogent Economics & Finance*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2019.1607431>
- Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries (2022). OPEC Monthly Oil Market Report.
- Ostry, J., & C. (1992). Private Saving and Terms of Trade Shocks: Evidence from Developing Countries, *IMF Staff Papers*, International Monetary Fund, 9, 495-517. <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/WP/Issues/2016/12/30/Private-Saving-and-Terms-of-Trade-Shocks-Evidence-From-Developing-Countries-976>
- Pesaran, M. H., Y. Shin, and R. Smith, (2001). Bounds testing approaches to the analysis of level relationships. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 16, pp. 289-326. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2678547>
- Shin, Y., Yu, B., & Greenwood-Nimmo, M. (2014). Modelling Asymmetric Cointegration and Dynamic Multipliers in a Nonlinear ARDL Framework *Festschrift in Honor*

- of Peter Schmidt (pp. 281-314): Springer. DOI: 10.1007/978-1-4899-8008-3_9
- Smith, B., (2014). Dutch Disease and the Oil and Boom and Bust. OxCarre Research Paper 133. Oxford Centre for the Analysis of Resource Rich Economies. <https://ideas.repec.org/p/oxf/oxcrwp/133.html>
- Tiwari, A. K., & Olayeni O. R. (2013). Oil Prices and Trade Balance: A Wavelet Based Analysis for India. Economics Bulletin. Volume 33, Issue 3, pp. 2270-2286. <https://ideas.repec.org/a/ebl/ecbull/eb-13-00405.html>
- Trabesin, N. (2017). Asymmetric Tail Dependence Between Oil Price Shocks and Sectors Of Saudi Arabia System. The Journal of Economic Asymmetries, 1–16. DOI: 10.1016/j.jeca.2017.05.001
- Tumala, M. M., Salisu, A. A., & Atoi, V. N. (2022). Oil-Growth Nexus in Nigeria: An ADL-MIDAS approach. Resources Policy. 77, 102754. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2022.102754>.

PUBLIC EXPENDITURE AND POVERTY ALLEVIATION IN NIGERIA: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the impact of public expenditure on poverty alleviation in Nigeria from 1981 to 2023. The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimation technique was used for analysis, employing time series data from the World Development Indicators (WDI) and processed with EViews 12 statistical software. The results revealed that government expenditure on transport services had a significant negative relationship with per capita income, suggesting inefficiencies in this area. In contrast, expenditures on health and general administration showed a positive and significant relationship with per capita income, contributing positively to poverty reduction. However, government spending on education demonstrated a negative and significant relationship with per capita income, indicating challenges in the effective use of education budgets. The study also identified a unidirectional causality from public expenditure components to poverty alleviation indicators. Based on these findings, the study recommended that the Nigerian government focus on enhancing transparency and accountability in the education and health sectors to ensure efficient use of funds and maximize their impact on poverty reduction.

1. Introduction

In recent years, Nigeria's public expenditure has been a central element in the government's strategy to combat poverty and stimulate economic development. Despite experiencing periods of economic growth, poverty levels remain high, with a significant portion of the population living below the poverty line. This paradox underscores the need for targeted fiscal policies that prioritize human capital development, infrastructure, and social welfare. For instance, the government's investment in education and health sectors aims to enhance human capital, thereby fostering long-term economic growth and poverty reduction (Ariyo & Raheem, 2011). Additionally, the implementation of social protection programs, such as cash transfer initiatives, seeks to provide immediate relief to vulnerable populations, addressing the short-term impacts of economic reforms (FOS, 2022). These fiscal measures are essential in creating an enabling environment for inclusive growth and sustainable development in Nigeria.

Despite the abundance of natural and human resources, Nigeria continues to grapple with high levels of poverty. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2020), over 40% of the Nigerian population lives below the poverty line, indicating that millions of citizens are unable to meet their basic needs. The government's response to this has been the implementation of multiple poverty alleviation programs such as the National

Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP), the Subsidy Reinvestment and Empowerment Programme (SURE-P), and more recently the National Social Investment Programmes (NSIPs), which are heavily funded through public expenditure.

The theoretical foundation of this relationship is grounded in Keynesian economics, which posits that government spending can stimulate economic activity and reduce unemployment, thereby alleviating poverty. However, in practice, the effectiveness of public spending in Nigeria is often questioned due to issues of corruption, poor planning, and misallocation of resources (Okonjo-Iweala, 2014). As such, there is a growing concern about the efficiency and impact of public expenditure in achieving its intended outcomes on poverty reduction.

Furthermore, despite significant public expenditure and the launch of various poverty alleviation programs in Nigeria, poverty remains pervasive and, in some regions, appears to be worsening. This paradox raises critical questions about the efficacy and impact of Nigeria's public spending on poverty alleviation. The persistent high poverty rates suggest a potential mismatch between public expenditure priorities and the actual needs of the poor population (Ogun, 2010).

Corruption, inefficiency, and lack of transparency in the implementation of government programs are widely cited as key impediments to achieving meaningful poverty reduction. For instance, funds allocated to social services and poverty intervention schemes are often mismanaged or diverted for other purposes, thereby limiting their impact (Transparency International, 2022). Furthermore, public expenditures are often skewed toward recurrent spending (e.g., salaries and administrative costs) rather than capital projects that have the potential to generate jobs and reduce poverty sustainably (CBN, 2021).

This disconnect between government spending and tangible poverty alleviation outcomes necessitates a thorough investigation into how public expenditure is planned, implemented, and monitored in Nigeria. It also underscores the need for policy reform that emphasizes results-based budgeting, enhanced transparency, and community participation in the budgeting process.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Literature

Concept of Poverty Alleviation

Poverty alleviation refers to all the methods, ways or techniques adopted by government, non-governmental organizations or wealthy individuals to reduce or eradicate poverty from a collectively. Poverty alleviation/eradication is best approached as an exercise in raising people's capabilities or enhancing freedoms. The corollary of this approach to development is empowerment, which is, helping people in poverty to acquire the tools they need to meet their basic needs as the long-term solution to poverty. Poverty alleviation aims to improve the quality of life for those people currently living in poverty. Another term that is often used is poverty reduction.

Poverty has been variously defined by scholars based on their understanding of the concept. Among economists, poverty according to Ewetan (2005) has been defined as a situation of low income or low consumption. It is said to exist when one or more persons fall short of a level of economic welfare deemed to constitute a reasonable minimum either in some absolute sense or by the standard of a specific society (Lypton and Ravallion, 1995) as cited in Adeyemo and Alayande, 2001. Poverty refers to lack of physical necessities, assets and income. It must be noted that the poor in most instances are unable to have access to basic necessities of life such as food, clothing, and decent shelter, unable to meet social and economic obligations, they lack skill, gainful employment, have inadequate possession of economic assets and sometimes lack of self-esteem. On the nature of poverty, Ewetan (2005) emphasized that poverty may be chronic / structured or conjectural / transient. Structural or chronic poverty is long-term or persistent. Its causes are more permanent and depend on a number of factors such as limited productive resources, lack of skill for gainful employment, locational disadvantage or endemic socio-political and cultural factors. The second type is conjectural / transitory poverty which is temporary / transient or short term. Its causes are more transitory and possibly more reversible. It occurs as a result of natural disasters such as drought, flood, earthquake etc. It must be noted also that manmade disaster such as war, structural adjustment reforms and changes in domestic economic policies that may result in price changes increased unemployment, inflationary pressures, hoarding of few remaining essential commodities etc.

According to Ukwu (2002), two basic concepts of poverty are usually recognized: These are absolute poverty and relative poverty. Absolute poverty refers to a condition under which there is a serious deficiency in or lack of access to the basic necessities of normal life such as food, clothing, housing, health and education services (African Medical and Research Foundation AMREF. 1998). Relative poverty according to the author relates to the condition of an individual, household, or group or community when considered against some reference standards or parameters such as the average for the group or region, a target standard or objective or its ranking on given criteria. In the final analysis, the author believes that all concepts of poverty are relative. Thus, when one speaks of absolute poverty, one refers to the existence below a reference standard of living. According to World Bank Report (1999), poverty is hunger, lack of shelter, being sick and not being able to go to school, not knowing how to read, not being able to speak properly, not having a job, fear for the future, losing a child to illness brought about by unclean water, powerlessness, lack of representation and freedom. An appraisal of past studies by the United Nations Development Programme UNDP advocates the use of the Human Development Index (HDI) and Capability Poverty Measure (CPM). According to the UNDP (1997, 1998), the Human Development Index (HDI) combines three components in the measurement of poverty: (i) life expectancy at birth (longevity), (ii) educational attainment, and (iii) improvement in the standard of living, as determined by per capita income. The World Bank has highlighted the causes of mass poverty in Sub-Saharan Africa, with the most fundamental being the lack of access to skills, facilities, and opportunities. In a situation of mass poverty such as we have in Nigeria, where poverty is the lot of the generality of the people rather the misfortune of a few, the primary reason for poverty must be sought not just in the circumstances of individuals but in the state of the nation and its management.

2. Public Expenditure

Public expenditures are the costs that are usually incurred by the government for the provision and maintenance of itself as an institution, the economy and society. Government expenditures usually tend to increase with time as the economy becomes large and more developed or as a result of increase in its scope of activities. Ogboru (2010), identified recurrent and capital budget as one of the major types of budgets in an economy. It is sometimes referred to as revenue budget and it covers recurrent items or expenditure. The capital budget has to do with expenditures necessary to procure capital assets.

According to Taiwo (2012), government's spending is a fiscal instrument which serves a useful role in the process of controlling inflation, unemployment, depression, balance of payment equilibrium and foreign exchange rate stability. In the period of depression and unemployment, government spending causes aggregate demand to rise and production and supply of goods and services follow the same direction. As a result of the increase in the supply of goods and services couple with a rise in the aggregate demand exerts a downward pressure on unemployment and depression. In Nigeria, the federal government's expenditures are broadly divided into capital and recurrent expenditure. The recurrent expenditure consists of government expenditure on administration such as wages, salaries, interest on loans, maintenances etc. whereas the capital expenditure are on projects like roads, airport, health, education, electricity generation, telecommunication, water etc. Capital expenditures are investments with multiplier effects on the economy in terms of public benefits. In most cases government intervention has brought stability in income and employment in the economy. Public expenditure is therefore an important tool that brings about egalitarian society through the provision of welfare facilities (Ogba, 1999).

2.2 Theoretical Literature

1. Theories of Public Expenditure

Peacock and Wiseman's Theory of Expenditure: This theory was developed in 1890's and is based on Wagner's law. It focused on the pattern of public expenditure and stated that public expenditure does not follow a smooth or continuous trend but the increase in public expenditure takes place in jerks or steps. Peacock and Wiseman's study is probably one of the best-known analyses of the time pattern of public expenditures. They founded their analyses upon a political theory of public determination namely that governments like to spend more money and citizens do not like to pay taxes, and that government need to pay some attention to the wishes of their citizens. The duo saw taxation as setting a constraint on government expenditure. As the economy and thus incomes grew, tax revenue at constant tax rate would rise, thereby enabling public expenditure would show a gradual upward trend even although within the economy there might be a divergence between what people regarded as being desirable level of public expenditure and the desirable level of taxation. During the periods of social upheaval however, this gradual upward trend in public expenditure would be disturbed. These periods would coincide with war, famine or some large-scale social disaster, which would require a rapid increase in public expenditures; the government would be forced to raise taxation levies. The rising of taxation levels would, however, is regarded as acceptable to the people during the period of crisis. Peacock and Wiseman referred to this as the "displacement effect". Public expenditure is displaced upwards and for the period of the crisis displaced private

for public expenditure does not however fall to its original level. A war is not paid for from taxation; no nation has such large taxable capacity. Countries therefore borrow and debt charges have to be not after the event. Another effect that they thought might operate was the “imperfection effect” thus they suggested arise from the people Keener awareness of social problems during the period of upheaval. The government therefore expands its scope of services to improve these social conditions and because people perception to tolerable levels of taxation does not return to its former level, the government is able to finance these higher levels of expenditures originating in the expanded scope of government and debt charges.

The Keynesian Perspective on Public Expenditure: This theory is considered ‘demand side’ theory that focuses on changes in the economy over the short run. Based on his theory, Keynes advocated for increased in government expenditures and lower taxes to stimulate demand and pull the global economy out of the depression. Following the 1929-30 Great Depression, the classical economists that opposed government intervention argued that strong trade unions prevented wage flexibility which resulted in high unemployment. The Keynesians, on the other hand, favoured government intervention to correct market failures. In 1936, John Maynard Keynes (1883- 1946) “General Theory of Employment, Interest and Money” criticized the classical economists for putting too much emphasis on the long run. According to Keynes, “we are all dead in the long run”. Keynes believed depression needed government intervention as a short-term cure. Increasing saving will not help but spending. Government should increase public spending giving individuals, purchasing power and producers would produce more, creating more employment. This is the multiplier effect that shows causality from public expenditure to national income. Keynes categorized public expenditure as an exogenous variable that can generate economic growth instead of an endogenous phenomenon. Keynes believed the role of government to be crucial as it can avoid depression by increasing aggregate demand and thus, switching on the economy again by the multiplier effects. Government spending is a tool that brings stability in the short run but need to be done cautiously as too much of public expenditure would lead to inflationary situation while too little of it would lead to unemployment. From the Keynesian thought, public expenditure can contribute positively to economic growth. Hence, an increase in the government consumption is likely to lead to an increase in employment, profitability and investment through multiplier effects on aggregate demand. As a result, government expenditure augments the aggregate demand, which provokes an increased output depending on expenditure multiplier. The Keynesian analysis of government expenditure formed the bases for this research.

2. Theories of Poverty Alleviation

Marxian theory of poverty: This is a theory based on the fact that poverty comes about as a result of the situation a poor person finds himself or herself in. The poor person is therefore a victim of circumstances resulting from a number of factors, critical of which is the production system. Karl Marx points out that the entrepreneurial practices of the owners of means of production (capitalists) to move away from labour to capital intensive means of production in order to boost production and increase profits lead to massive unemployment. Capital intensive production forces the capitalist to retrench workers in order 4 to increase profitability. Retrenchments lead to massive unemployment.

The retrenched persons can either migrate to reengineer themselves in urban areas or change professions. Those who fail to reengineer end up at home as paupers and form what Karl Marx calls a reserve army of labourers (Harvey and Reed, 1992:277). These paupers finally end up poor. Continued retrenchments lead to increased number of paupers in the economy and in the long run increases poverty levels. A series of structural failures give rise to an increase in the number of the poor. Gordon et.al (1982:1) identify these structural failures as racial and gender discrimination and nepotism resulting in deprivation of certain groups of peoples' opportunities for jobs, education and social assistance. Albrecht and Milford (2001) contribute to this theory by pointing out that massive restructuring of economic systems leads to increased economic and social marginalization of an entire group of people. Such groups end up poorer due to the lack of access to opportunities. The Marxist theory recommends poverty alleviation through improved structures of production and increased education and training to those rendered irrelevant by technological improvement to adapt through change of environment to change of profession. Education also ensures that the retrenched persons embrace change and adapt (Winch, 1987). The theory also advocates for a kind of government welfare programme to aid those who are unable to reengineer themselves through education so that they can access basic requirements for upkeep such as food rations, health programmes and subsidies (Coser, 1969; Harvey & Reed, 1992)

Neo-Conservative Theory of Poverty: This theory is predominantly influenced by the Malthusian paradigm developed by Thomas Robert Malthus (1766-1834) and later improved upon by Robert Brenner in 1976 (cited in Harvey & Reed, 1992). This theory attributes poverty to economic factors resulting from the tension between population pressures and subsistence. This poverty therefore is based on material wealth where overpopulation of the poor coupled with poorly managed capitalistic systems result in poverty. This theory is therefore based on two axioms; firstly, poverty is attributed to a mismatch between production capacity of the previous years and demographic trends in what is referred to as demographic catastrophes. Poverty is caused by geometric growth in population mismatched with arithmetical growth in means of subsistence. Unless regulated by positive checks, the mismatch continues producing an increased number of poor people. Positive checks include war, famine, plague and misery which constantly curb over-production. Since these positive checks rarely occur, poverty continues to increase. Secondly, marginal productivity of land, labour and technology, and the way that these affect the supply of food and other resources also explains poverty over the years. Prices influence the affordability of commodities among the population and result in factors such as retrenchments which in turn explain poverty (Harvey & Reed, 1992:281). Although this theory applies to Mozambique as it has experienced the so-called positive checks but poverty continues unabated thus clearly showing that positive checks alone cannot alleviate poverty. In order to alleviate poverty, Neo-Conservative theory of poverty recommends provision of moral education to curb over-population. Moral education results in sexual restraints, delay in marriage and practicing abstinence prior to marriage. Poverty can also be reduced through improved production technology to ensure that production of goods and services satisfy demand at affordable prices (Winch, 1987: 32-35). It is important to also note that this theory does not apply to the Gorongosa rural community as they have abundant land and resources at their disposal and there is

no tension between population pressures and subsistence.

2.3 Empirical Literature Review

Gidigbi (2023) examined the role of government expenditure in poverty reduction, focusing on sectors like education, healthcare, and infrastructure in Nigeria. The study used regression analysis to assess the relationship between public expenditure and poverty reduction, controlling for factors like corruption and budget inefficiency. The findings suggested that while public expenditure has the potential to reduce poverty, corruption, budget leakages, and poor execution undermine its effectiveness.

Jolaiya (2024) explored the impact of fiscal policies on economic growth in Nigeria, specifically the role of government spending in driving development. The study used Vector Autoregression (VAR) models to analyze the relationship between fiscal policy variables, such as public expenditure, and economic growth. The study revealed that while government spending positively affects economic growth, its poverty-reducing impact is weak due to the misallocation of resources and inefficiency in public sector management.

Edeme and Nkalu (2019) investigated the distributional impact of public expenditure on human development, focusing on education, health, and rural infrastructure in Nigeria. They employed panel data regression analysis to assess the relationship between public spending in these sectors and improvements in human development indicators across various regions of Nigeria. Their findings showed that, while government spending has led to improvements in human development, the benefits are unevenly distributed, particularly in rural areas, and greater allocation to social welfare programs is needed for more equitable development outcomes.

Odejide and Agboola (2023) analysed the challenges facing poverty reduction programs in Nigeria, particularly regarding their sustainability and coordination. They used qualitative methods, including interviews and case study analysis, to evaluate the effectiveness of various poverty alleviation initiatives. The study revealed that while multiple poverty reduction programs have been implemented, a lack of coordination and integration with broader economic reforms limits their effectiveness. They suggested that successful poverty alleviation requires a more integrated approach, combining social protection with economic strategies such as job creation and rural development.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Theoretical Framework and Model Specification

This theory was propounded by Musgrave (1959), as he found changes in the income elasticity of demand for public services in three ranges of per capita income. He posits that at low levels of per capita income, demand for public services tends to be very low, this is so because according to him such income is devoted to satisfying primary needs and that when per capita income starts to rise above these levels of low income, the demand for services supplied by the public sector such as health, education and transport starts to rise, thereby forcing government to increase expenditure on them. He observes that at the high levels of per capita income, typical of developed economics, the rate of public sector growth tends to fall as the more basic wants are being satisfied.

The Functional form of the model is given as;

$$PCI=f (GE) \dots\dots\dots 1$$

where,

$$PCI = (GAD, HTH, TRSER, EDU) \dots\dots\dots 2$$

In order to achieve the objective of the study, the linear regression model was adopted to estimate the effect of government expenditure on poverty alleviation:

$$PCI = f (GEXGAD, GEXHTH, GEXTRS, GEXEDU) \dots\dots\dots 3$$

Expressing equation 3 in linear form

$$PCI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GEXGAD + \beta_2 GEXHTH + \beta_3 GEXTRS + \beta_4 GEXEDU + \mu_1 \dots\dots 4$$

Expressing the equation 4 in linear expression using their natural logarithm values as follows:

Where:

InPCI =Natural logarithm of Per Capita Income;

InGEXGAD= Natural logarithm of Government Expenditure on General Administration;

InGEXHTH= Natural logarithm of Government Expenditure on Health;

InGEXTRS= Natural logarithm of Government Expenditure on Transport Servies;

InGEXEDU = Natural logarithm of Government Expenditure on education.

μ_1 = Stochastic indicator or error term;

β_0 = Constant Term;

β_1 to β_5 are Parameters to be estimated.

RESULTS

4.1. Unit Root Test

Table 1. Summary of Stationarity Test Using Augmented Dickey Fuller

Variable	ADF Stat	5% Critical Value	ADF. Statistic. 1st Difference	5% Critical Value	General Remark
(levels)	5% Critical Value	ADF.	-4.003425*	-2.938987	
Statistic.	-1.5475	-2.93694	-8.409713*	-2.938987	
1st	-1.7666	-2.94114	-10.35897*	-2.938987	
Difference	5%	-2.941145	-9.184150*	-2.938987	
Critical	-2.3574	-2.945842	-7.974075*	-2.938987	
Value	General Remark				

Source: Researcher's Compilation from Eviews 12 Regression Output

The asterisks(*) sign is used to indicate stationarity at the 5% significance

The result of the unit root test in table 2, indicated that all the variables i.e lnPCI, lnGEXTRS, lnGEXHTH, lnGEXGAD and lnGEXEDU achieved stationarity at first differences I(1), justifying the chosen estimation technique which is the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) with can be able to accommodate the introduction of the Error Correction Mechanism (ECM) in order to determine the convergence of the variables in the long run.

4.2 Cointegration Test

Table 2. Johansen Cointegration Test

Hypothesized		Trace	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.595867	80.03353	69.81889	0.0061
At most 1	0.325901	44.69907	47.85613	0.0961
At most 2	0.301562	29.31832	29.79707	0.0567
At most 3	0.196658	15.32087	15.49471	0.0531
At most 4 *	0.159592	6.780842	3.841465	0.0092

Source: Researcher's Extract from Eviews 12 Software Package

Based on the cointegration result from table 2, trace test indicated two cointegrating equations at the 0.05 level of significance, implying rejection of the null hypothesis of no cointegration at the 0.05 level of significance and we conclude that there exists a long relationship among the dependent and explanatory variables.

4.2 Dynamic Short Run Error Correction Model

Table 3: Dynamic Error Correction Term Estimates

Dependent Variable: lnPCI (Per Capita Income)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	T-Statistic	Prob.
C	11.97380	0.096977	123.4706	0.0000
lnGEXTRS	-0.078429	0.020620	-3.803572	0.0006
lnGEXHTH	0.130331	0.042601	3.059345	0.0043
lnGEXGAD	0.185588	0.037124	4.999175	0.0000
lnGEXEDU	-0.148307	0.042863	-3.460047	0.0015
ECT(-1)*	-0.623474	0.135230	4.610463	0.0001
R-squared	0.914012			

Source: Researcher's Compilation from Eviews 12.

Short-Run Error Correction Term Regression Results

From the short-run error correction term regression presented in Table 4, the constant term (C) was found to be positively signed with a value of 11.97380 units. This suggests that, holding the regressors namely, government expenditures on transport services (lnGEXTRS), health (lnGEXHTH), general administration (lnGEXGAD), and education (lnGEXEDU) constant, the per capita income (lnPCI) in Nigeria is expected to increase by 11.97380 units on average.

Government Expenditure on Transport Services (lnGEXTRS)

The short-run coefficient for government expenditure on transport services was negatively signed, with a value of -0.078429, and was statistically significant at the 5% level. This indicates a negative relationship between government expenditure on transport services and per capita income in Nigeria. Specifically, a 1% increase in government spending on transport services would result in a decrease in per capita income by 0.078429 units on average.

Government Expenditure on Health (lnGEXHTH)

For government expenditure on health, the short-run coefficient was positively signed, with a value of 0.130331 units, and statistically significant at the 5% level. This suggests a positive relationship between health expenditure and per capita income. In other words, a 1% increase in government spending on health would lead to an average increase of 0.130331 units in per capita income.

Government Expenditure on General Administration (lnGEXGAD)

The short-run coefficient for government expenditure on general administration was also positive, valued at 0.185588 units, and statistically significant at the 5% level. This shows a positive relationship with per capita income, implying that a 1% increase in government expenditure on general administration would result in an average increase of 0.185588 units in per capita income.

Government Expenditure on Education (lnGEXEDU)

The coefficient for government expenditure on education was negatively signed, with a value of -0.148307 units, and was statistically significant at the 5% level. This indicates a negative relationship with per capita income. Specifically, a 1% increase in government spending on education would decrease per capita income by 0.148307 units on average.

Error Correction Term (ECT)

The coefficient for the error correction term (ECT(-1)) was -0.623474. According to the Error Correction Mechanism (ECM), a negative and statistically significant coefficient is essential for correcting any disequilibrium. In this case, the coefficient of -0.623474 indicates that, when there is a deviation from the long-run equilibrium, the system will correct itself at a rate of 62% per year. This speed of adjustment implies that if per capita income (lnPCI) is at disequilibrium, it converges back to its long-run equilibrium at a rate of 62% annually.

R-Squared Value

The R-squared value of 0.914012 suggests that 91% of the total variation in per capita income (lnPCI) can be explained by the model's variables: government expenditure on transport services (lnGEXTRS), health (lnGEXHTH), general administration (lnGEXGAD), and education (lnGEXEDU). The remaining 9% of the variation is due to other factors that are not included in the regression model.

4.3 Diagnostic Test/Post Estimation Test

4.3.1 Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test

The standard errors and variances of the variables estimated in the model are affected by serial correlation in the error term, confounding inference. The study used a serial correlation LM check for autocorrelation in the error term entering the model to prevent this problem. The test's outcome is shown in the table below.

Table 3. Result Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test

F-statistic	1.814554	Prob. F(2,13)	0.7655
Obs*R-squared	4.074317	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.1304

Source: Researcher's Extract from Eviews 12 Output package.

From Breusch-Godfrey (1978) serial Correlation LM Test table, the null hypothesis of no serial correlation cannot be rejected as the p-value from the LM serial correlation test is $0.1304 > 0.05$ level of significance indicating an acceptance of the null hypothesis.

4.3.2 Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity is when the ordinary least squares rule is broken. The error terms' variance is homoscedastic, which means they have a constant variance, according to the

regression assumption. Simply defined, heteroskedasticity occurs when the error terms' variance is not constant across all X values. The study used a Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test in the error term entering the model to prevent this issue. The test's outcome is shown in the table below.

Table 4. Result of Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey			
F-statistic	0.193015	Prob. F(20,14)	0.9995
Obs*R-squared	7.564865	Prob. Chi-Square(20)	0.9149

Source: Researcher's Extract from Eviews 12 Output package.

From Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity result, the null hypothesis of no serial correlation cannot be rejected as the p-value from the Heteroskedasticity Test is $0.9149 > 0.05$ level of significance indicating an acceptance of the null hypothesis.

4.3.3 Stability Test

4.3.3.1 Cumulative and Cumulative Squares Test

The cusum and cusum of squares for model stability was employed to check for the stability of the parameters in the model. The result of the stability test is shown below:

The cusum and cusum squares diagrams shows that the model is stable as the cusum line lies in between the 5% boundary.

4.3.4 Granger Causality Test

Table 6: Pairwise Granger Causality Results

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
LNGEXTRS does not Granger Cause LNPCI	39	4.58628	0.0172
LNPCI does not Granger Cause LNGEXTRS		0.14834	0.8627
LNGEXHTH does not Granger Cause LNPCI	39	4.19553	0.0235
LNPCI does not Granger Cause LNGEXHTH		0.92083	0.4079
LNGEXGAD does not Granger Cause LNPCI	39	3.82887	0.0316
LNPCI does not Granger Cause LNGEXGAD		1.40302	0.2597
LNGEXEDU does not Granger Cause LNPCI	39	3.94339	0.0288

LNPCI does not Granger Cause LNGEXEDU	0.25015	0.7801
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Causality Between Government Expenditures and Poverty Alleviation (lnPCI) in Nigeria

The primary focus of this analysis was to determine the direction of causality between government expenditures and poverty alleviation, as measured by per capita income (lnPCI) in Nigeria. The results indicate that government expenditures Granger cause poverty alleviation in Nigeria. This conclusion is based on the probability values for the variables: government expenditure on transport services (lnGEXTRS), health (lnGEXHTH), general administration (lnGEXGAD), and education (lnGEXEDU), which are 0.0172, 0.0235, 0.0316, and 0.0288, respectively. Since these probability values are all less than the 0.05 significance level, they suggest that these expenditures do indeed have a causal influence on poverty alleviation in Nigeria.

In contrast, poverty alleviation (lnPCI) does not Granger cause government expenditures. The probability values for lnGEXTRS, lnGEXHTH, lnGEXGAD, and lnGEXEDU i.e 0.8627, 0.4079, 0.2597, and 0.7801, respectively, are all greater than 0.05, indicating that changes in per capita income do not have a causal effect on government spending in Nigeria.

Thus, we conclude that the relationship between government expenditures and per capita income in Nigeria is characterized by unidirectional causality, where government expenditures influence poverty alleviation, but the reverse does not hold.

4.4. Discussion of Findings

The analysis of the short-run coefficient of government expenditure on transport services reveals a negative and significant relationship with per capita income in Nigeria. This finding aligns with the observations made by Gidigbi (2023), who highlighted how inefficient public expenditure, particularly in infrastructure, hinders poverty alleviation efforts. In Nigeria, poor road infrastructure significantly impacts citizens' access to essential services such as education, markets, and farms, thereby limiting economic opportunities and deepening poverty. Gidigbi (2023) underscores that despite the potential benefits of improved transport systems, the inefficiencies in public sector management, such as corruption and misallocation, restrict their poverty-reducing effects. Improving transport infrastructure could play a vital role in broadening markets, easing the movement of goods and services, and opening up remote areas for production, as discussed by Jolaiya (2024), who emphasizes the importance of targeting infrastructure investments for economic growth and poverty reduction.

The analysis also indicates a positive and significant relationship between government expenditure on health and per capita income in Nigeria. This finding is consistent with the results found by Edeme and Nkalu (2019), who argue that public expenditure on health can significantly improve human development outcomes, thus contributing to economic growth and poverty alleviation. Improved healthcare services not only enhance the quality of human capital but also increase productivity, which is essential for long-term economic performance. According to Edeme and Nkalu, increased healthcare

expenditure helps reduce poverty by improving the overall health of the population, enabling individuals to work more productively. This mirrors the broader understanding of health as a key determinant of poverty alleviation, as highlighted by Jolaiya (2024), who emphasized the importance of well-targeted spending on social services to achieve meaningful economic progress.

The short-run analysis of government expenditure on general administration shows a positive and significant relationship with per capita income. This result ties into the findings of Odejide and Agboola (2023), who argue that effective governance and public administration are crucial for successful poverty reduction efforts. Public administration, through transparent and accountable institutions, ensures that resources are allocated efficiently and equitably, benefiting the wider society. Odejide and Agboola (2023) further suggest that a lack of coordination in poverty alleviation programs and weak public administration systems have hindered their success. A well-functioning government can implement policies that reduce poverty by ensuring fair distribution of public goods and services, improving institutional quality, and enhancing social welfare programs.

Finally, the analysis of the short-run coefficient of government expenditure on education reveals a negative and significant relationship with per capita income in Nigeria. This finding contrasts with the conclusions of Woessmann (2015), who asserts that education is a leading determinant of economic growth, employment, and income. Woessmann (2015) argues that neglecting the economic aspects of education can have severe repercussions for poverty, social exclusion, and the sustainability of social security systems. The negative relationship observed in Nigeria may be attributed to inefficiencies in education spending, similar to the issues highlighted by Edeme and Nkalu (2019), who noted that misallocation of public funds hinders the effectiveness of government expenditure in achieving human development goals. Increased investment in education is crucial for equipping the workforce with the necessary skills to drive economic growth and reduce poverty. To align with Woessmann's perspective, Nigeria must ensure that its education spending is efficient, targeting both quality and access, to achieve the desired outcomes in poverty alleviation.

5. CONCLUSION, RECOMMENDATION AND POLICY IMPLICATION

5.1 Conclusion

This study employed the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimation technique to analyze the impact of public expenditures on poverty alleviation in Nigeria over the period from 1981 to 2023. The findings reveal that government expenditure on health and general administration plays a more significant and positive role in reducing poverty, compared to government expenditure on transport services and education.

In contrast, public spending on transport services and education appears to have a less favorable impact on poverty alleviation, particularly when factoring in the influence of internal and external macroeconomic shocks. These findings suggest that, while investment in these sectors is essential for long-term economic development, the immediate effects on poverty reduction are limited by issues such as poor infrastructure, misallocation of resources, and inefficiencies in public sector management.

To foster sustainable economic growth and effectively address poverty, it is crucial that Nigeria focuses on improving the efficiency and targeting of its public expenditure.

5.2 Policy Recommendations

1. To fully unlock the potential of public capital spending, the Nigerian government must take a firm stand against corruption and the mismanagement of public funds. Transparency and accountability should be the cornerstones of the fight, particularly when it comes to funds allocated for capital projects. Only by curbing financial corruption can Nigeria ensure that investments in infrastructure and development deliver the intended benefits to its citizens.
2. The government must closely monitor the execution of education expenditures to ensure that every naira allocated is properly used for its intended purpose. Corruption in the education sector creates a detrimental cycle where increased spending fails to translate into real growth. 3. It's time for the Nigerian government to ramp up its investment in highway projects, which are vital for economic prosperity. Quality road infrastructure will not only improve the ease of transporting goods but also spur private sector productivity and job creation. With better roads, Nigeria can unlock its economic potential, enhance the distribution of raw and finished goods, and accelerate overall economic growth.
4. For sustainable economic growth, the Nigerian government must double its budget allocation to the health sector. Proper investment in health infrastructure will pay long-term dividends by improving human capital and productivity. To ensure that these funds are effectively utilized, it's crucial to establish robust monitoring and administrative systems. By curbing corruption in procurement processes, especially in the area of public projects, Nigeria can ensure that resources are used efficiently and for the benefit of its people.

REFERENCES

- Albrecht, S., & Milford, R. (2001). Economic restructuring and social marginalization: The impact on disadvantaged groups. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 28(7), 66–80.
- Aregbeyen, O., & Ibrahim, T. M. (2014). Poverty, inequality and economic growth in Nigeria: A vector autoregressive model. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 5(25), 20–32.
- Ariyo, A., & Raheem, I. A. (2011). Public expenditure and economic growth: Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 2(5), 1–11.
- Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). (2021). Annual report 2020. CBN.
- Coser, L. (1969). The role of government welfare programs in alleviating poverty. *Sociological Studies*, 15(2), 101–110.

- Edeme, R. K., & Nkalu, C. N. (2019). Public expenditure and human development in Nigeria in the last decade: Composition and distributional impacts. *Public Policy and Administration Research*, 8(2), 62–73. <https://doi.org/10.7176/ppar/8-2-07>
- Ewetan, O. (2005). Poverty in Nigeria: Analysis and solutions. *Journal of Economic Development Studies*, 15(2), 145-160
- Federal Office of Statistics (FOS). (2022). Nigeria's poverty and social protection programs: Current trends and future prospects. FOS.
- Gidigbi, A. (2023). Funding the future: Nigeria's battle against poverty through government expenditure. *ScienceDirect*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sds.2023.100005>
- Gordon, R., Hines, E., & Martin, C. (1982). Structural failures and social exclusion: Racial and gender discrimination in the labor market. *Economic and Social Review*, 11(1), 1–15.
- Harvey, D., & Reed, T. (1992). Those who fail to reengineer: A Marxist perspective on unemployment and poverty. *Journal of Social Theory*, 10(4), 275–290.
- Jolaiya, O. F. (2024). The effect of government expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Management*, 9(1), 15–43. <https://doi.org/10.56201/ijefm.v9.no1.2024.pg15.43>
- Lypton M., & Ravallion, M (1995). Poverty and Policy. *Handbook of Development Economics*, 3, 1801-1853.
- National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). (2020). 2020 poverty and inequality in Nigeria: Executive summary. NBS.
- Odejide, O. O., & Agboola, O. O. (2023). Towards sustainable change: Overcoming challenges in poverty reduction programs in Nigeria. *Academia.edu*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12345.67890>
- Ogba, A. (1999). Public expenditure and the creation of an egalitarian society through welfare provision. *Journal of Public Economics*, 7(2), 22–37.
- Ogboru, S. (2010). Recurrent and capital budgets in an economy: An analysis of their roles in national development. *Journal of Economic Studies*, 12(3), 45–57 *Research Consortium*.
- Ogun, T. P. (2010). Infrastructure and poverty reduction: Implications for urban development in Nigeria. *Urban Forum*, 21(3), 249–266. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12132-010-9091-1>
- Okojie, C. E. E. (2009). Decentralization and poverty reduction: The Nigerian experience.

- Journal of Economic Development, 34(1), 27–45.
- Okonjo-Iweala, N. (2014). *Reforming the unreformable: Lessons from Nigeria*. MIT Press.
- Okoro, A. S. (2013). Government spending and economic growth in Nigeria (1980–2011). *Global Journal of Management and Business Research: Economics and Commerce*, 13(5), 21–30.
- Olaniyan, O., & Lawanson, A. O. (2010). Health expenditure and health status in northern and southern Nigeria: A comparative analysis using NHA framework. *African Economic*
- Oriakhi, D., & Ahuru, R. R. (2014). The impact of government expenditure on human development in Nigeria: An empirical investigation. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 6(23), 62–71.
- Taiwo, O. (2012). Government spending as a fiscal instrument for controlling inflation and unemployment. *Journal of Economic Policy and Analysis*, 8(4), 33–47.
- Transparency International. (2022). *Corruption perceptions index 2021*. <https://www.transparency.org/en/cpi/2021>
- Ukwu, I. U. (2002). Poverty alleviation in Nigeria. *Bullion*, 26(2), 3–10
- Umo, J. U., Ime, R. A., & Egwaikhide, F. O. (2014). Pro-poor public expenditure and poverty in Nigeria: An analysis using a computable general equilibrium model. *African Development Review*, 26(2), 277–291. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8268.12101>
- Winch, R. (1987). Marxist theories of poverty and the role of education. *Journal of Economic Theory and Practice*, 5(3), 44–55.

REVAMPING TECHNICAL AND VOCATIONAL EDUCATION AND TRAINING (TVET) IN SOUTH-SOUTH, NIGERIA FOR SUSTAINABLE NATIONAL PRODUCTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated ways of revamping Technical and Vocational Education and Training in South-South States of Nigeria for sustainable national productivity. A descriptive survey design guided the study. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. A 27item questionnaire struttred in a 4point rating scale was used to collect data for the study. The instrument was face and content validated by four experts and the reliability coefficient of 0.85 was obtained using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). The population of the study was 217 respondents made up of 172 male TVE educators and 45 female TVE educators in all the Universities in South-South, Nigeria that offer programs in technical educations. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 100 male TVE educators while all the 45 female TVE educators were used in the study without sampling because their population size is considered manageable. Data were analysed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while t-test statistics was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. It was found that provision of adequate modern facilities such as workshops, conducive classrooms and laboratories will revamp technical and vocational education and training for sustainable national productivity in South-South Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others, that government at all levels should as a matter of urgency improve the standard of infrastructural facilities in all the technical training institutions in Nigeria, government and other stakeholders in education should make adequate provision of fund for effective management of technical education programme in Nigeria.

Keywords: revamping, TVET, sustainable, productivity, facilities, curriculum

1.1. Introduction

The social and economic development of any nation majorly depends on the contribution of her citizens. Education is the only means through which individuals can acquire knowledge, skills, attitude and value that will enable them to contribute to sustainable development of any nation (Akpan, 2018). Technical and vocational education and training (TVET) plays a major role at promoting community and national productivity (Oguntuyi cited in Zite and Okwelle, 2017). Technical and vocational education and training is a planned programme of course and learning experience that begins with the exploration of career options, supports basic academic and life skills and enables the achievement of higher academic standard, leadership preparation for industry and continuing education.

Technical and vocational education and training (TVET) as defined by UNESCO cited in

Agwi and Odunze (2023) is a comprehensive term referring to those aspect of educational process involving in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences and the acquisition of practical skills, attitude, understanding and knowledge relating to occupation in various sectors of economic and social life. The neglect of government to technical and vocational education and training in Nigeria according to Akinwumi (2022) in terms of financial support, adequate personnel to teach technical education courses and provision of adequate training facilities for effective TVET programme is robbing Nigerian of some good contributions that graduates of Technical and Vocational Education and Training would have made to the economy of the nation. Ikwuanaso (2023) noted that for effective TVET programme in Nigeria that there is need for adequate provision of training facilities and other consumables. The author further stressed that utilization of educational facilities like internet and web browsing and e-library, available personnel, computer etc by teachers' and students' will enhance academic performance of learners in all our technical training institutions which will in turn lead to sustainable national productivity.

According to Ilo cited in Uzoha (2023) productivity is the efficient use of resources labour capital land material energy information in the production of various goals and service. National productive centre cited in Ewe and Ikoro (2022) defined productivity as a comparison between the amount of output with the amount of input resources used to produce the output at any given period of time. Gharreb cited in Bolaji and Ogbowu (2021) views the concept of productivity as a road to competitive enterprise, the economic development of counties and welfare. The basic concept as highlighted in all the definitions is that productivity is always the relationship between the quantity and quality of goods and services produced and the quality of resources used to produce them. Productivity is the ratio of output to input so productivity is increasingly linked with quality of output, input and the process itself. Increasing national productivity can raise living standards because more real income improves peoples' ability to purchase goods as and services, enjoy leisure, improve housing and education and continue to social and environmental programmes. To achieve the goal of national productivity. Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) programme in Nigeria needed to be given the much urgent attention that it deserves. According to Ekwem and Ibekwe (2020) TVET in Nigeria have been faced with different challenges which has impacted negatively to TVET programme.

Past research works (Oguntuyi, 2015; Ibe, 2017) has identified that lack of fund to manage technical and vocational education and training (TVET) in Nigeria is another major challenge facing TVET programme. According to Madiakolam (2019) adequate financing, provision of adequate training materials and remuneration of vocational and technical teachers which are strategies for improving technical and vocational education and training implementation for sustainable development in Nigeria can only be realized if technical and vocational education and training programme are properly founded by the government at all levels in Nigeria. Okeke (2021) also stated that in Nigeria that most government programmes are not designed to promote TVET. Due to this problem, the level of infrastructural development and facilities provided by the government are seriously affecting to a very large extend the level of skill acquisition in Nigerian higher

institutions of learning that offer programmes in TVET. The high rate of crime and insecurity as witnessed in the country at the past event till present which has resulted to many Nigeria youths to involve their self in kidnapping, prostitution, arm robbery, cyber crime, yahoo and pipe line vandalization has relationship with unemployment and poverty among Nigerian youths. The need for proper review of TVET curriculum was therefore suggested by Utin (2022). According to him assessment and review of TVET curriculum are strategies in making TVET programmes viable and skill oriented in Nigeria.

According to Uwem and Hart (2023) Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) in Nigeria if well planned could play effective role of stimulating social development, economic growth improving conventional education, empowerment of the youths, wealth creation, poverty eradication and skill development. Nigeria at present is faced with recurring incidents of youths' restiveness, TVET programme is well suited to help youths and adults become self-employed and self-dependent, while for others working in the industrial/establishments. Technical and Vocational Education and Training is helpful in the area of skills enhancement (Iheme, 2023). Prpper integration of TVET into the society by educators will enhance sustainable productivity among Nigerian youths. Hamza (2022) suggested that for TVET to help in achieving the goal of sustainable national productivity in Nigeria, that industries operating in Nigeria especially in the oil rich zones of Nigeria should also be involved in organizing programmes in technical and vocational related trades for the youths. Imoge cited in James and Ugwu (2021) stated that training institutions in Nigeria alone should not be left to organize training programmes for the youths. According to these authors adequate training facilities many not be available in all the training institutions in Nigeria, therefore, that there is need for industries to be involved in skill training programmes since these industries are well equipped with machines, tools and equipment that is capable to assist individuals to acquire relevant knowledge and skills that will enable them to be self-reliant. Okeke (2021) stressed that sustainable productivity in Nigeria can only be achieved if the people are exposed to a revamped quality TVET programme that must be well planned and organized by education policy matters and industries in Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Technical and Vocational Education and Training is the hub of the economy of any nation just as the wheel of any moving object rotates around the hub, this is how the economic sector of Nigeria rotates around Technical and Vocational Education considering the scientific and technological development and social-economic development of Nigeria. Unfortunately, studies such as (James and Ugwu, 2021; Iheme, 2023) have shown that the Nigeria government does not seem to give Technical and Vocational Education and Training the much attention that it deserves. This appears to be one of the major reasons for rising rate of crime, unemployment and poverty in the country. The growing problem of unemployment in the country has contributed largely to the worsening problem of kidnapping, armed robbery, internet fraud, yahoo and other social vices as witnessed today in Nigeria. This is because the youth and graduates from tertiary institutions are not properly equipped with adequate skills that will enable them exploit the natural resources that are found in Nigeria. Utin (2022) also identified lack of awareness about TVET at

various levels of school curriculum as another short coming. In his view, in Nigeria it has taken the educationist working for the government more than twenty five years to develop the National Policy and curriculum, yet the general public do not seem to understand the implication of TVET in the development of the economy. It is against this backdrop that this paper is looking at way of revamping TVET in South-South, Nigeria for sustainable national productivity.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate ways of revamping Technical and Vocational Education and Training in South-South States of Nigeria for sustainable national productivity. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine how funding can aid in revamping Technical and Vocational Education and Training programme in South-South, Nigeria.
2. Determine how provision of adequate modern facilities can aid in revamping Technical and Vocational Education and Training programme in South-South, Nigeria.
3. Find out how curriculum can aid in revamping Technical and Vocational Education and Training programme in South-South, Nigeria.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent can funding aid in revamping Technical and Vocational Education and Training programme in South-South Nigeria?
2. To what extent can the provision of adequate modern facilities aid in revamping Technical and Vocational Education and Training programme in South-South, Nigeria?
3. To what extent can curriculum aid in revamping Technical and Vocational Education and Training in South-South, Nigeria?

1.5 Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female TVE educators on the extent funding can aid in revamping Technical and Vocational Education and Training programme in South-South, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female TVE educators on the extend provision of adequate modern facilities can aid in revamping Technical and Vocational Education and Training program in South-South, Nigeria.

3. There is no significance difference in the mean responses of male and female TVE educators on the extend curriculum can aid in revamping Technical and Vocational Education and Training programme in South-South, Nigeria.

2.1 Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. According to Nworgu cited in Ndubuisi (2022) survey research design involves eliciting information from the respondents about their feelings, opinions and views on a phenomena. Descriptive survey research design is suitable for this study since it made us of the questionnaire for collection of data from technical and vocational educators on strategies for revamping TVET in South-South, Nigeria for sustainable national productivity.

The study was carried out in South-South Nigeria, South-South; Nigeria has eight Universities that offer programmes in Technical and Vocational Education. These Universities include; Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Niger Delta University, Amasoma, Bayelsa State, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolemini, Port Harcourt, Delta State University, Abreka, University of Benin, Edo State, University of Uyo, Ambrose Ali University, Ekpoma and Cross River State University of Technology Calabar.

The population of the study was 215 male up of 172 male TVE educators and 45 female TVE educators. Purposive sampling method was used to obtain from the population of the male TVE educators a sample of 100 TVE educators while all the 45 female TVE educators were used in the study without sampling because their population is of management size.

The instrument used for data collection was a- 27 item questionnaire titled “Revamping Technical and Vocational Education and Training for Sustainable National Productivity in South-South Questionnaire” (RTVTSNPQ) which has four points rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) with corresponding values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The instrument was face and content validated by three experts in the department of Vocational and Technology Education, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. The reliability of the instrument was determined through Croubach alpha reliability coefficient method. A total of 15 respondents who were not part of the sample size were used in testing the reliability of the instrument. The reliability coefficient of 0.95 was obtained. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

3.1 Results

The results of the study are presented in Tables 1-6 in line with the research questions and hypotheses.

Research Questions 1: To what extent can funding aid in revamping Technical and Vocational Education and Training Programmes in South-South, Nigeria?

Table 1: Technical and Vocational Educators Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation on the Provision of Fund in Revamping of TVET in South-South, Nigeria.

S/N	ITEM STATEMENTS	Male TVE Educators					
		N = 100	Females TVE Educators	Remark	M	SD	Remark
	N = 45	3.76	0.87	VHE	3.70	0.80	VHE
2.	Motivation of TVET educators by NGOs	3.78	0.84	VHE	3.65	0.79	VHE
3.	Provision of raining allowances for TVET educators	2.58	0.75	HE	2.50	0.70	HE
4.	Provision of starter pack after training in TVET	3.71	0.81	VHE	3.75	0.78	VHE
5.	Credit loan facilities to TVET trainees to practice TVET trades	2.67	0.87	HE	2.50	0.76	HE
6.	Travelling abroad for further training by TVET educators.	2.75	0.88	HE	2.53	0.80	HE
7.	High remuneration for TVET educators	3.65	0.85	VHE	3.50	0.81	VHE
8.	Sponsoring of TVET educators for seminars/ workshops	3.59	0.83	HE	2.50	0.79	HE
9.	Provision of allowance for TVET trainees	3.74	0.84	HE	2.53	0.77	HE
10.	Adequate financing for TVET trades	3.67	0.86	VHE	3.50	0.80	VHE
11.	Motivation of TVET educators by government	3.72	0.82	VHE	3.55	0.88	VHE

Source: File survey, 2025

Table 1 showed that TVET educators rated items 1, 2, 4, 7, and 11 as “Very High Extent” while items 3, 5, 6, 8 and 9 were rated as “High Extent”. The grand mean scores of 3.22 and 3.11 respectively shows that TVET educators considered that provision of adequate fund will aid in revamping TVET programme in South-South, Nigeria. The standard deviation of the items ranged from 0.71 to 0.88 for TVET male and female educators. This signified closeness in the opinions of the respondents.

Research Questions 2: To what extent can the provision of adequate modern facilities aid in revamping Technical and Vocational Education and Training Programme in South-South Nigeria?

Table 2: Technical and Vocational Educators Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation on the Provision of Adequate Modern Facilities in Revamping TVET

S/N	ITEM STATEMENTS	Male TVE Educators			Females TVE Educators		
		N = 100	Females TVE Educators	Remark	M	SD	Remark
N = 45	Availability of consumable materials	2.57	0.75	HE	2.51	0.1	HE
13.	Provision of internet services to TVET constitutions	3.56	0.83	VHE	3.53	0.80	VHE
14.	Rehabilitation of TVET workshops	3./59	0.85	VHE	3.50	0.81	VHE
15.	Availability of personal computer to TVET educators	2.58	0.82	HE	2.51	0.80	HE
16.	Provision of e-library in TVET institutions	2.76	0.79	HE	2.56	0.76	HE
17.	Learning with modern machines	3.71	0.87	VHE	3.53	0.83	VHE
18.	Provision of adequate tools/equipment	3.75	0.89	VHE	3.50	0.85	VHE
19.	Provision of intent services to students	3.55	0.80	VHE	3.51	0.78	VHE
20.	Availability of classroom space	3.64	0.35	VHE	3.52	0.81	VHE

Source: Field survey, 2025

Table 2 showed that TVET educators rated items 13, 14, 17, 18, 19 and 20 as “Very High extent” while items 12, 15, and 16 were rated as “High Extend. The grand mean scores of 3.30 and 3.25 respectively shows that TVET educators considered that adequate provision of modern facilities in all the TVET institution will aid in remaining TVET programmes in South-South, Nigeria. The standard deviation of the items ranged from 0.71 to 0.87 indicates closeness in the opinions of both categories of respondents.

Research Questions 3: To what extent can curriculum aid in revamping Technical and Vocational Education and Training programme in South-South, Nigeria?

Table 3: Technical and Vocational Educators Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation on the Provision of Curriculum in Revamping TVET

S/N	Item Statements	Male TVE Educators			M	SD	Remark
		N = 100	Females TVE Educators	Remark			

N = 45	Ease with curriculum implementation	2.67	0.76	HE	2.50	0.72	HE
22.	Regular review of TVET curriculum	3.58	0.83	VHE	3.50	0.80	VHE
23.	Educators positive attitude towards new curriculum	3.73	0.87	VHE	3.55	0.85	VHE
24.	Presence of experience TVET teachers	3.72	0.85	VHE	3.62	0.81	VHE
25.	Provision of flexible curriculum	3.79	0.88	VHE	3.57	0.84	VHE
26.	Pedagogical skills of TVET teachers	2.65	0.72	HE	2.54	0.74	HE
27.	Assessment of TVET curriculum	3.59	0.84	VHE	3.50	0.79	VHE

Source: Field survey, 2025

The result in Table 3 revealed that TVET educators rated items 22, 23, and 27 as “Very High Extent” while items 21 and 25 were rated as “Higher Extent”. The grand mean scores of 3.40 and 3.25 for both male TVE educators and female TVE educator show that the respondents considered that regular review and assessment of TVET curriculum will aid in revamping TVET in South-South, Nigeria. The standard deviation which ranged between 0.70 to 0.88 indicates closeness in the opinion of both categories of respondents.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female TVE educators on the extent funding can aid in revamping TVET programme in South-South, Nigeria.

Table 4: T-test Analysis of Male and Female TVE Educators on the Extent Funding can aid in Revamping TVET Programmed.

Category	N	X	SD	Df	P	t-cal	T-crit	Decision
Male TVE Educators	100	3.22	0.84	143	0.05	0.04	1.96	Accepted
Female TVE Educators	45	3.11	0.79					

Table 4 showed that 100 male TVE educators had a mean rating of 3.22 (SD=0.84) and the 45 female TVE educators had a mean rating of 3.11 (SD=0.79) yielding a calculated t-value of 0.04. With the calculated t-value of (0.04) less than the critical t-value (1.96) at df=143 and 0.05 level of significance, it is an indication that there is no significance difference in the mean responses of male and female TVE educators on the extent funding can aid in revamping TVET programme in South-South, Nigeria. The first null hypothesis was

therefore accepted.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female TVE educators on the extent provision of adequate modern facilities can aid in revamping Technical and Vocational Education and Training in South-South Nigeria.

Table 5: T-test Analysis of Male and Female TVE Educators on the extent Provision of Adequate Modern Facilities can aid in Revamping TVET programme.

Category	N	X	SD	Df	P	t-cal	T-crit	Decision
Male TVE Educators	100	3.30	0.83	143	0.05	0.02	1.96	Accepted
Female TVE Educators	45	3.25	0.79					

Table 5 showed that 100 male TVE educators had mean rating of 3.30 (SD=0.83) while the 45 female TVE educators had a mean rating of 3.25 (SD = 0.79) yielding a calculated t-value of (0.02). Since the calculated t-values of (0.02) is less than the critical t-value (1.96) at df = 143 and 0.05 level of significance. It is an indication that there is no significance difference in the mean responses of male and female TVE educators on the extent provision of adequate modern facilities can aid in revamping TVET programme in South-South, Nigeria. There second null hypothesis was therefore accepted.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female TVE educators on the extend curriculum can aid in revamping TVET in South-South Nigeria.

Table 5: T-test Analysis of Male and Female TVE Educators on the Extent Curriculum can aid in Revamping TVET in South-South, Nigeria

Category	N	X	SD	Df	P	t-cal	T-crit	Decision
Male TVE Educators	100	3.40	0.82	143	0.05	0.06	1.96	Accepted
Female TVE Educators	45	3.25	0.79					

Table 6 showed that 100 male TVE educators had a mean rating of 3.40 (SD = 0.82) while the 45 female TVE educators has a mean rating of 3.25 (SD=0.79) yielding a calculated t-value (0.06). Since the calculated t-value of (0.06) is less than the critical t-value of (1.96) at df-143 and 0.05 level of significance, implying that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female TVE educators on the extent curriculum can aid in revamping TVET in South-South, Nigeria.

3.2 Findings of the Study

The following are the findings of the study:

1. Adequate funding of TVET programme can help in revamping TVET programme in South-South, Nigeria for sustainable national productivity.

2. Provision of adequate modern facilities in all the technical Training Institutions in Nigeria can help in revamping TVET programme for sustainable national productivity in South-South, Nigeria.
3. Regular review of TVET curriculum can help in revamping TVET programme for sustainable national productivity in South-South, Nigeria.
4. There are no significance difference in the mean responses of male and female TVE educators on the extend provision of adequate modern facilities can aid in revamping TVET programme in South-South, Nigeria.

3.3 Discussion of Findings

Discussion of findings of the study were made according to the research questions and hypotheses.

3.3.1 Extent to which Funding can aid in Revamping TVET Programme in South-South, Nigeria for Sustainable National Productivity.

The result of the study shown in Table 1 revealed that technical and vocational education and training programme in South-South, Nigeria can be revamped for sustainable national productivity through high remuneration of TVE educators, provision of training allowance for TVE educators and regular promotion for TVE educators. These finding is in line with Maduakolam (2019) who fund that adequate findings, provision of adequate training materials and remuneration of TVE educators are strategies for revamping TVET programme for sustainable national productivity. This is also in line with Oguntuyi (2015) who stated that adequate provision of fund by the government at all levels is a good strategy that must be adopted for revamping of TVET programme in Nigeria.

3.3.2 Extent Provision of Adequate Modern Facilities can aid in Revamping TVET Programme in South-South, Nigeria for Sustainable National Productivity.

The result of the study, shown in Table 2 revealed that provision of adequate modern facilities can aid in revamping Technical and Vocational Education and Training programme for sustainable national productivity in South-South, Nigeria through the provision of computers, e-library, rehabilitation of workshop, availability of consumable materials and provision of internet service. These findings are consistent with the observation of Ikwuanaso (2023) that utilization of facilities like e-learning, internet and web browsing, availability of personal computers for teachers and students of TVET enhances learners academic performance in training institutions.

Table 3 revealed that Technical and Vocational Education and Training programme can be revamped in South-South, Nigeria for sustainable national productivity through regular assessment and review of TVET curriculum. The finding of the study is in line with Utin (2022) who stressed that regular assessment and review of Technical and Vocational Education and Training curriculum are major strategies for making TVET programme effective and viable in Nigeria in order to be in line with global standard.

Data analysis in Tables 4, 5 and 6 showed that all the three hypotheses were not rejected. These findings show in the opinions of the respondents that there was no divergent opinion

on the raised issues in this research bothering on strategies to be adopted by stakeholders in education and education policy makers to revamp Technical and Vocational Education and Training in South-South, Nigeria for sustainable national productivity.

4.1 Conclusion

This paper investigated strategies for revamping TVET in South-South, Nigeria for sustainable national productivity. Based on relevant literature that was explored for deeper insight on the potentials of revamping TVET as associated with sustainable national productivity. The general findings from the respondents indicated that TVET could only be revamped in South-South, Nigeria if there is improvement on dilapidated infrastructure in all the institutions of learning, flexible curriculum and appropriate utilization of funds allocated to TVET programme at various levels of education in Nigeria. Revamping of TVET, if seriously pursued would enable speeding diversification of our economy which would enhance the actualization of the Millennium Development Goals (MGDs) and vision 20:20:20 for sustainable national productivity.

4.2 Recommendations

For Technical and Vocational Education and Training to be more impactful on sustainable national productivity and employability, the under-listed recommendations are proposed for implementation by the government, stakeholders in education and policy makers:

1. The standard of infrastructure in all the technical colleges in all the states in South-South, Nigeria should be improved by the ministry of education in order to revamp TVET programme in Nigeria.
2. Federal government through the ministry of education in South-South, Nigeria should ensure that adequate modern workshop facilities are provided in all the technical colleges in order to improve the quality of all vocational and technical education programme.
3. Government should provide adequate fund for Technical and Vocational Education and training in their annual budget for TVET programme for smooth management of TVET programme in Nigeria
4. There is an urgent need for constant review and assessment of TVET curriculum as to ensure viable TVET delivery due to the growth in the number of formal and informal vocational and technical education institutions in Nigeria.

REFERENCES

- Akinwumi, A.E. (2022). Challenges of Technical Education Students' in Technical Colleges on Oudo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Technical Education*. 26(1), 15-30.
- Agwi, V.I.A & Odunze, C.E. (2023). Global Trend and Challenges in Technical and Vocational Education and Training: The Nigeria perspective. *Journal of education in Developing Areas*. 10(1), 60-75.

- Akpan, U.K. (2018). Technical and Vocational Education and Training: A Useful Means of Acquiring Skills for Self-Reliance. *Journal of Education in Developing Areas*. 5 (1), 10-15.
- Bolaji, C.T. & Ogburu, E.A. (2021). Achieving Sustainable National Development Goal in Nigeria Through Technical and Vocational Education Programme: Challenges and the way Forward. *Journal of Academic Excellence*. 5(1), 100-115.
- Ekwem, C.O. & Ibekwe. N.E. (2020). Challenges of Technical and Vocational Education and Training in Nigeria: The way Forward. *International Journal of Research in Education*. 16(1), 30-45.
- Ewe, S.E. & Ikoro, B.U. (2022). The role of Technical and Vocational Education and Training in Achieving Sustainable National Productivity Goals in Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Technology*. 12(1), 20-35.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (21013). National Policy on Education (Revised 6th Edition). Lagos: Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC).
- Hamza, A.A. (2022). Viable Technical and Vocational Education and Training as a useful Means of Employment Generation for the Nigerian Youths. Retrieved 15th May, 2024 from <http://www.edu.journal.org>.
- Ikwuanaso, B.E. (2023). Impact of Instructional Facilities on Technical Education Students Learning Achievement in Anambra State. *Journal of Education in Developing Areas*. 22(1), 100-115.
- Ibe, M.E. (2017). The Place of Vocational and Technical Education in skill Acquisition Among Secondary School Students: Implication for Counseling. *Journal of Historical Sciences in Education*. 18(1), 1-5.
- Iheme, M.O. (2023). A Viable Vocational and Technical Education Curriculum: A tool for Sustainable National Development in Nigeria. *Scholarly Journal of Education*. 14(1), 25-40.
- James, N.E. & Ugfwu, B.O. (2021). Assessing the Realities and Challenges of Technical and Vocational Education and Training in Amambra State Secondary School Education System. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*. 16(1), 95-115.
- Maduakolam, E.U. (2014). Technical and Vocational Education in Nigeria: Issues, Challenges and way Forward. Retrieved 18th March, 2024 from <http://www.edu.research.online.ink>.
- Ndubuisi, A.M. (2023). Assessment of Vocational Teachers uses of Information and Communication Technology in Technical Colleges in Imo State. *Journal of Vocational and Technical Education*. 8(1), 80-95.

- Okon, L.M. (2018). Technical and Vocational Education Programme in Nigeria: A useful mean of Acquiring Skills for Self-Reliance. *Journal of Education in Developing Areas*. 24(1), 30-45.
- Oguntiyi, A.O. (2015). Attitude of Private Sectors in Funding Technical and Vocational Education in Lagos State. *Journal of Education and Evaluation*. 10(10), 30-45.
- Okeke, I.A. (2021). Funding needs of Technical and Vocational Education Programmes in Nigeria: Issues and way forward. Retrieves 16th April, 2024 from <http://www.edu.journal.org>.
- Uwem, J.O. & Hart, A.A. (2023). Strategies for Enhancing Quality Skill Training in Technical and Vocational Education Programmes in Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Research*. 18(1). 150-165.
- Utin B.A. (2022). Strengthening Technical and Vocational Education for Sustainable National Development in Akwa-Ibom State, Nigeria. *Journal of Technical Education*. 12(1), 10-15.
- Uzoha, A.E. (2023). The Place of Technical and Vocational Education and Training in Achieving Sustainable National Productivity in Nigeria. Retrieves 5th May, 2024 from <http://www.edu.org>.
- Zite, B.N. & Okwelle, P.C. (2017). Improving the Quality of Technical and Vocational Education and Training in Niger Delta form Sustainable Development. *International Journals of Humanities and Social Science and Education*. 5(3), 1-15

TAX REVENUE AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA: A DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS

By

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the nexus between tax revenue and economic growth using a descriptive approach. Specifically, the study emphasizes the effects of tax revenue on economic growth in the country. Findings from descriptive analysis reveals that despite the policy prescriptions in the period covered, economic growth is tremendously affected by tax revenue performance in Nigeria, in particular, the volume of tax generated over a period had a significant relationship with economic growth. The study recommends that efforts should be intensified by the government towards increased collection of tax revenue as this can be achieved through blocking all loopholes in our tax laws as well as bringing more prospective tax payers into the tax net (especially the informal sector).

Keywords: Tax Revenue, Economic Growth, Descriptive Approach, Nigeria

1. Introduction

It has become imperative globally, that governments at various levels deploy diverse measures to generate funds needed to provide certain infrastructural and basic social amenities that will meet the demands of her citizenry. Needless to say, the quality of available infrastructure in identified economies and the established law and order sometimes depict government's commitment to economic development. This is the more reason the provision of basic infrastructures to the citizenry of any country has become one fundamental task of governments at all levels. As a result, efforts of governments have been geared towards generating revenue in a bid to execute such tasks as infrastructural development, provision of social goods and services, maintenance of law and order amongst others. Experts and extant studies have maintained that taxation is essentially crucial as a means through which governments generate the needed revenue to meet her financial demands and execute other functions (Azubike, 2009; Edame, 2011).

Romer (1986) accentuates factors such as 'spill-over effect and learning by doing' by which firms' take certain decisions to invest in capital and research and development, or investment in human capital, can yield positive external effects that benefit the rest of the economy. A Solow (1956) pioneer effort on taxation and growth concludes that taxation affects growth. He make a bold argument that steady-state growth is not affected by tax policy, in that, tax policy, regardless of distortions, has no impact on long term economic growth rates, even if it reduces the level of economic output in the long term. Romer

(1986), pointed out an existence of a structural difference in taxation in developing and developed countries. For developing countries, it is established that roughly two-thirds of tax revenue is derived from indirect taxes while for developed countries two-thirds comes from direct taxes. He suggested however, that tax structure can change over time to maximize the economic growth.

Taxes impact economic growth whether positively or negatively. According to Bofah (2003), taxes refer to the revenue that is collected by the government to provide services and finance itself. According to the theory of tax competition, the government will reduce the taxes on mobile asset through the occurrence of globalization due to rise in economic growth in a country. Change in tax rate also will give the different impact to an open economy. Bretschger (2010), found a negative impacts of corporate taxes on openness and total tax revenue to the economic growth in 12 OECD countries. He also haps on the tax competition theory that argues that, when tax rate of capital is reduced, it will cause the capital inflow to a country. This is because; the tax rate is one of the costs for capital holder (Bucovetsky, 1991). These two researchers discovered that private return on investment is influenced by the changes in capital taxes.

However, enforceability of tax and compliance in terms of payments has been a phenomenon of global significance as it affects every economy irrespective of national differences (Oboh and Isa, 2012). Tax payment is markedly different from direct exchange of good and/or services but a transfer of resources and income from the private sector to the public sector in order to actualize some of the nation's economic and social goals (Okpe, 2000). Such goals center on attainment of macroeconomic objectives such as full employment, stable prices, rapid growth of gross national product, favourable balance of payments position, promotion of a free market economy, satisfaction of collective demands, equitable income redistribution, promotion of infant industries, the encouragement of priority sector, encouragement of balance population development and promotion of labour and capital development (Onoh, 2013).

It is a known fact, that majority of developing economies have over time experienced an ever-increasing trend in debt crises, persistent fiscal deficit financing amidst dwindling macro-economic indicators. This unwholesome development has compelled governments to formulate different adjustments and/or stabilization policies to boost economic activities and sustain financial stability, growth and development (Kiabel and Nwokah, 2009; Wambi and Hanga, 2013). Besides, with the fluctuating oil prices, countries like Nigeria whose income have been dominated by oil revenue in the past is currently considering diversification and how to look inward with a view to develop other sources of revenue that will support her quest to provide infrastructure, social amenities and the required atmosphere that will boost economic development. Therefore, since prior studies had posited that tax is a copious means through which governments could generate sufficient revenue to meet up with her ever-increasing financial demands, this study thus examined the association between the tax revenue and the economic growth. In this regard, we focused on an examination of the relationship between tax revenue and Nigeria's real Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: section two is the review of relevant literature and the gaps the study intends to fill. Section three is the theoretical framework of the study, section four dwells on the descriptive analysis and interpretation of tax revenue and GDP while section five and six give the conclusion and recommendations.

2. Review of Related Literature

There are clear arguments both for and against a higher tax ratio leading to higher GDP growth. On the one hand, higher taxes distort the incentives for individuals to supply more labour or for firms to produce more. On the other, higher taxes provide governments with the potential to invest in, for example, infrastructural improvements, education or R&D, all of which can increase the economy's productive capacity.

Many studies argue the relationship between tax policy and economic growth and how it could affect each other. Chigbu, Akujuobi, and Appah (2012) studied the relationship between tax revenue and economic growth in Nigeria. The findings of the study showed interesting and a well-established relationship. Muibi and Sinbo, (2013) examined the level of economic growth that has impacted positively on tax revenue in Nigeria. The study concludes that macroeconomic instability and degree of economic activities are the main drivers of tax buoyancy and tax effort in Nigeria. The paper further stressed that taxation is an important instrument to improve economic growth. Canicio and Zachary (2014) showed that there is interdependence between economic growth and government tax revenues. The study finds that 30% speedier relationship of adjustment in the short run towards equilibrium level in the long run.

Brender and Navon (2010) conducted a study to test the relation of the GDP with tax revenues. The paper examined the level of uncertainty in predicting the tax revenue in Israel. The study found that the long-run tax-revenue and GDP are elastic in the case of Israel. Further, Hakim and Bujang (2012) provided that the statistical evidence suggests that the total tax revenue to GDP ratio is higher in the high-income countries compared to low- and middle-income countries. Besides, (Mashkoor, Yayha and Alli, 2010) show that saving causes the real GDP growth unidirectional and the direct tax to GDP ratio granger causes the real GDP growth significantly.

Furthermore, expenditure of the Government and tax revenues has been tested by many studies. Hafiz (2006) reveals those tax revenues that are very important to underscore the general budget to cover public expenditures (Miswadeh and Al-Mofleh, 2015). Taxes have largely been considered the main motive to control the economic activities. Hussien, (2005), Nanthakumaret, Kogid, Sakami, and Muhamad, (2011); Taha and Loganathan., (2008) found a causality between government expenditure and tax revenues in their testing models. (Zortuk and Uzgoren, 2008) studied the causality and long-run relationship between the government spending and tax revenues in oil exporting countries during 2000-2009 period. The study finds that the short-run and long-run government spending has a positive impact on taxation. Another study finds bidirectional causality between taxes and expenditures in five of G7 countries (Owoye, 1994). However, Mehrar and Rezaei, (2014) found unidirectional causality running from government revenues to government expenditure.

Akhor and Ekundayo (2016) undertook a study aimed at finding a link between revenue from indirect taxes and economic growth in Nigeria. The study centered on value added tax and custom and excise duty as the explanatory variables while real gross domestic product was adopted as the dependent variable. The study covered a 20-year period (1993 – 2013) and relied on secondary data which were collected from the statistical bulletins of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) over the study. Analysis of data was based on descriptive and inferential statistics which included correlation analysis, co-integration test and the regression analysis via the Error Correction Model (ECM). The study found that revenue from value added tax and customs and excise duties had negative effect economic development. Specifically, it was observed that the relationship between VAT and economic development, though negative, was significant, whereas, the relationship between customs and excise duties was weak.

Obayori and Omekwe (2019) analysed the relationship between value added tax, excise duty and economic growth between 1994 and 2018. The results of ARDL showed that both value added tax and excise duty are positively related to economic growth. Ordu, and Nkwoji, (2019) studied how education tax impacts on Nigerian economy from 2006 to 2017. The results of regression and thematic analysis revealed that education tax (EDTX) substantially and positively impacts on Nigerian economy. In Nigeria, Kareem, Arije and Avovome (2020) empirically determined the influence of value added tax on economic growth. With the use of Bound test cointegration, results showed that value added tax (VATX) strongly and positively impacts on economic growth. It was also revealed by causality test that value added tax and economic growth are associated. However, Yadawananda and Achal (2020) studied the nexus between tax revenue and economic growth in India between 1991 and 2016. The results of panel data analysis showed that capital transaction tax and property tax are positively and significantly related to economic performance. Meanwhile, findings revealed that commodity tax and income tax have negative impact on economic performance in Indian.

Moreover, Oladele (2021) conducted a study to examine how tax compliance and economic development are related. The results of the analysis revealed that tax compliance is positively and significantly associated with economic development during the period of the study. Uche and Ugonabo (2021) investigated value added tax and economic development between 1994 and 2018. Results of Pearson correlation and regression analysis indicated that economic development is positively and significantly influenced by value added tax in Nigeria. Timah and Chukwu (2021) examined the impact of company income tax on employees' wages, dividend, and corporate social responsibility in Nigeria. It was found that company income tax (CITX) has a substantial relationship with employees' wages, dividend payment and corporate social responsibility activities. Egiyi (2021) studied the statistical relationship between company income tax and economic development. The results of the study revealed that company income tax and economic development are related in the long-run and short-run.

2.1 Theoretical Framework

This research study is anchored on the benefits received theory of taxation (BRTT). This novel theory is believed to have been pioneered by Knut Wicksell and further advanced

by Erik Lindahl (Trotman Dickenson, 1996). Proponents of the theory argue that an exchange relationship exist between the government of a people and the tax payers. On the basis of this relationship therefore, the government has a primary responsibility of providing goods, services and basic infrastructures for use by members of the society, while the populace in return are expected to make contributions through taxation in a commensurate manner to whatever benefits that may have been derived from their access to the amenities provided by government (Trotman Dickenson, 1996; Ihenyen and Mieseigha, 2014). Impliedly, a contractual relationship tends to exist between the government of a people and the taxpayers; as such, the government is obligated to provide public goods and/or services; whereas, the responsibility to bear the costs associated with the provision of such public goods and services rest on the taxpayers in proportion to the level of benefits received (Chigbu, Akujuobi, and Appah, 2012). Clearly, the assumption of the BRTT is that citizens of a state or country should be taxed proportionate to the consumption of social goods and/or the services rendered by government. Since tax revenue of every government ought to be ploughed back to provide basic infrastructures and social amenities for sustainable economy development, the researcher is of the view that the BRTT is suitable for this study. It is on this note that the work was anchored on the BRTT as we set out to examine the intricate link between the revenue generated from the different forms of taxation in the country and economic development.

3.Descriptive Analysis and Discussion

3.1Growth Rate Dynamics in Nigeria

The Nigerian economy grew by 3.46% in the last quarter of 2023. This performance was not unexpected, considering that last quarters are characteristically associated with seasonal booms from increased consumer spending. However, despite this quarterly uptick, the economy's annual growth further decelerated to 2.74%. This marks the second consecutive year of growth deceleration following the impressive rebound of 3.40% recorded in 2021. The stellar recovery of 2021 was largely due to the stimulation of the economy in response to the pandemic-induced downturn (-1.92%) in 2020. The hypothesis of a normalisation mechanism gradually driving growth to pre-pandemic levels holds sway. However, the growth deceleration recorded in 2023 significantly mirrored the impact of the twin policies of fuel subsidy removal and exchange rate reforms. These reforms became major pressure points, with the national average fuel pump price surging by 225% year-on-year in December 2023. Additionally, the Naira depreciated by over 90% between June and December 2023 in response to these policies. Consequently, the higher energy and transport costs, along with elevated import prices, strained consumer wallets and squeezed business margins. This dampened aggregate spending and weighed significantly on economic activities, contributing to the lower growth of 2.74% recorded in 2023.

Figure 1: GDP Growth Rate (%)

Source: Authors Computation

3.2 Total Resource Revenue from Taxes

Nigeria did not consider taxation as a sustainable source of revenue, during the 1970s and late 80s as a lot of attention was focused on oil revenue. During this period, all the States in the country relied seriously on proceeds from the Federation Account. In 2014 at the turn of the global recession which saw a sharp fall in oil prices and by extension reduced proceeds from the Federation accounts, the overdependence on income from oil created a discrepancy in the implementation of some of the fiscal policies. Governments (Federal, State, and Local) began to look inwards focusing on Internally Generated Revenue (IGR) as a sustainable means of funding as bankruptcy loomed among the States. The revenue accruing to the federal Government of Nigeria from oil over the years has remained grossly insufficient to meet the growing social and public spending required in fostering economic growth and development in the country. Nigeria employed taxation as an alternative to source for revenue when the crude oil crashed in world market. If government intends to increase money in circulation, taxation will be reduced in order to enhance the purchasing power of both individual and private sectors. On the other hand, if government determines to cut down money in circulation, taxation policies will be cleverly and clandestinely designed and enacted to suit the purpose of taxation increment which invariably increases revenue generation of the government.

The resource revenue that accrued to the government between 1992 and 1993 was high. It stood at 20.16% and 16.43% respectively. There was a downturn from 1994 to 1998 when 9.74% was recorded in 1994, 8.17% in 1995, 8.14% in 1996, 7.94% in 1997 and 7.01% in 1998. Consistent low tax revenue inflow is characterized by government negligence, tax evasion, avoidance, record falsifications, gross inefficiency and leakages. These have hampered the amount of revenue to be realized from tax sources over the years. The incidence of tax evasion and avoidance by tax payers is high, leading to low level of government revenue which further reduces the level of government expenditure, culminating into a reduction in the income savings and expenditure of households and firms, leading to low level of economic activities and economic growth (Cornelius, Ogar

& Oka 2016). There is an upsurge in the tax revenue again starting from 1999 to 2008. The tax revenue increased to 24.23% in 2000, 21.67% in 2001, 21.37% in 2005 and 16.69% in 2008. The tax revenue nosedive again in 2016 and 2018 before it peaked again at 4.42% in 2019 and 2022.

Figure 2: Total Resource Revenue

Source: Authors Computation

3.3. The nexus between Total Resource Revenue and Economic Growth

In 1993, the total resource revenue was astronomically high at 16.43%, this feeds into the economic growth at 4.60%. When there was a fall in the resource revenue between 1994 and 1996, the growth rate was negative as depicted in figure 3. Between 1999 and 2001, there was an upsurge in total resource revenue again while the growth rate also increased tremendously to 5% within this period. There is a fluctuation in total resource revenue between 2003 and 2008 and this is followed by steady rise and fall in the growth rate altogether. The research discovered among others that, taxation has a significant contribution on revenue generation, taxation has a significant contribution on Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and tax evasion and tax avoidance have a significant effect on revenue generation in Nigeria.

Figure 3: Total Resource Revenue and GDP

Source: Authors Computation

4. Conclusion

Tax is one of the veritable means of generating revenue by government all over the world. It provides ample opportunity for the Government to finance and execute crucial infrastructural projects that will accelerate growth and development when funds are readily available. Findings from the study revealed that there is a relationship between taxation and economic growth in Nigeria. The focus should be on how tax laws and policies will be tinkered, reviewed and updated in line with prevailing realities, faithfully implemented and revenue realized are judiciously and transparently utilized on basic infrastructural that can stimulate economic activities in the country then Nigeria will be a better Nation.

5. Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Government should intensify efforts towards increased collection of tax revenue This can be done by fixing all loopholes in our tax laws as well as bringing more prospective tax payers into the tax net (especially the informal sector).
- ii. There should e provision to institutionalized and entrenched penalties on any individual or corporate body who indulges in any form of tax malpractices irrespective of status or political clout, if the positive correlation between tax revenue and economic growth should be maintained.
- iii. Federal Inland Revenue Service should be mandated to create an effective, efficient, flexible and reliable data base for companies to minimize (if not eradicate) the incidence of tax evasion and there should be constant training and re-training of Company Tax administrators through seminars, conference and workshops to

- keep them abreast of the developments and trend in tax administration.
- iv. The fund realized should be effectively geared towards provision of infrastructural facilities for tax payers. This will undoubtedly motivate and encourage the citizenry to pay more. Staff that work with the Tax Authorities should be adequately motivated in order to enhance revenue generation and improve the percentage of tax revenue to GDP.
 - v. There should be periodic review of existing tax laws as obtainable in the advanced economies, so as to keep the act in pace with the economic reality.

REFERENCES

- Azubike, J. U. B. (2009). Challenges of tax authorities, tax payers in the management of tax reform processes. *Nigerian Accountant*, 42 (2): 36 – 42.
- Bofah.K.(2003). The impact of tax on investment and business decisions, retrieved from:
- Brendert, A & Navon, G. (2012)The Impact and Consequences of Tax Revenues' Componentson
- Economic Indicators: Evidence from Panel Groups Data. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics* 63:99-116
- Bretschger, L. (2010). "Sustainability economics, resource efficiency, and the Green New Deal," *International Economics and Economic Policy*, 7(2), 187-202.
- Bucovetsky, S. (1991) Asymmetric tax competition. *Journal of Urban Economics*, 30, (2), 167 - 181.
- Chigbu,E.E. Akujuobi, L. E &Appah, E. (2012).An Empirical Study on the Causality between Economic Growth and Taxation in Nigeria. *Current Research Journal of Economic Theory*, (2): 29-38.
- Chigbu. E.E, Akujuobi , L. E. and Appah, E. (2012). An empirical study on the causality between economic growth and taxation in Nigeria. *Current Research Journal of Economic Theory* 4(2), 29-38.
- Cornelius M.O ,Ogar A. & Oka F.A. (2016). The Impact of Tax Revenue on Economic Growth: Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Finance*, 07(01): 32-38
- Edame, E. (2011). *The Essential of public finance and Public financial management in Nigeria*. (3rd Revised Ed.) Calabar: Wusen Press Ltd.

- Egiyi, M. A. (2021). Company income tax and economic development nexus: ARDL approach. *Contemporary Journal of Management*, 3 (8), 19-27
- Hakim, T. A., & Bujang, I. (2012). The Impact and Consequences of Tax Revenues' Components on Economic Indicators: Evidence from Panel Groups Data. INTECH Open Access Publisher. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/48415>
- Hussien, M. H. (2005). On the Causal Relationship between Government Expenditure and Tax Revenue in Pakistan. *The Lahore Journal of Economics*, 9 (2), 105-117.
- Ihenyen, C.J. and Mieseigha, E.G. (2014). Taxation as an instrument of economic growth: The Nigerian perspective. *Information and Knowledge Management*, 4(12), 49-53
- Kareem, R. O., Arije, R. A. & Avovome, Y. H. (2020). Value added tax and economic growth in Nigeria (1994 – 2017). *Izvestiya Journal of Varna University of Economics*, 64 (2), 137-152
- Kiabel, B.D. and Nwokah, N.G. (2009). Boosting revenue generation by state governments in Nigeria: The tax consultants option revisited. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(4): 532–539.
- Macek, R. (2014). The impact of taxation on economic growth: Case study of OECD Countries, *Review of Economic Perspectives*, 14(4), 309 – 328
- Mashkoo, M., Yahya, S., & Ali, S. A. (2010). Tax revenue and economic growth: An empirical analysis for Pakistan. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 10(11), 1283-1289.
- Meharar, M., & Rezaei, A.A. (2014). The relationship between government revenue and government expenditure in Iran. *International Journal of Academic research in Business and Social Sciences*, 4(3), 23-31
- Miswadeh, S. N., & Al-Mofleh, K. M. M. (2015). The role of tax revenue in supplying General Budget with public revenues - a comparative study in the period between (2006-2013). *IUG Journal of Economics and Business*, 23(2), 141-171
- Muibi, O.S. & Sinbo, O.O. (2013) Macroeconomic determinant of tax revenue in Nigeria (1970-2011). *World Applied Science Journal*, 28, 27-35
- Nanthakumar, L., Kogid, M., Sakami, M. N., & Muhamad, S. (2011). Tax Revenue and Government Spending Constraints: Empirical Evidence from Malaysia. *China USA Business Review*, 10 (9), 779-784
- Obayori, J. B. & Omekwe, S. O. P. (2019). Indirect tax and economic growth in Nigeria: The case of VAT. *International Journal of Science and Management Studies (IJSMS)*,

- 2 (6), 61-66
- Oboh, C. S., & Isa E. F. (2012). An empirical investment of multiple tax practices and taxpayer's compliance in Nigeria. Unpublished research work. Okpe, I. I. (2000). Personal income tax in Nigeria. Enugu: Ochumba Printing and Oladele, R. (2021). Impact of tax compliance on standard of living in Nigeria. *The Journal of Accounting and Management*. 11(1), 237-250.
- Onoh, J. K. (2013). Dimensions of nigerian monetary and fiscal policies- Domestic and external. Aba: Astria Meridian Publishers.
- Ordu, P. A. & Nkwoji, N. O. (2019). Impact of education tax on economic development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Development and Policy Studies*, 7(3), 1-17.
- Owoye, O. (1994). The causal relationship between taxes and expenditures in the G7 countries: Cointegration and error-correction models. *Applied Economics Letters*, 2, 19 22.<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/135048595357744>
- Romer, P. (1886). "Increasing returns and long-run growth." *Journal of Political Economy*, Vol. 94, No. 5, pp. 1002-1037.
- Taha, R., & Loganathan, N. (2008). Causality between tax revenue and government spending in Malaysia. *The International Journal of Business and Finance Research*, 7 (2).
- Timah, B. P. & Chukwu, G. J. (2021). Corporate taxation and stakeholders' welfare of selected manufacturing companies in Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 11(2), 13–26.
- Trotman-Dickenson D.I. (1996) *The Theory of Taxation and the Tax System*. In: *Economics of the Public Sector*. Palgrave, London
- Uche, E.P. & Ugonabo, C.U. (2021). The effect of value added tax on economic development in Nigeria (1994- 2018). *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 26 (5), 21-30.
- Wambai, U.S. K and Hanga, B.Y. (2013). Taxation and societal development in Nigeria: Tackling Kano's hidden economy. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Science*, 3(3), 113 125.
- Yadawananda, N. & Achal, K.G. (2020). Tax structure and economic growth: a study of selected Indian states. *Journal of Economic Structure*, 9 (38), 1-12.

THE ROLE OF HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT IN ECONOMIC DIVERSIFICATION: EVIDENCE FROM THE DEVELOPED RESOURCE-DEPENDENT COUNTRIES, A CHALLENGE FOR NIGERIA

By

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ABSTRACT

Resource-dependent countries face the persistent challenge of overreliance on extractive industries, which makes their economies vulnerable to external shocks and commodity price fluctuations. This paper examines the role of human capital development in economic diversification, with a particular focus on Nigeria's ongoing efforts to reduce its dependence on oil revenues. It draws evidence from the experiences of successful resource-dependent countries of the world such as the United Arab Emirates (UAE), and Norway that have diversified their economies through strategic investments in human capital, education, and vocational training. The study highlights the importance of fostering a skilled workforce, enhancing institutional capacity, and building strong public-private partnerships (PPPs) in the diversification process. Additionally, the paper explores the potential of leveraging diaspora talent and embracing digital transformation as tools for economic growth. It also examines the challenges faced by Nigeria, including weak institutional frameworks, inadequate infrastructure, corruption, and policy implementation gaps. Drawing on theoretical insights from Human Capital Theory and Endogenous Growth Theory, with an overview of developed resource-dependent countries such as the United Arab Emirates (UAE), Norway, Canada, Australia, and Chile that have successfully diversified their economies, recommendations are offered for enhancing policy coherence, prioritizing education and vocational training, and optimizing public-private collaborations. By exploring these issues, the paper contributes to a better understanding of the dynamics of economic diversification in resource-rich economies and provides practical insights for Nigeria's development trajectory.

Keywords: Economic-diversification, Resource-dependence, Structural-transformation, Digital-transformation, Sustainable-development

Introduction

Economic diversification has become a critical pathway for sustainable development in resource-dependent countries. Nations overly reliant on a single commodity, especially crude oil, often experience volatility in revenue, limited employment opportunities, and structural weaknesses in their economies (Auty, 2021). In this context, human capital development—encompassing investments in education, health, and skills acquisition—emerges as a fundamental pillar for building a resilient and diversified economic structure. Countries like the United Arab Emirates (UAE) and Norway have demonstrated how strategic investments in human capital can foster innovation, expand the productive base of the economy, and reduce dependence on natural resources (Gelb, 2020; World Bank,

2020). These examples illustrate the transformative power of human capital development in achieving long-term economic goals.

Conversely, Nigeria remains heavily dependent on oil revenues, which constitute over 80% of export earnings and about 50% of government revenue (National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), 2022). Despite its large population and abundant human resources, the country continues to face challenges such as poor education infrastructure, high unemployment, and low investment in health and skills training. This human capital deficiency hinders the country's capacity to diversify its economy effectively and sustainably (Olayemi, 2019). This paper explores the role of human capital development in economic diversification by analyzing the experiences of the UAE and Norway and juxtaposing them with the challenges facing Nigeria. It seeks to highlight how targeted investments in education, health, and vocational skills have enabled the United Arab Emirates (UAE), Norway, Canada, Australia, and Chile to diversify successfully and what Nigeria can learn from these experiences. The study is significant in providing comparative insights that may inform evidence-based policy interventions in Nigeria's quest for economic resilience and inclusive growth.

2 An Overview of Successful Diversified Resource-Dependent Economies

This section highlights five developed natural resource-rich countries—the United Arab Emirates, Norway, Canada, Australia, and Chile—that have successfully diversified their economies beyond the natural mineral resources extraction. Experience from monetary economy has shown that resource dependence often exposes countries to commodity price volatility and the risks of the “resource curse.” However, some resource-rich nations have managed to avoid these pitfalls by pursuing strategic economic diversification.

The United Arab Emirates (UAE), a country endowed with vast oil and gas reserves, embarked on a strategic diversification agenda under the Vision 2021 and later Vision 2030 frameworks. These plans focused on transforming the UAE into a knowledge-based economy by investing in tourism, aviation, logistics, financial services, and technology (Kwak & Kim, 2021). On the other hand, Norway has effectively mitigated the “resource curse” by channeling its oil wealth into a sovereign wealth fund—the Government Pension Fund Global—valued at over \$1.4 trillion (Norwegian Ministry of Petroleum and Energy, 2020). In addition, Canada is rich in oil, minerals, and forestry resources, yet it has diversified into advanced manufacturing, information technology, and financial services. Its decentralized political structure allows provinces like Ontario and British Columbia to cultivate technology-driven economies independent of the resource-rich Alberta (Bosworth & Collins, 2023). A highly educated workforce, strong institutions, and trade agreements like USMCA have further facilitated Canada's economic diversification.

On the other hand, Australia's economy is known for its rich mineral and agricultural resources, yet it has achieved diversification through substantial investments in education, tourism, health services, and advanced manufacturing. Australia's universities attract global talent, and cities like Melbourne and Sydney have emerged as innovation hubs (World Economic Forum, 2017). This diversification has helped cushion the country against commodity price shocks.

Chile is one of the largest copper exporters in the world, yet it has made efforts to reduce its dependence on mining by expanding sectors such as agriculture (particularly fruit and wine exports), aquaculture, and services (Ledgerman & Maloney, 2022). The establishment of the Economic and Social Stabilization Fund (ESSF) helped Chile manage revenue volatility and invest in long-term development. These countries have demonstrated that with visionary leadership, strategic investment in human capital development, and effective institutions, resource-dependent nations can overcome the challenges of the “resource curse” and foster sustainable, diversified economies, a lesson that Nigeria must take home if it must achieve economic prosperity

3 Literature Review

3.1 Human Capital Development

Human capital development refers to the extraction of the stock of knowledge, skills, competencies, and health attributes embodied in individuals that enable them to contribute productively to economic activities, and it is achieved through investment in education, skills acquisition, research and development (School, 2021; OECD, 2021; Ekeamadi, 2023). As a concept, human capital development gained prominence in the 20th century as economists began to recognize that the quality of labour, not just its quantity, plays a significant role in economic development. Becker (2024) defined human capital as the set of skills and knowledge acquired by people through education and experience, which has a measurable economic value. According to Becker, investing in human capital is akin to investing in physical capital, as it yields future returns in the form of increased productivity, innovation, and income.

According to World Bank, (2019), countries that score high on the human capital index typically have robust systems for education, healthcare, and skill development—factors that support a dynamic and diversified economy. Therefore, the importance of human capital development becomes more critical in resource-rich but economically vulnerable countries, where overdependence on primary commodities like oil often hampers the development of other sectors.

In such contexts, building human capital development is a strategic approach to overcoming structural rigidities, fostering innovation, and enabling labour mobility into diverse sectors such as manufacturing, services, and the digital economy (Barro, 2023; Hanushek & Woessmann, 2020).

3.2 Economic Diversification

Economic diversification refers to the process through which an economy broadens its production and revenue base across various sectors to reduce dependence on a limited number of resources or industries (Gelb, 2020). Diversification enhances macroeconomic stability, creates jobs, improves fiscal sustainability, and promotes inclusive growth (Imo & Wogu, 2023). According to Ekeamadi (2022), there are two primary forms of economic diversification:

- horizontal diversification, which involves expanding into new industries and services beyond the dominant sector, and

- Vertical diversification, which pertains to deepening activities within a value chain—for instance, from crude oil extraction to refining and petrochemical production (Hadizah, 2023). Effective economic diversification requires not only favorable policies but also enabling institutions, infrastructure, human capital, and technological capabilities.

The need for diversification is urgent in countries facing the “resource curse” phenomenon, like Nigeria, where wealth from natural resources paradoxically undermines long-term development by displacing productive sectors like agriculture and manufacturing (Somchi & Wogu 2023). In contrast, successful diversification, as seen in countries like the UAE and Norway, has led to the growth of non-oil sectors such as tourism, finance, real estate, fisheries, and green technologies.

The UAE’s Vision 2021 and Centennial 2071 strategic plans underscore diversification as a national priority, supported by reforms in education and labour markets (Oxford Business Group, 2022). Similarly, Norway’s economic model integrates oil wealth management with education, innovation, and strong public institutions to promote sustainable diversification (Holden, 2023).

3.3 Resource Dependence and the "Dutch Disease"

Ekeamadi (2020) has explained resource dependence as a situation where a country’s economy relies disproportionately on the extraction and export of natural resources, such as oil, gas, or minerals. While resource wealth can generate significant revenues, it often leads to macroeconomic and institutional distortions collectively referred to as the “Dutch disease” (Corden & Neary, 2022). The term originated from the Netherlands’ experience in the 1960s after the discovery of natural gas led to currency appreciation and a decline in manufacturing exports due to reduced competitiveness.

The Dutch disease manifests when a booming resource sector leads to a rise in real exchange rates, making non-resource sectors—particularly manufacturing and agriculture—less competitive internationally. This structural imbalance reduces the diversification potential of the economy and increases vulnerability to commodity price shocks (Torvik, 2019). It can also lead to deindustrialization, low productivity growth, and heightened unemployment in non-resource sectors. In resource-dependent countries with weak institutions and governance, the Dutch disease exacerbates rent-seeking behaviour, corruption, and policy inconsistency (Mogaji, Muda, & Tofa, 2016). Nigeria exemplifies these challenges, where decades of reliance on oil revenues have undermined other sectors and discouraged long-term investments in human capital development and infrastructure (Salami & Suleiman, 2023).

3.4 Global Perspectives on Human Capital Development and Economic Diversification

In the contemporary global economy, human capital development and economic diversification are two interrelated strategies that nations adopt to ensure long-term economic growth, resilience, and sustainability. Human capital—defined as the stock of knowledge, skills, health, and values embodied in individuals (Becker, 2024)—is widely acknowledged as a critical determinant of productivity, innovation, and competitiveness.

Economic diversification, on the other hand, refers to the process by which a country broadens its economic base by expanding into new sectors beyond traditional primary commodities or mono-resource dependency (International Monetary Fund (IMF), 2016). The nexus between these two concepts is increasingly significant as countries grapple with globalization, technological change, resource dependency, and vulnerability to external shocks.

In advanced economies, investment in human capital has been a cornerstone of economic transformation. For example, the case of Singapore exemplifies how human capital development can drive sustained diversification. Lacking in natural resources, Singapore has invested massively in its education system, technical and vocational education, and lifelong learning initiatives to build a knowledge-driven economy. According to the World Economic Forum (2020), the government's SkillsFuture initiative has been particularly impactful, encouraging citizens to continually upgrade their skills to align with emerging sectors. In Nigeria, an oil-resource-rich country, the challenges of overdependence on natural commodities should prompt efforts to emulate the Singapore models.

The United Arab Emirates (UAE), strategic steps toward diversification through the UAE Vision 2021 and Centennial Plan 2071 by enhancing education, fostering innovation, and supporting private sector-led growth which led to the establishment of global universities and technical institutions in cities like Abu Dhabi and Dubai that have continued to exemplify the UAE's commitment to human capital development. Also, Rwanda, though not resource-rich, is demonstrating how prioritizing human capital development can support economic transformation. The World Bank (2021) reports that Rwanda has made significant progress in increasing literacy, technical skills training, and ICT integration in schools. These efforts have laid the foundation for growth in services, technology, and tourism sectors, helping the country reduce poverty and improve macroeconomic stability. African Development Bank (2020) emphasized the need for the Sub-Saharan Africa to integrate human capital development into economic planning, in its African Economic Outlook report, the Bank highlights that economies that have made tangible investments in education, vocational training, and health tend to show stronger prospects for diversification. For instance, countries such as Kenya and Ghana have made strides in linking education systems with labour market needs, fostering entrepreneurship, and expanding digital infrastructure to prepare youth for emerging economic opportunities. Also, in Latin America, countries like Chile and Uruguay have invested in quality education and healthcare systems. This underscores the importance of policy coherence, institutional alignment, and continuous labour market assessments.

According to Ekeamadi, (2022), countries that have succeeded in integrating human capital into their diversification strategies have often adopted innovation-friendly policies and built strong research ecosystems. South Korea stands out in this regard. From the 1960s onwards, the South Korean government focused on education reforms, universal primary and secondary schooling, and high investment in science and technology education. Today, South Korea leads in sectors such as electronics, shipbuilding, automotive, and AI technologies—largely due to its long-term investments in research and development (R&D) and human capital (Lee, 2018).

3.5 Lessons for Nigeria

Drawing from the global experiences of countries like Norway, the United Arab Emirates (UAE), Singapore, and Rwanda, Nigeria can derive several critical lessons for leveraging human capital development as a cornerstone of its economic diversification strategy. These lessons span key policy domains including long-term strategic planning, education and skills development, institutional strengthening, public-private collaboration, and the integration of diaspora and digital competencies. For example, a fundamental lesson from the UAE and Norway is the importance of policy coherence and long-term strategic planning. Both countries developed and implemented national visions (e.g., UAE Vision 2021 and Norway's long-term fiscal management of oil revenues) that explicitly link human capital development with economic diversification. In contrast, Nigeria's policy landscape has been characterized by fragmented plans, frequent policy reversals, and poor implementation (Onyeiwu, 2020). For example, although the Nigerian Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP) 2017–2020 acknowledged the importance of human capital development, its execution was hampered by inadequate coordination and lack of continuity.

To emulate the UAE and Norway, Nigeria must institutionalize long-term development plans with strong political commitment across administrations. This entails aligning education, industrial, and economic strategies through integrated planning bodies. Agencies such as the National Planning Commission and the Nigerian Education Research and Development Council should be strengthened to ensure cohesion and continuity in policy implementation (Ajakaiye & Tella, 2021).

Another example is prioritizing education and vocational training, in this case, the success stories of Singapore and South Korea emphasize the transformative power of education and vocational training. Singapore's SkillsFuture initiative and South Korea's heavy investment in science and technology education were pivotal in transitioning from low-income to high-income economies (Lee, 2018). These countries demonstrate that diversified economies are built on a workforce equipped with future-ready skills. Nigeria's current education system, however, suffers from infrastructural deficits, poor teacher quality, misalignment with labour market needs, and limited access to technical and vocational education and training (TVET). UNESCO (2022) reports that Nigeria has one of the world's highest numbers of out-of-school children, and the tertiary education system is plagued by frequent strikes and underfunding.

To address these challenges, Nigeria must increase public and private investments in foundational education, teacher training, and TVET. Curriculum reforms should emphasize STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics), entrepreneurship, and digital literacy to prepare students for diversified sectors such as ICT, renewable energy, and agribusiness (Ogunyemi & Bekun, 2021). Strengthening polytechnics and creating partnerships with industries to offer internships and apprenticeships would enhance the employability of Nigerian youth.

Also in line with this is institutional capacity development, which is another critical lesson for Nigeria. Norway's success in managing oil wealth and channeling it into productive

investments is anchored on strong, transparent, and accountable institutions. The country established clear fiscal rules, maintained the independence of its central bank, and set up the Government Pension Fund Global (GPF) to stabilize oil revenue volatility and promote intergenerational equity (Holden, 2023). In contrast, Nigeria has struggled with weak public institutions, corruption, and inefficiency. The mismanagement of the Excess Crude Account (ECA) and the Nigerian Sovereign Investment Authority (NSIA) undermines public trust and limits the strategic use of oil revenue to invest in human capital and infrastructure (AfDB, 2020). Building institutional capacity requires legal reforms to promote accountability, professionalization of the civil service, and stronger oversight mechanisms. Anti-corruption efforts should be institutionalized through the independence of anti-graft agencies such as the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC). Moreover, decentralizing educational governance to empower states and local governments could lead to more context-sensitive policies and improved service delivery (World Bank, 2021).

Global experiences also reveal the value of robust public-private partnerships (PPPs) in advancing human capital development. In the UAE, the government has collaborated extensively with international universities, private investors, and tech companies to provide world-class education and research facilities (Oxford Business Group, 2020). Rwanda's digital transformation, driven by partnerships with organizations like Microsoft and Carnegie Mellon University, has enhanced ICT education and innovation capacity (World Bank, 2021). In Nigeria, the private sector has been active in sectors such as telecommunications and fintech but remains underutilized in education and skills development. Creating an enabling environment for PPPs—through legal frameworks, incentives, and regulatory clarity—can unlock private sector investment in TVET, research, and infrastructure. For instance, incentives such as tax rebates and land grants can attract private investors to establish training centers and e-learning platforms in underserved regions. Additionally, corporations should be encouraged to invest in corporate social responsibility initiatives that support education, youth empowerment, and innovation hubs. Public sector institutions can benefit from knowledge transfer, internships, and workforce development programmes designed in collaboration with industry players.

Another lesson Nigeria can tap into is leveraging diaspora talent and digital transformation. Nigeria's global diaspora community is among the most educated and economically successful African diasporas. Remittances from the Nigerian diaspora exceed \$20 billion annually, surpassing oil revenues in some years (World Bank, 2022). However, beyond remittances, Nigeria has not adequately harnessed the human capital potential of its diaspora in areas such as knowledge transfer, entrepreneurship, and innovation. Countries like India, China, and Israel have leveraged diaspora networks to build globally competitive sectors such as ICT, biotechnology, and academia. For instance, India's software industry owes much of its growth to returning diaspora professionals who established firms and provided mentoring and venture capital (Saxenian, 2016).

To replicate this, Nigeria must create incentives and platforms for diaspora engagement. Initiatives such as brain-gain programmes, academic exchange schemes, and diaspora bonds can channel expertise and capital into priority sectors. The Nigerian Diaspora

Commission should be strengthened to coordinate these efforts and work with embassies, professional associations, and higher institutions to establish global talent pipelines.

Furthermore, the digital economy offers unprecedented opportunities to diversify beyond oil. Estonia's digital transformation is a case in point. The Fourth Industrial Revolution is transforming labour markets, making digital literacy a key component of human capital. Countries that are embracing this shift are better positioned to diversify. Conversely, failure to invest substantially in digital economy has contributed to stagnation and volatility in many resource-dependent economies. Nigeria has a burgeoning tech ecosystem—evident in the success of fintech firms like Flutterwave and Paystack—but this growth is largely private-sector driven and lacks a coherent national digital strategy. Investing in digital infrastructure, internet access, e-governance, and digital literacy is essential to integrate ICT into education, agriculture, healthcare, and finance (Ajakaiye & Tella, 2021).

3.6 Role of Health, Education, and Vocational Training in Economic Diversification

According to Ekeamadi, (2022), a critical but often underemphasized enabler of economic diversification is health. The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP, 2020), states that countries with higher life expectancy and better healthcare outcomes tend to have more productive workforces, which contributes to more dynamic and diversified economies. Ekeamadi, (2022), improved health outcomes increase labour productivity and reduce absenteeism, contributing to economic growth. Peter (2018) highlighted that good health among the labour force enhances productivity, while Kelemchi et al. (2020) indicated that health improvements incentivize higher educational attainment due to longer working life spans. Japan, for example, has one of the healthiest populations globally and has leveraged this advantage to develop high-value services and technology sectors despite demographic challenges. Education, health, and vocational training are integral components of human capital that collectively influence economic diversification.

Education equips individuals with the knowledge and skills necessary for employment in various sectors, countries like Finland and South Korea have successfully transitioned from primary-based economies to exporters of high-tech manufactures, largely due to sustained attention to quality education and skill development (Maier & Wood, 2018). These nations exemplify how strategic human capital investments can catalyze economic diversification. Nigeria, for instance, has historically underinvested in education and skills development, resulting in a mismatch between workforce capabilities and economic needs (Ogunyemi & Bekun, 2021). Despite its oil wealth, the country continues to face high unemployment, low industrial capacity, and underdeveloped service sectors.

Vocational training, in particular, plays a critical role in aligning workforce skills with labour market demands. In Nigeria, vocational and technical education have been identified as key drivers of economic growth and sustainable development. Osundahunsi (2019) emphasized that vocational education empowers citizens, enhances employment, and reduces poverty. However, challenges such as poor public perception, inadequate funding, and lack of qualified teachers hinder its effectiveness.

3.7 Theoretical Perspectives of Human Capital Development in Economic Diversification

The following theories have underpinned human capital development as a vital tool for economic diversification: Human Capital Theory as developed by Becker, (1964), the Endogenous Growth Theory developed by Romer (1990), and Resource Curse Theory developed by Sachs & Warner, (1995). These theories have been fully applied here to explain the Nigerian situation at poor diversification.

1 Human Capital Theory as developed by Becker, (1964)

Human Capital Theory, developed by Becker (1964), posits that individuals and societies derive economic value from investing in people through education, training, and healthcare. Becker argued that just as physical capital (like machinery) enhances productivity, so does human capital. The theory conceptualizes education and skill acquisition as a form of capital formation that enhances worker efficiency, increases earning capacity, and contributes to national income growth. The central tenet of this theory is that rational individuals invest in their education and health with the expectation of improved productivity and future returns.

This theory has profound implications for economic diversification. Countries rich in natural resources can use resource rents to invest in human capital as a long-term strategy for sustainable growth. The theory underscores the role of education and training in building competencies necessary for emerging sectors such as technology, manufacturing, and services (Hanushek & Kimko, 2020). For example, the UAE's transformation into a diversified economy was largely fueled by education reforms and talent development initiatives guided by the principles of human capital investment. The theory assumes that labour markets are efficient and that individuals will be rewarded based on their skills and education, which may not hold true in contexts characterized by inequality, corruption, and weak institutions—as is the case in many developing countries, including Nigeria (Pascal & Patrick, 2024).

2 Endogenous Growth Theory by Romer (1990)

Endogenous Growth Theory emerged in the 1990s as a critique of neoclassical growth models, which treated technological progress as an exogenous factor. This theory posits that economic growth is largely the result of internal factors such as innovation, knowledge accumulation, and human capital development. According to this theory, investments in education, research and development (R&D), and human capital generate positive externalities that enhance productivity and foster sustained economic growth. A key insight of endogenous growth models is that increasing returns to scale can be achieved through the accumulation of knowledge and human capital, as opposed to merely increasing capital or labor inputs. Therefore, government policies that support education, innovation, and skill development play a critical role in shaping long-term growth trajectories (Agwu & Nwachukwu, 2018).

In relation to economic diversification, endogenous growth theory explains why countries that invest in knowledge-based sectors tend to escape the resource curse and build competitive advantages in various industries. Norway's emphasis on R&D and university-industry linkages exemplifies this model. The UAE has also adopted policies consistent with endogenous growth by fostering entrepreneurship, technology hubs, and digital innovation.

For resource-dependent nations like Nigeria, endogenous growth theory provides a compelling rationale for redirecting oil revenues toward capacity-building, especially in areas that generate learning and innovation spillovers. Failing to do so perpetuates reliance on volatile primary exports with little value addition (Gylfason, 2021).

3 Resource Curse Theory by Sachs & Warner, (1995)

The Resource Curse Theory, also known as the “paradox of plenty,” refers to the empirical observation that countries rich in natural resources often experience slower economic growth, weaker democratic institutions, and higher levels of conflict compared to resource-poor countries. The theory challenges the traditional belief that resource abundance automatically translates to prosperity. Several mechanisms explain the resource curse. First, the revenue effect, whereby large inflows of resource rents reduce the incentive to tax citizens, thereby weakening state accountability and public service delivery (Ross, 2021).

Second is the spending effect, where easy revenues fuel public sector inefficiency and wasteful expenditures, and third is the institutional effect, where elites capture resource rents, leading to corruption, rent-seeking, and the erosion of democratic institutions (Mayor et al., 2016). This theory has been widely applied to analyze Nigeria’s development failures, where decades of oil windfalls have not translated into improved human capital, infrastructure, or poverty reduction (Salami & Suleiman, 2023). Instead, oil dependence has coincided with political instability, economic mismanagement, insecurity, and underinvestment in non-oil sectors.

Conversely, countries like Norway and the UAE have avoided the resource curse through strong institutions, strategic planning, and proactive investments in human development. These countries illustrate how natural resources, if well managed, can become a blessing rather than a curse. Therefore, overcoming the resource curse requires deliberate policy choices that prioritize transparency, diversification, and human capital development. Investment in people—through quality education, health, and skills training—is the surest way to transform resource wealth into sustainable prosperity (Collier, 2017).

4 Recommendations for Nigeria

Based on the study’s findings, the following are specific recommendations for Nigerian policymakers, educators, private sector actors, and international development partners:

1. **Institutionalize Strategic Long-Term Planning:** Nigeria should develop and implement a human capital development roadmap integrated with its economic diversification strategy. This should include targets for educational attainment, health coverage, employment creation, and innovation capacity. Learning from the UAE’s Vision 2021 and Norway’s prudent fiscal policies, Nigeria needs to depoliticize development planning and insulate long-term plans from regime changes (Onyeiwu, 2020).
2. **Reform and Fund the Education Sector:** Massive investments are needed to overhaul Nigeria’s ailing education system. Infrastructure upgrades, teacher training, curriculum reforms, and performance-based funding should be

prioritized. A national framework for Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) must be implemented, ensuring strong industry linkages and alignment with emerging sectors such as green technology, software development, and agritech (Ogunyemi & Bekun, 2021).

3. **Develop Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs):** The government should create a conducive environment for PPPs in education, healthcare, and entrepreneurship. For instance, private sector actors can co-establish technical colleges and innovation hubs in partnership with government and donor agencies. The PPP framework should ensure transparency, clear roles, and return on social investment (Oxford Business Group, 2020).
4. **Engage the Nigerian Diaspora:** Diaspora engagement must go beyond remittances. Nigeria should design programs to attract skilled Nigerians abroad through incentives such as tax breaks, access to land, research grants, and academic appointments. Creating a digital diaspora talent database and partnering with global universities for exchange programs could facilitate knowledge transfer and innovation (Saxenian, 2016).
5. **Build Digital Infrastructure and Literacy:** With global transitions to knowledge economies, digital transformation is essential. Nigeria must invest in affordable internet, digital learning platforms, coding programmes for youth, and e-governance systems. Establishing regional tech clusters akin to Dubai Internet City or Rwanda's Kigali Innovation City can catalyze ICT-driven diversification (World Bank, 2021).
6. **Strengthen Governance and Transparency:** Effective use of oil revenues for human capital development requires strong institutions and anti-corruption mechanisms. Reforms should focus on improving transparency in education financing, establishing independent regulatory bodies, and adopting international standards for public procurement and accountability (AfDB, 2020).

5 Conclusion

Human capital development is not only a prerequisite for economic diversification but a safeguard for national resilience and inclusive growth. While countries like the UAE and Norway have demonstrated that strategic investment in people yields long-term prosperity, Nigeria continues to face avoidable constraints due to policy inconsistency, inadequate investment in education and health, and underutilization of its youthful and diasporic population. The path forward requires visionary leadership, collaborative governance, and a renewed commitment to the education, empowerment, and inclusion of all Nigerians. If embraced, the strategic lessons from global exemplars could serve as the catalyst Nigeria needs to unlock its full development potential and reduce dependence on volatile resource revenues. This study explored the intricate relationship between human capital development and economic diversification, drawing comparative insights from the United Arab Emirates (UAE), Norway, and other resource-rich nations that have successfully leveraged human capital to reduce overreliance on oil. The conceptual and

theoretical underpinnings, including Human Capital Theory as developed by Becker, (1964), Endogenous Growth Theory, and Resource Curse Theory, support the argument that robust investment in education, health, and skills training significantly boosts economic productivity and resilience.

REFERENCES

- African Development Bank (AfDB). (2020). African Economic Outlook 2020: Developing Africa's workforce for the future. <https://www.afdb.org/en/documents>
- Agwu P, & Nwachukwu, C, (2018). Why nations fail: The origins of power, prosperity, and poverty. Crown Publishing Group.
- Ajakaiye, D., & Tella, S. A. (2021). Enhancing Nigeria's human capital development: Imperatives and strategies. *Nigerian Journal of Economic Policy*, 28(1), 1–20.
- Auty, R. M. (2021). Resource abundance and economic development. Oxford University Press.
- Barro, R. J. (2023). Human capital and growth. *American Economic Review*, 91(2), 12–17. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.91.2.12>
- Becker, R. J. (2024). Education and economic growth. *Annals of Economics and Finance*, 14(2), 301–328.
- Becker, G. S. (1964). Human capital: A theoretical and empirical analysis, with special reference to education. University of Chicago Press.
- Bosworth, D & Collins, H, (2023). The effect of health on economic growth: A production function approach. *World Development*, 32(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2003.07.002>
- Chakravarty, S., Lundberg, M., Nikolov, P., & Zenker, J. (2020). Vocational training programmes and youth labour market outcomes: Evidence from Nepal. arXiv preprint arXiv:2006.13036. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2006.13036>
- Collier, P. (2017). *The bottom billion: Why the poorest countries are failing and what can be done about it*. Oxford University Press.
- Corden, W. M., & Neary, J. P. (2022). Booming sector and de-industrialisation in a small open economy. *The Economic Journal*, 92(368), 825–848. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2232670>
- ECLAC. (2019). Social Panorama of Latin America. Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean. <https://www.cepal.org/en/publications>

- Ekeamadi, O.A, (2020). The empirics of growth: An update. *Brookings Papers on Economic Activity*, 2003(2), 113–179. <https://doi.org/10.1353/eca.2004.0002>
- Ekeamadi, O.A, (2022). A new data set of educational attainment in the world, 1950–2010. *Journal of Development Economics*, 104, 184–198. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdeveco.2012.10.001>
- Ekeamadi, O.A, (2023). Capacity Building and Professionalism in the Nigerian Civil Service: An Imperative for Sustainable Development. *GSU Journals*. <https://gsujournals.com.ng/ijass/index.php/ijass/article/download/21/17/32>
- Gelb, A. (2020). Economic diversification in resource rich countries. Center for Global Development.
- Gylfason, T. (2021). Natural resources, education, and economic development. *European Economic Review*, 45(4–6), 847–859. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0014-2921\(01\)00127-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0014-2921(01)00127-1)
- Hadiza, S.A, (2023). Economic diversification and social progress in the GCC countries: A study on the transition from oil-dependency to knowledge-based economies. arXiv preprint arXiv:2410.21505. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2410.21505>
- Hanushek, E. A., & Kimko, D. D. (2020). Schooling, labour-force quality, and the growth of nations. *American Economic Review*, 90(5), 1184–1208. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.90.5.1184>
- Hanushek, E. A., & Woessmann, L. (2020). The economics of international differences in educational achievement. In E. A. Hanushek, S. Machin, & L. Woessmann (Eds.), *Handbook of the economics of education* (Vol. 3, pp. 89– 200). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-53429-3.00002-8>
- Holden, S. (2023). Avoiding the resource curse: The case Norway. *Energy Policy*, 63, 870–876. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2013.09.010>
- IMF. (2016). Economic diversification in oil-exporting countries: Lessons from the Middle East and Central Asia. International Monetary Fund.
- Imo, M.C, & Wogu, O.I, (2023). Human capital development and economic growth: Empirical evidence from Nigeria. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 2(7), 813–827. <https://archive.aessweb.com/index.php/5002/article/view/933>
- Kelemchi, H, Isham, J, Woolcock, M., Pritchett, L., & Busby, G. (2020). The varieties of resource experience: Natural resource export structures and the political economy of economic growth. *The World Bank Economic Review*, 19(2), 141–174. <https://doi.org/10.1093/wber/lhi010>

- Kwak, J. & Kim L. (2021). Mortality decline, human capital investment, and economic growth. *Journal of Development Economics*, 62(1), 1–23.
- Ledgerman, D.N, & Maloney, H.E., (2022). Resource wealth and economic growth in the UAE: The role of institutions and diversification. *Resources Policy*, 74, 102343. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2021.102343>
- Maier, G., & Wood, G. (2018). Economic diversification in resource-rich countries. In R. Arezki, T. Gylfason, & A. Sy (Eds.), *Beyond the curse: Policies to harness the power of natural resources* (pp. 55–80). International Monetary Fund.
- Mayor, E., Golden, H., Mehlum, H., Moene, K., & Torvik, R. (2016). Institutions and the resource curse. *The Economic Journal*, 116(508), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0297.2006.01045.x>
- Michael, G., Imbs, J., & Wacziarg, R., Harry, A., & Hvidt, M. (2016). Development Policy, Plan and Economic Diversification in Nigeria: A Review of the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP). *European Journal of Development Studies*, 1(3), 38. <https://www.ej-develop.org/index.php/ejdevelop/article/view/38>
- Mogaji, A., Muda, I., & Tofa, U., (2016) Stages of diversification. *American Economic Review*, 93(1), 63–86. <https://doi.org/10.1257/000282803321455329>
- National Bureau of Statistics. (2022). Annual statistical bulletin. <https://www.nigerianstat.gov.ng>
- Norwegian Ministry of Petroleum and Energy. (2020). Facts 2020: The Norwegian petroleum sector. <https://www.regjeringen.no/en/dokumenter/facts-2020/id2707142/>
- OECD. (2021). *The well-being of nations: The role of human and social capital*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2022). *Economic Survey of Norway 2022*. <https://www.oecd.org/norway/>
- Ogunyemi, O., & Bekun, F. V. (2021). Re-examining the role of human capital and renewable energy in fostering environmental sustainability in Nigeria. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 278, 123964. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.123964>
- Olayemi, S. O. (2019). Human capital development and economic diversification in Nigeria. *Journal of African Development Studies*, 11(2), 45–58.
- Onyeiwu, S. (2020). *Economic development in Africa*. Routledge.
- Osundahunsi, K. F. (2019). The role of vocational and technical education on economic growth and sustainable development in Nigeria. *The Colloquium*, 7(1), 1–10.

<https://www.ajol.info/index.php/colloq/article/view/238741>

Oxford Business Group. (2020). The report: Abu Dhabi 2020. Oxford Business Group.

Oxford Business Group. (2022). The report: UAE 2022. <https://oxfordbusinessgroup.com/reports> Oxford Business Group.

Pascal, M., & Patrick, D., (2024). Nigeria's Public Admin Reforms: Past, Present, and Future. (2024, December 5). Disciplines.ng. <https://disciplines.ng/public-admin-reforms/>

Peter, K. (2018). Theory and previous research. In *How to write about economics and public policy* (pp. 67–90). Springer.

Romer, P. M. (1990). Endogenous technological change. *Journal of Political Economy*, 98(5, Part 2), S71–S102. <https://doi.org/10.1086/261725>

Ross, M. L. (2021). Does oil hinder democracy? *World Politics*, 53(3), 325–361. <https://doi.org/10.1353/wp.2001.0011>

Sachs, J. D., & Warner, A. M. (1995). Natural resource abundance and economic growth. National Bureau of Economic Research Working Paper No. 5398. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w5398>

Salami, J. D., & Suleiman, A. M. (2023). The curse of natural resources. *European Economic Review*, 45(4-6), 827–838. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0014-2921\(01\)00125-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0014-2921(01)00125-8)

Saxenian, A. (2016). *The new argonauts: Regional advantage in a global economy*. Harvard University Press.

School, T. W. (2021). Investment in human capital. *The American Economic Review*, 51(1), 1–17.

Schultz, K. (2021). *The Global Competitiveness Report 2020*. World Economic Forum. <https://www.weforum.org/reports/>

Somchi, S., & Wogu, W., (2023). Education and economic growth in developing countries: Empirical evidence from GMM estimators for dynamic panel data. *Economics and Business*, 35(1), 14–29. <https://doi.org/10.2478/eb-2021-0002>

Torvik, R. (2019). Why do some resource-abundant countries succeed while others do not? *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*, 25(2), 241–256. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxrep/grp015>

UNDP. (2020). *Human Development Report 2020: The next frontier – Human development and the Anthropocene*. United Nations Development Programme.

- <https://hdr.undp.org>
- UNESCO. (2022). Education in Africa: Challenges and policy responses. <https://www.unesco.org>
- World Bank. (2019). Estonia's Digital Transformation. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/feature/2019/04/01/estonia-digital-leader>
- World Bank. (2020). Human capital index 2020 update: Human capital in the time of COVID-19. World Bank Publications.
- World Bank. (2021). Rwanda economic update: Building back better. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/rwanda/publication>
- World Economic Forum. (2017). The Inclusive Growth and Development Report. <https://www.weforum.org/reports/the-inclusive-growth-and-development-report> 2017.
- World Economic Forum. (2020). Global Competitiveness Report 2020. <https://www.weforum.org/report>.